

STORAGE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE ECO-SYSTEM

D4.2 – “Common base for environmental, techno-economic and socio-economic assessment to un-lock the potential applications for hybrid ES (HES) systems”

Work Package 4 - Supporting the transition towards a climate-neutral continent

Task 4.2 - Sustainability Assessments of Hybrid ES Technologies

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

AHP	Analytical Hierarchy Process
CA	Criticality Assessment
CCUS	Carbon capture, Utilization and Storage
DCM	Decision-making
e-LCC	Environmental Life Cycle Costing
ES	Energy Storage
FBC	Filtration-based Control
FC	Fuel Cell
GD	Green Deal
GHGs	Greenhouse gases
GRI	Global Reporting Initiative
HES	Hybrid Energy Storage
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment or Life Cycle Analysis
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
LCOE	Levelized Cost of Electricity
LCOH ₂	Levelized Cost of Hydrogen
LCOHeat	Levelized Cost of Heat
LCOS	Levelized Cost of Storage

LCOX	Levelized Cost of Energy (where X refers to different energy vectors)
LCSA	Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment
LCT	Life Cycle Thinking
MAUT	Multi-Attribute Utility Theory
MCDA	Multi-criteria Decision Analysis
MEFA	Material and Energy Flow Accounting
MFA	Material Flow Analysis
MRIO	Multiregional Input-Output Analysis
NGO	Non-governmental Organization
NPV	Net present value
PBA	Prussian Blue Analog
PHS	Pumped Hydro Storage
RBC	Rule-based Control
SC	Supercapacitor
SCESS	Supercapacitor Energy Storage System
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SEA	Socio-economic Analysis
SEIA	Socio-Economic Impact Assessment
SETAC	Society for Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry
SFM	Social Footprinting Method
SHM	Social Handprinting Method
s-LCA	Social Life Cycle Assessment
s-LCC	Societal Life Cycle Costing

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SMES	Superconducting magnetic energy storage
TBL	Triple-Bottom-Line
TCO	Total Cost of Ownership
TESS	Thermal Energy Storage System
TRL	Technological Readiness Level
UNEP	United Nations Environment Program
VRFB	Vanadium Redox Flow Batteries

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The goal of the deliverable is to provide a guideline offering a streamlined approach to conducting enviro-techno-economic assessments for Hybrid Energy Storage (HES) systems. Addressees are practitioners, technology developers, doctoral students, and other relevant stakeholders. The document is structured to efficiently guide users through the assessment process, key performance indicators, and calculation procedures, with detailed descriptions provided in an accompanying annex for comprehensive reference. A state-of-the-art section establishes a common understanding of Energy Storage (ES), particularly HES, by defining standard terms, reviewing applications, and summarizing existing literature and ongoing projects. An Introduction to Sustainability section provides an overview of relevant sustainability frameworks, regulations, and aspects relevant to HESS. Essential KPIs applicable to all storage technologies are also identified here. The core of the guideline lies in the Sustainability Assessment Approaches, which detail how to carry out a sustainability assessment for HESS. This section covers crucial aspects such as method selection, KPI identification through literature review, defining system boundaries, impact allocation, and an overview of assessment methods. The identified methods are provided in detail in the comprehensive annex, including calculation procedures, KPIs and reference studies. The guideline also incorporates business proposition canvas templates for sustainability tailored to various storage technologies and their hybridization combinations. These templates, designed for both storage manufacturers and system integrators, facilitate the identification and documentation of key performance indicators and calculation procedures. A working example from the second StoRIES workshop illustrates how to provide decision support for HESS by integrating all relevant sustainability dimensions as well as Stakeholder preferences. Here a set of potential HESS KPIs has been identified. Further working examples are related to the Hybris and SH2E projects and published results from StoRIES partners. The document serves as a common base for environmental, techno-economic, and socio-economic assessments to un-lock the potential applications for HES systems.

1 INTRODUCTION

In December 2019, 27 EU member states pledged that Europe will be the first climate-neutral continent by 2050. With the European Green Deal (GD) the European Commission has achieved an agreement on implementing the before named UN's *2030 Agenda of Sustainable Development* and the SDGs [1]. Achieving a climate-neutral continent by 2050 necessitates reduction of net greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by more than 55% until 2030 with respect to 1990 [2]. The GD has implications on the energy sector stipulating a clean energy transition where secure and affordable energy supply in the EU shall be ensured via availability of a fully integrated, interconnected, and digitalized EU energy market. In quest of this ultimate goal, the GD prioritizes and promotes improved energy efficiency in industrial and residential energy systems and maximized utilization of renewable sources in energy supply [3]. However, achieving climate neutrality is a complex challenge bound with the transition of the existing energy system with advanced green technologies and state-of-the-art smart infrastructures. In this sense, the European energy system must employ smart grids for efficient supply and demand management, using integrated solutions for decarbonization and decarbonized energy supply at all times such as hydrogen networks, carbon capture, storage and utilization (CCUS), energy storage (ES), as well as sector-coupling [1]. Due to increased intermittence in the decarbonized energy supply caused by renewables, the future European power grid is envisaged to accommodate various ES technologies to be highly flexible. Hence, a fully decarbonized energy system cannot be achieved with suitable ES solutions, making ES a critical element of the energy transition [4]. Acknowledging that there is no single ES solution which can serve for this aim, harmonization of all available state-of-the-art technologies (electrochemical, mechanical, chemical, thermal, and electrical) is required for building required ES capacities when considering various performance criteria such as supply flexibility, duration, reaction time, and proper range for e-mobility depending on the service.

Moreover, another way to spur the efficient cross-sectoral development of ES is the development of hybrid systems, combining the ES technologies with complementary characteristics to support the European Strategic Energy Technology Plan (SET) objectives [5]. Such a hybridisation approach is expected to serve for overcoming barriers and drawbacks of a single technology. Hybridization can be considered the combination of two or more inherent features to meet specific needs. Applying hybridization strategies requires argumentation by improvement in one or multiple aspect(s) considering the technical performance, economic feasibility, environmental sustainability, and societal benefits. Identification of which ES types are required and how synergies can be used among them poses a challenge considering material to device combination levels (e.g., hybrid materials for battery storage and supercapacitors, hydrogen with superconducting magnetic energy storage (SMES), etc.). For instance, combining high-energy storage capacity technologies with a high-power capacity designed technology is one of the common approaches (e.g. combining batteries with supercapacitors or thermal storage for enhancing the energy capacity and overall system reliability). Furthermore, a consensual agreement has not been established for the definition of HES, which creates terminological unclarity. This guideline document aims to serve for implementation of hybridization strategies for

improved performance and sustainability to ensure ES technologies to be hybridized comply with mentioned aspects. To this aim, this guideline document provides multiple strategies identifying the important aspects to support hybridized ESS practices considering overall lifecycle stages holistically (e.g., manufacturing, operation, use, recycling, and reuse).

1.1 Abstract: The StoRIES project

Achieving a climate-neutral continent requires elimination of GHG emissions systematically, where decarbonization of the energy and mobility sectors will play a significant role. In accordance with this goal, an overall re-design of the European energy system mainly relying on carbon-free or low-carbon energy sources is essential. In terms of power supply, undoubtedly solar and wind power sources will form the backbone of the supply system requiring integration of various ES technologies responding the flexibility demand covering various storage durations (i.e., short-, mid- and long-term). Besides provided flexibility and satisfied grid services, ES technologies have a vital importance in terms of energy generation system sizing for optimized installed capacities. A range of ES technologies are available in the market showing variable technological readiness levels (TRLs), and technological characteristics to provide required services. Although economic aspects of ES remain as a main constraint for decision-making, environmental and societal aspects associated with these technologies makes decision-making a more complex process. Considering distinctive features of available diverse technologies, the establishment of an ecosystem of industry and research organizations, presently missing link in the European innovation landscape, is a straightforward acceleration strategy for the wide adoption and deployment of ES technologies. On that matter, StoRIES project emerged as an initiative gathering all relevant stakeholder groups for fostering a European ES ecosystem for successful and mutually beneficial cooperation for achieving efficient, competitive, and cost-effective ES systems. StoRIES brings together a consortium of 32 beneficiaries from 17 countries: European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) facilities, technology institutes, universities, and industrial partners to jointly improve the economic performance of storage technologies. Members of the European Energy Research Alliance and from the industry lead European Association for Storage of Energy are establishing the core of this world-class European ecosystem. The main objectives of StoRIES are linked to the ES development by providing access to world-class research infrastructures and services, with a specific focus on improving materials for devices and optimizing hybrid energy systems with a view to make energy technologies more competitive and cost-efficient. In addition, StoRIES focuses on the analysis of socio-technical and environmental aspects of new developments and systems, providing training and education on these matters for improving competences by using resources effectively. By promoting complementary expertise, interdisciplinary cooperation and a broader exchange of knowledge and technologies throughout the academic world and with industry, StoRIES is significantly improving the technological basis for ES applications. Furthermore, StoRIES is establishing an ecosystem with international peer partners from Research and Industry to foster open science and promote new energy technology standards.

1.2 Work Package 4: Supporting the transition towards a climate neutral continent

Given the objectives of the StoRIES project, WP4 aims to serve for conducting activities to support a fair transition towards climate neutrality within the project through:

- (i) Supporting the product development process in the early-stage design related to HES aiming at optimizing the raw material use, increasing the circularity, reducing the environmental impact, maximizing the social benefit.
- (ii) Understanding how to unlock the potential of HES identifying bottlenecks and suggesting solutions in all the following aspects: environmental, economic, and societal.
- (iii) Setting-up of a common, shared, recognized, and open access primary data to support Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Life Cycle Costing (LCC) and Social Life Cycle Assessment (s-LCA) as well as Multiregional Input-Output (MRIO) analysis.
- (iv) Building up a network of competence, exchange of know-how, and shared data related to modelling of environmental, economic, and societal assessments. In particular, supporting the early-stage design of new devices and systems exploiting the full potential of the hybridization of different storage technologies.
- (v) Establishing an ES sustainability workshop series in cooperation with WP1 and WP3.

Regarding defined goals, a guiding reference consisting of three deliverables are foreseen to address the ES related requirements of a just transition, as depicted in Figure 1.1.

Figure 1.1. Deliverables in WP 4, goals, and interdependencies.

Even though, the deliverables are designed to have different scopes, they are structured in a complementary way. The present deliverable (i.e., D.4.2) aims to elaborate on methodological capacities to assess sustainability of HES systems building upon provided guidance in terms of data collection in D. 4.1. Hence, D. 4.2 focuses on assessment methods, key performance indicators (KPIs) and use cases ([APPENDIX H. – Use Cases Selection](#)). Accordingly, provided guidance here will fall into D.4.3, which will be delivered in month 48 as a conclusive white paper providing a blueprint for sustainability assessment of HES technologies. An overview of the activities carried out in frame of T4.2 is provided in the [APPENDIX A](#).

1.3 Aim and Scope of the Deliverable

Deliverable 4.2 aims to provide a common base for environmental, techno-economic, and socio-economic assessments to unlock the potential applications of HES systems. Exploiting the full potential of the HES concepts, requires standardized assessment procedures for generating inferences about achieved improvement via hybridization. Hence, the guidance needs to be provided on method selection to address sustainability aspects accurately, critical KPIs for the corresponding services, and data collection. This is realized via provided precise definitions for calculation procedures for the assessments or links to corresponding standards, publications, and reports. Based on this, the following aspects are covered:

- General guideline for the sustainability assessments.
- Identification of KPIs.
- Provision of an integrated sustainability assessment approach.

In addition to the integrated sustainability assessment approaches for decision-making, a business proposition canvas template is provided within this deliverable with the aim of creating a strong influence of assessment-based knowledge generation into sustainable business development practices. The provided business canvas template extends the business dimensions beyond economics with regards to ESG via inclusion of relevant sustainability KPIs within the economic value chain following materials, manufacturers, and system integrators perspectives.

In this manner, the deliverable is developed in a way to serve as a basis for *D4.3: White paper on Sustainable HES for the European Clean Energy Transition: Unlocking the Potential applications for HES*.

1.4 Structure of this Deliverable

The deliverable is structured into 10 chapters, which will be briefly outlined. First a general understanding of sustainability and relevant frameworks and regulations will be provided. This is followed by a brief introduction into energy storage and different hybridization strategies to provide a common base on the topic. Then relevant aspects from sustainability assessment of ES and HES systems are presented and discussed regarding, e.g., indicators and criteria. Within this chapter, a decision tree is provided of how to proceed with a sustainability assessment. Lastly, a business canvas template for sustainability assessment is provided. In [Chapter 6. Methods for Sustainability](#)

[Assessment](#), all collected methods are presented briefly and supplemented by corresponding use cases. Furthermore, for practical context and enhancing the aimed baseline for the sustainability assessments of HES, different working examples are provided for sustainability assessment. In particular project working examples are included in this guideline to benefit from synergistic effects for strengthening the validity of the defined common base considering their outcomes and progress. Here, the 2nd StoRIES workshop on decision making and then two projects are presented. Finally, collected use cases covering a set of the methodologies in the input papers are shown.

1.5 Target Group

The present deliverable addresses a broad audience of actors involved considering all lifecycle stages starting from raw material supply to end-of-life. However, sustainability assessment practitioners can be considered as the main target group of this deliverable where their role is to act as a mediator speaking science-based knowledge holding an objective position. Beyond that, the following groups can be considered as target group of this deliverable:

- **Academia:** here the guideline can serve as a starting point for sustainability assessments in the field. Doing so it allows starting faster with assessments, by providing a common base for different spheres.
- **Policy-making and regulation:** The Deliverable is intended to provide an overview of the relevant context on a European level and depict the main KPIs in the field of sustainability.
- **Industry:** due to increasing regulations, the guideline can serve as a viable base to carry out corresponding assessments.
- **Incipient practitioners, young scientists:** the guideline provides a comprehensive base by linking to relevant guidelines and literature in the field of different sustainability assessment methods.

2 METHODOLOGY

A structured approach has been followed to deliver a guiding document for paving the way to establish a common base for sustainability assessments of HES applications. The approach combines several methods (surveys, discussions, publications, interviews, and workshops) to fully benefit from the sustainability assessment competences of consortium partners to create a comprehensive guiding document to support assessments in the field of both ES and HES systems. Initial efforts were invested in asking partners fundamental questions to understand their perspectives and experiences on sustainability assessment of HES applications (See [APPENDIX A.](#)). Considering the diverse background of the partners that contributed to this deliverable, an approach consisting of four steps has been followed based on the gathered answers to the questions illustrated in Figure 2.1. HES is an emerging topic, and this guiding document will serve as a “lighthouse” for sustainability assessments to identify the potential of HES.

Figure 2.1. Fundamental questions and guideline development.

To identify how sustainability of HES can be addressed, the first question to be posed was “What needs to be assessed?”, which revealed the necessity of identifying important key performance indicators (KPIs) to be used as metrics. KPI results comparing specific application benchmarks can generate inferences regarding considered aspects. Hence, used common KPIs for ES technologies have been screened considering technical, economic, environmental, and social dimensions. Accordingly, their relevance for decisions on hybridization has been discussed, showing strong dependence on the considered technology, application, and provided services. Nevertheless, technological characteristics set here benchmarks considering the best alternative capable of meeting service requirements within an application. Considering this, comparing KPIs of the best performing technology with those of HES is proposed to be the most practical approach. Hence, identifying technologies suitable for each service and their KPI performance is fixed which resulted in identification of standard KPIs.

Following the order of an assessment, identification of important KPIs served as the second step for exploration of robust and reliable methodologies and frameworks as a consequent step for estimating both quantitative and qualitative KPIs. Within the second step of the followed methodology, to answer the question “How can it be assessed?”, existing diverse sustainability assessment methods and frameworks are screened which resulted in a wide set of methods that can be applied to HES with slight adjustments to assess their sustainability on different dimensions. At this stage, used state-of-the-art methods are collected for estimating these KPIs from peer-reviewed literature, project deliverables and other guiding documents. Conducted screening activities provided a base for an understanding of the assessment landscape (see [Chapter 6. Methods for Sustainability Assessment](#)), nevertheless it revealed the need for collaborative efforts to provide guidance on how to conduct these assessments properly to deliver implications for supporting HES decisions. Thus, it has been decided to deliver methodological input papers to close the methodological guidance gap for economic, environmental, and social assessments as a supplement to this deliverable. Finally, an additional input paper covering integrated assessment methods considering the relevance of these assessments for informed decision-making has been developed.

To benefit from the resources in terms of available expertise of WP members on sustainability assessments, small groups were formed for developing the input papers as shown in Figure 2.2.

Figure 2.2. Development of the guideline via thematic input papers.

Asking the final question “How sustainability assessment methods can be used for unlocking the potential of HES?”, experts’ opinions played a role in defining the role of the assessments and elaborating on methodological capacities considering the important criteria for method selection. Furthermore, the conducted discussions resulted in a common structure defining aspects to be covered in the input papers to allow a direct comparison of methods regarding, e.g., typical system

boundaries, required data and software, standardization, and guidelines. Each input paper follows a consistent structure, aiming to serve as an efficient starting point for conducting corresponding assessments. The chapter's structure and layout follow the work of Andes et al. [6] and are adapted for HES systems. Each method is succinctly presented within an average length of up to 5 pages. These methods are briefly introduced and summarized in [Chapter 6. Methods for Sustainability Assessment](#) while further elaboration and a selection of use cases for methods are provided for application-oriented guidance in input papers. Experts shared their own work providing a use case for each method as far as possible. Additionally, some methods that potentially can be used for estimating the determined KPIs are also included in the use case selection even though it is not currently applied for ES. By this way, gaps for addressing future assessment demand are also covered in the input papers.

Additionally, the guideline provides information about various ES technologies, their typical applications, and covered services in the following chapters. Including these aspects provides enough background information for sustainability assessment practitioners with little knowledge in the ES field. Consequently, it is linked to the HES topic introducing different hybridization strategies, and available examples in the literature. This should serve for providing an introductory technical background which will be useful for translating the technology relevant information into sustainability assessment terms for HES. A comprehensive chapter delves into important aspects of sustainability assessments such as definitions, conceptual frameworks, sustainability dimensions, technical KPIs, impact allocation, system boundaries, and stakeholder involvement.

So far, the followed approach for creating this document provides comprehensive material for addressing the goal and scope of this deliverable. Additional materials (e.g., decision tree or business canvas) and working examples (e.g., use cases, projects) are included in this document to take the shared theoretical and practical knowledge one step ahead. Since sustainability assessments should serve for informing decisions, a very comprehensive example for decision-making aid is also provided in which a specific workshop was organized. This workshop aimed at “Setting up a common base for environmental, techno-economic and socio-economic assessment to unlock the potential applications for HES systems”. The main goal of this workshop was to establish a consensus on selected KPIs and methods, considering further their use in decision-making for supporting hybrid energy applications. Furthermore, provided example in this guideline can be used as a blueprint for decision-making processes considering for setting definitions, defining KPIs and methods, as well as for choosing from various HES alternatives. The workshop is explained in a way elaborating on the subsequent steps starting from the preparation to execution of the task which can be modified for named different purposes. By this way, a comprehensive guidance is provided by harmonizing and synthesizing available operational research methods considering the available resources.

3 ALIGNING SUSTAINABILITY DEFINITIONS

Sustainability as a concept emerges in the early 1700s due to overexploitation of agricultural land and forests [7]. Emerging resource scarcity concerns in the 1950s and increased pollution driven by the population growth in the 1960s raised the questions associated with ecological concerns caused by anthropogenic activities [8]. One important milestone was the establishment of World Commission on Environment and Development by the United Nations which kept sustainability further as an agenda. The main outcome of this initiative was the report "Our Common Future" from 1987, also known as the Brundtland Report [9]. This report, for the first time, defined the concept of sustainable development as follows:

“Humanity has the ability to make development sustainable to ensure that it meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.”

The Brundtland report revealed the first proper consideration of sustainability by end of the 20th century. Later, in the 21st century, climate-change driven circumstances promoted and shaped the understanding of sustainability. Since then, multiple concepts emerged addressing various sustainability dimensions and attention was drawn to the need for an overarching sustainability definition to assist the delivery of concrete actions to achieve sustainable development. As a result of this need, in the course of time, weak and strong sustainability terms emerged representing different views and both aiming to address sustainable development [10]. The weak sustainability is based upon the ability of sustaining human well-being by use of non-renewable resources in economic terms with the core idea that natural capital can be replaced by produced capital. In other words, it assumes technological progress can increase the productivity of the natural capital stock faster than it is being depleted. Hence, the weak sustainability in practice refers to the genuine savings to ensure that next generations will have at least the same living conditions of today. In contrast, according to strong sustainability natural capital is difficult to substitute, but requires consideration of non-monetary criteria to protect critical natural capital via the following: (i) the harvest rate for renewable resources should not exceed the rate of regeneration, (ii) the depletion of non-renewable resources should require comparable development of renewable substitutes for that resource (not measured in money), and (iii) waste generation should not exceed the assimilative capacity of the environment.

As a key observation, the strong sustainability view highlights the strong links between sustainability and the planetary boundaries attributing to Earth’s *safe operating space*. It emphasizes that there are limits to how much ‘natural capital’ can be substituted or degraded without risking irreversible harm to the Earth’s systems. Therefore, a strong sustainability approach, respecting planetary boundaries, would advocate for balanced consideration of ecology, economy, and society, ensuring that economic and social development does not come at the cost of environmental integrity. The planetary boundaries concept presents a set of nine processes that regulate the stability and resilience of the Earth system. Currently, six of the nine boundaries have been transgressed (see Figure 3.1.a), increasing the risk of environmental change [11]. Moreover, the green area at the centre of Figure

3.1.a) indicates the safe operating space for the earth system. It defines the carrying capacities of the Earth in which a global sustainable development needs to be achieved prioritizing the ecosystem. The outer dotted line surrounding the safe operating space indicates the ecological ceiling where beneath this line a *safe and just operating space* is to be established for the sustainable development. Furthermore, it is extended by incorporation of elements of social foundation as illustrated in Figure 3.1.b). In the “doughnut” model, where social foundation aspects are placed at the centre of the safe operating space creates a boundary between social foundation and ecological ceiling defining the area for a regenerative and distributive economy.

Figure 3.1 a) planetary boundaries of the Earth’s system [11], b) the doughnut of social and planetary boundaries [12].

With the inclusion of social aspects, a solid boundary can be drawn within the Earth safe operating space defined via the social boundaries. It that enables the utilization of natural capital to increase prosperity and well-being of world citizens via a global sustainable development. From this aspect, the strong sustainability portrays an ideal approach highlighting the interdependencies between society, environment and economics relating to social and planetary boundaries. In other words, a sustainable development can only be achieved in the intersection of these three domains. Based on the explained relationship between the Earth and societal systems, the sustainability Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) serve as a main overarching framework for policy orientation aligning the given definitions. Hence, in the following SDGs and its implications for the ES development in Europe are further put in relation to policies and regulations.

3.1 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and the SDGs

The Agenda 2030 with its SDGs is a continuation and extension of the *Millennium Development Goals* (eight international development goals to fight extreme poverty, further information [13]). In 2012, during *The United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development* in Rio de Janeiro, it was decided to

launch the process of setting SDGs until 2015. During the United Nations Sustainable Development Summit on 25 September 2015, *Transforming our world: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development* was unanimously adopted by the 193 member states.

The adopted agenda sets the **people, planet, prosperity, peace, and partnership** as focal aspects of sustainable development. These aspects are considered as enablers of a global sustainable development ensuring that human dignity stands at the centre, meaning that all world citizens deserve to enjoy prosperity and peace. Protecting the planet is a result of collaborative efforts established by global partnerships. Furthermore, within this agenda 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are defined which consolidate the essential focus areas for achieving worldwide sustainable development until 2030. (see Figure 3.2) As it is stated in the agenda “These are universal goals and targets which involve the entire world, developed and developing countries alike. They are integrated and indivisible [...]” [14]. The topic of energy is also integrated in the SDGs as goal 7 is defined as the availability of affordable and clean energy for all. In more detail, it states that “Ensuring access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all will open a new world of opportunities for billions of people through new economic opportunities and jobs, empowered women, children and youth, better education and health, more sustainable, equitable and inclusive communities, and greater protections from, and resilience to, climate change.” [15].

Figure 3.2. UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) within Agenda 2030 [14].

Furthermore, main targets of the SDG 7 to be achieved by 2030 are summarized below:

- **Universal Access:** Ensure that all people have access to affordable, reliable, and modern energy services.
- **Renewable Energy:** Substantially increase the share of renewable energy in the global energy mix.

- **Energy Efficiency:** Double the global rate of improvement in energy efficiency.
- **International Cooperation:** Enhance international cooperation to facilitate access to clean energy research and technology, including renewable energy, energy efficiency, and advanced fossil-fuel technology. This also involves promoting investment in energy infrastructure and clean energy technology.
- **Infrastructure and Upgrades:** Expand infrastructure and upgrade technology to provide modern and sustainable energy services for all in developing countries, especially least developed countries, small island developing states, and land-locked developing countries.

As it can be concluded from the main goal, focal points of SDG 7 are accessibility, energy transition towards renewables, improved energy efficiency, cooperation and infrastructure requirements underlining associated environmental and social aspects. However, progress is still needed to achieve these targets by 2030, particularly in regions where energy access remains limited [16]. Considering addressed actions in SDG 7, global joint effort for energy transition might function as a catalyst promoting the climate protection, improved economic growth and prosperity [4]. However, the energy transition requires massive adoption to renewable energies, decarbonizing the energy supply. A central aspect is its intermittent behaviour which necessitates the availability of ES providing the required flexibility, robustness, and resilience in the power supply. The availability of ES also plays a role for the achievement of other SDGs. SDG 9 (Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation) and SDG 13 (Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts) require the use of renewable energies and therefore also the use of ES to be fulfilled. Given the brief introduction to SDGs and its energy-related aspects in terms of an overarching global political framework, particular attention is given in the next subchapter scrutinizing policy actions and regulatory efforts defined by the regulations, frameworks, and guidelines regarding sustainability requirements of ES systems on European level.

3.2 Regulatory Implications, Frameworks, Guidelines for Sustainability of ES technologies

The European Commission presented a concept defining its targets in order to translate the implications of the Agenda 2030. The Commission envisions a comprehensive approach for implementing necessary actions for achieving all SDGs by the aid of six political frameworks namely the European Green Deal, Economy that works for the people, Europe fit for digital age, European way of life, Stronger Europe in the world and European Democracy. Bearing in mind, that the given six frameworks have implications on ES sector either directly or indirectly, among mentioned political frameworks, the Green Deal provides the core guiding principles that have strong implications on the overall supply chain and lifecycle stages of the ES technologies. The Green Deal operationalizes the defined principles via the following initiatives also beyond 2030 [18]:

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- **Fit for 55:** cutting net greenhouse gas emissions in the EU by at least 55% by 2030, compared to 1990 levels.
- **European climate law:** The European climate law regulation turns the political ambition of reaching climate neutrality by 2050 into a **legal obligation** for the EU.
- **EU strategy on adaptation to climate change:** A long-term vision for the EU to become a climate-resilient society that is fully adapted to the unavoidable impacts of climate change by 2050.
- **EU biodiversity strategy for 2030:** Recover Europe’s biodiversity by 2030.
- **Farm to fork strategy:** Shifting the current EU food system towards a sustainable model.
- **European industrial strategy:** Towards a more dynamic, resilient, and competitive European industry.
- **Circular economy action plan:** Decoupling economic growth from resource use and shifting to circular systems in production and consumption.
- **Batteries and waste batteries:** Regulation on batteries to create a circular economy for the sector by targeting all stages of the life cycle of batteries, from design to waste treatment.
- **A just transition:** A just transition mechanism to provide financial and technical support to the regions most affected by the move towards a low-carbon economy.
- **Clean, affordable, and secure energy:** Decarbonization of the energy sector is a crucial step towards a climate-neutral EU.
- **EU chemicals strategy for sustainability:** Endorsing the EU chemicals strategy for sustainability.
- **Forest strategy and deforestation:** The EU’s biodiversity strategy forms a key part of efforts to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030.

All the named initiatives under the Green Deal have direct or indirect consequences for designing European ES capacities to meet the set targets.

Since this guideline aims to present required orientation for evaluating the sustainability of HES systems, a high-level summary of frameworks and regulations that are relevant for the development and implementation of ES technologies are presented in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1. Overview of relevant European regulations for HES. Note that some regulations are more relevant for specific technologies while others aim to regulate sustainability on a project- or corporate-level.

Name	Description	Who/what
Eco-design for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR)	ESPR is Part of the Sustainable Products Initiative (SPI) in the Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP). A common ESPR draft is initiated, likely in early 2024	Companies >500 employees €150 million+ net turnover worldwide, in the future companies with 250 employees and a net turnover beyond €40 million worldwide Relevant for any ES technology.
EU Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (EU CSDDD)	Directive to harmonize corporate due diligence requirements. Companies will be required to identify and, where necessary,	Relevant for any corporal activity.

	prevent, end or mitigate adverse social and environmental impacts of their activities.	
EU Critical Raw Materials Act	Aims at a secure, diversified, affordable and sustainable supply of critical raw materials. The act sets a regulatory framework to support the development of domestic capacities and strengthen sustainability and circularity of the critical raw material supply chains in the EU.	Non-binding, communication.
EU Taxonomy Regulation / Sustainable finance (Additional information: A short-guide to the EU's taxonomy regulation)	Represents a classification system, establishing a list of environmentally sustainable economic activities, which aims to help scale up sustainable investment and implement the European Green Deal. The six environmental objectives of the Taxonomy are: (1) climate change mitigation, (2) climate change adaptation, (3) sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources, (4) transition to a circular economy, (5) pollution prevention and control, and (6) protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems.	Relevant for any project activity.
Registration, Evaluation, Authorization and Restriction of Chemicals REACH Regulation (1907/2006)	REACH aims places responsibility on industry to manage the risks from chemicals and provide safety information on the substances, e.g., via registration in the central database of the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA). REACH also calls for the substitution of substances of very high concern where possible.	Industry, in particular chemical industry, production of components.
Classification, Labelling and Packaging (CLP) Regulation	The CLP Regulation implements the GHS (Globally Harmonized System of Classification and Labelling of Chemicals). It provides globally uniform physical, environmental, and health and safety information on hazardous chemical substances and mixtures and administrated by the United Nations.	All companies handling chemical substances before placing them on market.
Net Zero industry Act COM(2023) 161 - Proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on establishing a framework of measures for strengthening Europe's net-zero technology products manufacturing ecosystem (Net Zero Industry Act) (not in power)	The Net-Zero Industry Act is an initiative stemming from the Green Deal Industrial Plan which aims to scale up the manufacturing of clean technologies in the EU. This means increasing the EU's manufacturing capacity of technologies that support the clean energy transition and release extremely low, zero or negative greenhouse gas emissions when they operate. This Act will attract investments and create better conditions and market access for clean tech in the EU. The Act also simplifies the regulatory framework for the manufacturing of these technologies.	Energy technologies including solar PV and solar thermal, electrolyzer and fuels cells, onshore wind and offshore renewables, sustainable biogas and biomethane, batteries and storage, carbon capture and storage, heat pumps and geothermal energy and grid technologies.
Batteries regulation REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL concerning batteries and waste batteries, amending Directive 2008/98/EC and Regulation (EU) 2019/1020 and repealing Directive 2006/66/EC	Entered into force on 17 August 2023 to ensure that batteries are collected, reused and recycled in EU. Starting from 2025, the new rules will gradually introduce declaration requirements, performance classes and maximum limits on the carbon footprint of electric vehicles, light means of transport (such as e-bikes and scooters) and rechargeable industrial batteries. Starting in 2027, consumers will be able to remove and replace the portable batteries in their electronic products at any time of the life cycle.	Batteries manufacturers and users.

Provided regulations and guidelines are the result of joint efforts of member states focusing on supporting policy development and law enforcement for implementing the indicated principles of the named policy frameworks. In that manner topics such as eco-design for sustainable products, corporate sustainability, raw material criticality, sustainable financing, chemicals, and labelling are very relevant aspects that influence the developments in the energy sector.

The circular economy action plan adopted in 2020 is relevant, especially for resource intensive ES technologies using materials with low recyclability rates. Circularity is included as a key principle within

the EU’s Green Deal for securing sustainable supply of required resources to achieve climate-neutrality. The created action plan promotes sustainable supply and efficient use of resources to avoid unintended impacts of this transition on economics, environment, and society. Also on this matter, the *Sustainable European Investment Plan* defines the criteria for mobilizing at least €1 trillion of sustainable investments (until 2030) to facilitate public and private investments for transition to a climate-neutral, green, competitive and inclusive economy [19].

In line with that EU’s taxonomy and sustainable financing regulations shall ensure that used economic resources will flow into sustainable projects creating economical, ecological, and societal benefits. Technology specific regulations are herein applied most prominently for batteries. As introduced earlier, due to strategic importance of batteries a particular attention is dedicated via specific initiatives to establish the conditions required for their sustainability in EU. A significant progress has been achieved in terms of sustainability assessment and reporting. The battery regulation reflects on many aspects complementing the circular economy action plan, where similar ambitions can be observed in EU’s Strategic Action Plans as stated: “This Strategic Action Plan combines targeted measures [...] to make Europe a global leader in sustainable battery production and use, in the context of the circular economy” [20]. Furthermore, the strategic action plan highlights the relevance of the following elements:

- (i) Secure access to raw materials.
- (ii) Support European battery cells manufacturing at scale and a full competitive value chain in Europe.
- (iii) Strengthen industrial leadership through stepped-up EU research and innovation.
- (iv) Develop and strengthen a highly skilled workforce in all parts of the battery value chain.
- (v) Support the sustainability of EU battery cell manufacturing industry with the lowest environmental footprint possible.
- (vi) Ensure consistency with the broader enabling and regulatory framework.

Additionally, the Batteries Directive (see [DIRECTIVE 2006/66/EC](#)) defines important rules in the EU for avoiding and minimizing primarily environmental impacts associated with batteries and accumulators. This is achieved by prohibiting the marketing of batteries containing hazardous substances and setting clear rules for collection and recycling schemes. The directive additionally addresses some aspects related to socio-economics, technological advancements, market dynamics, and emerging applications of batteries by involving regulating aspects relevant for the value chain actors throughout the lifecycle of batteries and accumulators, including topics such as waste management. The European Commission proposed a new Batteries Regulation in December 2020, aiming to ensure sustainable and safe batteries throughout their entire life cycle. This regulation came into force in August 2023 and will eventually replace the existing directive by 2025. (see European Commission press release: [EC Proposal for a Regulation on batteries and waste batteries \(Dec 2020\)](#)).

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These regulations provide adequate information defining the aspects for ensuring the sustainability of an energy technology covering all lifecycle stages. It can be concluded that existing political frameworks and resulting regulations build a base for defining a path to a climate-neutral continent through protecting the vulnerable entities from the unintended impacts of the ongoing disruptive change. Here, depending on the evaluation context for HES systems, different regulations and frameworks might apply and must be considered accordingly. Ultimately, all named regulatory frameworks here are relevant in the sustainability definition and decision context for the sustainability assessments and sustainability reporting of ES technologies.

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4 HYBRID ENERGY STORAGE: DEFINITIONS AND STATE OF THE ART

Since sustainability assessment practitioners using this guideline document may come from diverse backgrounds, essential terms and concepts are elaborated in this chapter for providing fundamentals of the ES technologies. The given definitions and information here should serve as a bridge to a better technical understanding of hybridization approaches required for conducting assessments in the field. The architectural structure of the ES technologies (i.e., materials, components) and their performance influences their sustainability performance predominantly. Hence, sustainability assessment practitioners should be able to understand relevant technological information and interpret this into the corresponding models.

As a starting point, it is essential to grasp the actual function of an ES. *Energy storage* means deferring the final use of energy to a moment later than when it was generated, or the conversion of energy into a form of energy which can be stored, the storing of such energy, and the subsequent reconversion of such energy into electrical energy or use as another energy carrier. In this context, an *energy carrier* refers to a substance or mean to embody energy in storable and/or ideally transportable forms of material. One, or more assembled components, capable of storing energy and providing usable forms of energy into the premises via wiring system or an electric power production and distribution network constitutes an *ES system*. Components consolidating an ES system can show variability consisting of one reversible process (e.g., redox cycle), multiple processes and even sectors depending on the technology. The round-trip efficiency of an ES system is influenced by the energy losses of involved processes, namely the charge and discharge steps as well as self-discharge (see Figure 4.1).

Figure 4.1. Simplified illustration of a storage cycle considering power conversion and ESS within energy system.

Box 4.1 provides an overview of relevant design and operation parameters for energy storage.

Box 4.1. Design vs Operation Parameters of Energy Storage Technologies	
<p>Design Parameters</p> <p>Nominal energy capacity: The amount of energy that an energy storage system is designed to store under specific conditions, typically expressed in kilowatt-hours (kWh) or megawatt-hours (MWh).</p> <p>Power capacity: The maximum rate at which energy can be drawn from or delivered to an energy storage system, usually measured in kilowatts (kW) or megawatts (MW).</p> <p>Depth-of-discharge: The percentage of the total available energy storage capacity that has been discharged from a battery or energy storage system.</p> <p>The energy-to-power (E/P) ratio: The ratio of the energy capacity to the power capacity of an energy storage system, indicating how much energy can be stored relative to how quickly it can be delivered.</p> <p>Discharge Duration: The length of time an energy storage system can continuously provide power at a specified rate before needing to be recharged.</p> <p>Response time: The time it takes for an energy storage system to respond to a request to either charge or discharge energy.</p>	<p>Operation Parameters</p> <p>State of charge: The current level of energy stored in an energy storage system, usually expressed as a percentage of the total capacity.</p> <p>Round-trip efficiency: The efficiency of an energy storage system in converting input energy (during charging) to output energy (during discharging) and back again, expressed as a percentage.</p> <p>Self-discharge: The gradual loss of stored energy in an energy storage system over time, even when it is not actively being used.</p> <p>Degradation: The gradual loss of capacity or performance of an energy storage system over time due to various factors such as cycling, temperature, and aging.</p> <p>Cycle life, Calendar life: The number of charge-discharge cycles an energy storage system can undergo before its capacity falls below a specified threshold. The expected operational lifespan of an energy storage system based on time, regardless of the number of charge-discharge cycles.</p> <p>End-of-life threshold: The point at which an energy storage system is considered to have reached the end of its useful life, typically defined by a certain level of capacity loss or performance degradation.</p> <p>State-of-health: The current condition or health status of an energy storage system, often assessed by measuring its capacity, performance, and other relevant factors.</p>

Referring to the relevance of required steps for ES, the conversion path is often referred as an attribute for technological classification of ESS such as:

- **Mechanical systems:** Flywheels, Pumped Hydro-storage (PHS), Compressed Air Energy Systems (CAES) and adiabatic CAES (ACAES).
- **Electrical systems:** capacitors, Super-Conducting Magnet ES (SMES).
- **Thermal systems:** sensible & latent storage, chemical heat.
- **Electrochemical systems:** battery systems as like lithium-ion batteries (LiBs), vanadium redox flow batteries (VRFB) and lead acid batteries (PbA,) as well as supercapacitors).
- **Chemical systems:** Power-to-X (P2X) and hydrogen (fuel cells).

Considering distinct conversion paths of energy in different ES systems, each technology shows different performance characteristics (see Table 4.1) that need to match with design parameters. Mainly, nominal energy capacity, power capacity, depth-of-discharge, energy-to-power (E/P) ratio, discharge duration, and response time can be named as typical design parameters. Note, that these depend on the viewed technology and might show variabilities. Design parameters are defined by the application and service requirements and are influenced by economic aspects since some ESSs require high initial investments. In addition to the design parameters, for the operation of ESSs parameters such as state-of-charge, round-trip efficiency, self-discharge, degradation, cycle life, end-of-life, or state-of-health needs to be considered. Especially, those parameters are intended to be optimized in a way to ensure designed ESSs will be able to provide the intended service(s) over a sufficient period maintaining same service quality within operable economic boundaries.

Providing an introduction by addressing basic principles of ES, following chapters elaborate on ES applications and services attributing attaching importance to their reflection on the sustainability aspects.

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Table 4.1. Overview of different ES technologies, type of storage, conversion paths and use [21].

	Sub-technologies	Energy carrier in	Energy carrier out	Energy capacity	Power installed capacity	Storage duration at full power	Round-trip efficiency (%)	Response time	Availability factor	Lifetime (years)	Number of cycles
Mechanical	Pumped Hydro Storage (PHS)	electricity	electricity	0.5 – 100 GWh	0.01 – 3 GW	min – some 10 h	70 – 85	s – min	> 95	50 – 100	20-100 k
	Adiabatic Compressed Air ES (A-CAES)	electricity	electricity	0.1 – 10 GWh	10 – 300 MW	hours – some 10 h	>70	min		30 +	<= 1000
	Diabatic Compressed Air ES (D-CAES)	electricity	electricity	0.1 – 10 GWh	10 – 300 MW	hours – some 10 h	42 – 54	min	95 – 96	25 – 40	5-20 k
	Liquid Air ES (LAES)	electricity	electricity	0.01 – 7.8 GWh	5 – 650 MW	2 – 24 h	45 – 70	min		40	22–30 k
	Flywheel	Electricity	electricity	5 kWh – 5 MWh	1 – 20 MW	secs – mins	85 – 95	s	> 99,9	20 +	10 ⁵ – 10 ⁷
Electrochemical	Sodium Sulphur batteries (NaS)	electricity	electricity	0.1 – 300 MWh	few kW up to 50-100 MW	min to 7 hours	75-85 (90)	ms	up to 99,98	10-20	4-7.3 k
	Sodium Nickel Chloride batteries (NaNiCl, ZEBRA)	electricity	electricity	few kWh up to 10 MWh	few kW up to 5 MW	min – 4 h	80-90 (95)	ms	>99,9	10-20	2.5-4.5 k
	Lead Acid batteries (LAB) – Short-term storage / UPS	electricity	electricity	< 200 kWh (usable, not installed)	<1 MW	10 to 30 min	75-85 (lower range)	ms	99,997	8 – 20	250 – 2000
	Lead Acid batteries (LAB) – ES	electricity	electricity	< 10 MWh	< 40 MW, typical 1 MW	1 to 6 hours	75-85 (upper range)	ms	99,997	8 – 20	250 – 2000
	Lithium-ion batteries (LIB)	electricity	electricity	< 1000 MWh	< 500 MW	5 min – 6h	85 – 89	ms	>97	10-20	1.5-3.5 k
	Lithium-ion batteries (LIB) – Energy Small/Large	electricity	electricity	< 100 kWh	< 100 kW	30 min – 6h	85 – 89	< 1 s	>97	10-20	1.5-3.5 k
	Lithium-ion batteries (LIB) – High Power, medium-size	electricity	electricity	< 40 MWh	< 40 MW	5 min to 1h	>88	<100 ms	>97	10-20	> 1000
	Lithium-Metal-Polymer batteries R&D	electricity	electricity	< 30 MWh	< 10 MW	1 to 3 hours	<97 % (cell)	ms	n.a.	n.a.	< 4000
	Ni-Cd batteries	electricity	electricity	some MWh	< 40 MW	min – hours	60-70	ms	99	10 – 25	1-5 k
	Ni-MH batteries	electricity	electricity	some MWh	< 3MW	min – hours	50-80	ms	99	5 – 15	300 – 1800
	Sodium-ion batteries R&D (SIB)	electricity	electricity	< 100 kWh max: 1 MWh	20-25 kW max: 200-250 kW	< 4 – 5 h	up to 92% (R&D)	ms	n.a.	<10	< 1500; < 10000 future
Redox flow batteries – Vanadium (VRFB)	electricity	electricity	10kWh – 800 MWh	< 200 MW	10-12 h	68-80	ms – sec	96-99	10-25	> 10000	

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	Redox flow batteries – Zn Br	electricity	electricity	few kWh to < 100 MWh	5 kW – 10 MW	< 10 hours	70-75	ms – sec	94	5-15	2000-3000
Electrical	Superconducting Magnetic ES (SMES)	electricity	electricity	up to 20 MWh	< 40 MW	ms- mins	90 – 95	5 ms	> 99,9	20 – 30	10 ⁴
	Supercapacitor	electricity	electricity	up to 1 kWh	up to 300 kW	secs – mins	90 – 95	ms	> 99,9	20 +	10 ⁴ – 10 ⁸
Chemical	Power to Hydrogen	electricity	hydrogen / electricity	some 10 kWh – several GWh	1 kW -1 GW	hours – weeks	20 – 40	< sec - < min	97	5 – 30	n.a.
	Power to Ammonia	electricity	ammonia	1 MWh – several GWh	1 MW-1 GW	weeks	n.a.	sec	92 – 97	30	n.a.
	Power to Methane	electricity	methane	1 MWh – several GWh	1 MW-1 GW	some weeks	n.a.	sec	97	30	n.a.
	Power to Methanol	electricity	methanol	1 MWh – several GWh	1 MW-1 GW	weeks	n.a.	sec	97	30	n.a.
	Power to Methanol to Gasoline	electricity	gasoline	1 MWh – several GWh	1 MW-1 GW	weeks	n.a.	sec	97	30	n.a.
Thermal (buildings, district)	Sensible Thermal ES (STES)	heat/ electricity	heat	0,032-5400 MWh	2-56 MW	hours-months	55-99	<30 sec. - 3 min.		10-50	5.000 - >10.000
	Latent	heat /electricity	heat/cool	0,01-2,5 MWh	80-110 kWh	hours-weeks	> 90	min		>10 up to 50	
	Thermochemical Storage (TCS)	heat	heat	10 MWh	5 MW	hours-days	50-100	min		15-20	3500
Thermal (non-residential)	Latent – Phase Change Material (PCM)	Heat /electricity	heat/cool	4-375 kWh	0.002-1.4 MW	hours-weeks	75-98	min		15-50	3500-10.000
	Latent – other	heat	heat/cool	0.002-480 MWh	0.002-60 MW	hours-months	95	2-5 minutes		20-50	
Thermal (industrial)	Sensible Thermal ES (STES)	heat /electricity	heat/cool/electricity	0.8-29.2 MWh	0.12-60 MW		50-90	<1 – 2 min			1.000-3.000
	Latent – Phase Change Material (PCM)	heat	heat	7.66 kWh	3.5 kW		> 90	<1 min			1.000-3.000
	Latent – other	heat	heat	5.22-162 MWh	6-22.4 MW			2 min			
	Thermochemical Storage (TCS)	heat	heat/cool	1 Wh	500 W		40-50				< 100
Thermal (Power Plants, CSP)	Sensible Thermal ES (STES) – Molten salts	electricity/heat	Heat/ electricity	350-4000 MWh	75-330 MW		>98-99	<1 min			< 10.000
	Sensible Thermal ES (STES) – other	electricity/heat	heat/ electricity	20-3000 MWh	34-250 MW		>90->98				

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	Latent – Phase Change Material (PCM)	electricity/heat	electricity				>90				3.000-5.000
	Thermochemical Storage (TCS)	electricity/heat	heat/electricity	0.015-4 MWh	5 kW		40-60	5 min			< 100
Thermal (solar PV, wind generation)	Sensible Thermal ES (STES) – Solid State (hot rocks)	electricity	heat/electricity	30 MWh	1.5 MW	hours	< 60 - > 90				> 5.000
	Latent – Thermophotovoltaic	electricity	heat/electricity	capacity 100 kWh; density: 1000 kWh			Heat +electricity: 90 %				3.000-5.000
	Mechanical-thermal	electricity	heat	density: 2-70 kWh	10-300 MW		40-65			20-40	

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4.1 Energy Storage Applications and Services

In this part application- and service-related aspects are briefly introduced due to the relevance of the use phase of ES systems for sustainability. In terms of technological differences, conversion pathways can be a relevant attribute for classification, nevertheless for the application depending on technological characteristics a different classification is required considering the service requirements. In terms of services and applications, storage duration and power capacity are important determining parameters. As shown in Figure 4.2, depending on the technological characteristics available technologies can provide distinct services across various storage durations within the indicated power capacity ranges.

Figure 4.2. Overview of different ES technologies regarding applicable power capacities and storage durations.

Typical ES applications are grid (transmission and distribution), off-grid, industrial grid, mobility, and smart building for electricity storage as illustrated in Figure 4.3. Locating ESSs both front-of-the-meter (FTM) and behind-the-meter (BTM), in addition to storage duration and required capacity applications requirements show variability considering reaction time, lifetime, efficiency, energy-to-power ratio, as well as economics [22].

Typically, generation sources are located at the FTM in the energy system. In the context of energy transition, increasing penetration of renewables in the energy generation necessitates intermittence mitigation, covering extended durations from days to weeks, and even months. Hence, on the grid level storage duration and reaction time of ES technologies are important KPIs together with economic

KPIs. Conventional transmission and distribution grid services are covered with ES technologies. Where minimum technical ES service requirements specified for supporting the transmission infrastructure necessitates storage durations of milliseconds to minutes, and distribution infrastructure services typically requiring one or more hours. ES systems provide essential grid services on the transmission level such as operating reserves, voltage regulation, and black start capabilities. Depending on several factors, ES technologies can provide additional services such as capacity adequacy, load shifting and arbitrage, or transmission upgrade deferral. Considering duration of peak demand, share of PV in the generation mix, and storage capacity costs providing capacity adequacy services is needed via bulk-power storage. For bulk storage, required storage durations can vary from minutes to several hours. Additionally, there are some ancillary services such as power quality improvement and power system protection, and energy management with several sub-categories of different use cases. More information on different applications and services can be found in Ref. [23]–[25]. Furthermore, additional storage capacity requirements stem from required industrial grid and off-grid applications.

Figure 4.3. Identified application and required duration for services provided by ES technologies.

Load shifting and energy arbitrage are both terms used for describing shifting generated excess energy via storage. This service can be advantageous particularly for handling fluctuating renewables and inflexible baseload generation considering mainly the spread of electricity costs and cost of storage services provision. Additionally, ES can also support transmission grid management to avoid the failure of costly transmission grid equipment and extending the lifespan of existing assets which is often referred as transmission upgrade deferral service. It is sensitive to cost of transmission upgrades and

additions, rate of demand growth, magnitude of overload of key transmission corridors, and additional benefits provided by storage in terms of techno-economics [26].

As for the distribution level, improvements are required for the distribution system similar to the transmission system. Conventional solutions for distribution system upgrades are replacing distribution lines, substations, or transformers. Considering local demand profiles and forecasted demand growth, siting constraints, response reliability and storage technology costs, distribution network upgrade deferral can be a feasible solution using ES technologies. Further applications on a distribution level are fast-reacting ES technologies for voltage support and power quality management. The distribution system suffers from losses depending on the power travelling distance, and voltage transformation. In addition to design strategies implemented for minimizing distribution losses, integration of ES technologies is an alternative for compensating these losses.

ES technologies can be integrated into distribution system for improved supply resilience which provides higher potential for applications. In contrast to reliability, resilience refers to stability and recovery ability of the system after a rare disruption case for critical infrastructure. Considering the required long storage durations and low utilization rate of such systems due to low occurrence frequency, implementing ES technologies that can provide system resilience can be designed for multiple services improving their techno-economic feasibility. The benefit dimension also provides an indicator of the potential stakeholder groups that are involved when an ES system is used for a particular application field. Each application area represents a service provided by ES with a certain value. ES technologies can provide multiple operational uses across the power system value chain. The aggregation of complementary benefits through the provision of multiple services is also named as “stacking” and is considered as a prominent benefit of HES systems as illustrated in Figure 4.4.

Figure 4.4 Example of value stacking for a hypothetical energy storage project compared to project costs [26].

BTM services can be defined as customer-level services since these services are provided by the ES technologies (mainly batteries) located on customer’s own premises. Other technologies (e.g., CAES, flywheel, SMES, supercapacitors, power-to-X, thermal storage) can find applications with case-specific techno-economic feasibility to support customer energy management services. Typically, industrial, or residential consumers adopt ES technologies for bill management (via increased self-consumption of prosumers), uninterruptible power supply, or power quality assurance with storage durations varying from seconds to hours, which is presumed to contribute demand-side management of the energy system. Moreover, BTM storage can provide upstream grid services to stakeholders from all voltage levels.

4.2 Energy Storage Actors

Generation, distribution, and transmission are fundamental elements of the energy system where power plant operator, transmission system operator (TSO), distribution system operator (DSO) and industrial actors can be considered as the main actors located FTM. A distributed energy system creates a participative environment involving also the actors located BTM, such as private actors, industrial actors, and aggregators [27], [28]. A coordinated environment for secured energy supply requires consideration of all these actors with their specific requirements. It is also crucial to consider that each application field or more specifically each ES service can be allocated to different stakeholders, reaching from end users to transmission system operators. Here, the challenge is to identify the corresponding value streams for ES owners. Remember that collaboration among these actors is essential for a successful energy transition and the widespread adoption of ES solutions.

Distribution System Operators (DSOs) play a pivotal role in maintaining equilibrium between power supply and demand by seamlessly incorporating a diverse array of distributed energy resources (DERs) into the electrical grid. In stark contrast to their traditional counterparts, distribution network operators (DNOs), DSOs adopt an active, data-driven methodology for managing power distribution. While DNOs historically oversaw the unidirectional flow of electricity from centralized generators to end consumers, the emergence of distributed energy resources necessitates a shift toward DSOs. These operators excel at integrating DERs through real-time monitoring and sophisticated modelling techniques.

Transmission System Operator (TSO) is an entity entrusted with the responsibility of transporting energy, either in the form of natural gas or electrical power, on a national or regional level. TSOs operate using fixed infrastructure and play a critical role in ensuring the safety, stability, and reliability of the energy grid.

ES Developers and Manufacturers: These entities design, develop, and manufacture ES technologies. They create batteries, flywheels, compressed air energy storage (CAES) systems, and other storage solutions.

Project Developers and Independent Power Producers (IPPs): Project developers and IPPs invest in ES projects. They identify suitable sites, secure financing, and oversee the construction and operation of storage facilities.

Consumers and Prosumers: Consumers benefit from ES by reducing electricity bills, improving reliability, and supporting renewable energy integration. Prosumers (those who both consume and produce energy) use storage to optimize self-consumption.

Grid Operators and Aggregators: Grid operators manage distributed energy resources (including storage) to maintain grid stability. Aggregators bundle multiple smaller storage systems to provide grid services.

Herein relevant actors for ES field are briefly described consisting of key stakeholders to be considered in the applications. Hence, identifying these actors and their roles is an important aspect to be considered in sustainability assessment. Nevertheless, certain extensions can be necessary considering the case-specific considerations depending on the goal and scope of the conducted assessments.

4.3 Hybrid Energy Storage

The need for ES technologies stem from the required energy services defined by each application. It can be concluded that there is no single technology which can act as a one-for-all solution considering the provided technological overview and discussed service-related aspects in the previous chapters. ES technologies demonstrate distinct techno-economic features and depending on their match with the service requirements, choosing the suitable technology is a known task if techno-economics are considered as one and only constraint. However, current approaches followed for improved sustainability stipulates consideration of environmental and social aspects to ensure the well-being of all stakeholder groups. In this manner, HES is perceived as a new area that has an unexploited potential for improving techno-economic feasibility and sustainability of ES technologies. Presumably, hybridization can support reducing unintended impacts via combinatory characteristics of ES technologies. Fundamentally, hybridization is the combination of two or more inherent features to meet specific needs. Within the StoRIES project, an overarching definition has been generated after some discussion rounds, which resulted in the following definition:

“Hybridization of ES refers to the utilization of two or more ES technologies together on either a system, device, or material level to provide technical and economic advantages beyond what any single ES technologies can provide, also considering the sustainability and reliability over the lifetime of the hybridized solution.”

As it is referred in the presented definition, hybridization of ES technologies can be carried out at different levels. Expecting that hybridization does not serve only as a mean to enhance techno-economics, but also provide benefits beyond that. For instance, fuel reduction, emission reduction, and improvements in energy and reliability efficiency are some examples to be named. The development of a HES system is a problem-driven task to solve a certain problem and not a purpose on itself. Hybridization can provide following the benefits:

- Optimized system design (avoiding over dimensioning).
- Increased lifetime of the overall system through optimized operation.
- Reduced lifecycle costs.
- Offer several services including high-power and high-capacity applications.
- Coupling different sectors (e.g. heat and power), optimizing the use of energy providing versatility and flexibility.
- Improved sustainability aspects of the system (e.g. minimized carbon footprint, less resource used).

As mentioned earlier technological features of a hybrid system must be matched and optimized for a specific problem. Such optimization depends on the level of the targeted application (e.g., utility-scale, decentralized systems, industrial applications, transport systems, grid services, trans-sectoral, high-temperature industrial heat and pressure, production of chemical feedstock) in different fields. Besides combining technologies physically, hybridization through control strategies is another way of optimizing the proposed solution. Here, hybridization is considered with regards to different architectural scales which serves better to work out sustainability aspects since it has a more prominent technological relevance than control. However, it should be noted that the implementation of optimized control strategies is an inseparable part of hybridization.

At the material level, hybridization finds practical application in electrochemical ES technologies. By combining different battery chemistries within a single battery to achieve synergistic effects. For instance, the hybridization of lithium titanate (LTO) and nickel manganese oxide (NMO) batteries has demonstrated improved energy density and increased cycle lifetime [29]. Another example involves combining a zinc electrode with lithium manganese oxide (LMO) chemistry, effectively addressing the instability of zinc electrodes and the capacity fading observed in LMO batteries [30].

On the device level many hybridization configurations can be designated by implementing optimized control strategies to achieve the goal of hybridization. A collection of existing literature assessing the hybridization of various ES technologies at device level is provided in Table 4.2 with their indicated application, technology, and benefits, also supplemented by the recent projects (see Table 4.3) in the field of HES. The given spider chart in Figure 4.5 illustrates an example of hybridization at device level between batteries and supercapacitors. As it can be concluded considering the technical performance comparison, such hybridization results in significant improvements in terms of power density, specific power, cycle lifetime, and energy costs thanks to high-power applicability of supercapacitors. The provided example illustrates a widely applicable hybridized ES solution at device level.

Figure 4.5. Spider chart displaying KPIs of a battery-supercapacitor hybrid application [31].

With regards to storage duration, most of the hybridized solutions can be applied for short durations. However, there exists some combination which can be applied for long-term HES such as flywheel-fuel cell, supercapacitors-superconducting magnetic ES, and supercapacitors-fuel cell depending on the purpose of hybridization and case-specific improvement potential on the relevant KPIs. Finally, system-level hybridization refers to concepts where synergistic effects are turned into feasible use cases integrating sectors. For instance, Power-to-X, which utilize existing infrastructure (e.g., methane and oil infrastructure) to replace fossil fuels in an efficient and environmentally friendly manner on a long-term and large-scale basis. While acknowledging the interplay of such technologies with other storage solutions, there is a recognition of the need to explore novel approaches since such approaches provide versatility and flexibility in terms of form of energy. This exploration leads to the delineation of energy vector clusters for heating and cooling, electric grids, biomass and fuels, and cross-sectoral solutions.

In the following typical control strategies used in HES applications are explained due to their high relevance for HES systems. Classical control approaches are rule-based control (RBC) and filtration-based control (FBC) that are applicable to HESs. The RBC requires the formulation of a sequence of empirical and predetermined rules for optimized operation where FBC is a more control sophisticated method illustrating a complex but more efficient control considering dynamic share of power between hybridized ES technologies with improved system reliability [31]. Applicability of the named control approaches highly depends on the HES topologies such as passive, semi-active, and active topologies. (see Figure 4.6) The passive topology refers to hybridization of high-power and low-power ES technologies operated using one power converter setting power flow as primary and secondary between hybridized ES technologies. The semi-active topology refers to integration of another power converter for enabling changes between voltage level depending on the actual power requirement. In the case of active topology, each ES technologies is connected to the system through an own power converter showing variability in terms of connection as parallel and cascade.

Figure 4.6. Hybrid Energy Storage (HES) topologies.

The reported topologies demonstrate different properties in terms of cost, controllability, complexity, flexibility, and efficiency. Active hybridization topology proves better in all mentioned aspects except efficiency, where semi active topology demonstrates moderate. As for passive topology, besides efficiency it proves the worst in all evaluation criteria.

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Table 4.2. Overview of HES cases compiled from Ref. [31].

Hybrid Storage Technology	Application	Technology	Benefits of hybridization	Source
FC/SC	Power quality	MG including Hybrid PV ES system	The HES system provided a higher power response and offered energy balance during load transition, thus improving power quality and efficiency.	[32]
Battery/SC	Techno-economic design	Standalone solar PV and wind	The HES system improved the dynamic system performance, kept the power balance between system parts, controlled the DC bus voltage, and kept the load voltage and frequency stable throughout various weather instabilities. SC/lead-acid batteries are more efficient than battery only.	[33]
Flywheel/Battery	Peak-shaving and dynamic behaviour	Microgrid	This HES system reduces peak current by 58% and 30% less transient time. The flywheel offers peak-shaving functions for both the battery and the grid. Increased the lifespan of the battery.	[34]
Battery/SMES	Pulse load Grid-connected	Pulse load Grid-connected	Pulse load Grid-connected.	[35]
Battery/SC/FC	Frequency control	Power grid storage	SC handled the high-frequency portion of the power load; battery life is extended. Stabilized the frequency.	[36]
Battery/SMES	Stability during different events	PV-wind DC microgrids	Hybridization of SMES and battery has enhanced the MG stability during various events like wind fluctuation, shadow, and sudden outage of PV.	[37]
Battery/SMES	Improve voltage profile	Grid-connected PV-wind system	The voltage fluctuations have been mitigated during symmetrical and asymmetrical faults. Secure and withstand the influence of grid-connected hybrid wind-PV power system voltage variations.	[38]
SC/Battery/CAES	Frequency stability and optimal sizing	PV-wind in MG System	The CAES, Li-ion battery, and SC dealt with the source-load differential power's low, intermediate, and high frequencies. The cost of the PV-wind HES system was superior to the PV-wind-Li-ion battery system.	[39]
Battery/FC/SC	Power quality and power-sharing	Microgrid	Regulated voltage and frequency, optimal power share during disturbances, and enhanced the dynamic response of the microgrid.	[40]
CAES/Flywheel	Mitigate wind power fluctuations	Wind system connected grid	The power fluctuation is mitigated, and the percentage of wind energy associated with the grid rises to 93.4%.	[41]
FC/Flywheel	City transit buses efficiency Improvement	Electric bus	The suggested hybrid power unit allows for overall power output for the FC stacks that more closely matches road power demands, improving system energy efficiency.	[42]
Battery/FC	Optimal voltage of direct current coupling	Standalone PV system	It has been discovered that an on-off couple with a voltage range of 49–51 V presents the best transition period, indicating that the FC and the batteries are well harmonized.	[43]
Battery/FC	Desalinate seawater	Standalone Hybrid PV HES system	The best configuration for desalinating seawater is PV/FC/BS. The best size is 30 kW FC, 235 kW PV array, and 144 batteries.	[44]
Battery/FC	Electric vehicle energy management	PV-FC-battery hybrid EV	Under various solar radiations and battery states, the hybridization proposed performs admirably in terms of pushing the vehicle and managing power distribution.	[43]

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FC Battery/SCESS	Techno-economic hybridization /sizing	Grid-independent PV system	From an economic standpoint, the FC–SCESS configuration is preferable. FC–SCESS arrangement operates better by properly regulating the voltage and maintaining an active power balance between different constituents.	[45]
Battery/TESS	higher power rates on FCR markets and by converting excessive power into heat	Power and heat grid connected	hybrid battery and power-to-heat system potentially improving the economics in comparison to a standalone BESS for FCR.	[46]
Battery/TESS	park-level integrated energy system – based on photovoltaic (PV), electric chiller (EC), heat pump (HP), and combined cooling heating and power (CCHP) systems	Thermal ES systems in coordination with second-life battery	Prolongation of ES service life, minimization of operation and investment cost.	[47]

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Table 4.3. Projects in the field of HES.

Project Name	Goal and scope	Technology	Description	Sustainability aspects
HYBRIS - Hybrid Battery energy stoRage system for applications in advanced grid and behind-the-meter Systems segments Start date: January 2021 – December 2024, Funding: 3.995.822,50 € Call: H2020-LC-BAT-2019-2020	battery-based hybrid storage solutions for smarter, sustainable and more energy efficient grids and behind-the-meter systems.	Lithium Titanite (LiTO), a high-power density component, and Aqueous Organic Redox Flow Batteries (AORFB), a high energy density component.	Battery hybridization by twinning at system level of two ES technologies, via a novel Battery Management System, Novel Power Electronics and an advanced Power Management System which is fully integrated with Energy Management Systems (EMS) and grid systems.	Levelized Cost of Storage, Life Cycle Assessment, Screening of Materials Safety, Recyclability analysis, eco-design proposal.
Bi-flow	Hybridization of Lithium and vanadium redox flow battery.	Lithium-ion battery with those of the redox-flow battery including an innovative heat regeneration unit.	Increase the building’s independence of the power grid via sustained Power and Heat Supply	Not defined.
Music – Materials for Sustainable Sodium-Ion Capacitors Start date: January 2023 - December 2026, Funding: 5 863 047,50 € Call: HORIZON-CL4-2022-RESILIENCE-01-24 - Novel materials for supercapacitor ES (RIA)	Develop a new sodium based super capacitor; energy density comparable to power batteries, but still recharges within a few seconds and offers long cycle life with minimum efficiency loss over time for application in renewables, industry, and transport.	Sodium-ion capacitors cells with gravimetric energy and power of at least 40 Wh/kg and 10 W/kg.	A new super capacitor cell, and a 12V module will be built.	Life Cycle Assessment and Life Cycle Cost studies, sustainability has high role.
ALUSTORE - Aluminium Metal as Energy Carrier for Seasonal Energy Storage Start date: September 2022- December 2023, Funding: 400,000€ Call: Future Fields Project within KIT / Germany	The project aims to experimentally demonstrate the feasibility of using Al as ES and carrier medium to achieve a carbon-free energy system.	Primary Al-air battery coupled with Hall-Héroult-Process for electricity and heat supply.	A lab-scale demonstrator will be set up to prove the feasibility under operation conditions (TRL 3-4).	The Al-based HES’s sustainability and circularity will be assessed for the entire cycle, including the Al production, storage, and electrochemical energy generation using life cycle assessment.
MIAMI (Innovative Materials for Hybrid Storage Systems) Start date: September 2023 – August 2026, Funding: 4,061,278€ Call: Italian Ministry of Environment (MASE) (website is not available)	Develop an improved VRFB that exploits internal hydrogen production and enables renewable charging even above 100% state of charge.	Vanadium Redox Flow Battery (VRFB) and Hydrogen Production	MIAMI project aims to design and test an innovative energy storage system prototype with an improved VRFB that in addition to storing electricity, can also produce hydrogen (Power-to-X). The project also develops a reactor that can transform hydrogen and CO ₂ into synthetic methane.	Compact device to be paired with intermittent renewables that stores extra energy in form of H ₂ and/or CH ₄ .

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5 SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT FOR HES SYSTEMS

Sustainability assessment as a broad field of research uses multiple qualitative and quantitative assessment frameworks and methodologies for providing knowledge to support decision-making. Although methods show variabilities in terms of coverage, workflow, and criteria, plenty of methods are available for adequate assessment and interpretation of sustainability implications of processes, and products. Primarily this guideline document aims to introduce an application-oriented reference for assessing the sustainability of HES systems.

There is no standardized framework that is tailored to sustainability assessment of HES technologies. Even though, archetypal applications of existing sustainability assessment frameworks for ES technologies are to be found in numerous literature studies. The application of these frameworks for HES systems, differs only in terms of impact allocation due to involvement of more than one technology and extended services. Paying regard to this, a conceptual understanding of terms, frameworks, sustainability dimensions, and KPIs are provided and supplemented with other crucial aspects that influence the operationalization of sustainability, in the following.

5.1 Definitions

Sustainability science as a multidisciplinary field aims to address complex challenges associated with sustainable development. In the operationalization of sustainability scientific frameworks play a crucial role for shaping how it will be addressed, assessed, monitored, and improved drawing perspectives from ecology, economics, and social sciences. Frameworks serve as bridges, integrating various research disciplines and creating a common language. To provide the required terminological understanding for following this guideline, an overview of key terminologies provided by Sala et al. is given in the following [48]:

- **Framework:** overarching structure into which concepts, methodologies, methods, and tools are organized based on their relationships to each other.
- **Methodology:** collection of methods with different characteristics for assessing economic, ecological, and social aspects and evaluating them.
- **Model:** a mathematical or non-mathematical description of a system used to calculate a specific indicator value.
- **Tool/Instrument:** software, application, or database that supports the use of a specific methodology, including its associated models.
- **Criteria:** is defined as an aspect within sustainability assessment which is considered important and by may be assessed through different methodologies.
- **Key Performance Indicator:** a measurable parameter or derived numerical value that provides information about the state or significance of a situation. Every criterion is usually accompanied by a set of KPIs which describes it.
- **Parameter:** quantitative, semi-quantitative, or qualitative value derived from a model.

5.2 Conceptual framework and requirements for HES system sustainability assessment

In the operationalization phase of sustainability, conceptual frameworks are great helpers for sustainability assessment practitioners maintaining a coherence in the assessment structure and formulating the assessment steps. They are also useful for predicting potential outcomes, methodological choices, and used indicators. One can follow an existing framework (e.g., Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA) Framework) for the sustainability assessment of HES system, but the aspects elaborated in the following have to be addressed as highlighted by Sala et al. in [48]:

- **Guiding vision:** Overall goal of the assessment, e.g. SDGs, Brundtland report definition. The guiding vision also contributes to definition of sustainability in the given context, which can be used deriving sustainability criteria of a HES system.
- **Essential considerations:** Relevance of sustainability dimensions (i.e., economy, social and environmental) as well as their interplay need to be addressed adequately in relation to the guiding vision and regulatory schemes emphasizing the additional benefits achieved by hybridization.
- **Adequate scope:** Consecutively a proper definition of time horizon (short- to long term), appropriate geographical scope (local and global effects) and many other aspects to be considered in sustainability assessments in order to concretize the essential considerations.
- **Framework and indicators:** In accordance with the concatenated factors, choosing a conceptual framework serves for systematic identification of indicators, related data as well as modelling principles. In the context of HES, a proper evaluation of the chosen KPIs and their capability to generate inferences is essential for accomplishing the targets via hybridization.
- **Transparency:** As in every modelling approach, transparency and accessibility of relevant data, models and used KPIs leading the conclusions of the assessment.
- **Effective communication:** An effective communication of the results based on the carried interpretation steps can be realized using aggregated results. Here, one should maintain an aggregation level avoiding miscommunication of outcomes due to over-simplification.
- **Continuity and capacity:** Assessment models and results typically follow a long-term vision to provide information accompanied by repeated measures and monitoring.
- **Broad participation of stakeholders:** It is of utmost importance that relevant stakeholders are engaged in the assessment to strengthen legitimacy and relevance of results to provide robust and useful orientation knowledge.

Hereunder, the drawn assessment procedure by Sala et al. [48] provides an outline (see Figure 5.1) on the incorporation of the introduced principles and aspects in relation to assessment workflow. As illustrated in Figure 5.1, definition of sustainability approach is carried out considering values and principles which leads to sustainability targets. Based on the selected sustainability approach it is possible to generate targets and an established decision context with the consideration of assessment objects such as policies/measures, institutions (private/public) or production and consumption (goods/services). The objects of the assessments influence the decision context regarding actors, scale,

complexity, uncertainty, timing, impacts and strategy. These fall into the definition of a scenario- or target-oriented decision context to be considered.

Figure 5.1. Sustainability assessment procedure and incorporation of sustainability assessment principles based on Ref [48].

As a central aspect, the methodology encompasses the philosophical underpinnings, framework, and overall approach where a method refers to a specific and ideally standardized procedure or technique for data collection, analysing the information to achieve a goal. Hence, the identification of robust methods that can be integrated into overarching methodological frameworks is essential for conducting sustainability assessments [48]–[54]. With strong dependence of the approach and decision context, methodological choices can be evaluated in terms of methods, models/tools, and indicators. Additionally, it is an essential decision criterion how the uncertainties will be handled when choosing an assessment methodology in accordance with methodological capacities for delivering adequate precision to support the defined targets. These steps are intended to function as practical guidelines for the development of diverse sustainable ES technologies and their hybridization. Individual projects, technologies and newly tailored hybridization approaches may also have specific requirements that extend beyond the covered principles and aspects so far.

5.3 Sustainability dimensions

Referring to weak and strong sustainability definitions, it can be understood that sustainability cannot be defined by consideration of economics as one and only domain, since economic activities are strongly tied with the earth system and socio-economic trends as illustrated in Figure 5.2. Starting with industrial revolution Earth’s capital has been rapidly exploited, thereafter showing steep increase globally due to accelerated industrialization after WWII.

Figure 5.2. Trends from 1750 - 2010 for ten socio-economics and Earth's system trends [55].

Exhaustive utilization of natural capital provided a significant contribution to the well-being and prosperity in socio-economic terms. However, increasing global population, limited resources, and climate change enforces a global sustainable transition. Safeguarding of all global citizens against unintended implications of such transition can be realized only with simultaneous consideration of multiple domains/dimensions and their interplay. Hence, considering environmental and societal parameters in the equation is inevitable, having strong implications for the definition of sustainability frameworks. Any sustainability framework requires defined sustainability targets defining the compliance of assessment results with criteria using a suitable methodology. For sustainability assessments to deliver maximum value and generate actionable insights, the establishment of clear and measurable goals is paramount [48]. There are several concepts that can be used for this purpose, for instance, the three-pillar model which entails the three dimensions of sustainability (i.e., economy, environment, and society) is used here for orientation, wherein the overlapping areas are considered as the intersection where sustainable development can take place. Of course, other guidance can be used, e.g., the use of the SDGs can be adapted depending on the assessment context [54]. A useful and

more technical definition of sustainability which applies for HES system technologies as well by Caldeira et al. as follows [56]:

“to deliver its function without exceeding environmental and ecological boundaries along its entire life cycle while providing welfare, socio-economic benefits and reducing externalities”

This definition implies that the given three domains are integral parts of sustainability, highlighting the interdependency of ecological, economical, and societal dimensions. These goals are broadly accepted and applied in a wide range of publications as in Ref. [54], [57], [58]. Considering each domain in its sphere, the following sustainability dimensions can be summarized:

Environmental sustainability involves conserving natural resources and protecting ecosystems to promote human health and wellbeing within planetary limits. To assess environmental sustainability, one must evaluate the impacts materials/products and systems throughout their life cycle, aiming for a **toxic-free environment**, a **climate-neutral economy**, **resource efficiency**, and **biodiversity conservation**.

Economic sustainability encompasses factors like techno-economic feasibility and operational costs. In the context of a life cycle perspective as well as sustainability by design. Economic factors also influence the ranking of materials, products, and technologies. In any case, it's crucial to consider the availability of renewable raw materials; if materials aren't renewable or are scarce and unsustainable sourced, they can't be deemed.

Social sustainability entails various social goals (also covered within the SDGs) such as poverty eradication, food security, health, education, gender equality, decent work, reducing inequalities, and promoting peace and justice. Additionally, aspects such as acceptability of technologies, their value chains, used materials and projects are crucial to consider. Other aspects also entail the creation of local welfare.

5.4 Life cycle perspective

Achieving sustainable technologies by its nature requires a holistic consideration of the technosphere and its interaction with the environment and society. The life cycle perspective aims to understand the interaction of technosphere with ecosphere (atmosphere, biosphere, and lithosphere) using the material and energy flows considering overall supply chain starting from raw materials extraction to end-of-life stage. Since the early 1990s, EU policies have increasingly recognised the significance of adopting a life cycle perspective to assess the sustainability of production and consumption systems. For example, the European Green Deal incorporates various policy initiatives that explicitly acknowledge and incorporate life cycle thinking and methods [59]. There is a high need on perspectives that allow to model the complex interplay of all life cycle stages and provide knowledge on impacts. Thus, Life Cycle Thinking (LCT) and life cycle-based approaches play a crucial role in comparing options and solutions in terms of sustainability. Typical phases in the life cycle of a product usually include [60], [61]:

- The manufacturing phase, encompassing all processes from raw material extraction to delivery to a store or consumer.

- The use phase, the duration of which depends on the product's short or long-term durability.
- The disposal phase, during which portions of the product are partially reused, recycled, or ultimately returned to the natural environment. In contrast, in business administration, the product life cycle represents the journey of a product into the market, where the relationships between generated revenue and the product's market lifespan are the focus of interest.

A proper evaluation of sustainability implications of a HES system requires consideration of all lifecycle stages. The process from raw material extraction to product delivery, known as "cradle-to-gate," or until disposal, referred to as "cradle-to-grave," or, in the case of material reuse as secondary raw materials, "cradle-to-cradle," encompasses the entire lifecycle of a product [62]. In addition, life cycle-based methods enable assessments across environmental, social, and economic dimensions through methodologies like LCA, s-LCA, and LCC. LCSA framework integrates these methodologies to offer a holistic evaluation of a product's life cycle implications [54]. As illustrated in Figure 5.3, an optimized hybrid of two technologies can result in better sustainability characteristics considering the overall lifecycle stages. In practice, it is recommended that for the optimization of hybridized system designs one needs to consider first sustainability of each technology separately to understand in which impact categories hotspots exist, and then how to enhance the overall sustainability performance via simultaneous consideration of all relevant aspects integrated. The hotspots can be associated with used materials, manufacturing, use phase or end-of-life treatment. LCT here provides means for contemplating all crucial aspects widening the perspectives towards enhanced sustainability. For instance, assuming a case where two ES technologies hybridized for extended system lifetime, a significant enhancement can be observed in the sustainability of the ES system due to increased extended service life eliminating additional burdens, where consequently a slight reduction in the service efficiency can occur.

Figure 5.3. Life cycle stages and impact dimensions with tentative indicators for the potential improvement via hybridization. (Abbreviations used in the figure, EST: Energy Storage Technology, GWP: Global warming potential, FFD: Fossil fuel depletion, AP: Acidification potential, EP: Eutrophication potential)

Hence, incorporating lifecycle perspective in the sustainability assessments is useful for determining the trade-offs. Covering all life cycle stages through all dimensions provides a robust base for decisions about sustainability of HES technologies. Even though it is a complex task, available and emerging sustainability assessment frameworks serve here as a starting point employing methods and tools with well described assessment procedures. In the following, considering the ES technologies and

sustainability, some guidance is provided incorporating LCT for complete and comprehensive assessments.

5.5 Creating the Links Between Technical and Sustainability Spheres

Beyond the techno-economic benefit accomplished via hybridization, additional benefits can be achieved in terms of sustainability. Here, the definition of sustainability KPIs enables adequate consideration and monitoring of caused impacts across all dimensions in both quantitative and qualitative ways. Mostly, established methodologies deliver results for a set of pre-defined KPIs, however, a reverse approach can be used to first determine relevant KPIs and subsequently choose a compatible methodology for providing the aimed KPI results. Following the first approach can provide practical guidance since the assessment procedures are defined considering the subsequent steps. An example is illustrated in Figure 5.4, where the SDGs are set as focal points classified under sustainability domains, identifying the areas of protection, and sustainability indicators to be considered for achieving these goals [63], while showing the linkage between technical and sustainability spheres.

Figure 5.4. Summary of the hierarchical framework for the formulation of sustainability assessments.

It is often perceived as a challenge to create the links between technological aspects and their implications for the assessment framework. Noting that there is not only one correct approach for accomplishing this it is recommended to follow an iterative approach when conducting sustainability assessments paying attention to the goal and scope, technical KPIs, and adopted methodological framework. This should potentially serve for better identification of suitable technical KPIs which will lead to an adequate consideration and estimation of indicator results [64]. In general, KPIs serve as crucial and quantifiable metrics allowing to monitor if desired outcomes, in this case fulfilling sustainability criteria, is achieved. Criteria define the essential elements or dimensions against which sustainability is assessed. Each criterion relates to a key element of sustainability and may be described by one or more KPIs [65]. There exist many frameworks where certain guidance is provided for incorporating indicators into assessment procedures for business practices. Sugai and coll. [66], screened 15 global top sustainability reporting frameworks¹, revealing 360 publicly reported micro-KPIs. The collected micro-KPIs are then grouped under macro-KPIs aligned with stakeholder categories as tabulated in Table 5.1.

Table 5.1. Macro-KPIs considered in sustainability reporting frameworks [66].

		SDGs	GRI	GIIN-IRIS	SASB	BIA	JUST 2.0	Natural Capital Protocol	Social & Human Capital Protocol	Common Approach to Impact	TOMs Framework	Shared Value	B-Team	Organizational Guidance System	McKinsey	Cradle to Cradle
Employee	Diversity & Equity	•	•	•	•		•		•		•		•			
	Fair Wages		•	•		•	•			•						
	Health, Welfare, Safety		•			•	•	•	•		•	•		•	•	
	Development	•	•	•		•	•		•	•				•		
	Engagement and Satisfaction		•		•	•	•		•					•		
	Human Rights	•	•	•					•				•			
Environment	Waste and Pollution	•	•	•	•	•		•			•		•			
	Water	•	•	•	•	•		•								
	Energy	•	•		•			•				•				
	Products		•		•	•	•	•			•	•				•
	Biodiversity	•	•	•			•	•			•			•		
	Buildings				•	•					•					
Society	Taxes		•						•							
	Local Community Development	•	•			•			•		•	•		•		•
	Local Employment and Engagement		•			•	•		•		•					

¹(1) the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), (2) the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI), (3) Global Impact Investing's GIIN-IRIS+, (4) the Sustainability Accounting Standards Board (SASB), (5) B-Lab's B Impact Assessment (BIA), (6) the International Living Future Institute's JUST 2.0, The Capitals Coalition's (7) Natural Capital Protocol and (8) Social & Human Capital Protocol, Canada's (9) Common Approach to Impact Measurement, The UK's (10) The National TOMs Framework, Michael Porter's (11) Measuring Shared Value, Richard Branson's (12) The B-Team, RBL's (13) Organizational Guidance System, (14) McKinsey's Five Fifty psychological safety framework, and McDonough & Braungart's, and (15) Cradle to Cradle Certification.

	Charity and Volunteer						•	•						•					
Firms	Reporting	•	•	•			•											•	
	Governance		•	•			•										•	•	
	Management Capability																		
Customer	Relationship		•	•															
	Privacy		•	•	•	•							•						
	Satisfaction, Health & Safety	•	•	•			•						•					•	
Partner	Reporting		•	•			•						•						
	Structure		•	•			•	•				•			•				
	Environment and Society		•	•			•	•					•						
	Fair Labour		•	•	•								•						

The provided screening and grouping shows that existing frameworks differ in terms of impact dimensions and stakeholders in their scope. Hence, provided macro-KPIs and stakeholder groups in scope can be useful for choosing from suitable sustainability reporting frameworks which falls to the identification of micro-KPIs and methods for estimating them.

5.6 Technical KPIs for ES Technologies

This subchapter aims to provide a brief overview of most common technical KPIs which must be considered due to their implications on sustainability indicators, explaining the structure of assessment frameworks and creating the links between various sustainability domains and technosphere. Technical KPIs are aggregated compact parameters, which enable representation of a complex technological system in single quantitative terms. Hence, they are great helpers simplifying the modelling procedure of complex systems into terms, which will be interpreted into sustainability KPIs with the aid of the used tool. Table 5.2 provides a very brief overview of commonly adopted technical KPIs for most of the ES technologies attributing energy- and power-related KPIs, time, and efficiency. The given KPIs can be shortened or extended depending on the technological relevance, design criteria, and designated services.

Table 5.2. Relevant KPIs for ES based on Technical sphere [22].

	Indicators	Unit	Short Description
Power related	Power (P)	W	Power = Energy per time
	Power Density (P _d)	W/kg, W/m ³	Usable power per mass or volumetric unit
	Stand by losses (P _l)	W	Power losses
	Power gradient (P _g)	W/s	Speed to store or release Power
Energy related	Energy (E), Work (W)	Wh	Usable energy from a storage unit
	Energy density (e)	Wh/kg, Wh/m ³	Usable amount of energy per mass or volume
	Discharged energy (E _d)	Wh	Available energy after discharge for specific services
Time and efficiency	Losses	Wh	Losses during charging, storing, and discharging
	Charge duration (C _d)	S	Duration of charging process
	Self-discharge rate (S _{dl})	% per day, per week, per month	Share of lost energy over a defined period.
	Storage duration (t _s)	S	Time of storage
	Discharge duration t _d	S	Duration of discharge process
	Charging efficiency (η _{in})	%	Efficiency of charging conversion process
	Storage efficiency (η _{out})	%	Efficiency of storage process
	Total efficiency (η _{total})	%	Efficiency of an entire storage cycle
	Full load hours (FLH)	h/a	time for which an ES works at it nominal power

Usually, different ES systems have different performances when it comes to sustainability, which needs to be evaluated considering all lifecycle stages. For example, in the case of lithium-based battery systems based on, e.g., lithium-nickel-manganese-cobalt oxide ($\text{Li}(\text{NiMnCo})\text{O}_2$), resource criticality plays a high role, whilst this does not play a significant role for flywheels (except if magnetic bearings are used with permanent magnets containing NdFeB or SmCo, etc.). Here ideally, HES system, combining different technologies mitigate such drawbacks, by providing a superior performance to single, conventional storage solutions.

5.7 Impact Allocation

A very critical aspect when assessing the sustainability of HES systems is applying a proper allocation method which enables allocation of impacts correctly. Allocation approaches play a crucial role in sustainability assessment by determining how resources, impacts, or responsibilities are distributed among various entities or factors. These approaches are integral to understanding the allocation of costs, benefits, and environmental burdens within complex systems. Eventually, impact allocation reveals the contribution of various actors causing these impacts within the whole supply chain and identifies what/who is the cause of the beared consequences by other actors. This relation has a strong influence in reflecting the responsibility of stakeholders against each other.

The combination of different ES technologies in one system extends the boundaries of the covered product system, making it a more complex system to analyse. Furthermore, choosing an allocation method becomes even more challenging when the scope is further enlarged, e.g. when recycling is considered. Here further methods can be used, e.g. avoided burden or mass balance approach (e.g., as in LCA see Ref. [67]). For a HES system, it is important to identify the processes within the product system of hybridized technologies capturing the entire life cycle stages. The impacts stemming from the overall lifecycle stages of the hybridized system, and the contribution of each ES technology on the estimated impacts can be investigated properly with allocation methods. In general, the chosen allocation methods show differences depending on the covered sustainability domain and methodology, in line with the goal and scope of the conducted assessment. However, commonly used allocation methods are contribution analysis and system expansion (in LCA), environmental responsibility allocation and footprint analysis (in Input-Output Analysis), weighted criteria allocation and scoring allocation (in Cost-benefit Analysis) and so forth [68]–[70]. Noting that the chosen allocation method will influence the results significantly, the most commonly used allocation methods that are applicable as well for HES technologies herein described briefly:

Physical Allocation: Allocating impacts based on physical properties such as mass, volume, or energy content of each technology component. For example, if a system comprises lithium-ion batteries and flywheel ES, the impacts can be allocated based on the ES capacity of each component.

Economic (Value) Allocation: Allocating impacts based on the economic value or cost of each technology component. This method assigns a portion of the impacts to each component based on its contribution to the overall cost of the system, or the service value generated by each component of a HES system.

System Expansion Allocation: This method considers the impacts of producing additional units of each technology component to meet the demand for the functional unit. It evaluates the impacts of increasing the production of each component in isolation.

It is challenging to define an optimal allocation method since for each of the methods certain reasoning exists which cannot be strictly right wised. Nonetheless, the explained methods here find general acceptance in many sustainability assessment frameworks also considering their compatibility of the assessed subject (i.e., ES and energy supply). Furthermore, more details on different allocation methods are provided in the methods section and the corresponding input papers (see [Chapter 5.8](#) in [APPENDIX D.](#)).

5.8 System boundaries

An important step for sustainability assessment approaches is the definition of an appropriate system and its borders. This is of high relevance to understand the scope of the study and potential impacts of the analysed system. Every system is always in interrelation with its environment. Over its borders, there is a continuous flow of in and outputs as depicted in a schematic way for a technological system and a market as indicated in Figure 5.5. This approach makes it possible to understand major dynamics inhibited in such a system and to identify enablers that might lead to a better system in terms of sustainability. For a HES system, these boundaries include not only the ES units themselves, but also associated components like converters, control systems, and integration infrastructure.

Figure 5.5. Scheme for the interrelation of a technological system showing the exchange of services and money with its environment [71].

Beyond that, depending on the applied method, system boundaries might extend from raw material extraction through to end-of-life disposal or recycling, encompassing all stages of production, operation, and decommissioning. As an example, LCA can evaluate environmental impacts across these stages, assessing factors such as resource consumption, emissions, and potential ecosystem impacts. Different than that, the LCC considers the economic implications throughout the system's life cycle, including initial investment, maintenance costs, and revenue generation. However, there are some general recommendations that can be given for the definition of system boundaries:

- **Life cycle perspective:** System boundaries should cover all life cycle stages, if possible, from raw materials, manufacturing, use and recycling or disposal.
- **Scope of analysis:** The scope must be defined clearly, e.g., which components of a HES system (batteries, capacitors, flywheel etc.), and if balance of the whole plant is considered.

- **Functional unit:** consistent functional unit for comparison purposes, such as energy stored, power output, or service provided, to ensure meaningful comparisons between different HES system configurations or alternatives.
- **Direct and indirect impacts:** direct impacts (e.g., emissions, resource consumption) and indirect impacts (e.g., land use change, supply chain impacts) associated with the production, operation, and disposal of the HES system components.
- **Boundary exclusion:** It is important to clearly state which component and processes are excluded in the assessment and to provide a justification.
- **System interaction:** Interactions between the HES system and its surrounding environment should be considered (including the grid, renewable energy sources, energy demand patterns, and potential impacts on ecosystem services or social dynamics).
- **Temporal considerations:** consider temporal variations in impacts, entailing, e.g., changes in energy demand over time or changing technological properties, different socio-demographic conditions.
- **Spatial considerations:** consider variations in impacts, entailing, e.g., differences in environmental conditions across regions, different energy mixes, socio demographics.

Detailed information on further aspects related to system boundaries can be found in Ref. [60] and will be further specified in the method sections and the corresponding input papers.

5.9 Stakeholder involvement

As mentioned above, there are different stakeholders relevant for the development of HES system, such as technology developers, citizens, political decision-makers. However, when carrying out a sustainability assessment there might be more groups that should be involved. In general involvement can happen in different ways when it comes to sustainability and the level might vary from informing, through consulting and involving, to collaborating with stakeholders [72]. It is of utmost importance to consider relevant stakeholders for the assessment of HES systems. Their selection and legitimacy are critical elements, and these are the most important challenges in sustainability assessment. There are various examples of how to involve stakeholders, within different decision-making steps [48]. Different stakeholders can express their views/perspectives towards different sustainability dimensions as in the case of weight elicitation in decision analysis [28]. In addition, their inputs can help to check if all relevant sustainability aspects are covered. Involving stakeholders can also help to prioritize different sustainability aspects and thus ensure that an adequate focus is put to certain dimensions via weights for different sustainability criteria [73]. The involvement of stakeholders can also be dependent on the used sustainability assessment methodology, where for example in s-LCA five main stakeholder groups are considered: (i) worker, (ii) consumer, (iii) local community, (iv) society and (v) value chain actors [74], [75]. At the end involving stakeholders ensures/assures that decisions are well-informed, balanced, and aligned with stakeholder interests and concerns. Furthermore, it promotes transparency, inclusivity, and accountability while ensuring that the assessment addresses the most relevant sustainability aspect.

5.10 Decision Tree for Sustainability assessment of HES technologies

An exemplary decision tree (see [APPENDIX B., Figure B.1.](#)) is provided to guide sustainability-oriented hybridization decisions for the ES systems. The decision tree consists of question and action blocks defining the paths and corresponding actions to identify the answers which will lead to decisions on applicability of hybridization. Corresponding assessment requirements, necessary for decisions, are integrated within the action blocks to address the role of assessments in decision-making. Moreover, the decision tree also incorporates the role of stakeholders as a fundamental element of decision-making process in a customizable generic format. By this way, as it referred very often in the sustainability context three dimensions are covered considering interdependencies, engaging stakeholder perspectives, and evaluating the whole spectrum of technology options. Since the provided decision-tree offers a very compact version of important constraints and aspects it can just serve as a tentative or preliminary orientation. A more advanced practice which contains the same principles but deepening each of these steps is the multi-criteria decision analysis approach, which is elaborated in this guideline (see [Chapter 7. Decision-making Aid for Promoting Future HES system Applications: A Working Example from StoRIES](#)) and is recommended for guiding and comprehending HES application decisions at later stages.

5.11 Business Sustainability Canvas Template

Business canvas templates (also referred as “business model canvas”) are strategic tools used by entrepreneurs and businesses to visualize, analyse, and communicate various aspects of their business model in a concise format. Typically presented as a one-page document, these templates consist of key components such as customer segments, value propositions, channels, customer relationships, revenue streams, key resources, key activities, key partnerships, and cost structure [76]. By filling out each section of the canvas, organizations can gain a holistic understanding of their business model, identify potential strengths and weaknesses, and iterate on their strategies accordingly. Business canvas templates provide a framework for brainstorming, planning, and refining business ideas, making them invaluable tools for startups, established companies, and even academic institutions seeking to innovate or evaluate new ventures. The abundance of versions of the business canvas template stems from its adaptable nature, catering to diverse industries, strategic approaches, and user preferences. These variations arise to meet specific needs, incorporate emerging trends, and accommodate customization by entrepreneurs and business professionals. The high variety of templates reflects the dynamic and evolving nature of business strategy and innovation.

In the sustainability context, with its considered comprehensive aspects, business canvas templates can indeed serve for developing HES system business cases. Benefiting from the customizable structure of the template, the conventional business canvas template has been slightly modified in frame of StoRIES as presented in Figure 5.6. To do so, the default block for identifying value propositions is extended including sustainability goals, and an additional block called “regulatory framework” has been integrated into the template to address legislative aspects due to its high relevance. Furthermore, it has been understood over the course of time that a classical business development approach is too abstract if sustainability aspects shall be considered, since non-monetizable aspects are not clearly

addressed. Ongoing discussions showed the need for modifying the business canvas template in a way to address different sustainability domains not adopting an economic-centred perspective as in the default layout. To incorporate sustainability into a business canvas template environmental, social, and economic considerations need to be integrated. In quest for better representation, a brief literature screening proved some attempts addressing this matter [77]–[80]. In particular, the Triple Layered Business Model Canvas (TLBMC) proposed by Joyce and Paquin has been used in the energy field to analyse and improve business models. In the context of sustainable energy systems, it provides a comprehensive template covering all aspects for capturing the sustainability domains [81]. In their work the vertical and horizontal coherence of the three layers is featured. The horizontal coherence is implicit by the definition or name of the layer, since for example the ecological layer mainly focusses on the ecological aspects, the social layer on the social ones. The vertical coherence means, that the layers should not act independently, but rather each box should exist in each layer, but with a different angle of view. To give an example the box “resources” in the “original” “economic only” centred version of the canvas FEATURES materials in the ecologic layer (meaning for example raw material which must be used) and employees in the social layer, being also valuable resources for the business case to address identified aspects more straightforward.

Business Model Canvas

Figure 5.6. First version of the StoRIES Business Canvas Template. (see [Figure C.1](#) in [APPENDIX C](#) for a larger format of the figure)

To name a second example found in literature Pappas et al. (2023) modified the TLBMC to analyse smart and local energy systems (SLES) projects, incorporating environmental and social value into the

PU

analysis [82]. They found that the value proposition of SLES extends beyond economic value and includes environmental and social value. This framework helps stakeholders to identify and add environmental and social value to their business models. (further ref [83]–[85]) The last version of StoRIES Business Canvas Template shows an attempt to look at each of the boxes from a different angle to also grasp the ecological and social impacts synthesizing different perspectives, gained through the conducted literature research as presented in Figure 5.7. In following the three-layer approach was chosen by simultaneously trying to be able to depict the template on one A4 page rather than three separate pages addressing different dimensions. The template was readjusted to also account for the other layers. The different layers (horizontal coherence) are thereby symbolized by a color scheme where blue, green, and red colors correspond to economic, environmental, and social aspects, respectively.

Business Model Canvas

Figure 5.7. Second version of the StoRIES business canvas template. (see [Figure C.2](#) in [APPENDIX C](#), for a larger format of the figure)

As an annex, the canvas applied to specific use cases can be found in different versions. An aluminium wet combustion system for electricity and hydrogen supply for EV refuelling stations or Home Storage Battery + hot water tank (for household) were chosen as examples (see [Figure C.3 – C.7](#) in [APPENDIX C](#).) among others. Here the evolution of the template can be seen since some examples are provided for the first as well as for the second version of the template, showing the more in-depth analysis in the second version.

6 METHODS FOR SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT

In reference to the definitions and background provided in [Chapter 5. Sustainability Assessment for HES Systems](#), this section introduces sustainability assessment methods. Specifically, it covers those identified in frame of the project, aiming to elucidate their methodological capabilities. Sustainability assessment in general functions as a unifying framework, blending various analytical methods and models tailored for specific applications. It considers decision contexts, multidisciplinary aspects, and value-based elements. An effective and comprehensive sustainability assessment ideally adopts LCT perspectives, considering multiple dimensions and engaging stakeholders adequately to address the sustainability needs of the ES field. Furthermore, the chosen framework should accommodate various scales and target values, allowing for the weighting of indicators within and across the three dimensions of sustainability. Methodological frameworks and assessment methods vary primarily due to differing perspectives, such as monetary, material flow-based, multicriteria, and indicator-based approaches (e.g., as discussed in Ref. [64], [86], [87]). These aspects can all be integrated into assessments through two approaches. Firstly, by incorporating sustainability criteria and aspects into existing assessment approaches, similar to a reductionist approach. Secondly, by conducting separate studies for the three sustainability dimensions followed by result consolidation. In the context of integrated sustainability assessment, it is necessary to blend different methods, models, and indicators [48]. Available methods can be clustered with regards to sustainability dimensions and scale level (macro-, meso-, product- and material level) as displayed in Table 6.1.

Table 6.1. Levels and dimensions of different sustainability assessments methodologies and frameworks, own table based on [6].

	Environmental	Economic	Social	Integrative
Macroeconomic level (e.g. national energy system)	-	Macroeconomic calculus (e.g. MRIO)	-	MCDA
Meso-level (e.g. sectors, local energy systems)	Ecologic Input-out analyses / hybrid MRIO/LCA	-	Socio-Economic Assessment	MCDA
Product Level (e.g. HES system unit)	Life cycle assessment, material flow analysis	Life Cycle costing, LCOE, LCOx,	Social Life Cycle Assessment, Social Return on Investment	LCSA, MCDA
Material level (e.g. cathode materials)	Simple MFA, LCA, Criticality assessment	Cost screening	S-LCA	MCDA

A significant challenge was accessing studies or project reports that offer methodological insights, specifically for assessing the sustainability of HES technologies. All frameworks or methodologies must be carefully selected, considering the study's goals and scope.

6.1 Guidance to use the input papers

The following provides an overview of the four types of methodologies and frameworks in a general manner to offer a quick understanding of the different methods considered. Detailed explanations of each methodology and framework have been compiled following the methodology outlined in [Chapter 2. Methodology](#) and provided via following appended input papers:

[APPENDIX D. Input Paper: Economic Aspects](#)

[APPENDIX E. Input Paper: Environmental Aspects](#)

[APPENDIX F. Input Paper: Social Aspects](#)

[APPENDIX G. Input Paper: Integrative Aspects](#)

[APPENDIX H. Use Cases Selection for Sustainability assessment of HES Systems](#)

Additionally, a brief review of relevant studies applying the named methodology and framework in the context of both ES and HES systems is provided, supplementing data for assessing the sustainability across economic, environmental, and social dimensions as well as integrated assessment frameworks employing these methods for HES and ES in general. As previously mentioned, while numerous sustainability approaches exist, this document focuses on the most pertinent ones, considering regulatory frameworks, emerging issues across various dimensions, and key policy orientation such as the SDGs. The guideline document advocates for the integrated model of sustainability as the basis for structuring methods, depicted in Figure 6.1.

Figure 6.1. Integrated concept of sustainability with corresponding methods

Subsequent sections of this chapter offer condensed versions of the input papers. Generally, these input papers are organized around the three dimensions of sustainability (environmental, social, and economic) and frameworks that amalgamate these dimensions.

Table 6.2. Input paper structure for each methodology or framework considered.

Sections	Explanation
Synonyms / Other Related Methods	Common name including abbreviations, synonyms.
Assessment Level	Which disciplines are addressed, what is the scope (e.g. Process, System...).
Short Description	Brief description of focus of each methodology or framework.
Scope	Main application describing nation, unit, company/organization, process, product/service, person/lifestyle, product/services.
Methodology	Brief description of the procedure including main steps and “how to” guideline to start with corresponding assessments-
Dimensions and indicators	Assignment to the dimension(s) of sustainability covered by the corresponding methodology or framework-
Applications in the Field of (Hybrid) ES	establishing the application reference for energy storage (if available).
Data Availability	Explanations of specific data quality requirements, data sources, notes on data procurement and/or collection,
Reporting	Notes on reporting requirements, on standard practice
Strengths and Weaknesses	Discussion of advantages and disadvantages or opportunities and challenges are provided in text and table form
Standards and Guidelines	Information about guidelines and recognized standards, further literature
Use Cases	Mini Review on different ES use cases in form of a table. Here the aim, technology, use case as well as functional unit is considered, also general comments to each source is provided

6.2 Economic methods

The market success of ES systems heavily relies on their cost performance. Additionally, creating viable business cases, as well as corresponding regulations for the economically feasible operation of HES is a fundamental prerequisite. To evaluate the economic aspects of HES systems quantitatively various methods can be applied. Specifically, for storage technologies, the common practice involves different services, often represented by levelized cost of X (LCOX), where X denotes various energy vectors, alongside other currency per functional unit variations. Furthermore, different indicators can be utilized for analysing ES, which depend on factors such as the selected region, corresponding markets, specific use cases, and ownership structure. As a result, deriving general benchmarks without adequate consideration of potential ES value streams is challenging. Also, contrasting the cost performance of a given technology with a state-of-the-art reference of similar design and purpose is recommended. Considering the diverse stakeholders involved in different life-cycle stages, conventional and integrated LCC estimation methods are also useful tools as explained.

The following section will provide a compact overview of the selected methods:

- Static and dynamic basic calculation methods.
- Life cycle costing methods and application.
- Levelized cost of energy calculation methods for various energy vectors and services.
- Allocation approaches.
- Socio economic analysis (SEA).

Economic assessments for ES technologies necessitate detailed information, often requiring reasonable assumptions considering the significance of TRLs and data availability. An overview of fundamental parameters and key performance indicators (KPIs) calculations required for the following economic assessment methods. Verified expert judgments are crucial, especially for capital-intensive projects, where cost complexity is high. Various methods like engineering cost, cost accounting, analogy, and parametric approaches are used to estimate the total cost of ownership (TCO) employing bottom-up and top-down approaches. An elaborated version of the introduced methods and practical guidance on how to conduct corresponding assessments can be found in the corresponding input paper in [APPENDIX D](#).

6.2.1 Life Cycle Costing

LCC (also referred as TCO) is one of the most common methods to analyse the economic dimension of a product in a standardized way. In addition to conventional LCC which monetary value oriented, the LCC methodology includes with its variations Environmental Life Cycle Costing (e-LCC) and Social or Societal LCC (s-LCC) serves as a method for evaluating investment alternatives throughout their life cycle and is part of techno-economic assessments. Considering these variations, the purely economic perspective of conventional LCC extends covering external costs (i.e., environmental and social costs). Mostly, the scope of LCC is on a product level, covering a "cradle-to-grave" perspective and can be applied universally [88], [89]. Although data collection and data availability can be challenging for LCC various methods such as parametric cost methods and analogous cost methods, used for estimation, help to overcome these challenges. Calculation methods for LCC involve static and dynamic approaches, with discounted dynamic methods like net present value (NPV) and annuity method commonly applied [90]. To ensure robustness of the results a sensitivity analysis should be conducted, e.g., by alternating central parameters. Additionally, while there are no standard reporting formats, transparency and traceability of data and modelling approaches are highly important [91].

6.2.2 Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOX)

Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOX) and its related methods, such as Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCOE), Levelized Cost of Energy Storage (LCOS), Levelized Cost of Hydrogen (LCOH₂), and Levelized Cost of Heat (LCOHeat) are widely applied methods, accepted for techno-economic assessments [92]. Typically, they are carried out on product level (e.g., for ES and HES systems), but can also be applied on a meso- and macro-level. The LCOX method is utilized to compare the actual costs of various ES and HES systems, considering their full life cycle costs per unit of energy produced or delivered. The term

“levelized” refers to the average net present cost. It enables stakeholders to compare technologies regardless of size, cost structure, or useful life. Widely applied in investment decisions for conventional and renewable energies, LCOX models are used at national and regional levels for energy system design, generation projections, and technology assessments. The calculation involves comparing all costs that incurred over the lifetime of a technology for production and operation with the total amount of energy generated or delivered, typically over a 20 to 40-year period depending on the analysed ES and HES systems. The method considers factors like capital expenditure, operation expenditure, and discount rates [93]. Variants of LCOX, including LCOE, LCOS, LCOH₂, LCOHeat, and LCOU, are described in the input paper, each tailored to specific energy domains aiding in benchmarking of relative costs and assessing economic feasibility. However, challenges exist in data availability, particularly in the dynamic development of technology costs and uncertainties associated with input parameters. While LCOX provides a simplified metric for economic evaluation, its narrow viewpoint (i.e., purely economic) and dependence on assumptions require careful consideration and substantiated assumptions for accurate comparisons.

6.2.3 Socioeconomic analysis (SEA)

Socioeconomic analysis (SEA) or Socio-Economic Impact Assessment (SEIA) is a structured process aimed at understanding the benefits and drawbacks of various processes or developments for communities. Here the scope is on a meso-level. It assesses impacts across different disciplines and scopes, including social, economic, cultural, and environmental aspects. SEA evaluates costs against benefits, aiming to identify and quantify potential impacts on individuals, groups, and communities. The method considers stakeholders' perspectives and policy implications. Key components encompass health, sustainable livelihoods, cultural preservation, and infrastructure sustainability. Various analysis techniques such as fiscal analysis, input/output analysis, cost-benefit analysis, and risk-benefit analysis are employed to assess project viability and societal value [94]. Indicators measure progress across different sectors, guiding decision-making, and planning processes. SEA provides valuable insights into the socio-economic dimensions of proposed developments, facilitating informed decision-making and mitigation strategies. Standards and guidelines from organizations like UNESCO offer frameworks for conducting robust socio-economic assessments.

6.3 Environmental methods

The European Commission identified ES systems as a crucial element due to its role for achieving the transition towards circular economy [95]. Moreover, as outlined in the European directive on batteries and accumulators and waste batteries and accumulators [96], the eco-efficiency and environmental impact reduction of ES systems during their whole life cycle, the manufacturing of storage systems containing small quantities of dangerous and polluting substances, and the promotion of secure and low-impact raw materials are key considerations for their sustainability. The role of ES systems in the decarbonization process highlights the need to support the growth of a manufacturing industry with the minimized environmental footprint, as specified by the European Battery Alliance [97]. The manufacturing of low-impact products starts with the consideration of embodied environmental impacts from raw material supply to end-of-life. These environmental impacts must be identified by

following an LCT approach, which means looking at its whole life cycle and considering all the environmental impacts (e.g., raw material consumption and emissions into air, water, and soil). The LCT approach can identify production strategies that are able to reduce negative environmental effects [98]. In the following sections, a brief overview of some of the most relevant methods/concepts for assessing the environmental performance of storage systems will be provided:

- Material Flow Analysis.
- Life Cycle Assessment.
- Criticality Assessment.
- Hybrid Multi Regional Input Output - Life Cycle Assessment.
- Consideration of Circular economy aspects.

Elaborated versions of the named methods can be found in [Chapter 3-7](#) in [APPENDIX E](#).

6.3.1 Material Flow Analysis

Material Flow Analysis (MFA) records and describes interconnected material flows, employing scientific calculations for interpretation [99]. It encompasses various scopes such as country/region, company/organization, process, and product/service levels, utilizing models ranging from first-principles to data models [100]. MFA explores material throughput across processes like extraction, manufacturing, consumption, and disposal within defined system boundaries and timeframes [99]. Dynamic MFA accounts for changes in stocks over time, aiding in scenario planning and investment decisions [101]. (Dynamic) probabilistic MFA integrates uncertainties into flow modelling, useful for environmental assessments, especially in emerging fields like nanotechnology [102], [103]. An expansion of MFA is Material and Energy Flow Accounting (MEFA), analysing socio-economic metabolism and energy flows, vital for understanding societal interactions with ecosystems [104], [105]. MEFA aligns with Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) in environmental assessments, providing insights into resource usage and environmental impacts [106]. Despite its strengths in scientific rigor and visualization, MFA lacks consideration for potential environmental damages [99], [105]. Guidelines and standards like those from the University of Freiburg offer frameworks for MFA and socio-metabolic research [107]. Use cases illustrate MFA's applicability in environmental policy, urban planning, and industrial ecosystem analysis [108]–[110].

6.3.2 Life cycle assessment

The Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), also referred to as Life Cycle Analysis (LCA), is a methodical approach aimed at providing a comprehensive evaluation of the environmental impacts associated with products and services throughout their entire life cycle. LCA quantifies potential environmental consequences from the initial extraction of raw materials, through production, use, and eventual disposal or recycling, offering insights into environmental "hot-spots" and opportunities for enhancement. With its perspective, LCA encompasses a wide range of applications, including informing designers about the ecological ramifications of their creations, comparing different products and services, aiding in planning and marketing decisions, and even guiding public policy-making processes.

The methodology of LCA involves four main phases: scope and goal definition, LCI, life cycle impact assessment (LCIA), and interpretation. In the scope and goal definition phase, the purpose and scope of the analysis are defined, establishing the functional unit to be studied and defining system boundaries. LCI involves analysing material and energy flows throughout the life cycle of the product or service, where data reliability and quality must be ensured. LCIA assesses the potential environmental impacts associated with the identified resource use and emissions, while the interpretation phase focuses on the results and communicates them effectively to decision-makers. It is crucial to mention that the four phases are not carried out sequentially but carried out in an iterative way [111].

Within LCA, various impact categories are considered, such as resource depletion, global warming potential, ozone depletion potential, human toxicity potential, and ecotoxicity potential, among others. These categories aid decision-makers in understanding environmental trade-offs and complexities within analysed products and systems, guiding them towards more sustainable choices. Despite its strengths, LCA faces challenges related to data availability, interpretation, and standardization. While international standards like ISO 14040 provide a framework for conducting LCA studies, there's still a need for sector-specific standards, particularly in areas such as ES systems. LCA is a powerful tool for environmental assessment, providing a comprehensive view of a product or service's environmental impacts and helping stakeholders to make informed decisions. Through its use, LCA contributes to raising awareness of environmental consequences. There are several use cases available for ES and HES systems as [112], [113].

6.3.3 Criticality Assessment

Criticality Assessment (CA) encompasses several methodologies aimed at evaluating the interplay between risk factors associated with availability disruptions and the inherent vulnerability of systems to such perturbations, with an emphasis on minerals and materials. Whereas earlier discourses predominantly focus on energy dependencies, the contemporary CA paradigm places a more spotlight on minerals, frequently in tandem with life cycle approaches, signifying an evolving perspective. There is a wide set of frameworks developed to address the complex landscape of criticality. One such framework is the EU-CRM List [114], evaluating critical raw materials based on their supply risk and economic importance, thereby spotting materials considered as indispensable to the EU's economy yet associated with high supply risk. Conversely, the GeoPolRisk methodology adopts a geopolitical lens, calculating supply risk from a different perspective and considering geopolitical dynamics and domestic production, enriching the criticality discourse with geopolitical insights [115], [116]. The ESSENZ methodology offers a comprehensive characterization approach with global applicability, integrating socio-economic, environmental, and geopolitical indicators to paint a holistic portrait of criticality [117]. In a similar way, the SPOTTER methodology emerges as a foresight approach, not only assessing short-term supply disruption impacts but also casting its gaze into the medium-term horizon, thereby empowering stakeholders address impending future risks [118]. These methodologies cover several dimensions—geological, technological, geopolitical, social, and environmental—facilitating the understanding of criticality over disciplinary boundaries [119]. Nevertheless, challenges persist, including data scarcity and methodological disparities, and the absence of a standardized approach.

Despite these impediments, CA's versatility finds resonance across diverse industries, spanning from battery technologies to fuel cells, offering invaluable insights into resource scarcity, sustainability screening, and strategic decision-making across the energy landscape and beyond.

6.3.4 Hybrid Multi Regional Input Output - Life Cycle Assessment

[Chapter 6.3.2](#) introduced LCA as a widely utilized method for estimating environmental impacts of products and services, yet it's constrained by the need for detailed technical data and extensive time requirements. LCA practitioners often define system boundaries, leading to truncation errors where processes beyond these boundaries are considered negligible, potentially underestimating environmental impacts [120]. Input-Output (IO) Analysis, particularly its multiregional version (MRIO), is increasingly used but suffers from highly aggregated representations of processes, affecting accuracy. To address these limitations, hybrid approaches like Hybrid LCA-MRIO have been proposed, aiming to combine the completeness of IO Analysis with the technological representativeness of LCA. However, different hybridization methods have their limitations, such as double counting, overestimation, and increased complexity, posing challenges for accurate environmental assessment [121].

6.3.5 Consideration of Circular economy aspects

Circular economy (CE) is rather a concept that entails maintaining the value of products, materials, and resources in the economy for as long as possible while minimizing waste generation, diverging from the linear "take-make-use-dispose" model to a regenerative growth model. CE operates under the principles of reduce, reuse, recycle, and recover, aiming to extend product lifecycles and increase resource productivity [122]–[124]. Circular business models (CBMs) are crucial in this transition, representing different approaches to producing and consuming goods and services sustainably, with categories like circular supply models and product life extension models [125]. CE spans environmental, economic, and social dimensions of sustainability, with indicators including resource pressure and typical CE indicators. While CE offers numerous benefits such as reducing waste and emissions, creating new markets, and improving resource efficiency, challenges include its developmental stage, the need for significant changes in business models and technology, and the requirement for synchronized participation among stakeholders. Standards and guidelines for CE are under development, with use cases including eco-design of battery cells and second life applications for batteries in buildings and vehicles.

6.4 Social dimension

Assessing the social implications within the ES field is essential for ensuring its sustainable development and widespread adoption [126]. Beyond technological advancements and economic feasibility, understanding the social impacts of ES systems throughout their lifecycle is crucial. These assessments help identify potential disparities in access, affordability, and distribution of benefits, ensuring that ES solutions contribute positively to society. Moreover, addressing social considerations such as community engagement, job creation, and cultural sensitivities can enhance acceptance and facilitate smoother integration of ES projects into communities. By prioritizing social assessment

alongside technical and economic evaluations, the ES sector can foster equitable and inclusive energy transitions while mitigating potential risks and conflicts associated with the material supply chain. Compared to the environmental or economic assessments, the social counterpart is a relatively new research field and literature covering social aspects of ES systems are scarce regarding economic and environmental dimensions [127]. Moreover, availability and application of these methods is an untapped focus area considering emerging ES technologies and HES systems. Methods for the assessment of social aspects can be situated within the general sustainability framing, hence following methods are covered in this context:

- S- LCA.
- Social Footprint/Social Handprint.
- Social Impact Assessment.
- Social Return on Investment.
- Technology acceptance.

In the following, these methods are introduced briefly where further methodological elaboration is provided in [Chapter 3-7](#) in [APPENDIX F](#).

6.4.1 Social LCA

Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) is an extension of the LCA framework, aiming to identify social hotspots and delve deeper into the life cycle of a product to enhance stakeholder living conditions [60]. It can be used independently or combined with other methods like LCA and LCC within LCSA. S-LCA assesses potential impacts on stakeholders' wellbeing across different stages of a product's life cycle, offering flexibility in scope from cradle-to-grave to gate-to-gate analyses. Methodological advancements are ongoing, with efforts to align S-LCA with ISO standards and develop quantitative approaches. Use cases include assessing social sustainability hotspots of lithium-ion batteries, impacts of responsible sourcing initiatives for cobalt [128], and addressing data gaps in social life cycle inventory analysis, particularly in cobalt mining contexts [129].

6.4.2 Social Footprint/Social Handprint

The concept of Social Footprint/Handprint (SFM or SHM) encompasses various methods within sustainability assessment. Originating from the notion of sustainability pillars, it assesses human impacts on ecosystems, societies, and economies, introduced after the Earth Summit in 1992. While footprints measure negative impacts, handprints focus on positive contributions towards sustainability, distinguishing between impacts and positive changes. Typically applied in lifecycle assessments like S-LCA, SFM utilizes diverse methodologies such as PROSA and SHDB, with a focus on social sustainability performance, often involving large datasets as elaborated in the corresponding chapter of [APPENDIX F](#). Despite challenges like data scarcity and the risk of greenwashing, it facilitates measurable objectives for sustainable development and can be integrated with other footprints. As in other assessment methods for assessing the social dimension of sustainability, neither SFM nor SHM

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is a standardized method, where the assessment procedure base on guidelines provided by organizations like Global Reporting Initiative (GRI), United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) or Society for Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry (SETAC) [130].

6.4.3 Social Impact Assessment

Social Impact Assessment (SIA), often considered within Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA), is a multidisciplinary process analysing the social impacts of plans, policies, and projects. Utilising methods from sociology, anthropology, economics, and other fields, it aims to understand and mitigate the effects of development interventions, contributing to sustainable outcomes. SIA involves phases like data collection and analysis, often requiring iterative validation through stakeholder consultation. Indicators cover demographics, access to social services, and infrastructure. While SIA facilitates ongoing monitoring and management, challenges include integration with other issues like health and culture, and the fatigue of stakeholders during consultation processes [131]. Best practices involve transparent reporting, including Social Impact Management Plans (SIMP), with established guidelines and principles for conducting assessments. Use cases include evaluating integrated power facilities [132] and assessing the social effects of energy projects in various regions [133].

6.4.4 Social Return on Investment

Social Return on Investment (SROI), often referred to as social impact investing or Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), measures the societal value generated by various interventions, incorporating social, environmental, and economic costs and benefits [134]. Developed initially for the non-profit sector, SROI has gained traction in both non-profit and for-profit sectors, focusing on impacts rather than just performance [135]. Its methodology, based on a cost-benefit approach using Net Present Value, assesses stakeholder value against investment, aiming to reduce inequality and environmental degradation [136]. The assessment involves six stages: identifying stakeholders, mapping outcomes, evidencing outcomes, establishing impact, calculating SROI, and reporting [137]. SROI's application extends to evaluating the social dimension of sustainability and identifying social hotspots in ES value chains. However, challenges include imprecise measures of societal costs and benefits and the complexity of causal claims [138]. Standard guidelines for conducting SROI assessments exist (see Ref. [139]), with use cases including quantifying the cost and social returns of micro hydropower demonstrations in Europe [140].

6.4.5 Technology Acceptance

Technology acceptance, also known as social acceptance or societal acceptance, encompasses attitudes and actions towards technology, crucial in determining the success of energy-related projects like HES. With roots in social science research, acceptance involves factors like trust, perceived benefits, risks, and knowledge [141]. Studies highlight socio-psychological factors influencing acceptance, essential for policymakers and practitioners in strategy development and technology implementation within the energy transition [142]. Methodologies range from surveys to discrete choice experiments [143] ideally involving a broad societal spectrum. Challenges include the time-consuming nature of data collection and the complexity of survey development and statistical evaluation [144]. Despite lacking standard reporting schemes, technology acceptance frameworks

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provide insights into potential pitfalls and facilitate project implementation, though they may overlook diverse consumer needs and social impacts. Use cases like assessing social acceptance of energy technologies and analysing user acceptance of PV battery storage systems offer valuable insights for stakeholders and project planning.

6.5 Integrated methods and frameworks

Although the usefulness of the identified methods is undeniable, performing a sustainability assessment is more than an integration of results from different methodologies. It requires integrating sustainability principles and employing transdisciplinary approaches in order to become a solution and action-oriented assessment able to guide the transformation of our society towards sustainability [145]. In general, too little attention is devoted to the higher-level approach of sustainability and therefore beyond the discrete dimensions of the three pillars. There is a need to transcend the reductionism of the different methods and pursue a holistic approach that takes into consideration the complex relationships between nature and society. The need extends to explicitly stating the sustainability principles and employing transdisciplinary to create strong links with the social context and to engage stakeholders in knowledge co-production [146]. Decision-making regarding the sustainability assessment of energy technologies is complex due to sometimes conflicting goals (e.g., low costs for end users, minimum environmental impact, maximum social acceptance) and requires an integrated consideration of economic, environmental, and social criteria. This thematic cluster includes a description of the methods used to simultaneously assess these three aspects of sustainability. Following frameworks and methodologies are included:

- LCSA
- EMRIO
- MCDA.

Similarly, as in the other thematic clusters, all methods introduced here are further elaborated in the corresponding chapter of the input paper in ANNEX G.

6.5.1 Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA)

LCSA (often referred in short as LCA and Triple-Bottom-Line (TBL) analysis), provides a standardized method to evaluate the environmental, economic, and social impacts of products, services, and systems, including HES systems [147], [148]. It ensures that no burden shifting among impact categories and along steps of the supply chain occur via integration of LCA, LCC and S-LCA to offer a comprehensive understanding of sustainability [149]. LCSA framework involves defining goals, analysing impacts, and interpreting results, following principles as outlined in ISO standards for LCA. While LCSA offers benefits such as simultaneous data collection and comparability, challenges remain, including methodological difficulties and the need for further research and standardization. Despite these challenges, LCSA serves as a valuable tool for decision-making in various sectors, including ES, with applications ranging from assessing different ES technologies to guiding decision-making in energy retrofit measures for buildings.

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6.5.2 Extended Multiregional Input Output Analysis (EMRIO)

EMRIO provides a macroeconomic tool to assess sustainability impacts by tracking financial flows between major economic sectors across regions. This approach extends traditional input-output analysis to estimate impacts such as employment creation, environmental footprints, and social risks by integrating data from environmental, socioeconomic, and social accounts. Extended with environmental and social accounts is also a pivotal approach to assess sustainability as it provides a system-wide overview of the functioning of value chains involved in supplying products or services, which otherwise would be difficult to assess [136]. EMRIO models allow the analysis of sustainability impacts of investments, products, technologies, and trade [151], [152]. The methodology involves input-output tables that describe economic interrelationships, incorporating final demand and transaction matrices to capture inter-sectoral transactions [153]. While EMRIO offers systemic insights into global value chains and allows for the simultaneous assessment of social, economic, and environmental dimensions, limitations include sectorial aggregation, lack of updated data, and insufficient handling of waste treatment. Despite these challenges, EMRIO remains widely used for sustainability analysis, with applications ranging from assessing the environmental and economic impacts of ES technologies like batteries [154] and hydrogen production [155] to analysing global value chains and trade impacts.

6.5.3 Multicriteria Decision Analysis (MCDA)

Multi-criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) is widely used for ES, drawing from various sources in [28], [64], [71], [156]. Results from both LCSA and MRIO are a compilation of indicators belonging to various sustainability dimensions that need to be combined in a common framework in order to have solution-oriented sustainability assessment tools. In this vein, MCDA is often used to reconcile the often-conflicting results from these analyses [157]. MCDA serves as decision-making aid, in facilitating the organization of information, in understanding of alternative relations, and in the exploration of stakeholder perceptions and needs. Its significance lies in the ability to consider multiple criteria or indicators simultaneously, quantifying stakeholder preferences and making their influence on results visible. The methodology entails several phases, starting with the structuring of the decision problem, selection of criteria and alternatives, and elicitation of stakeholder preferences. Subsequently, criteria weights are determined, and alternative performance is measured and compared. Various subjective and objective weighting methods, such as pair-wise comparison and Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP), are applied, alongside aggregation methods like Weighted Sum Method and Multi-Attribute Utility Theory (MAUT).

Criteria in MCDA encompass economic, environmental, technical, and social dimensions, each requiring careful consideration and quantification. Economic indicators play a crucial role, as the market success of an energy technology is highly dependent on its economic performance. Environmental criteria often adopt a life cycle perspective, quantifying potential effects on the environment throughout the product lifecycle. Technical criteria directly influence environmental, social, and economic performance, including factors like efficiency, maturity, and system life. Social criteria, although challenging to define and quantify, are increasingly recognized as crucial for

technological success. Despite their importance, social aspects such as acceptance and trust are often addressed ambiguously in the literature, posing a challenge for their inclusion in MCDA.

The process of MCDA should involve sensitivity and robustness analyses to ensure the reliability of results. Sensitivity analyses typically involve varying criteria weights or performance values, while robustness checks may include additions or deletions of alternatives or criteria. These analyses provide insights into the stability and reliability of rankings, essential for decision-making. Despite its strengths in providing justifiable decisions and considering multiple dimensions, MCDA faces challenges. These include criteria interdependence, data collection complexities, stakeholder skill requirements, and uncertainties related to preferences, weighting, and aggregation. However, guidelines from various sources aid in effectively presenting MCDA results, promoting transparency and contextualization. Use cases of MCDA in ES are diverse, ranging from technology selection and project evaluation to sustainability prioritization. These applications emphasize the importance of stakeholder involvement and comprehensive criteria assessment in decision-making processes. Overall, MCDA serves as a valuable tool in navigating the complexities of ES decision-making, enabling informed and robust decisions.

6.6 Use Cases for HES Sustainability Assessments

As a supplement to the thematic input papers, a use case selection is provided complementarily for presenting practical examples in which the introduced methods are applied. In the formulation phase, using interactive surveys the format of the use cases has been discussed in terms of way of presentation and content. Majorly supported format was a brief presentation of use cases from literature as an appendix considering applicability, conciseness, guidance, interpretability, etc., as presented in [APPENDIX A](#). To diversify the covered technologies, partners were asked to specify ES technologies and assessment method used in their use case contributions. Due to scarcity of available use cases assessing each technology applying different methods, in line with the goal and scope of this document it was prioritized to provide at least a use case for each method. Similar to the approach for input paper creation, partners provided a shortened version of the use case contributions as committed which were structured in a similar way to the input papers. (see [APPENDIX H](#) for the use case selection)

Additionally, the contributors were asked to provide case information sheet based on the predefined structure to indicate important technical and methodological aspects in

Table 6.3. Attributes such as storage media, delivered energy, TRL, hybridization level, and technology classification should serve for choosing from use case examples considering technological relevance. Additionally, information regarding application field, storage duration, and services are included due to their relevance for the assessments covering use phases. The KPIs and used methods for estimating these are also included in the use case overview. The use cases are summarized in Table 6.4. Here the relevant results, methods and sustainability dimensions are provided.

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Table 6.3. Unified table structure for overview of the use cases.

Storage Media	
Delivered Energy	<input type="checkbox"/> Electricity <input type="checkbox"/> Heat <input type="checkbox"/> Fuels (Please specify: _____)
Technological Readiness Level (TRL)	<input type="checkbox"/> TRL 1-3 (Research) <input type="checkbox"/> TRL 4-6 (Development) <input type="checkbox"/> TRL 7-8 (Deployment)
Hybridization Level	<input type="checkbox"/> None <input type="checkbox"/> Device <input type="checkbox"/> Material <input type="checkbox"/> System
Storage technology classification	<input type="checkbox"/> Mechanical <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (buildings, district) <input type="checkbox"/> Electrochemical <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (non-residential) <input type="checkbox"/> Chemical <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (industrial) <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (power plants, CSP) <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (solar, PV, wind)
Application field	<input type="checkbox"/> TSO <input type="checkbox"/> DSO <input type="checkbox"/> Private actors <input type="checkbox"/> Energy Supplier <input type="checkbox"/> Aggregator <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial Actors <input type="checkbox"/> Power plant operator <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial Clients <input type="checkbox"/> Power plant operator incl. PtX
Storage duration	<input type="checkbox"/> Short-term <input type="checkbox"/> Mid-term <input type="checkbox"/> Long-term
Services	<input type="checkbox"/> Generation support and bulk storage (minutes to hours) <input type="checkbox"/> Transmission infrastructure support (ramp-up, milliseconds or minutes) <input type="checkbox"/> Distribution infrastructure support (one or more hours) <input type="checkbox"/> Ancillary services <input type="checkbox"/> Behind-the-meter (>=100 kW) <input type="checkbox"/> Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G)
Key performance indicators (KPIs)	
Hybridization purpose	
Methods	
Abstract	

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Table 6.4. Use cases selection for sustainability assessment of HES systems.

Use case	Hybridization	Technologies	Services	Short description	Sustainability dimension	Methods	KPIs
Hybrid Energy Storage and Hydrogen Supply Based on Aluminium	Yes	Aluminium wet combustion	General support and bulk storage, distribution infrastructure, ancillary services	Aluminium-based ES offers a feasible and sustainable solution for generating both electricity and hydrogen, with high round-trip efficiencies and full recycling of waste. The estimated cost of producing hydrogen through aluminium-based ES is competitive, ranging from 4.2 to 9.6 € per kg, compared to 6.5 to 12.1 € per kg for wind and solar power-based green hydrogen production.	Economic	Levelized cost of electricity (LCoE) Levelized cost of hydrogen (LCoH)	€/kWh, €/kg H ₂
True Cost of Solar Hydrogen	No	Photovoltaic for H ₂ Production	Ancillary services	This study underscores green hydrogen's pivotal role in achieving sustainability. By 2050, a significant portion of solar and wind electricity will be utilized for hydrogen production through water electrolysis. Using a learning curve approach, it predicts a substantial decrease in electrolyzer capital expenditure and the levelized cost of hydrogen. By 2050, the cost is estimated to range from 10 to 27 €/MWhH ₂ , emphasizing the growing influence of solar PV in cost calculations.	Economic	Levelized cost of hydrogen (LCoH)	€/kgH ₂
Life-Cycle Costs of Electrochemical Energy Storage for Stationary Grid Applications	No	Lithium-Ion batteries, Vanadium Redox Flow, NaNiCl	Ancillary, decent. storage, Wind energy support and electric time shift	Assessing various battery technologies for stationary applications emphasizes the significance of cycle life in determining both cost and carbon emissions, with lithium-ion and NaNiCl batteries demonstrating strong performance while lead-acid batteries face challenges due to low efficiency and cycle life.	Environment Economic	LCA; LCC combined in MCDA with Monte Carlo simulation	€/kWh, kGCO _{2eq} /kWh
Life cycle energy and environmental impacts of a solid oxide fuel cell micro-CHP system for residential application	Yes	SOFC - micro-CHP	Combined heat and power	This study evaluates the life cycle energy and environmental performance of a solid oxide fuel cell system for household use, utilizing primary manufacturing data and experimental data for start-up and operation. The analysis underscores the significance of the operational stage, responsible for the majority of energy demand and environmental impacts, while emphasizing the potential for eco-design solutions to enhance efficiency, reduce emissions, and increase component durability, thereby minimizing the need for replacements.	Environment	LCA	Several impact categories referred to 1 MJ of Exergy
Life cycle assessment of storage systems: the case study of a sodium/nickel chloride battery	No	NaNiCl	Multiple scenarios considering various energy supply sources	This study evaluates the energy and environmental impacts of sodium/nickel chloride batteries, an emerging technology for ES and smart grids, using the LCA. Findings reveal that the operational phase has the most significant energy impact, while cell manufacturing contributes the greatest environmental impact, underscoring the need for improvements in efficiency and sustainability standards for electric storage devices.	Environment	LCA	Several impact categories per produced battery

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Use Case: Societal Acceptability of Large Stationary Battery Storage Systems	No	Batteries	NA	Study examines social acceptability of large stationary battery storage (BS) through an online survey focusing on visual impact. Results suggest higher acceptability of BS in industrial and rural areas compared to residential areas, indicating the importance of adapting BS design to its surroundings, particularly in residential areas, to minimize visual intrusion and increase acceptability.	Social	Online survey, Technology acceptance	Visual impact, mitigation strategies, choice of geographical location
Working conditions in hydrogen production	No	Hydrogen	Ancillary services, Distribution infrastructure	Paper examines social implications of hydrogen production via advanced alkaline water electrolysis (AEL) from a life cycle perspective, focusing on manufacturing of electrolyzer and hydrogen production in Germany, Austria, and Spain. Results suggest least social impact along the German process chain, followed by Spain and Austria, highlighting the need for policymakers and industry to collaborate to enhance working conditions, particularly in global upstream processes, to contribute to Sustainable Development.	Social	S-LCA	Association and bargaining rights, trade unionism, fair salary, gender wage gap and weekly hours of work per employee
Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis to find the more sustainable location for hydrogen production in Europe	No	Hydrogen	H ₂ generation	A Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA) of industrial hydrogen production using alkaline water electrolysis (AEL) in Austria, Germany, and Spain integrates Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) to compare environmental, economic, and social impacts, revealing Germany as the most sustainable production location.	Integrated	PROMETHEE I	Comprises indicators from LCA, LCC, and S-LCA and Outranking flow
Sustainability Assessment of Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) plants with thermal storage in Spain compared to photovoltaic systems with batteries	Yes	Batteries, CSP and thermal storage	Distribution infrastructure	The deployment of CSP in the European Union generates value added and employment, with potential benefits for the economy, while minimizing carbon and water footprints compared to fossil fuel alternatives. However, the involvement of Chinese components in CSP projects may increase social risks such as unfair wages and child labour, highlighting the importance of ensuring responsible supply chains.	Integrated	Input–output analysis (IOA), MRIO	Value added, employment, climate change, water cons., sweat free wage, child labor, outranking flow

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7 DECISION-MAKING AID FOR PROMOTING FUTURE HES SYSTEM APPLICATIONS: A WORKING EXAMPLE FROM STORIES

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The guideline incorporates a Multi-Criteria-Decision Analysis (MCDA) as a supplementary method. Establishing a common base for environmental, techno-economic, and socio-economic assessments is crucial for realizing the potential applications of HES, necessitating collaboration among experts and stakeholders to reach consensus. Decision-making aid serves to clarify methodological discussions or aid in technological comparisons. Providing an example of a decision-making exercise is deemed important for illustrating HES decisions. Hence, here an example MCDA exercise is provided that could act as a blueprint. Furthermore, applying such methods can be useful for generating common definitions and defining KPIs to measure decision attributes in the decision context. The MCDA process involves comparing different alternatives based on a set of criteria, with stakeholders and experts ideally participating in the selection of alternatives, criteria, and discussions of results [158]. On December 6th, 2023, within the framework of the StoRIES project's Work Package 4, an interactive workshop titled "Establishing a Unified Framework for Assessing Sustainability to Unleash the Potential of Hybrid Energy Storage Systems" was convened at the Austrian Institute of Technology in Vienna. ([Link to event](#)) The primary aim of the workshop was to identify and prioritize sustainability implications and associated key performance indicators (KPIs) related to ES technologies and to pinpoint prospects for hybridization across diverse application domains. To achieve this objective, an MCDA process flow supported by an interactive decision support software (Helmholtz MCDA Software) was developed [158] and deployed in conjunction with collaborative group discussions to foster stakeholder engagement and facilitate consensus-building regarding KPIs and their significance. Approximately 45 participants hailing from various corners of Europe, including the seven organizers representing KIT, FZJ, and the Helmholtz Working group on MCDA were actively involved in the workshop proceedings. Through the utilization of a pre-established MCDA model designed for evaluating the sustainability of ES technologies across short-, medium-, and long-term applications, participants explored potential synergies among different technologies and application scenarios.

Figure 7.1. Participants on the 2nd StoRIES Workshop in December 2023.

In the following, the conducted MCDA working example is explained in detail for providing information about the capabilities of such decision-aid approaches and how it can be carried out considering the consecutive practical stages. Herein, the given example harmonizes deliberative approaches such as expert interviews, questionnaires, and group discussions through preparation and actual task implementation via tool-aided decision-making practice. Following flowchart in Figure 7.2 provides a procedural overview of the working example.

Figure 7.2 MCDA process flow. Based on: Mesa Estrada, L. S.; Haase, M.; Baumann, M.; Wulf, C.; Müller, T.; Ersoy, H. Stakeholders integration for MCDA sustainability assessment of energy technologies: a use case in energy storage 2023, September 22. 96th Meeting of the EWG-MCDA (MCDA-96), Paris, 21st-23rd September 2023 (2023), Paris, France, September 21–23, 202.

Note that, the given example is structured in a specific way for the StoRIES project, but the provided procedure can be tailored for different applications with different scopes.

7.1 Pre-Workshop: Problem Structuring

7.1.1 Identification and Involvement of Stakeholders

Incorporating stakeholders' perspectives and priorities into decision analysis processes is crucial for addressing sustainability issues. Azapagic and Perdan outline two pertinent questions in their work for this purpose [159] accordingly:

1. **Identification of Stakeholders and Their Interests in ES technologies:** Stakeholders fall into two categories—internal and external. Internal stakeholders, such as project partners or collaborators in the StoRIES project, are directly associated with the organization. External stakeholders, like the public, are not part of the organization but are impacted by its decisions. Recognizing the diverse levels of interest, knowledge, and influence among stakeholders is essential for analyzing group dynamics effectively.

2. **Involvement of Stakeholders in Decision-Making:** While involving all stakeholders may seem ideal, decision analysis processes involving heterogeneous groups can lead to conflicts and hinder consensus [159]. However, in sustainable development decision-making, understanding and representing stakeholders' varied perspectives is a necessary precondition for building consensus. In the StoRIES project, internal stakeholders were invited to participate due to the project's scope and the intention to test the methodology within this closed group. Although external stakeholders were not initially included, their perspectives later influenced the preferences of internal stakeholders.

In this workshop the participants were assigned different stakeholders' categories, a list of predefined categories was provided during the registration process. These categories included **associations, government energy and environmental agencies, academia (with subdivisions based on research focus), NGOs, energy suppliers and consumers, government regulators, politicians, and others.** Anticipating a significant number of participants from academia, further differentiation based on specific topics was implemented to facilitate efficient grouping.

7.1.2 Problem Definition

In decision-making processes, the problem definition is pivotal. It involves delineating objectives, setting scope, and establishing boundaries. Early stakeholder engagement is essential to foster a shared understanding of fundamental concepts and definitions. In the StoRIES project, the proposed MCDA process aims to support early-stage HES product development in Europe. Here, the focus lies in integrating the community (StoRIES project) objectives and values in the construction of a decision model, emphasizing stakeholder integration.

The overarching goal of the StoRIES project is to unlock HES systems' potential in achieving climate-neutrality. Specific objectives include optimizing raw material utilization, enhancing circularity, minimizing environmental impacts, and maximizing social benefits. To streamline decision-making, separate analyses for short/medium-term (S/MT) and long-term (LT) storage were proposed in the StoRIES Workshop. This approach simplifies considerations by emphasizing storage durations and technological aspects. Subsequent sections delve into stakeholders' perspectives, aiming to develop an effective decision model for HES systems.

7.1.2.1 Stakeholders' values and objectives: Sustainability KPIs

A sample of six individuals was purposefully selected to conduct individual interviews in advance of the workshop. The average interview duration was 60 minutes. Here are the key details of this process:

Step I – Sample Selection Criteria: The choice of six participants was deliberate, guided by the saturation effect theory. According to this theory, a comprehensive set of objectives can typically be achieved by interviewing five to nine participants [160]. Three specific criteria were used for participant selection:

Relation to WP4: Ideally, individuals not directly involved in WP4 were chosen, as their perspectives align with the pre-defined decision problem.

Role in the StoRIES Project: Stakeholders such as project coordinators, work packages (WP) and task leaders, and advisory board members, were prioritized. Their insights provide a comprehensive overview of objectives and team activities.

Expertise in ES Systems: Participants from diverse fields—technical, environmental, economic, and political—were included to ensure a holistic perspective.

Step II – Interview Protocol: An interview protocol was designed and implemented using the Value-Focused Thinking (VFT) framework [161].

VFT techniques guided participants in structuring values and objectives related to the decision problem. Keeney defines values as “anything decision-makers care about regarding a decision”, and objectives as “values stated in a verb-object format that clarifies their meaning” [161]. During the initial part of the interview, participants brainstormed values and objectives related to the overarching decision: ES technologies supporting a fair energy transition toward climate neutrality. Specific objectives for short/medium-term (S/MT) or long-term (LT) ES technologies were also explored.

Step III – Attribute Measurement: Once objectives were identified, interviewees were asked to suggest attributes for measuring objective achievement, following the approach outlined by [162]. Although in general the objectives are similar for both type of application e.g. minimizing GHG emissions, slightly different concerns were identified and resulted in the creation of two different sets of KPIs for each case (S/MT and LT). Resulting KPIs obtained during the process are presented as tabulated in Table 7.1. These were used as a base for the discussion during the workshop in Vienna.

Table 7.1 Pre-defined sustainability KPIs with interviews.

Objective	KPIs (Sustainability implications)	Application	Description
Carbon neutral technologies	Climate change	S/MT and LT	Carbon neutrality involves mitigating greenhouse gas emissions across the entire lifecycle of energy storage technologies. Emissions of greenhouse gases change temperature and the climate for the worse.
Good health and wellbeing	Human health	S/MT and LT	Negative impact on people causing death and illnesses as consequence of e.g. emitted chemicals or radiation that take place during the life cycle of ES technologies. This KPI includes ozone depletion, human toxicity, particulate matter, ionizing radiation, photochemical ozone formation (equally weighted)
Environmentally friendly technologies	Ecosystems quality	S/MT and LT	Negative impact on the function and structure of natural ecosystems because of e.g. emitted chemicals or physical interventions that take place during the life cycle of ES technologies. This KPI includes Acidification potential, eutrophication terrestrial/ freshwater/ marine, ecotoxicity freshwater (equally weighted).
Affordable renewable energy	CAPEX	S/MT and LT	Capital expenditures (CAPEX) drive initial development and innovation in ES technologies. CAPEX refers to the funds a company invests technologies in acquiring, upgrading, and maintaining physical assets, such as equipment, property, and infrastructure.
	OPEX	S/MT and LT	Operational expenditures (OPEX) play a crucial role in ensuring the ongoing functionality, efficiency, and safety of ES technologies throughout their lifecycle. Effective allocation of resources enables the optimization, maintenance, integration, and continuous improvement of ES technologies, thereby contributing to their reliability and lifetime (LT) viability in various applications.
Positive public perception of	Social acceptance: safety risk	S/MT	The public's perception of safety risks associated with ES technologies significantly impacts their acceptance, implementation, and success in the market. Addressing safety concerns through rigorous safety

renewable energy technologies			standards, transparent communication, risk mitigation strategies, and continuous improvement efforts is essential to build public trust and foster greater acceptance of these technologies.
	Social acceptance: visual impact	LT	
Reliable and stable supply chain	EU Manufacturing capacity	S/MT and LT	The EU's reliance on imports of primary feedstock for ES technologies (concentrates and intermediates) for conversion in its refineries is expected to continue in the coming years. However, the expansion of refining capacity for key raw material, components and assemblies is feasible and will reduce supply risks considerably. It strengthens Europe's energy security by reducing vulnerability to geopolitical uncertainties and disruptions in the global market. It can generate economic growth and create jobs within Europe.
Resource efficiency and circularity	Resource efficiency and circularity	S/MT and LT	As the demand for ES technologies grows with the transition to renewable energy sources, ensuring resource efficiency becomes crucial for energy security. Maximizing the use of available resources efficiently helps meet the increasing demand for ES without overreliance on scarce or geopolitically sensitive materials.
Technical performance and durability	Efficiency	S/MT and LT	Higher efficiency means less energy loss during these processes, maximizing the amount of usable energy stored and retrieved, which directly impacts the overall performance of the ES technology.
	Durability: lifetime	S/MT	The lifespan of storage technologies is vital for the LT stability of energy systems by ensuring reliability, consistent performance, economic viability, grid stability, sustainability, regulatory compliance, and public trust.
	Ease of transportation	LT	

7.1.2.2 Identification of Alternatives

Once stakeholders understand their values and objectives, brainstorming alternative solutions that align with these values can begin [163]. Depending on the problem type, stakeholders or experts and analysts may initially design these alternatives. For instance, McKenna and colleagues elicited values and objectives from stakeholders to generate a set of alternatives using an energy system model, subsequently discussing this set with stakeholders [164].

In our decision problem, the primary goal is not to select the best alternatives but rather to establish a common foundation for sustainability assessment of ES and HES systems (including Key Performance Indicators and group decision modelling). Therefore, we base our alternative selection on current strategic ES technologies in Europe [165]–[167].

Note: Each technology will undergo an assessment as a potential component of the HES system. Ultimately, the results for each component will be compared to predict an overall assessment of the HES systems. In our working example, two experts have endorsed the selection of these alternatives for short/medium-term (S/MT) and long-term (LT) storage applications.

7.1.3 Preference Modelling: Selection of MCDA Method

Once the decision problem is defined, along with the sustainability Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and available alternatives, the appropriate MCDA method can be selected. Different MCDA methods serve distinct purposes and contexts [168]. In our case, we followed guidelines for selecting MCDA

methods for sustainability assessment, aligning with the nature of the decision problem [169]–[171]. We considered several key criteria for method selection:

- Ease of use.
- Null compensation between criteria.
- Threshold values (where small differences are not considered significant for at least one criterion).
- Handling qualitative and quantitative information.
- Incommensurability (due to heterogeneous scales of criteria, no normalization required).
- Uncertainty.
- Group decision modelling.

Given these characteristics, ELECTRE methods are suitable for modelling preferences. In ELECTRE, preferences are expressed through binary outranking relations, indicating whether one alternative is at least as good as another [172]. Specifically, we opted for a variation of ELECTRE III that incorporates Net Flow Score (NFS). More information about the methods can be found in [173].

With criteria, alternatives, and the MCDA method in place, the next step involves creating the evaluation matrix. We integrated other methods such as Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and literature reviews to quantify alternative performance from a life cycle perspective [169], [170]. Overall, this comprehensive approach ensures robust sustainability assessment within our application. The calculations relevant for the ELECTRE III method, weights elicitation and group decision modelling were carried out with the Helmholtz MCDA software [174]. Figure 7.3 presents the evaluation matrices for S/MT and LT ES technologies in the named software.

Figure 7.3 Evaluation matrices for a. S/MT and b. LT ES in the Helmholtz MCDA Software.

In the scope of this working example, we were interested on the integration of stakeholders for setting the weights of sustainability KPIs. For this, two approaches were implemented:

1. A simple 10-score scale was provided to stakeholders so they could directly assign weights to the criteria. Here, 10 is the most important and 1 the least important KPI. The objective is to provided relative importance of the KPIs, therefore a score of 10 means the KPI is 10 times more important than the KPI with score 1, and 2 times more important than a KPI with score 5. For this exercise to be meaningful, the stakeholders were asked to use the whole scale.
2. The Deck of Cards Method (DCM), a recognized approach for eliciting weights in outranking methods proposed by [175]. In this method, the DM ranks all the considered criteria from the least important to the most important; then, DM adds blank cards between them to express the strength of preference between consecutive criteria and, finally, defines the ratio between the weight of the most important criterion and the weight of the least important one.

The following part of this guideline presents the procedure for reflecting on and choosing the KPIs and eliciting weights from stakeholders with the software.

7.1.4 Workshop Setup

The workshop was divided into two parts which will be called *Plenum* and *Group* work in the following sections. To facilitate the interaction between stakeholders, five groups were created, considering the

categories of stakeholders in the registration process (see section 7.1.1) to achieve the most diverse composition possible. The five groups (Group 1-5) and accordingly for each group, one facilitator was assigned to (F₁, F₂, ... F₅) who was responsible for guiding the participants through every step of the prepared exercise. In addition, there were two coordinators, one responsible for supporting the facilitators of each group, and another one for the operation of the Helmholtz MCDA software. As mentioned before, the workshop took place the 6th of December 2023 in the Austrian Institute of Technology. There, one main room and four smaller rooms for group work were provided. Table 7.2 shows the distribution of stakeholders according to each group.

Table 7.2 Distribution of stakeholders in each working group.

Group Name →	Group 1 (Nickel)	Group 2 (Aluminium)	Group 3 (Lithium)	Group 4 (Cobalt)	Group 5 (Manganese)	Total
Stakeholders' category	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	
Association (e.g. trade or industry)			1			1
Government Energy & Environmental Agencies	1				1	2
Researcher/ Academia – Engineering/manufacturing	2	2	3	3	2	12
Researcher/ Academia – Sustainability	2	2	1	2	2	9
Researcher/ Academia – Market integration		1				1
Energy supplier				1	1	2
Others	1		1	1	2	5
Total	6	5	6	7	8	32

The following materials were prepared to support the activities in the workshop:

The participants are provided with a survey where they are asked to reflect and assign weights via the online survey plugin of the Helmholtz MCDA software. When scanning the QR code from Figure 7.4., stakeholders got access to a survey as presented. Please note that there is one survey for KPIs selection and a different survey for KPI Weighting. Therefore, two QR codes are provided to the stakeholders.

Figure 7.4. Screenshot of online survey plugin of Helmholtz MCDA Tool. (LHS) Screenshot of online survey filled out by stakeholders. (RHS)

Please note that this plug-in takes criteria directly from the evaluation matrix created in the same software. Three online surveys were generated for different sessions within the workshop consolidation:

- **Plenum – S/MT ES applications:** individual selection and weighting of KPIs for short/medium-term applications. The aim of this part of the workshop was to gather information about the stakeholders’ preferences before interacting with others and to familiarize them with the online surveys. This exercise was not conducted in the Plenum for the LT applications due to time constraints.
- **Group work – S/MT ES applications (GW I):** same online surveys as for the Plenum exercise, however including the names of the groups as stakeholder categories instead of participant’s categories.
- **Group work – LT ES applications (GW II):** online survey using the evaluation matrix for long-term applications and the names of the groups as stakeholder categories.

D4.2 – “Common base for environmental, techno-economic socio-economic assessment to un-lock the potential applications for hybrid ES systems”

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Note: Two posters per group were designed, one for S/MT and one for LT ES applications for supporting KPIs weighting using the 10-score scale method in the Group work.

Two decks of cards (DC) per group with one card for each of the KPIs for the two ES applications. Including blank white cards to express the strength of preference between consecutive criteria as well as for additional KPIs suggestions.

7.2 Workshop: Task Execution

After explaining the workshop preparations required for bringing different pieces in [Chapter 7.1 - Pre-Workshop: Problem Structuring](#), in this section the actual conducted exercise will be explained in terms of procedure and achievements. The interactive decision-making exercise consists of three sessions, where the first session takes place in plenum together with all participants and other two sessions are organized as group works with different focus.

7.2.1 Preference Modelling: Elicitation Choices

The workshop started in the plenum with the presence of all participants, a brief introduction to the methodology, the Helmholtz MCDA Software, and details related to the workflow of the exercise. Consequently, the following interactive tasks are carried out in the plenum:

Session #1: Plenum

Task 1. Sustainability KPIs Selection: Stakeholder’s individual preferences were elicited using the Online Survey of Helmholtz MCDA Software in plenum: Participants were asked to select the KPIs they found relevant for S/MT ES sustainability assessment from the pre-defined list (see Table 7.1). In addition, they could provide further KPIs which were missing from their point of view.

Task 2. Sustainability KPIs Weighting: The Online Survey with the 10-point scale weighting method was shared with the participants using the Helmholtz MCDA Software.

Upon completion of these two tasks in the plenum, as introduced the participants are asked to join their predefined group after some instructions are given.

Session #2: GW-I, S/MT ES

In this session, groups are created to deal with the same tasks namely the S/MT ES. Two main tasks are defined within this session to carry out KPIs weighting and reflect on KPIs selection.

Task 1. Sustainability KPIs Weighting: Each group has been provided with a poster involving the predefined KPIs. The group participants were divided into two sub-groups and asked to provide their weightings on a scale of 1 to 10 as presented in the provided example in Figure 7.5. The given green dots refer to the given scores by subgroups. Accordingly, they are asked to conduct a discussion an achieve a consensus as represented with blue dots in the poster.

Figure 7.5. Example of KPIs weighting within GW-I using 1-10 score.

Accordingly, consensus results were sent to the Helmholtz MCDA software via online survey where a weighting set for each of the five groups is collected. The conducted discussions created the links to the second task since new opinions or remarks are raised during this exercise regarding the selected KPIs.

Task 2. Sustainability KPIs Weighting and Selection using DCM: Using the outcomes of the poster group work, each group is asked to order the deck of cards from the least important to the most important KPI. Additionally, using blank white cards in between to provide some flexibility in terms of scale (see figure 7.6). Also, participants were asked to define the ratio z ($z = 5$ in the example in figure 7.6).

Afterwards, participants could reflect on the selected KPIs and provide missing KPIs (on green cards) or remove KPIs they agreed on. The method is introduced to the groups by the facilitators, providing them the required materials and the following guiding questions to start the exercise:

- Are selected KPIs sufficient? /Which KPI would you add or remove?
- Are any KPIs missing?
- Where would you add it in this existing ranking (deck of cards)?

Figure 7.6. Weights elicitation with DCM (Part-I) and reflection on sustainability KPIs (Part-II).

Accordingly, as in the first tasks the achieved ranking scores are communicated to MCDA tool.

Session #3: GW-II, LT ES

The third session is carried out following identical steps and methods presented however focusing on long-term ES sustainability. Please note that the KPIs proposed are slightly different as presented in section 7.1.2.1. The following KPIs are provided in the default KPIs set (KPIs differing from S/M term case are written in bold):

- **Ease of transportation.**
- **Social acceptance (visual impacts).**
- EU manufacturing capacity.
- Resource efficiency and circularity.
- Efficiency.
- CAPEX.
- OPEX.
- Human health.
- Climate change.
- Ecosystem quality.

7.2.2 Problem Analysis

After the working groups executed their tasks, a presenter from each group provided was given the opportunity to present the outcome of the executed tasks in the group work. Main highlights in terms of group work results can be summarized as follows:

- Participants reported that using a 1-10 scale was not easy when reflecting on the relative importance of different KPIs in the first part of the group exercise.

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- Though, the participants underlined that reflecting on the relative importance DCM method enabled a better reflection using blank cards and adding additional cards to imply how many times the considered KPI is more important with respect to others.

Noting that both results can be adopted as weighting set for the exercise, based on the received feedback from the groups, an individual choice has been made here to consider the weighting results from the DCM. Accordingly, the global results are interpreted using Helmholtz MCDA software and are presented to the participants. The results are presented in the following for each session.

Session #1 Results: Plenum

In Figure 7.7 the results of the KPIs selection and weighting exercise carried out in the plenum is presented in a bubble chart. It can be seen from the results how the importance of various sustainability KPIs are prioritized and perceived depending on the stakeholder type. However, it needs to be underlined that the given results are indicative since number of participants in each stakeholder group was very different (e.g., 18 participants from Researcher/Academia – Engineering/manufacturing versus one participant from Government, Energy and Environment Agencies).

Figure 7.7. Weighting sets of sustainability KPIs for different stakeholders’ categories (short- and medium-term ES)

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Furthermore, the resulting aggregated weights (see Figure 7.8.a) are presented to the participants where climate change and resource efficiency (REC) have the highest relevance by 11.7% and 11.6%, respectively. On the other hand, social acceptance, and EU manufacturing capacity as sustainability KPIs are resulted in the lowest weights by 7.9% and 7.8%, respectively. Considering the collected weightings, the named technologies are ranked indicatively using ELECTRE III method as presented in Figure 7.8.b. The global ranking results imply that Pumped Hydro Storage (PHS) is the best performing technology considering the given sustainability KPIs followed by Na-ion PBA, VRFB and LFP batteries. In terms of stakeholder group preferences, in all stakeholder categories PHS ranked as the best alternative where LFP corresponded to the worst excepts NGO stakeholder category. VRFB and Na-ion batteries are ranked as 2nd and 3rd best alternatives showing variations depending on the stakeholder category.

Figure 7.8. a. Aggregated weights from plenum session. b. Indicative ranking of alternatives for short- and medium-term ES with average weights.

Note: The presented results here serve only for proving the methodological capacities and presenting the potential of decision-making exercises in line with the purpose of this guideline. Hence, provided results do not address certain decisions within the given workshop consolidation.

Session #2 & #3 Results: Group Work-I and -II

Since in both sessions a similar procedure is applied considering S/MT and LT ES, here results from both sessions are presented together for enabling the comparison. As previously mentioned, DCM method was favoured over 1-10 scale weighting by the participants, hence all the given results here are generated using participant inputs from Part-II. It can be observed from Figure 7.9.a that for S/MT ES sustainability KPIs provided weightings from group work show high relevance for climate change and resource efficiency, low relevance for social acceptance and EU manufacturing capacity which is in line with the plenum session results.

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Figure 7.9. a. Aggregated weights for S/M-term ES sustainability KPIs, b. Aggregated weights for long-term ES KPIs.

Nonetheless, for LT ES, ecosystems quality resulted in the highest weighting followed by climate change and human health (almost equivalent weights) as shown in Figure 7.9.b. The indicative ranking of LT ES technologies results in Power-to-H₂ (highest, 1st), Norwegian PHS, and Power-to-Methane (worst, 3rd) based on provided weights for the sustainability KPIs. Moreover, since participants had the chance to add or replace sustainability KPIs during the DCM exercise, a consolidated list of KPIs is presented in Table 7.3 for evaluating the sustainability of ES technologies considering the gathered input from participants.

Table 7.3. Consolidated list of objectives and sustainability KPIs for assessing ES technologies for S/MT and long-term applications.

Objective	KPIs	Application	Reasoning from reflection activity
Carbon neutral technologies	CO2 footprint (neutrality)	S/MT and LT	Relabelling: CO2 footprint (neutrality) instead of climate change
Good health and wellbeing	Human health	S/MT and LT	No further remarks provided.
Environmentally friendly technologies	Impact on Ecosystems quality	S/MT and LT	Relabelling: Ecosystems impact instead of Ecosystems quality
Affordable renewable energy	LCOS	S/MT and LT	“LCOES added as OPEX and CAPEX are given in absolute terms” “LCOE and LCOS (combination of CAPEX OPEX Efficiency Durability)”
	CAPEX	S/MT and LT	KPIs importance highly related to type of technology
	OPEX	S/MT and LT	KPIs importance highly related to type of technology
Positive public perception of energy technologies	Safety risk	S/MT	No further remarks provided.
	Social awareness	S/MT	No further remarks provided.

Reliable and stable supply chain	EU Manufacturing capacity	S/MT and LT	“if climate change is on the top, it should not matter where we produce different technologies”
	Diversification of suppliers (raw materials)	S/MT and LT	Diversifying suppliers is more realistic than increasing EU manufacturing
Resource efficiency and circularity	Resource efficiency and circularity	S/MT and LT	No further remarks provided.
Technical performance and durability	Efficiency	S/MT and LT	KPIs importance highly related to type of technology
	Durability: reliability	S/MT and LT	Relabelling: “Reliability instead of Durability” “Durability is needed also for long duration”
	Ease of transportation	LT	“Out of scope for HES” “Chemicals vs. electricity, different priorities”
	Ease of storage	LT	“Due to geographical constraints in hydrogen storage as a prominent energy carrier for LT.”
	Capacity factor	S/MT	No further remarks provided.
Promote inclusive and sustainable ES and foster innovation	Novelty	S/MT	No further remarks provided.
	Transferability	S/MT	No further remarks provided.

7.3 Outlook for HES systems

All in all, this working example consolidates the required methods, methodological considerations, materials, and available tools for implementing decision-making analysis in the field of HES. In addition, a list of consolidated KPIs is provided. However, the provided results here aim rather to illustrate what can be achieved with the aid of MCDA than providing results for making actual decisions. The goal was testing the use of such approaches and discovering the potential. Hence, the provided guidance in terms of required organizational preparations prior and during such workshop serves here as a base for conducting analysis of various hybridization alternatives for different applications under consideration of the chosen sustainability framework attributes. Furthermore, the interactive means enabled by the Helmholtz MCDA software supported demonstration of methodological capacities and can be considered as a robust utility for supporting such analysis.

8 WORKING EXAMPLE ON HES SYSTEMS – PROJECT CASES

This guideline is designed to establish a common base for sustainability assessments of HES systems. The authors believe it's crucial to substantiate the statements and guidelines presented here with the results of external activities. Therefore, due to its significant relevance to HES, the 'HYBRIS project' is included in this deliverable as a practical example. While HES is an emerging research field, sustainability assessment is already well-established. Another example provided is the 'SH2E Project', chosen for its practical implications for technology-specific adjustments (i.e., hydrogen) in sustainability assessment.

These two examples were selected based on the wider involvement of StoRIES participants.

8.1 HYBRIS Project

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(see also Table 4.3 for brief information about the HYBRIS project)

The HYBRIS project aims at integrating an aqueous organic redox flow battery (AORFB) with a lithium titanate oxide (LTO) battery to respond to the need of flexible ES systems satisfying both power and energy demands. In the hybrid configuration, the high-power efficiency and fast response from the LTO launch facilitates the use of the ORFB energy capacity, allowing ORFB to work at the maximum efficiency working points. Moreover, the ORFB extends the storage capacity of the LTO, resulting in a final system that can cover a significant part of the requirements that an ES system might have. The integration of both systems will be realized by choosing the right power electronics architecture.

A wide range of applications have been identified for the HYBRIS system. At a consumer level, the system is conceived to be part in microgrids as scaled or pooled Battery ES System (BESS) with at least 1 MW to engage energy-sharing systems. This system is also meant to provide flexibility in terms of frequency and voltage regulation for distribution and transmission operators. With this regard, one of the main objectives of the HYBRIS project is to validate its concept for different applications. Therefore, the HYBRIS prototype will be deployed at three different sites to demonstrate its feasibility and effectiveness. In this endeavour, Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Life Cycle Costing (LCC), including Levelized cost of storage (LCOS) calculation, is being carried out at two different levels: (i) to guide and optimize the economic and environmental performance of the device, and (ii) to finally validate and compare its footprint with state-of-the-art and innovative approaches. Moreover, a study on the standardization landscape has been carried out to identify remarkable aspects that could impact the project's implementation.

8.1.1 Demo Sites

Three sites were selected for this scope to demonstrate the system's functionality developed at different application levels. A pilot located in Messina, Italy, will demonstrate the realization of community services for residential microgrids through an islanded operation. The pilot in Brasschaat,

Belgium, will show the development of new flexibility services under the Energy as a Service (EaaS) model for a commercial and industrial business park with high solar penetration. Finally, a virtual site of a customer-owned system with stacked arbitrage and Frequency Containment Reserve (FCR) for residential buildings with a net metering tariff will be held at Voorhout, Netherlands. This last demo site will be demonstrated virtually through the Digital Twin developed by the project's partners and previously validated in the Italian demo.

8.1.2 LCA

As mentioned, at an early stage, HYBRIS project implementation has been guided under a sustainable framework through a preliminary LCA. This preliminary LCA has compared the environmental impacts of one-kilowatt-hour storage capacity for the two different battery types: LTO and AORFB.

The preliminary LCA included the life cycle inventories of two different batteries selected according to Balcke-Dürr Energy Solutions and KEMIWATT input. The inventories were adapted from literature data and modelled in SimaPro 9.5 software on a comparable basis. A total of eighteen environmental impact categories were assessed at the midpoint level using ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint. Particularly, due to their superior interest on this research field, the following midpoint impact categories have been selected and thoroughly analysed: global warming (GW), stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), terrestrial acidification (TA), human carcinogenic toxicity (HCT), human non-carcinogenic toxicity (HNCT), land use (LU), mineral resource scarcity (MRS), fossil resource scarcity (FRS) and water consumption (WC).

Figure 8.1 shows the relative impact per category for the two selected battery types. There is not a clear trend in the sustainability performance of the different battery types. During the assessment of the LTO batteries, the electrodes were identified as the most critical, making them a hotspot when studying the environmental impacts of this technology. On the other hand, AORFB was identified as the most harmful battery type for the human carcinogenic toxicity category and stratospheric ozone depletion. The main reason behind the high impact of this battery type is the quinone-based anolyte mainly synthesized from a fossil source. Cleaner production of the quinone-based molecule would considerably lower all the stated dominant impacts, making this technology a prominent sustainable option to store electricity. The NCO-LTO battery is the most detrimental battery type for terrestrial acidification, land use and mineral resource scarcity. This battery type is also highly detrimental to the water consumption category.

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Figure 8.1. Environmental impacts comparison among the studied batteries.

8.1.3 LCOS

The economic feasibility of the HYBRIS proposal was approached by studying its LCOS at different deployment scenarios. It compared with state-of-the-art data of different ES systems (ESS) hybrid configurations: hydrogen fuel cell (HFC), lithium-ion (Li-ion), supercapacitor (SC) and Lead-acid (Pb-acid), as presented in Table 8.1. This theoretical comparison did not consider costs linked to the system’s hybridization.

The HYBRIS system is meant to be charged from an electric input that relies on PV generation, but also on complementary supply from the electric grid. The LCOS has been assessed separately for each site by tailoring the share of input electricity according to their solar irradiation and their corresponding PV generation. For the case with 100% share, the higher the input from PV generation, the lower the LCOSs. While for the case with 0% share, the LCOS is directly linked with the electricity price. So, regions with cheaper electricity present lower LCOS than regions with higher

The results in Table 8.1 show that the HYBRIS System is a competitive alternative for the selected pilot sites as compared to existing references for both 0% and 100% PV share. It is important to note that HYBRIS system is significantly competitive and cost-optimized when relying entirely on PV share with a cost varying from 0.1310 and 0.0760 €/kWh for the demo site located in Netherlands and Italy, respectively.

Table 8.1. LCOS for studied configurations.

ESS Configuration	LCOS [€/kWh]	
HFC - Li-ion	0.4280	
HFC - Pb acid	0.6083	
HFC - SC	1.3128	
SC - Pb-acid	1.3847	
SC - Li-ion	1.2288	
HYBRIS Italy	0% PV share	0.5840
	100% PV share	0.0760
HYBRIS Netherlands	0% PV share	0.2200
	100% PV share	0.1310
HYBRIS Belgium	0% PV share	0.3920
	100% PV share	0.1020

Taking this into consideration, the operation of the HES systems should pursue prioritizing the storage from PV generation as its primary energy source. These results reinforce the fact that HYBRIS can be positioned in the market as a very attractive alternative and considered as a cost-competitive when compared to other previously studied ES and HES systems. Further insights of the LCOS for the HYBRIS system will be inferred from monitored data of the pilot sites.

8.1.4 Standardization opportunities

An exhaustive review of the standardization landscape is being performed to recognize the works under development in the fields of knowledge of the project. This study aims at evaluating the most remarkable aspects that impact the HYBRIS strategy for standardization. The analysis of the collected references highlighted the opportunities that the battery management system (BMS) should include in terms of communication protocols and cybersecurity, as well as the novelty of organic flow batteries.

BMS: Communication protocols

The need to define a common framework for communication protocols was one of the opportunities reported by the partners working on the related activities. The idea of unifying the list of inputs, outputs, and parameters, and setting minimum requirements, was indicated as a reasonable alternative to working for standardization, especially when models are shared or operated by a third party. In the same direction, specialized organizations such as Batteries Europe documented the need for communication protocols, a standard real-time data platform and nomenclature [176].

Standardization in this field has the potential to enhance the design and operations of BMS, providing better efficiency to BESS and achieving an adequate performance and shelf-life from the total system [177]. Furthermore, a logically consistent and expansive ontology is essential to support battery digitalization and standardization efforts, being necessary for the multidisciplinary consolidation of explicit knowledge [178]. More than 20 standardization initiatives related to the HYBRIS project’s main area of interest has been screened while identifying potentials for contribution to the project.

BMS: Security

A BESS is vulnerable to several threats that may negatively affect its integrity, confidentiality and availability, impacting the BESS operation and the electric grid [179]. At the physical level, a lack of applying safety-related standards regarding the system’s security has been reported, particularly the risk of fires [180]. Moreover, it has been reported that at a digital level, standards and policies are still not established for utility-scale batteries and BESS implementation projects [181].

Exploring potential contributions in this field is suggested to ensure secure and reliable BESS operation by preventing potential failures that can cause economic issues and physical damage to its components. Technical bodies IEC/TC 105, IEC/TC 120, IEC/TC 82, and IEC/TC 65A are working on standards related to safety issues from different approaches.

ORFBs: Out of EU strategies

In March 2022, the representatives of the flow battery stakeholders in Europe alerted the exclusion of flow batteries from the key requirements of the European Batteries Regulation [182]. This matter was later tackled by the European Parliament and Council of the European Union with the agreement to include the flow batteries in the scope of the sustainability provisions of the Battery Passport, even giving some time to the flow batteries industry to prepare for entry into force of the new rules.

As ORFB technology is still at an early operational stage [183], a close monitoring of the standardization initiatives is recommended by trying to ensure that the flow batteries requirements differentiate from general provisions for mainstream battery technologies, such as lithium-ion batteries.

8.1.5 Future work

As part of the LCA and LCC activities, the primary data from manufacturers and assemblers for implementing HYBRIS prototype along with the data for each use case is being collected throughout the first half of 2024. The final environmental and economic assessment will also include the use-stage and the end-of-life scenarios, broadening the scope of the assessment to the so-called cradle-to-grave. These studies are expected to demonstrate the environmental and economic performance and benefits of the proposed battery hybridization as compared to existing alternatives.

8.2 SH2E Project

Author: Dr. Christina Wulf (FZJ).

Within the SH2E project, the methodological framework proposed for Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA) follows the approach recommended by Ciroth et al. [184]. LCSA, as embraced in this framework, represents a harmonized combination of three key life-cycle techniques: environmental Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) [111], Life Cycle Costing (LCC) [185], and Social Life Cycle Assessment (SLCA) [186]. It is important to note that the overall outcomes of LCSA should be interpreted as a synergistic combination of the results derived from each individual technique.

LCSA is an iterative process composed of four interrelated phases [67], [184]:

- **Goal and scope definition:** This phase involves defining the overarching purpose of the LCSA study, including the intended applications and the decision-making context. The scope sets the

boundaries of the study, specifying aspects such as the system under analysis, its function and functional unit, the covered life-cycle stages, assumptions, stakeholders, methodological choices, sustainability impacts to be investigated, and the selected impact assessment methods.

- **Life cycle inventory analysis:** This phase entails systematically gathering data flows along the product's supply chain, which are subsequently fed to the environmental, economic, and social impact assessments.
- **Life cycle impact assessment:** During this phase, the inventory data of the LCSA study are evaluated to characterize the life-cycle sustainability performance of the product system. The selection of the assessed categories and indicators depends on a materiality assessment that takes into account stakeholders' perspectives.
- **Interpretation:** The interpretation phase involves the analysis of previous results to identify key contributions and potential areas for improvement. It can also enable technological or scenario benchmarking. This phase may encompass robustness tests, sensitivity analyses, uncertainty analyses, completeness analyses, and consistency checks. Results are recommended to be interpreted in a combined manner, identifying potential trade-offs across sustainability dimensions.

This project incorporates insights gained from the individual life-cycle guidelines developed within the SH2E project [113], [187], [188]. While other projects such as ORIENTING have proposed LCSA recommendations with generic applicability [189], the focus of this work was placed on offering practitioners a deeper understanding of the specific aspects in the specific field of fuel cells and hydrogen (FCH) systems, going beyond past initiatives [190], [191]. Consequently, the SH2E LCSA guidelines identify and promote good practices for LCSA of FCH systems, providing a valuable framework for practitioners and stakeholders to make informed, sustainability-oriented decisions.

Within this project four externally reviewed case studies will be published in summer 2024. They will include full LCSA studies on hydrogen production with a solid oxide electrolyzer with electricity from a concentrated solar power plant in Spain for the year 2030, hydrogen production with steam methane reforming of natural gas in Spain in 2030, hydrogen mobility with a fuel cell electric passenger vehicle in 2023 and mobility with a battery electric passenger vehicle in 2023.

9 CONCLUSION

Despite the potential of HES systems to contribute to sustainability, there is currently no assessment framework routine for evaluating their specific environmental, economic, and social impacts. Responding to this demand, this deliverable is formulated in a way to initiate the process towards standardized assessment frameworks for HES and to set a common base for sustainability assessments. Hybridization of ES systems is carried out via combination of two or more different materials, technologies, or even sectors. Thus, encountered challenges when assessing their sustainability exceed beyond the complexity of a single ES technology. Mainly, this complexity stems from the extended value system boundaries and lifecycle stages of the hybridized materials, technologies, or systems.

Considering this complexity, it is necessary to identify the potential pathways for assessing their sustainability. To this aim, a clear guidance is necessary on method selection to address sustainability aspects, identify critical KPIs, and collect relevant data. Moreover, beyond the methodological guidance, it is very important to introduce integrative sustainability assessment approaches into decision-making processes and sustainable business development practices. Particularly, considering the value chain and involved stakeholder perspectives in this assessment routines is essential. The lack of integration and interdependency considerations poses a challenge in unlocking the full potential of HES systems towards European clean energy transition. All in all, this guideline aims to serve as a valuable resource for assessment practitioners, companies, and other stakeholders for supporting informed HES decision-making processes.

The corresponding chapters of this guideline introduce a collection of relevant indicators, methodological frameworks, methods, and tool supplemented use cases for the practical guidance. Within the limits of state-of-the-art sustainability science practices, this deliverable represents a solid base for HES sustainability assessments in accordance with Task 4.2 targets. Hence, the following aspects are identified as the cornerstones of this guideline document:

- **Need for hybridization:** Before considering the hybridization, assessing the main alternative's sustainability thoroughly is fundamental considering all lifecycle stages and sustainability dimensions.
- **Considering benchmarks:** Considering the sustainability KPI benchmarks, one needs to make sure that the hybridized system all in all brings numerous benefits that worth for the increased system complexity with respect to main alternative.
- **Uncertainty:** Hybridization decisions cannot lead to improved sustainability if each of hybridized materials, technologies, or systems cannot be evaluated based on results in an acceptable uncertainty range. The results should incorporate uncertainties in a sensitivity analysis.
- **Choosing a suitable assessment framework:** Assessment results should ideally be the main orientation of the hybridization decisions, it is crucial to select a framework which integrates economic, environmental and social dimensions of sustainability using robust methods and functional KPIs.

- **Case-specific considerations:** Assessments in the field of ES in general requires case-specific considerations which need to be included in the goal and scope definition. This applies to HES sustainability assessment defining the assessment goals, functions, functional units, intended use, scope and other methodological considerations.
- **Impact allocation:** Impact allocation is a very essential part of the assessments when multiple systems are involved in HES systems or multiple functions of the hybridized system exists. Choosing an allocation approach is challenging and must be justified with validated arguments since the results can change drastically based on different approaches.
- **Decision context:** Decisions can be influenced by stakeholders towards different directions, here it is important to set a decision context involving diverse stakeholder groups to co-construct the process. Resulting decision context can be implemented as a decision-tree following a simplified approach as introduced in this guideline or taken a step forward benefiting the blueprint working example in this deliverable on MCDA.
- **Sustainable HES Business Cases:** Eventually, sustainability assessments and their implications need to be considered in the business context for applications. Herein, the developed business model canvas of StoRIES incorporating different sustainability dimensions can be employed for business case development.

Considering the highlighted cornerstones, this guideline provides required resources and tools for assessing the sustainability of HES systems. The appended resources such as input papers, use cases, provide a detailed starting point for the selected sustainability methodologies and frameworks, offering an overview of major methodological steps, used indicators, standards for modelling and reporting. Beyond that major challenges for each methodology and framework are addressed, and examples for ES and HES systems assessment are provided. Finally, setting here a base for the assessments to unlock the potential applications for HES systems, provided resources can be seen as an initiation of continuous development in terms of guidance.

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D4.2 – “Common base for environmental, techno-economic and socio-economic assessment to un-lock the potential applications for hybrid ES (HES) systems”

APPENDICES

Work Package 4 - Supporting the transition towards a climate neutral continent

Task 4.2 - Sustainability Assessments of Hybrid ES Technologies

Submission Date: 30th April 2024

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D4.2 – “Common base for environmental, techno-economic and socio-economic assessment to un-lock the potential applications for hybrid ES systems”

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DISSEMINATION LEVEL

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Date	Version	Author	Signature	Comment
09-04-24	1.0	Hüseyin Ersoy (KIT), Manuel Bauman (KIT)		The first draft
15-04-24	2.0	Hüseyin Ersoy (KIT), Manuel Bauman (KIT)		Updated version + Annexes
30-04-24	FINAL	Hüseyin Ersoy (KIT), Manuel Bauman (KIT)		Final and submitted version

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D4.2 – “Common base for environmental, techno-economic and socio-economic assessment to un-lock the potential applications for hybrid ES systems”

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- APPENDIX H. Use cases selection for sustainability assessment of hybrid es systems**

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APPENDIX A. OVERVIEW OF TASK 4.2. ACTIVITIES

Figure A.1. Schematic illustration of planned and conducted activities in frame of WP4, Task 4.2.

Table A.1. List of meetings and discussed agenda.

No	Date	Discussed points
1	08.02.2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Status of WP4.2 Input from the expert and KPI survey Structure of the guideline document Potential contributions from each partner Next steps
2	16.03.2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Status of WP4.2 Input from the expert and KPI survey Structure of the guideline document Potential contributions from each partner Next steps
3	01.04.2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Status of WP4.2 Definition of working mode (how do we get into the “doing”), working roadmap Basic Definitions, Structure Selection of relevant methods and responsible authors/Editors for the guideline document AOB
4	29.04.2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Status of WP4.2 Fix the responsibilities for thematic input papers Presentation of input paper structure including cross topics as Living documents Roadmap until November AOB

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5	15.06.2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Roadmap for development of the thematic input papers (roles, meetings) • Living documents • Roadmap until November • AOB
6	26.07.2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Task 4.2 Status • Living documents status • Roadmap until November • AOB
7	24.10.2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of the status of the LDs (Publishing) • Discussion on open point in the LDs • Discussion of next steps for LDs • Next steps for Task 4.2 • AOB
8	12.01.2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Status of Task 4.2 • Presentation of the status of the LDs • Next Steps for Task 4.2 (timeline) • Use case definition & input (Mentimeter) • AOB
9	30.03.2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Status of Task 4.2 • Presentation of Article status • Workshop on Criteria/KPIs for energy storage • Use case • AO
10	03.05.2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Status of Task 4.2 • Article Nature Sustainability • Workshop in November • Use case. • AOB
11	03.07.2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use cases. • Workshop in December • Main Document • AOB
12	09.02.2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current status • Workshop in December • Publications • Sustainability Guideline submission • AOB
13	28.02.2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current status • Publications • Sustainability Guideline submission • AOB
14	20.03.2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General discussion on the finalization of the deliverable

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1. FRAMING PROCESS

An online first meeting was held on 16th in March 2022. A Mentimeter© survey was carried out with the participants to gather a better understanding of the task and to identify relevant methods to be included in frame of the guideline.

From which Institution are you?
10 responses

Figure A.2. Affiliation of participants.

The participants provided a first overview of what they expect from the guideline, where they see major challenges and which methods are mostly used within their institutes. Methods use cover a broad field, mainly focusing on methods as Life cycle assessment, techno-economic methods, and others. Finally, the main target group for the sustainability guideline was discussed.

What do you expect from the Guideline (one short sentence)?

Where do you see main challenges in the sustainability assessment of hybrid energy storage?

Which methods do you use for your assessments?

Who do you think is the main target group of the guideline?

Figure A.3. Overview of collected inputs via interactive survey for the designation of the guideline.

The next steps was to identify how to structure the guidelines document, here it was decided to head towards a dimension wise structuring of the document, and not towards a method wise way.

2. STRUCTURING PROCESS

How should we define the thematic clusters?

Figure A.4. Gathered input via interactive survey on how to structure the thematic clusters.

Figure A.5. Outcome of the survey for choosing the methods to be considered in each thematic cluster.

Within several iterations, the process was fixed as depicted in Table A.2.

Table A.2. Timeline for the generation of the input papers on the selected thematic clusters.

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Date	Stage of the process	Who
June (14-17th)	General WP4 meeting, introduce process, status	Marco, Manuel, Ghanna
June (20-26th)	First thematic meeting (for each input paper) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discuss and confirm timeline • Discuss and define how to identify relevant methods, based on collected inputs • Identify contributors writing the single challenges 	Input paper group WP4: Editors, Co-Authors, WG 4
July (15)	Deadline for contributions Editors, co-authors and Coordinators combine them into a first draft	WP4: Editors, Co-Authors
July (18-22)	Meeting to discuss first draft Result: goals for improving the paper over the summer	Input paper group WP4: Editors, Co-Authors
July (25-29)	General WP4 meeting, Presentation of Guideline + input papers (15 min each)	Marco, Manuel, Ghanna, Editors, WP4 +WG 4(?)
Aug. 15	Deadline for contributions Editors and co-authors combine and edit them into a final draft	WP4: Editors, Co-Authors
Sept. 15	Distribute the paper among the authors and the commenters	StoRIES, EERA JP ES
Sept. 30	Deadline for comments	StoRIES, EERA JP ES
Oct. 10-14th	Meeting for finalization, corrections, alterations	Input paper group WP4: Editors, Co-Authors
Oct. 28th	Final papers	WP4: Editors, WP Coordinators
November	StoRIES Meeting, Presentation of Progress in WP4	Marco

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3. USE CASE GENERATION

A further step was to collect different use cases that can be used to illustrate sustainability assessments in the field. This was done at first on a WP4 level and extended during the project development. As for the methods partners were asked to express their expectation on the used cases for sustainability assessment.

Figure A.6. Overview of use case collection input.

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Which energy storage technology would be included in your use case?

Figure A.7. Overview of technology expertise of partners.

Figure A.8. Overview of expert across various sustainability assessment methods.

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APPENDIX B. EXEMPLARY DECISION TREE FOR HYBRID ES SYSTEMS

Figure B.1. Developed exemplary decision-tree for supporting hybridization decisions for ES.

APPENDIX C. BUSINESS SUSTAINABILITY CANVAS TEMPLATE

Figure C.1. StoRIES business model canvas.

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Business Model Canvas

Figure C.2. StoRIES business model canvas incorporating business aspects of three sustainability dimensions. (Blue: economics, green: environmental, red: social)

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Business Model Canvas

Use Case: Home Storage Manufacturer
(Battery only)

Figure C.3. An example business model canvas from StoRIES partners.

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Figure C.4. An example business model canvas from StoRIES partners.

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Business Model Canvas

Use Case: Aluminum wet combustion system for electricity and hydrogen supply for EV refuelling stations

<p>Key Partners/Stakeholders</p> <p>Manufacturer/supplier of various components:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expanders & turbines (Steam turbine, gas turbine), • Pumps & compressors (air and hydrogen compression), • Fuel Cell (SOFC), • Heaters, coolers, and heat exchangers, • Pipes, valves, mixers, splitters, • Reactor (Wet combustion chamber), • Phase Separators • Generators and electrical conversion equipment (batteries, transformers, etc.), • Process equipment housing • Cables, voltage and frequency regulators (transformers), grid connection • SCADA operations controls <p>Aluminum producers, Licensed installers and contractors Refueling station operators, Aluminum transportation logistics Test centers/ standardization (Labs)</p> <p style="text-align: right;">3</p>	<p>Key Activities</p> <p>Operation planning and business strategy, Securing material supply and transportation, System design and development, Optimization based on site requirements, Implementation, Running tests on-site, Operationalization: Aluminum production (RES surplus), use of Aluminum for electricity and H2 supply, planning the auxiliary services with grid operators. Active maintenance.</p> <p style="text-align: right;">4</p> <p>Key Resources/Infrastructure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aluminum supply chain (bauxite mining, alumina and aluminum production) • RE surplus, • Refueling stations, • Human resource, • Material and equipment manufacturers, • Know-how <p style="text-align: right;">2</p>	<p>Value Propositions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased Al production on RE surplus hours (cheap electricity), • Provide customer programs to shift demand hours to certain time frames where RE generation is low, • Dynamic price adjustment at refueling station for electricity and H2, • Provision of market/system services • Optimize the availability of services based on profitability and plan the auxiliary services <p style="text-align: right;">1</p> <p>Regulatory Framework</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Certifications • Annual inspection of installed systems • Subsidy guidelines • Grid connection conditions • Safety standards/construction guidelines (H2 storage and supply, and electricity as well) • Transport standards <p style="text-align: right;">10</p>	<p>Customer Relationships</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fuel purchase and material recycling contract. • Refueling station concept introduction • Customer royalty program for demand management <p style="text-align: right;">6</p> <p>Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trade fairs • Social media • Advertisement on mainstream • Anti-fossil propaganda and green fuel campaigns • Special offers for fleets. <p style="text-align: right;">7</p>	<p>Customer Segments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Refueling station of all kind, • Decentralized refueling and recharging stations located far from grid or pipeline, • Low/high duty vehicle fleet users or leasers <p style="text-align: right;">5</p>
<p>Cost Structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Equipment and installation cost • Construction cost • Contractor's fee • Electricity cost • Fuel Cost (Al) • Operation & maintenance costs (Plant and refueling) • Grid connection charges • Overheads • Logistics • Certifications • Insurance • Personnel <p style="text-align: right;">8</p>		<p>Revenue Streams</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sale and installation to private customers, • Income through arbitrage trade of prosumer Al smelters, • Preventative maintenance, • Subsidies and incentives <p style="text-align: right;">9</p>		

Figure C.5. An example business model canvas from StoRIES partners.

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Figure C.6 . An example business model canvas from StoRIES partners.

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Business Model Canvas

Partner: Home Storage Battery + hot water tank (for household)

Figure C.7. An example of business model canvas from StoRIES partners covering all sustainability dimensions.

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D4.2 – “Common base for environmental, techno-economic and socio-economic assessment to un-lock the potential applications for hybrid ES (HES) systems”

Work Package 4 - Supporting the transition towards a climate neutral continent

Task 4.2 - Sustainability Assessments of Hybrid ES Technologies

Submission Date: 30th April 2024

APPENDIX D. INPUT PAPER: ECONOMIC ASPECTS

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

AIRR	Adjusted Internal Rate of Return
ANF	Annuity Factor
BOP	Balance of Plant
CAES	Compressed Air Energy Storage
CAPEX	Capital Expenditures
CBA	Cost Benefit Analysis
CBS	Cost Breakdown Structure
eLCC	Environmental Life Cycle Cost
EOLEX	End-of-Life Expenditures
ES	Energy Storage
ESS	Energy Storage System
IRR	Internal Rate of Return
LCOE	Levelized Cost of Electricity
LCOEx	Levelized Cost of Exergy
LCOH ₂	Levelized Cost of Hydrogen
LCOHeat	Levelized Cost of Heating
LCOS	Levelized Cost of Storage
LCOU	Levelized Cost of Use
LCSA	Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment
MARR	Minimal Acceptable Rate of Return

NPV	Net Present Value
O&M	Operation and Maintenance
OPEX	Operational Expenditures
P&L	Profit and Loss
PCM	Phase Changing Material
PCS	Power Conversion System
PV	Photovoltaics
RBA	Risk Benefit Analysis
SCR	Self-Consumption Rate
SEIA	Socio-economic Impact Assessment
sLCC	Social or Societal Life Cycle Cost
TOC	Total Ownership Cost
TRL	Technological Readiness Level
VSC	Valued Social or Economic Components
WACC	Weighted Average Cost of Capital
WAP	Weighted Average (Wholesale Energy) Price

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SEA Socio economic analysis..... D-29

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1. INTRODUCTION TO THE THEMATIC CLUSTER

Efficient and affordable energy storage systems have a high relevance for a future sustainable energy and transport system. The market success of such technologies is strongly affected by their cost criterion due to its influence on creating business cases that operates under profitable conditions to satisfy required storage services. In order to evaluate this, various methods can be applied to quantify cost-related aspects. Nevertheless, considering the required wholistic approach to maintain the satisfaction of different stakeholders involved in different life-cycle stages using conventional and integrated Life Cycle Cost (LCC) estimation methods are powerful tools. In particular for the storage technologies, attributing the provided energy as a service most of the time is the used allocation as in levelized cost of X (LCOX), where X referring differing energy vectors) and other currency per functional unit variations. In line with these, different indicators can be applied for the analysis of energy storage. These values are highly dependent on the selected region and the corresponding markets, specific use cases and owner structure. It is thus difficult to derive general benchmarks in these regards, without adequate consideration of potential energy storage value streams. However, it is possible to contrast the cost performance of the considered technology to a state-of-the-art reference of its same purposed design. In the following sections a comprehensive overview of some of the most relevant methods will be provided in order to allow a fast “how to” carry out corresponding assessments. All chapters are structured in the same way and provide a state-of-the-art snippet of different methods. Considered methods share same basic principles and are often not sharply distinguishable from each other. Also, Techno-economic methods can be situated within the general sustainability framing, ultimately also be combined with other methods as indicated in Figure D.1.

Figure D.1. Overview of sustainability KPIs and Tools for (hybrid) energy storage technologies (Draft from Salome Hohl), with scope of this input paper.

This input paper is structured in a way to give an overview of fundamental parameters and key performance indicators (KPIs) calculations required for an economic assessment. The following methods are considered and explained in detail in frame of this input paper:

- Static and dynamic basic calculation methods,
- Life cycle costing methods and application,
- Levelized cost of energy calculation methods for various energy vectors and services,
- Allocation approaches,
- Socio economic analysis (SEA).

For each method, required data and accuracy of the method for the aimed result is specified under technology or process specific conditions supported with exemplary use cases are summarized at the end of each chapter. Additionally, commonly used allocation approaches are summarized using illustrative examples. In general, they can, but must not be summarized under techno-economic assessments. Also, the list presented here is not complete, only the most relevant ones, to the authors knowledge have been included here. These methods share some common basics, which will be addressed in the following.

2. OVERVIEW OF METHODS

This section aims to provide an orientation to the reader to identify relevant methods that are applicable for an economic assessment considering the stage of development. It is important to highlight that conducting an economic assessment for an energy storage technology highly depends on technological readiness level (TRL) which is also associated with the availability of the product or service specifications. Conducting an economic assessment for an energy storage technology requires most of the time many detailed information which will highly influence the investment decision. Nevertheless, it is not always the case that all the required data is available, hence missing data or details requires reasonable assumptions made by the practitioner. In particular, it is vital to make verified expert judgements for estimating costs in capital intensive projects where a major part of the cost is stemming from the capital expenditures. Here, the important criterion is the complexity of the proposed project. The optimal case is where all the direct investment costs are identified and estimated using real world data based on vendor information and contractors. Even so, most of the time this is not possible. Therefore, some approaches with a reasonable uncertainty could also be indicative for screening the potential or even estimating the project economics expressed with cost intervals using basic methods. These approaches can be summarized as explained in detail in [1]:

- **Engineering cost methods:** starting from the component level leading to the entire system,
- **Cost accounting:** using modern cost management systems to track and allocate expenses,
- **Analogy:** an estimate using historical results from similar products or components,
- **Parametric:** based on mathematical relationships (e.g., linear or non-linear regression using historical data) between costs and some product- and process- related parameters.

A method using any combination of these methods can be used to develop total ownership costs (TOCs). Given the first two methods refer to so-called bottom-up approaches while the latter two methods are top-down approaches. Here the bottom-up approaches refer to a cost model considering customer's requirements for system constituents in detail aiming a wholistic system assessment. The bottom-up approaches break the project down into elements using work breakdown structures and physical and functional architectures. On the contrary, top-down approaches considers a project based on the overall estimated cost where the project specifications and requirements are not clearly defined. This method is mostly used for a fast guess or rough estimation where large uncertainty related to the scaling effects, or design sensitive cost components.

In a standard product development process by the time course major part of the life cycle costs get involved starting from the commercialization phase, where the ability to influence LCC is minimum. (see Figure D.2) On the other hand, if it is possible to make an outreaching economic assessment considering the life cycle stages of a product starting from conceptual exploration the LCC of a project can be majorly influenced.

Methods / Stage	Conceptual Exploration	Component Advanced Development	System Integration / Preliminary Design	System Demonstration, Test, and Evaluation	Production	Operations, Support, and Disposal
Parametric Cost Estimation	Primary Technique	Primary Technique	Some Applicability	Little or No Utility	Little or No Utility	Some Applicability
Analogy	Primary Technique	Some Applicability	Some Applicability	Some Applicability	Little or No Utility	Some Applicability
Detailed Engineering Build Up	Some Applicability	Some Applicability	Primary Technique	Primary Technique	Primary Technique	Some Applicability

Figure D.2. Ability to influence LCC with respect to technological development stages and applicability of cost estimation methods. Based on [1].

Most of the time product developers prioritize the performance against cost, this can lead downstream cost overruns and potentially project failure. Using the presented methods, the following can be achieved as stated in [1]:

- Estimate the TOC to the various stakeholders.
- Reduce and capture TOC through using LCC trade-offs (in four domains: performance, cost, schedule, risk/quality) in the systems engineering and product development processes.
- Control cost through LCC contractual provisions in procurements.
- Assist in day-to-day acquisition management actions by providing timely, consistent, and relevant cost information.

The LCC assessments determine the cost of owning, operating and finally disposing a system over its lifespan. The approach doesn't only require an understanding of the time value of money (including price escalation, inflation, cost of capital, depreciation, and taxation) but also to estimate the true TOC. Above in Figure D.2, given methods and their applicability in various life cycle stages are presented.

An LCC model developed involved two principal types of uncertainties, these are:

1. Uncertainty stemming from cost-generating activities,
2. Uncertainty regarding the expected cost of these activities.

These uncertainties mostly high in the early stage of development where reasonable limits need to be defined in the model. Hence creating the cost categories and categorizing the uncertainties truly is sometimes a bigger challenge than estimating the cost itself. In this manner, classifying the categories in general terms and then elaborating for each life cycle stage is the common practice. Life cycle costs in general are viewed from a pre- and post-production perspective, with some typical main categories as shown in Figure D.3.

Figure D.3. Some general LCC categories.

Since costing is essential for making a profitability analysis of a system considering various life cycle stages a general outline is drawn so far. In the following chapters, required methods are explained for estimating the time value of the money and investment in order to estimate the true TOC from a life cycle -based perspective.

3. BASIC CALCULATION METHODS

As explained before considered methods share same basic principles and are often not sharply distinguishable from each other.

Static methods

Non-discounted investment analysis methods are still used in industrial practice due to their relatively simple handling [2], [3]. Well-known static methods are cost accounting and cost comparison calculations. In general, all methods observe one representative period of the total service life of a product (typically one year). This single period methods take into account all in and outgoing cash flows in one period. In line of this assessment the simple cost comparison will be used in an adopted way as an example for comparison of methods and will therefore be briefly explained.

The cost comparison method is a simple way of comparing investment alternatives determined by fixed and variable costs where the most economical option is selected [3]. A main problem of this method is that in reality cash flows are not uniformly distributed over the life cycle of a product. Furthermore, interest and liquidity effects of deferred cash flows as well as time factors (e.g. change of the value of money or present worth factor) are completely ignored [3], [4].

Dynamic Methods

Discounting techniques are used to compare costs and benefits that occur in different time periods. To do so the costs in different points over the lifetime must be converted to a common point in time to reflect the time value of money [5]. The start-up time or commissioning (Go-Live) point [4] of the assessed product or object should be taken as reference [3]. An interest rate which is based on an investors/stakeholder's time value of money perception [6] is used to discount future expenditures to present values at a certain reference time point [5]. It can be also calculated by applying the Weighted Average Cost of Capital (WACC) approach if enough information (usually very sensitive data) is available from the stakeholder. In the following relevant dynamic investment methods for LCC will be briefly presented and finally compared.

3.1. Net Present Value

The Net Present Value (NPV) method represents the basic principle for modern investment analysis to investigate the present worth of all future present values [4]. The present value is concerned to determine the worth at the end of t interest periods of equal payments invested at an annual compound interest rate i at the end of each interest period t (usually a year) [7]. These present values (P_t Income-Costs C_t) are then summed up in Equation 3.1 as follows.

$$C_{NPV} = -I_{t0} + \sum_{t=0}^T P_t - C_t(1+i)^{-t} + L(1+i)^{-t} \quad (3.1)$$

3.2. Annuity Method

A different form of the NPV is the annuity method. The NPV is distributed in yearly equivalent series of cash flows over the entire lifetime of the product and is calculated by Equation 3.2.

$$C_a = C_{NPV} \frac{(1+i)^T * i}{(1+i)^T - 1} \quad (3.2)$$

3.3. Internal rate of return

Another relevant method is the Internal Rate of Return (IRR) which is used to investigate the cost effectiveness of a potential investment. The investment alternative can be considered attractive if the calculated interest is higher than the expected Minimal Acceptable Rate of Return (MARR) or used depreciation rate respectively. If the calculated rate is lower the investment can be considered unattractive. The investor is indifferent in the case of equal interest rate. The method can be considered as supplement to the dynamic methods applied for LCC as annuity or NPV. IRR can be estimated by iterative approximation or more easily with rough arithmetical approximation methods as simple linear interpolation between a negative and positive NPV by the use of Equation 3.3.

$$-I_{t0} + \sum_{t=0}^T P_p (1+i)^{-t} + \sum_{t=0}^T C_p (1+i)^{-t} = 0 \quad (3.3)$$

A main problem of the IRR is that multiple results can be achieved if there are several cash flow switches from positive to negative. A more severe problem is that IRR assumes that cash flows are reinvested at the calculated IRR leading over or understates of project profitability [6]. The IRR can be used in an adopted form known as Adjusted IRR (AIRR) also known as Baldwin method as a supplement of LCC analysis to additionally measure economic effectiveness of an investment alternative [6]. AIRR uses an explicit reinvestment rate (usually the used depreciation rate which also represents the MARR) and is therefore considered more accurate than IRR. An additional advantage of AIRR is that it can be computed algebraically and has not to be found iteratively.

3.4. Comparison of methods

The presented calculations are based on a generic system showing the high number of influences that can appear when LCC is conducted. The purpose of the paper is not predominantly the evaluation of

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the energy storage technology used for assessment but rather to show the impacts of data sources and calculation methods.

The most challenging part beside data collection was to build an adequate model for LCC. A precondition for an adequate model is a sufficient understanding of the technology that is assessed as well as a robust data base for it. The used model was therefore especially developed for the assessment of emerging electrochemical storage technologies taking into account their certain technological properties. This process was accompanied with an extensive literature review about energy storage technology LCC assessments which showed that calculation methods where comparable, but the source of data tended to be outdated in many cases or did not use uniformed data (e.g. differing cell chemistry). Presented methods in this paper can be adopted for any other assessment and are briefly compared in Table D.1.

Table D.1. Brief comparison of cost calculation methods.

	Pro	Contra	Comments
Simple cost comparison calculation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Simple to conduct and transparent. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not realistic, neglects basic economic principles, no effective evaluation of investment objects. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Should not be used for in depth evaluations or decision making based on long-term considerations.
NPV	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Varying cash flows are considered with time preference. Easy to apply. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Choice of depreciation rate can be difficult. Estimates have to be done regarding future cash flows including uncertainty. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Approaches as real option valuation can help to achieve more accurate.
Annuity			
AIRR (IRR adoption)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Beneficial supplementary methods. Good for technology comparison. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Very time consuming. Has to be carried out carefully. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Proved to be very helpful for sensitivity analyses e.g., replacing different components.

4. LIFE CYCLE COSTING

The structure and outline of the chapters is based on Andes et. al [8] and is adopted to hybrid energy storage systems.

4.1. Synonyms / other related methods

Life cycle Costing (LCC), sometimes also labelled as Total Cost of Ownership (TCO), Environmental Life Cycle Costing (eLCC) [9], Social or Societal LCC (sLCC)

4.2. Assessment level

Which disciplines are addressed, what is the scope (e.g. Process, System...)

Table D.2. Assessment level of LCC

Discipline	Scope
<input type="checkbox"/> Social Sciences and Humanities	<input type="checkbox"/> Country / Region
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input type="checkbox"/> Company / Organisation
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Economic sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Process
<input type="checkbox"/> Natural sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Product/Service
<input type="checkbox"/> Environmental sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> System

4.3. Short description

Life Cycle Costing (LCC) is a method for life cycle oriented (life cycle) evaluation of investment alternatives and can be considered as part of techno-economic assessments. LCC is also considered to fill the gap between the economic pillar within environmental and social pillars for the Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA) [9].

4.4. Scope

In general, LCC can be applied anywhere and has a "cradle-to-grave" perspective. There is no strict common standard for LCC approach but a common definition of it as follows: “*process of economic analysis to assess the life cycle cost of a product over its life cycle or a portion thereof*” [9], [10] There are different scopes depending on the type of LCC. A brief overview based on s provided in Table D.3.

Table D.3 Various life cycle costing (LCC) assessment types.

	Assessment level	Scope	Description
LCC	Conventional	economy	
e-LCC	Environmental LCC	Economy and Environment	Inclusion of internal cost
Fe-LCC	Full environmental LCC	Economy and Environment	Extends with environmental cost
s-LCC	Societal LCC	Economy, Environment and Society	Further impacts as public health, well-being

4.5. Methodology

There are several levels of LCC available which will be introduced in brief in the following. Conventional LCC (see Equation 4.4) covers all expenses related to research and development (R&D) C_{RD} , extraction of raw materials supply & manufacturing C_m , construction C_i , which can be summarized as CAPEX operation and maintenance $C_{O\&M}$ or operational expenditures (OPEX and disposal or end of life respectively C_{EOL} or end of life expenditures (EOLEX). Additionally, cost of externalities C_{Ext} (such as greenhouse gas emissions) can be considered within an LCC, depending on the selected focus [11].

$$LCC = CAPEX + OPEX + EOLEX + C_{ext} + C_{int} \quad (4.4)$$

Usually, the calculated cost is divided by a functional unit, which has to be properly defined. Usually, this is the converted amount of energy stored. This is then expressed within a certain functional unit, which is selected depending on the analysed system as well as application field. Doing so, allows to describe the total cost of the storage system dividing it by its cumulative delivered energy. Here typically energy losses in the system are attributed as cost to the system [4].

4.6. Environmental Life Cycle Costing (e-LCC)

Environmental oriented LCC approaches (e-LCC) entail environmental aspects and impact by internalizing the costs. This is realized by applying the polluter pays principle, or by using information allowing to quantify potential impacts [13]. Doing so, it can be considered as an extension of conventional LCC approaches. Internal costs are costs in the life cycle of a product (any stakeholder directly involved in the product system value chain) paid for the production, use or EOL expenses. There is furthermore literature available that extends this type of e-LCC to a full e-LCC, where environmental impact stemming from a LCA are monetarized [9].

4.7. Social or Societal LCC (s-LCC)

The scope of s-LCC is very broad, it includes all relevant cost related to society and the life cycle of a product. Here impacts on different aspects as e.g. public health are monetarized [9]. This makes this type of assessment very challenging. Typically, no transfer payments, subsidies as well as taxes are not considered. A difference to conventional LCC is that the discount rates are rather low over time [14].

4.8. Dimensions and Indicators

LCC Covers the economic dimension of sustainability. Here it considers all costs (and revenues) in the life cycle of a product or system as real cash flows (inputs and outputs). (cash inflows and outflows) [8]. Typical indicators at the end are energy €/kWh or power related €/kW [15]. The indicators can depend on the type of service provided at the end of the storage system. This can be e.g., the use of heat, hydrogen or electricity.

4.9. Description and application in the field of (hybrid) energy storage

LCC and named comparable methods are widely applied in the field of energy storage evaluation. Some examples are e.g.;

- Comparison of storage alternatives within a certain applications field,
- Identification of cost hotspots,
- Identification of suitable application field for specific technologies,
- Assessing the commercialization chance of a technology.

4.10. How to

LCC can be used for a systematic comparison of alternative project designs including total expenditures (initial investment, capital, replacement, operation, energy and disposal costs etc.) over the whole economic lifetime of a product. LCC can provide insights to help society appropriately allocate limited financial resources to monetary optimize technical improvements. General steps according to Andes et. al [8] are:

Figure D.4. General procedure to carry out a LCC based on [8]

4.10.1 Goal definition

First of all, it is necessary to clearly formulate the goals and to derive concrete targets, which can be calculated using typical techno-economic methods. The target parameters are usually specific cost per generated economic unit, or monetary or derived variables such as the net present value or amortization period.

Besides that, a corresponding project run time as well as internal interest flow has to be defined. The target definition also includes the definition of system boundaries, i.e. the decision which life cycle stages of the investment object are to be considered in the analysis.

In general, up-front capital is only a part of a products life cycle. It is therefore necessary to state the application conditions under which (hybrid) energy storage unit in general will be operated. Operation conditions have a strong influence on e.g., necessary maintenance efforts as well as potential replacement investments and thus on the total LCC.

4.10.2 Definition of alternatives

Definition of relevant investment options or potential business cases. This can entail the selection among of e.g. system designs, material selection for energy storage.

4.10.3 Data collection and availability

The availability of reliable cost and technology performance data is vital when performing LCC. As explained before, ideally LCC covers all expenses related to every life cycle phase of a product which should be identified accordingly, which is in most cases not an easy task. For a systematic analysis, it is useful to create a Cost Breakdown Structure (CBS), a matrix from which dependencies become visible. For this purpose, the system is broken down into the individual cost elements and assigned to the individual stages in the life cycle which are assigned to the individual stages in the life cycle. Possible criteria are activity fields, main elements or classes of the same system elements. Also, collected data has to be normalized in respect to the corresponding currency using correct exchange and discount rates.

This is in particular also highly dependent on the TRL of the assessed technology. Usually, data is available for high TRL technologies, including cost as well as technical parameters. In contrast, the assessment of low TRL technologies is accompanied with limited availability of data and might prone to high uncertainties which have to be properly addressed via sensitivity analyses. There are different methods can be used to carry out parameter and cost element estimation. These are namely, i) parametric cost method, ii) analogous cost methods and iii) engineering cost method. The most used method is i) the parametric cost methods which is the most suitable method to be used in early TRL levels where available data is limited. In higher TRLs the other two methods may be used to obtain more robust results [5].

Typical data required for LCC including some examples is listed below following [5]:

Table D.4. LCC: typical data and examples

Basic data	Purchase price/ Upfront Investment of a product	Operation cost	End of life costs
Economic: expected project running time, depreciation rate, inflation, taxes etc. Relevant technical data: Efficiencies, lifetime, energy densities, self-discharge etc.	Concept and definition cost to ensure the feasibility of the product under consideration (project management, concept and design analysis etc.) Design and development cost for specification of the product and the proof of fulfilment of the requirement specification (Project management, prototyping, demonstration and validation etc.) Manufacturing and construction cost are assigned to the creation of the required number of individual parts of the product or the provision of the specified support services (plant design, Assembly, installation and functional testing etc.)	Costs related to the operation of the plant that are recurring as e.g., Labour costs, consumables, energy and one time cost e.g., Equipment, facilities and special tools. Costs related to preventive maintenance that are non-recurring e.g., Procurement of measurements devices and tools, and recurring cost as e.g., spare parts, consumables,	Recommissioning, Dismantling and disposal, recycling or safe disposal.

4.10.4 Calculation methods

There is no common standard for LCC. The choice of a specific LCC method is dependent on the availability of data, time, resources and aim of the study. The choice of a specific LCC method is dependent on the availability of data, time, resources and aim of the study. However, there are guidelines as the IEC 60300-3-3 or VDI 2884 for general application by both customers and suppliers

of products, explaining the purpose and value of LCC and outlines the general approaches involved [3], [10]. There are only few differences within literature regarding the entire LCC concept but there are variations regarding differentiation and calculation methods. A comprehensive comparison of LCC studies using different approaches is given in [7].

In general static and non-static methods (discounted dynamic methods) can be applied for LCC, however, mainly the latter are applied which will be explained briefly in the following. Discounting techniques are used to compare costs and benefits that occur in different time periods. Costs in different points over the lifetime must be converted to a common point in time to reflect the time value of money. The commissioning point of the assessed product or object should be taken as reference. An interest rate which is based on an investors/stakeholder’s time value of money perception is used to discount future expenditures to present values at a certain reference time point [5]. It can be also calculated by applying the Weighted Average Cost of Capital (WACC) approach if enough information is available from the stakeholder.

Typical discounted dynamic methods that are to be used for LCC are NPV and annuity method. Both methods discount all cash inflows and outflows associated with the investment to a reference date (start of the project). For detail see Section 3 where a basic overview of the same is provided.

Further dynamic methods to be named in the context of LCC are the discounted payback that displays the payback point in time with considering the time value of money [6]. However, most commonly the annuity method is used within the context of LCC for energy storage [15], [16].

In the following a detailed overview of major calculation steps is provided based on [15]. Here a rather technology agnostic description is provided as the method itself can be applied to any (hybrid) energy storage technology. It should, however, be noted that adjustments might be necessary depending on the analysed technology as well as selected dynamic investment calculation method.

Capital expenditure

The CAPEX (C_{cap}) includes all cost related to planning, the purchase of components, installation, as well as grid connection of a storage unit as expressed in Equation 4.5. The values can be displayed by either €/kW or €/kWh. Typically, depending on the type of storage balance of plant and power (C_{BOP}) conversions systems (C_{PCS}) and the core storage unit in kW (C_{stor}) multiplied by the discharge time (h) cost is included. Note that in case of using the annuity method, one has to add C_a to retrieve the annualized CAPEX (see Chapter 3.2).

$$C_{cap} = (C_{PCS} + C_{BOP} + C_{stor} \cdot h) \cdot C_a \quad (4.5)$$

The operational cost of a storage unit is usually including on a yearly base, as fixed O&M and variable O&M cost (C_{Fix}). Fixed cost is related to the storage unit O&M that have to be considered no matter if the storage system is converting and storing power or not. In contrast variable O&M (C_{Var}) relate to the required for operation (e.g. water, electricity) during the operation of the system. The cost C_{Var} is multiplied with t_{eh} equivalent full cycles n and the operation hours of the storage unit (also named as full load hours). The resulting cost is displayed in (€/kW -yr.) following Equation 4.6 [15].

$$\begin{aligned} LCC_a &= C_{Cap,a} + C_{OPEX} + C_{rep,a} + C_{EOL,a} OPEX \\ &= (C_{Fix} + C_{Var} \cdot n \cdot h) \cdot C_a \end{aligned} \quad (4.6)$$

It is worth mentioning that the variable cost has to consider the efficiency of the storage unit. Usually, the efficiency and self-discharge losses are attributed as cost to the storage unit. This also entails losses related to BOP as well PCS (if relevant, as e.g. in the case of electrolyzers or batteries).

Here no cost for replacement has yet been considered. These are usually addressed separately. This is done by taking into consideration the future replacement cost C_{rep} of any component (e.g. the storage unit itself, BOP or PCS). Here the cost (usually in €/kWh) has to be taken into account depending on the selected method and the corresponding year (t) for replacement (the depreciated (I) values is used, e.g. for purchase prices of batteries). Replacement costs ($C_{rep,a}$) can be calculated by using given the number of replacements (r) during the application lifetime, the present value in combination with C_a as presented in Equation 4.7. The latter an vary in dependence of the viewed technology which has to be reflected accordingly (e.g. batteries in combination with flywheels) [15]. Here, potential changes in technology performance should also be reflected (e.g. higher energy densities, efficiencies or life time extensions) [16].

$$C_{rep,a} = C_a \cdot \sum_{t=0}^T (1+i)^{-t} \cdot \left(\frac{C_{rep} \cdot h}{\eta_{(comp)}} \right) \quad (4.7)$$

Recycling and Disposal cost referred to as EOLEX ($C_{EOL,a}$) should be considered as far as possible. This comes in particular true if valuable materials are used, as e.g. cobalt and nickel for Lithium-ion batteries or platinum and iridium for PEM electrolyzers or fuel cells. Here the value of the materials shall be included as depreciated value at the year t where a replacement of the corresponding component takes place. Naturally, the entire C_{Rec} of a (hybrid) storage unit should be included as far as possible at the end of the project period (e.g. 20 years) as indicated in Equation 4.8.

$$C_{EOL,a} = C_{EOL} \cdot \frac{i}{(1+i)^T} \quad (4.8)$$

Finally, all costs are summed up to gather the full (annually) LCC in e.g. €/kW-y as shown in Equation 4.9.

$$LCC_a = C_{Cap,a} + C_{OPEX} + C_{rep,a} + C_{EOL,a} \quad (4.9)$$

In most cases the cost is displayed as a ratio of the converted energy to the full LCC, resulting in a functional unit, which allows it to show the cost in form of €/kWh, which sometime is referred to as Levelized Cost of Electricity (see Equation 4.10). Here the yearly full load hours are calculated taking the total yearly full cycles and the corresponding discharging times.

$$LCOE = \frac{LCC_a}{n_a \cdot h} \quad (4.10)$$

Such an indicator allows it to simply compare different storage alternatives delivering same services. However, the same calculation approach has to be followed to make alternatives comparable. Beside this direct costs LCC can also include cost of externalities. These may include the cost of emissions of greenhouse gases and of other pollutant emissions that occur to the analyzed product, service or works during its life cycle.

4.10.5 Sensitivity Analysis

There are numerous variables that influence the outcome of an LCC. Sensitivity analysis should therefore always be carried out in order to assure robust results of an LCC. Typically, full load hours are a sensitive parameter in the calculus of indicators as LCOE or LCOS, which has been proven in various works [17-19].

4.11. Reporting

There are no standards for reporting in LCC. However general standards of transparency and traceability of used data and modelling approach should be part of the report. Also, sufficient sensitivity analyses shall be provided.

4.12. Strength and weaknesses

Table D.5. Overview of strengths and weaknesses (S&W) based on [8]

Strength	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> LCC can be used to answer strategic questions, such as the economic impact of technical changes, the influence of individual technical changes, the influence of individual parameters on the LCC, the amortization of additional investments or an economically and ecologically conscious choice of an investment alternative. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data collection can be challenging Evaluation of the data represents a considerable additional expenditure

4.13. Standards and guidelines

Conventional LCC

- IEC, Dependability management – Part 3-3: Application guide – Life cycle costing (IEC 56/1549/CD:2014), Bd. 60300-3-3/Ed3/CD. 2014.
- K. Bourke, „Life cycle costing 1st edition, April 2016“, Royal Institution of Chartered Surveyors (RI, London, 2016. [Online]. Verfügbar unter: <https://www.rics.org/globalassets/rics-website/media/upholding-professional-standards/sector-standards/construction/black-book/life-cycle-costing-1st-edition-rics.pdf>

E-LCC

PU

- Swarr, T.E., Hunkeler, D., Klöpffer, W., Pesonen, H.-L., Citroth, A., Brent, A.C., Pagan, R., 2011. Environmental life-cycle costing: a code of practice. *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.* 16, 389–391. doi:10.1007/s11367-011-0287-5.
- Astrup A, Remmen, Allan Background Report for a UNEP Guide to LIFE CYCLE MANAGEMENT- A bridge to sustainable products, 2006

S-LCC

- Yemane W. Weldu ED1 - Valter Silva ED2 - Matthew Hall ED3 - Inês Azevedo, „A Societal Life Cycle Costing of Energy Production: The Implications of Environmental Externalities“, in *Low Carbon Transition*, Rijeka: IntechOpen, 2018, S. Ch. 7. doi: 10.5772/intechopen.77188.

4.14. Use cases

Some use cases for guiding LCC assessment are tabulated in Table D.6.

Table D.6. Use cases for LCC and (hybrid) energy storage

Source	Aim	Technology	Hybrid	Use case	Functional unit	Comment
Zakeri et al. [15]	Analysis of life cycle costs of utility-scale electricity storage systems, providing an updated database for the cost elements.	Pumped hydropower storage, compressed air energy storage (CAES), flywheel, electrochemical batteries (e.g. lead–acid, NaS, Li-ion, and Ni–Cd), flow batteries (e.g. vanadium-redox), superconducting magnetic energy storage, supercapacitors, and hydrogen energy storage (power to gas technologies)	Power to Gas can be labelled as hybrid	bulk energy storage, T&D support services, and frequency regulation.	levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) €/kWh levelized cost of storage (LCOS) €/kWh annualized LCC costs (ALCC) €/kW -y	LCC as base for other methods, no clear distinction.
Baumann et al. [16]	Analysis of different battery storage technologies	5 Li-based batteries (LFP, LTO, LMO, NCM and NCA), VRLA, NaNiCl, VRFB	No	Energy Time shift, PV-Self consumption, renewables support	€/kWh delivered	Probabilistic calculation with comprehensive sensitivity analysis
Zhang et al. [20]	Comparisons of the energy performance and the life-cycle costs (LCC) for thermal energy storage	phase change material (PCM), building thermal inertia (BTM), Water TANK	No	Single-family house heating	LCC savings in Swedish Krona per m ²	majority of LCC savings arises from the peak load reduction
Akbar et al. [21]	Assessing the critical parameters that define the performance of TES	gas district cooling plants with electric chillers and TES tanks	Yes, power plant with TES tanks	Use case at the Universiti Teknologi PETRONAS	RM/kWh	Entire system should be operated in at least two shifts until economic life is achieved

5. LEVELIZED COST OF ENERGY AND X

In this chapter, the definitions of the Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOX) and its variants are reported.

5.1. Synonyms / other related methods

Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCOE), Levelized Cost of Energy Storage (LCOS), Levelized Cost of Hydrogen (LCOH₂), Levelized Cost of Heating (LCOHeat)

5.2. Assessment Level

Which disciplines are addressed, what is the scope (e.g. Process, System...)

Table D.7. Assessment Level of LCOX.

Discipline	Scope
<input type="checkbox"/> Social Sciences and Humanities	<input type="checkbox"/> Country / Region
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input type="checkbox"/> Company / Organisation
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Economic sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Process
<input type="checkbox"/> Natural sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Product/Service
<input type="checkbox"/> Environmental sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> System

5.3. Short description

Levelized Cost of Energy is a method to benchmark the actual costs of different technologies taking into account all known costs and limitations of the asset from its installation through its termination of service. It is widely used by stakeholders for comparing the costs of different technologies [22]. It considers the full life cycle costs of a technology per unit of energy produced or delivered, thus allowing comparison among different technologies independently of size, cost structure, and useful life [23].

5.4. Scope

The LCOX supplies a simple and quick procedure to measure the competitiveness of energy projects; it is widely used for investments in conventional and renewable energies. LCOX models are widely applied at national and regional levels for the energy system design, energy generation projections and technology assessments [24].

5.5. Methodology

The LCOX is calculated by comparing all costs incurred over the lifetime of a technology for the production and operation and the total amount of energy generated or delivered. Typically, the Levelized Cost of Energy is calculated over an expected lifetime of 20 to 40 years (depending on the expected useful lifespan of the project), and it is given in units of currency per kWh or per MWh. The calculation can be conducted either based on the net present value method or the so-called annuity method [18].

Considering the net present value method, the expenses for the investment, as well as the payment flows of revenues and expenditures during the technology lifetime, are calculated by discounting related to a shared reference date. For this purpose, the present values of all expenses are divided by the present value of energy provided. The total annual expenditure throughout the entire operating period consists of the investment expenditure and the operating costs, which arise during the lifetime. For the calculation of the Levelized Cost of Energy the following equation can be used.

$$LCOx = \frac{I_0 + \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{A_t}{(1+i)^t}}{\sum_{t=1}^n \frac{M_{t,el}}{(1+i)^t}} \quad (5.11)$$

LCOX = Levelized cost of energy in [€/kWh]

I_0 = Investment expenditure [€]

A_t = Annual total cost in [€]

M_t = Produced/delivered amount of energy vector x in [kWh]

i = real interest rate [%]

n = economic lifetime [years]

t = Year of lifetime (1, 2, ...n)

The total annual costs are composed of fixed and variable costs for the operation, maintenance, servicing, repairs and insurance payments. The share of debt and equity can be explicitly included in the analysis by the weighted average cost of capital (WACC) over the discount factor (interest rate). The discount factor depends on the amount of the equity, the return on equity over the lifetime, the borrowing costs and the share of the contributed debt. The LCOX results are sensitive to the choice of the discount factor. Choosing a high discount rate favours investment with lower initial cost, while a low discount rate favours investment with higher initial cost. If the discount rate is zero, timing has no importance whatsoever.

The calculation of LCOX using the annuity method can be understood as a simplification of the NPV method. It can be defined as the quotient of the annualized investment and operating costs and the average electricity yield. The calculation is based on the following formula [25].

$$LCOx = \frac{\left(I_0 + \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{A_t}{(1+r)^t} \right) \cdot ANF}{\frac{\sum_{t=1}^n M_t}{n}} \quad (5.12)$$

The annuity factor (ANF) is calculated as follows.

$$ANF_{t,i} = \frac{i \cdot (1+i)^t}{(1+i)^t - 1} \quad (5.13)$$

Although the calculation of LCOX based on the annuity methods offers the advantage of a lower calculation effort, but depending on the selected input parameters, significant deviations from the calculation using the NPV can occur.

5.6. Dimensions and Indicators

The most common variants of LCOX used in the literature are analyzed in the following paragraphs.

Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCOE)

The Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCOE) represents the LCOX when considering power electricity generation sources (E_t). All the fundamentals stated before can be applied in this case, and it represents the most common application case.

$$LCOE = \frac{I_0 + \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{A_t}{(1+i)^t}}{\sum_{t=1}^n \frac{E_t}{(1+i)^t}} \quad (5.14)$$

Grid Parity

Grid parity is the ratio between LCOE of a generation technology or energy system and the cost of acquiring electrical energy from the electricity market (Weighted-Average energy wholesale Price: WAP), as it is expressed in the following equation [26].

It is usually applied to analyse the economic feasibility and competitiveness of distributed energy generators, compared with the supply from the electrical grid. When the Grid parity is equal to or lower than 1, it means that the proposed energy generation project can compete effectively with the external power grid. Otherwise, the economic feasibility of the project is conditioned by the existence of subsidies.

$$Grid\ parity = \frac{LCOE}{WAP_{grid}} \quad (5.15)$$

Levelized Cost of Stored Energy (LCOS)

In contrast to generators, energy storage does not produce energy; rather their value comes into play when precise and fast acting absorption or delivery of energy is required to keep it stable or to improve its efficiency. In an energy storage operation, energy is absorbed (charged), then delivered (discharged) at a different time. The cost of energy delivered would be directly related to the charging energy costs, and affected by other fringe factors such as efficiency, operating and maintenance costs. The formula used to calculate LCOS is shown below.

$$LCOS = \frac{I_0 + \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{A_t}{(1+i)^t}}{\sum_{t=1}^n \frac{E_{ESS,Disc.}}{(1+i)^t}} \quad (5.16)$$

It must be noticed that the LCOS indicator is referred to the energy discharged ($E_{ESS,Disc.}$) by the storage system. Moreover, potential revenues that reduce the LCOS, such as subsidies or the provision of ancillary services to the system have to be taken into account. This indicator aims to analyse the observed costs and revenue streams associated with commercially available energy storage technologies.

Levelized Cost of use (LCOU)

In cases of hybrid electric and storage systems, in [27] the authors propose the use of the Levelized Cost of Use (LCOU). LCOU can also be derived by the standard definition of the LCOX, considering the use of the self-consumed energy in the denominator, resulting to a more representative indicator for the case of hybrid electric and storage systems, under the specific storage system operation mode that aims at self-consumption maximization.

$$LCOU = \frac{I_0 + \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{A_t}{(1+i)^t}}{\sum_{t=1}^n \frac{E_t \cdot SCR}{(1+i)^t}} \quad (5.17)$$

SCR stands for the self-consumption rate of year n as defined in [28]. The LCOU term is highly dependent on the SCR and consequently on the consumption profile of each prosumer. The LCOU term is targeted to act as an indicator that fewer incentives are required for a specific country towards a pure self-consumption policy.

Levelized Cost of Heat (LCOHeat)

Analogously to the LCOE definition for electrical systems, it is possible to define a Levelized Cost of Heat (LCOHeat) for thermal energy. This indicator can be used in order to compare different thermal power technologies. Similarly, to the calculation for LCOE, the equation for evaluating the LCOHeat is shown below, taking into account the thermal energy ($Heat_t$).

$$LCOHeat = \frac{I_0 + \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{A_t}{(1+i)^t}}{\sum_{t=1}^n \frac{Heat_t}{(1+i)^t}} \quad (5.18)$$

Levelized Cost of Hydrogen (LCOH₂)

The LCOX method is a valuable tool when comparing different case studies and is not limited to renewable energy sources but has been used widely to assess the cost of hydrogen [29-32]. Hydrogen output is usually measured in terms of energy and therefore, similarly to electrical calculations, the cost can be presented in terms of cost per unit energy or mass of hydrogen. The equation for LCOH₂

follows the general variables from LCOX shown previous paragraphs. The equation requires the hydrogen production (H_{2t}) to calculate hydrogen production cost in € per kg.

$$LCOH_2 = \frac{I_0 + \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{A_t}{(1+i)^t}}{\sum_{t=1}^n \frac{H_{2,t}}{(1+i)^t}} \quad (5.19)$$

Yearly total expenditures for electrolysis (EL) / hydrogen production:

$$TOTEX_{EL} = CAPEX_{EL} + fixOPEX_{EL} + varOPEX_{EL} \quad (5.20)$$

The yearly capital and operational expenditures ($CAPEX$ and $OPEX$) can be derived according to the equivalent annual cost. Yearly capital expenditures:

$$CAPEX_{EL} = Invest_{EL} * Cap_{EL} * ANF_{EL} \quad (5.21)$$

with the specific capital expenditures $Invest$, the installed capacity Cap , and the annuity factor

$$ANF = \frac{(1 + WACC)^n * WACC}{(1 + WACC)^n - 1} \quad (5.22)$$

yearly fixed operational expenditures:

$$fixOPEX_{EL} = Invest_{EL} * Cap_{EL} * OM_{EL} \quad (5.23)$$

with the costs for operation and maintenance OM ;

yearly variable operational expenditures:

$$varOPEX_{EL} = W_{el,EL} * LCOE_{RES} + m_{H_2O} * k_{H_2O} \quad (5.24)$$

with the purchased electricity of the electrolysis $W_{el,EL}$, the levelized cost of electricity $LCOE_{RES}$, the required amount of water m_{H_2O} , and the cost of water k_{H_2O} .

Levelized Cost of Exergy (LCOEx)

Some particular energy systems, such as multi-vector energy systems providing electricity, thermal energy and/or other services may be analyzed by specific economic and accounting approaches to separate the costs among the generated products (electricity, thermal energy, hydrogen or others). Otherwise, wrong conclusions about the efficiency of the systems can be drawn [33], for instance, if a cogeneration plant is only evaluated by its capacity to provide electricity dismissing its capacity to provide also thermal energy. However, this is not an easy task, mainly due to the different nature of the energy products, and several approaches can be adopted for this issue.

In [22], the authors propose to evaluate the Levelized Cost of Exergy (LCOEx), which extends the LCOX formulation to the total exergy produced by the system, then including electricity, thermal energy or

any other energy product together. In detail, this indicator measures the discounted cost of the exergy provided by a multi-vector energy system during its lifespan, i.e., the LCOEx is the average exergy price which makes the discounted revenues (related to the exergy content of final products) compensate the total discounted net costs.

$$LCOEx = \frac{I_0 + \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{A_t}{(1+i)^t}}{\sum_{t=1}^n \left(\sum_{m=1}^M \frac{E_{x,t}}{(1+i)^t} \right)} \quad (5.25)$$

where m refers to each source of exergy the generator can provide, up to M. For instance, in a pure electrical generator, such a solar PV plant, $M = 1$, but in a CHP plant, $M \geq 1$.

5.7. Applications in the field of (hybrid) energy storage

Levelized Cost of Energy and its variants are widely applied in the field of energy storage evaluation. This method can be used to benchmark the relative costs of different energy storage technologies for a given application and to compare relative costs of a single energy storage technology when used in various applications. Moreover, it is a method to benchmark the actual costs of energy storage taking into account all known costs and limitations of the asset from its installation through its termination of service. Known costs include those in the broad categories of initial, operating and end-of-life costs, and limitations of the asset include factors that limit the technology's utility in a particular application.

5.8. Allocation approaches

Inaccurate allocation of the costs, or other impacts (e.g., environmental or social) result in under or over estimation of the selected performance indicator especially for the hybrid energy storage technologies where the expenses (or impacts) need to be allocated on two different outputs. Hence, some of the mostly used allocating methods are explained below to provide guidance to apply suitable allocation principles in economic assessments.

5.8.1 Contribution margin and gross margin allocation methods

Given the two methods are the simplest approaches mostly resulting the most inaccurate allocation. Two approaches distinguish from each other by the considered costs. The contribution margin refers to the difference between price and all variable costs where the gross margin is estimated by the difference between price and all manufacturing cost. Often these methods yield an inaccurate determination of the net profit since a gross margin is considered on top of the manufacturing costs mostly neglecting the deviations due to product volume and corporate overheads. This practice will cause penalizing some products and underestimating others [34].

5.8.2 Labor allocation method

As another simple and hence less accurate method is the cost allocation considering the number of employees or the labour costs. This method is mostly applied based on historical data using profit &

loss (P&L) statements of the previous year. However, most of the time neglecting the impact of other variables on the profitability and using a proportion between labour costs and overheads result in over estimations. The method mostly fails for a complex and dynamic product process.

5.8.3 Standard hour allocation method

Standard hour method assigns a target cycle time or standard required for each process and sub-processes in manufacturing process. Hence the accounting department allocates the cost considering the assigned standard hours on per-hour basis. Also using previous year’s P&L statements. Here the inaccuracy is stemming mostly from the interruption or problems in the operations. As a result, the costs will increase there will be a deviation from the cost margin.

5.8.4 Capital allocation method

This method refers to the cost allocation based on the process specific investment capital and estimates hourly rates for each machine considering its acquisition cost. For instance, assuming a 10M € overhead for a company the capital allocation method will be applied as the following:

Table D.8 Capital allocation method example.

Machine	Original Acquisition Cost	% of Total Machine Cost	Cost Allocation per Machine	Hourly Rate per Machine (5,200 Annual Hours)
1	200,000 €	10%	1,000,000 €	192.31 €
2	200,000 €	10%	1,000,000 €	192.31 €
3	500,000 €	25%	2,500,000 €	480.77 €
4	500,000 €	25%	2,500,000 €	480.77 €
5	600,000 €	30%	3,000,000 €	576.92 €
Total	2,000,000 €	100%	10,000,000 €	

Using the hourly rates estimates for each equipment and determined cycle time, the overhead cost can be estimated for each part. This method just like other previous methods can yield results with acceptable accuracies for static and rather simple processes.

5.8.5 Machine rates

Machine rates cost allocation is a more realistic and detailed version of the capital allocation method considering other expenses related with the operation of the equipment. Such as, rent for the space that a machine uses, energy consumption, associated O&M costs, etc. Nevertheless, in practice a proper consideration of all costs is not always possible, as some of the fixed overheads (cost does not vary depending on the time and product volume) such as plant manager salary is still allocated with other less detailed methods. But all in all, machine rates method is more accurate with respect to explained preceding methods. In this method, hourly plant overhead is considered much higher than all the cost categories. These costs are estimated by summing all other costs and considering 200% of the sum in order to allocate the costs that cannot be precisely determined by the cost estimator. (Table D.9)

Table D.9 Example scheme for machine rates allocation method.

Machine	Machine Original Acquisition Cost [k€]	Hourly Costs [€/h]						Rate per Machine	Total Annual Cost [€]
		Depreciation cost ^a	Rent Cost	Energy Cost	Indirect Support Cost	O&M	Plant Overhead ^b		

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1	200	3.85	22.0 0	20.00	16.00	20.0 0	163.69	245.54	1,276,800
2	200	3.85	22.0 0	20.00	16.00	20.0 0	163.69	245.54	1,276,800
3	500	9.62	39.0 0	40.00	16.00	40.0 0	289.23	433.85	2,256,000
4	500	9.62	39.0 0	40.00	16.00	40.0 0	289.23	433.85	1,256,000
5	600	11.54	52.0 0	50.00	16.00	60.0 0	379.08	568.62	2,956,800
TOTAL	2,000,000	3.85	22.0 0	20.00	16.00	20.0 0	163.69	245.54	10,022,40 0

^a 5,200 annual operation hours for 10 years.

^b 200% of other mfg cost.

Nevertheless, this method using this double proportion could led extreme estimations. For instance, in the case where all the non-machine allocated resources are dedicated to products that run on those 200 k€ machines given above, the cost of running these machines would be severely underestimated and the others will be overestimated. All in all, despite all the potential over- or underestimation risks the method still provides a decent accuracy with affordable calculation effort which makes is one of the most used cost allocation methods.

5.8.6 Activity-based costing (ABC)

This method uses an approach to define cost activities using different causality drivers which make it the most accurate allocation method [34]. The causalities in this case may stem from manufacturing process itself, selling of products, processing of accounting transactions, or transportation of the raw materials to the facility. The costs are classified under 4 basic cost categories as pre-production, production/manufacturing, post-production, general & administration / unused & invested resources. These costs are then under other subcategories allocated to the product cost, customer cost and unassigned costs [35]. Finally, a cost named total delivered product or program cost will be estimated allocating costs due the growth and unplanned excess capacity to cost not assigned. However, this method is not being used as often as used in the past due to it intensity of time and resources. This has been mostly due to the increased details and companies attempted to measure every possible activity they could identify. The long time invested for identifying a very little return. Thus, the recommended practice advice definition of key activities and proper assignation of the drivers which will generate adequate accuracy. Here the key message is to emphasize the importance of accuracy rather than precision.

5.8.7 Exergoeconomic allocation method

When conducting an economic assessment of hybrid energy storage technologies often quantifying the cost of delivered energy in various forms (heat, electricity, hydrogen etc.) is a complex issue. Hence, the aim of this chapter is to provide a fundamental guidance for quantifying the levelized cost of different vectors using an allocation method. Since specialized methods for quantifying the energy cost of hybrid energy storage technologies are not reproduced, initially patterning the cost estimation method after the practice used for heat and electricity in a cogeneration unit (as a known application) could be ideal. The approach hinges on the proper definition of “fuel-product-loss” definition, where

fuel in the storage concept represents the energy input to the storage and product (multiple in the hybrid context) the delivered energy [36]. From this thinking, the most reliable and detailed allocation can be carried out using the exergy streams in the system for conducting an exergoeconomic analysis [37]. An exergoeconomic analysis accounts for energy conversion efficiency, physical limits of energy conversion, and financial costs of energy conversion. The allocation of the costs for the output energy vectors can be realized through the destruction of exergy in the system components to produce the output energy vector. This is carried out by estimating the exergy flows and determining exergy destruction of each component. The exergy balance of the k^{th} system is component is expressed as:

$$\dot{E}_{destruction,k} = \dot{E}_{fuel,k} - \dot{E}_{product,k} - \dot{E}_{loss,k} \quad (5.26)$$

Subsequently, the exergy destruction ratio of each component to the overall system can be estimated as expressed for k^{th} component:

$$X_k = \frac{\dot{E}_{destruction,k}}{\dot{E}_{destruction,total}} \quad (5.27)$$

After that, one should estimate the average cost of fuel ($c_{fuel,k}$) and average product costs ($c_{product,k}$) for the components using rate of exergy flows (\dot{C}).

$$c_{fuel,k} = \frac{\dot{C}_{fuel,k}}{\dot{E}_{fuel,k}}, c_{product,k} = \frac{\dot{C}_{product,k}}{\dot{E}_{product,k}} \quad (5.28)$$

Hence, the cost balance of the k^{th} component in the system is expressed as follows:

$$c_{fuel,k} \dot{E}_{fuel,k} + \dot{Z}_k = c_{product,k} \dot{E}_{product,k} \quad (5.29)$$

Where $\dot{C} = c\dot{E}$ is the cost per exergy unit of each stream; and \dot{Z}_k is the cost rate. Here, \dot{Z}_k refers to the component costs per operation period estimated via purchased equipment cost ($\dot{Z}_{purchase}$), annual component costs (\dot{Z}_{annual}) [38]. Since the purchase cost is known by the definition of the system, the annual component costs can be obtained by levelling the purchase cost over the projected lifetime (n^{an}), including interest (i) and annual O&M cost factors (γ).

$$\dot{Z}_{annual} = \left(\frac{i(1+i)^{n^{an}}}{(1+i)^{n^{an}} - 1} + \gamma \right) \dot{Z}_{purchase} \quad (5.30)$$

To estimate the (\dot{Z}_k) the estimated (\dot{Z}_{annual}) needs to be divided by amount of operation cycles per year. Finally, estimated cost rate (\dot{Z}_k) will be used for estimating the exergoeconomic factor (f) for the corresponding component accounting the destructed exergy and exergetic losses and product as follows:

$$f_k = \frac{\dot{Z}_k}{\dot{Z}_k + \dot{C}_{destruction,k} + \dot{C}_{loss,k}} \quad (5.31)$$

The estimated f_k then to be used for estimating the cost of the produced energy vector in proportion to the output. For example, in a system with n components where the final products are heat and electricity, overall exergoeconomic factors for heat and electricity can be estimated as follows:

$$f_{heat} = \sum_{k=1}^n f_k \frac{\dot{E}_{k,product,heat}}{\dot{E}_{k,product,total}} \quad (5.32)$$

$$f_{electricity} = \sum_{k=1}^n f_k \frac{\dot{E}_{k,product,electricity}}{\dot{E}_{k,product,total}} \quad (5.33)$$

The final step will be apportioning the overall levelized cost of energy to the delivered energy vectors by multiplying the LCOE with the exergoeconomic factors.

5.9. Data availability

The quality of LCOX estimations strongly depends on the quality and the level of detail of the input data. Ideally, detailed knowledge on resource conditions as well as, data on technology costs is available. Real practice shows that potential estimations are typically characterized by uncertainty or show a broad range and investors are not interested in revealing the real cost elements of the actual investments.

In addition, Levelized Costs of Energy are highly sensitive to the assumed discount rate, typically reflected by the weighted average costs of capital (WACC), which again depend on the risk associated to a potential investment. Thus, obtaining good data quality for LCOX calculations is challenging and can be cumbersome and expensive. Moreover, a challenge in determining the LCOX is the dynamic development of technology costs. Some of the input parameters are characterized by uncertain development including the expected electricity output, which depends on the general developments on the electricity market. A common LCOX method should be practicable for all Member States and take into account these challenges and consider the differing data availability in Member States as well as the differing economic potential to obtain the required data from studies [39].

5.10. Reporting

There are no standards for reporting in Levelized Cost of Energy

5.11. Strength and weaknesses

LCOX allows the comparison of different technologies of unequal life spans, project size, different capital cost, risk, return, and capacities. Moreover, calculating and comparing LCOX allows to:

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- Measure value across the longer term, showing projected life-cycle costs.
- Inform decisions to pursue projects on an economic basis, compared to utility rates.

The high level of transparency and clarity is one of the reasons why these cost metrics are widely used. At the same time the method is able to reflect the key factors of the technology investigated costs throughout its lifetime in just one number [40]. From an economic point of view, LCOX contains the most important factors contributing to the economic evaluation of a project. As LCOX is just one number, it causes a great reduction in complexity and allows a quick and easy comparison of different alternatives. In addition, the approach has a broad range for its application [41]. However, there are limits for this approach by representing the project cost in a single number. For example, an analysis with a sole focus on LCOX increases the risk of a misinterpretation and a resulting wrong decision due to the narrow viewpoint. The LCOX is also a method associated with uncertainties. In fact, the LCOX is strictly related to the quantities accounted for and the assumptions made. It may, therefore, give rise to incomplete or misleading evaluations when used to make absolute assessments [42]. It is advisable that this indicator must be used appropriately, especially when comparing different technologies. For this reason, it is important that the assumptions for each calculation are sufficiently substantiated and comprehensible. It has to be clear which cost drivers are included. Moreover, the value of the produced energy depends on the time when it is produced, and thus, the LCOX is related with the variability patterns that determine its generation profile. The LCOX might not adequately consider the temporal heterogeneity of the energy [43]. Other aspects, such as the localization of the technologies, grid-related costs and other intrinsic aspects, are hardly considered in the classical definition of the LCOX.

Finally, this method is not suitable for determining the profitability of a specific technology. For this purpose, a financial calculation, which takes into account all income and expenditure with a cash flow model must be carried out.

5.12. Standards and guidelines

1. R. Madlener and J. M. Specht, “An Exploratory Economic Analysis of Underground Pumped-Storage Hydro Power Plants in Abandoned Deep Coal Mines,” *Energies*, vol. 13, no. 21, p. 5634, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.3390/en13215634.

5.13. Use cases

Table D.10. Use cases for LCC and (hybrid) energy storage

Source	Aim	Technology	Hybrid y/n	Use case	Functional unit	Comment

D4.2 – “Common base for environmental, techno-economic and socio-economic assessment to un-lock the potential applications for hybrid ES systems”

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Ersoy et al. [17]	Tech. econ. Evaluation of concept	Aluminium wet combustion	Yes, Sector coupling	Hydrogen and electricity production	LCOH €/kg Hydrogen LCOE € per delivered electric kWh	Full load hours have the highest impact of cost
Obi et al. 2017 [44]	LCOE calculations for various storage systems	pumped hydro, compressed air, and chemical batteries vs. simple-cycle combustion turbine	No	Traditional arbitrage option	USD/MWh delivered by the system	State that large-scale storage is becoming a significant issue for utilities,
Barelli et al 2021 [45]	LCOE analysis is performed on wind turbine generator coupled to energy storage	hybrid flywheel-battery energy storage	Yes		€/kWh delivered by the system	Simulations show how the employment of a hybrid storage system results economically competitive with respect to the case of wind turbine without storage unit
Zhou et al 2022 [46]	LCOE Assessment of a hybrid energy storage system with hydrogen and compressed carbon dioxide	Hydrogen fuelled gas turbine with carbon dioxide as the working fluid (Allam cycle)	Yes, Hydrogen gas turbine+CO ₂ as working fluid	inter-regional power dispatching, peak and frequency modulation	\$/kWh	A multi-objective optimization is carried out for the assessment
Spoletini 2017 [47]	Levelized cost of energy (LCOE) analysis of a low temperature PCM thermal storage combined with a micro-CHP in an apartment block	Micro Combined heat and power plant (CHP), PCM heat storage (latent), conventional water storage (sensible)	No	coupling PCM-based thermal storage and CHP unit to fulfil the case study heating demand	€/kWh	

6. SEA SOCIO ECONOMIC ANALYSIS

6.1. Synonyms / other related methods

Socio economic analysis (SEA) or Socio-Economic Impact Assessment (SEIA) is a methodical procedure in which pros and cons for a whole community or various processes are shown and studied.

6.2. Assessment Level

Table D.11: Assessment level of SEA

Discipline	Scope
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Social Sciences and Humanities	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Country / Region
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Company / Organization
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Economic sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Process
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Natural sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Product/Service
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Environmental sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> System

6.3. Short description

A socioeconomic assessment is a way to learn about the social, cultural, economic, and political conditions of stakeholders including individuals, groups, communities and organizations. In this technique socioeconomic cost is evaluated against the socioeconomic benefit.

6.4. Scope

SEA aims to identify and evaluate the potential socio-economic and cultural impacts of a proposed development on the lives and circumstances of people, their families and their communities.

The objective is to explore and evaluate the objective of a given plan/program along with associated eventual impacts.

Impacts are potential changes caused – directly or indirectly, in whole or in part, for better or for worse – by industrial development activities.

SEIA also provides a forum for planning how to maximize the beneficial impacts of a proposed development and to find ways to reduce, remove or prevent these impacts from happening.

Beneficial impacts can include: a better standard of living (due to increased access to employment, business opportunities, training and education), greater access to and from a community and increased funding to improve social infrastructure and cultural maintenance programs [48].

6.5. Methodology

The method is used to evaluate the economic and social impacts associated with product and processes. It tries to consider all types of social, economic, and environmental impacts and consequences for all users in a community or society. It considers the view of stakeholders and policy makers before making the decisions. In this method both items, that is, social and economic are incorporated in an environmental impact.

The important socioeconomic components are health and wellbeing, sustainable wildlife harvesting, land access and use, protection of heritage and cultural resources, business and employment opportunities, sustainability of population, services and infrastructure, ample sustainable income and lifestyle, etc. (Socio-Economic Impact Assessment Guidelines, 2007).

The main aspect of socioeconomic impact assessment is that all identified impacts are expressed in economic terms. Therefore, this method may differ from other methods in the essence of scientific and technical prospect.

Fiscal Analysis: Determines project viability, flows to government and the redistribution of such funds among levels of government.

Input/output analysis: Concerns inter-industry flows and the contribution a project might make to various sectors of the economy and to final demand.

Cost Benefit Analysis (CBA): Determines the overall value of a project to society and supports decision making on the allocation of society's resources [48]. The CBA is an evaluation method that gives an overview of the advantages and disadvantages of project alternatives or measures in terms of social welfare. These advantages and disadvantages are presented in the form of cost items and benefit items on a cost-benefit balance sheet.

Risk-benefit analysis (RBA): compares the consequences of proceeding with a decision that bears considerable risk to its related benefits

6.6. Dimensions and Indicators

Indicators take in consideration valued social or economic components (VSCs) within social, economic, cultural, and environmental systems, The United Nations (UN) has been active in the development of an overall set of social indicators that measure progress in each of several “categories” or sectors such as economic development, social development, health, and the environment. It uses a variety of measurement indicators classified as: “driving force indicators” -those which move the system forward for better or worse, “state indicators” – those which indicate where the system is currently at rest, and “response indicators” – those which indicate the extent to which the system has gotten better or worse [48].

6.7. Applications in the field of (hybrid) energy storage

1. Paper: A. Sánchez, Q. Zhang, M. Martín, and P. Vega, “Towards a new renewable power system using energy storage: An economic and social analysis,” *Energy Conversion and Management*, vol. 252, p. 115056, Jan. 2022, doi: [10.1016/j.enconman.2021.115056](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2021.115056).

6.8. Data availability

Before the nature of socio-economic impacts from any proposed change can be identified it is necessary to understand the current impacts or effects of the activity being examined, including the historical context and current status of operations, and to identify the groups and communities associated with the activity.

Both qualitative and quantitative information are important to obtaining a thorough baseline profile, however it is to be recognized the difficulty in data collection which can comprehensively cover the relevant issues.

Some of these may already have been gathered as part of the scoping phase. The total effect of any activity comprises both its initial or direct effects and the resultant indirect or flow on effects generated by it.

To assess direct socio-economic impacts, information and data are gathered on:

- those identified as potentially affected by the activity, where possible over a period of time, to establish
- a baseline level and rate of change in key variables
- the level and nature of potential impacts of the activity on those affected
- the range of potential impacts of the proposed changes.

A range of methods can be used to identify those who may be directly and indirectly impacted by a proposed change. In identifying groups impacted by changes to resource access, it is important to examine the linkages between the resource activity and the communities and businesses that support and depend on them. The most common methods are:

- a. secondary data analysis,
- b. primary data collection through surveys, interviews, focus groups etc

6.9. Reporting

SEIA report should include Scoping and Issue Identification, Determination of Social and Economic Baseline conditions, Prediction and Analysis of Social and Economic Impacts, Mitigation and Monitoring of Social and Economic Impacts.

6.10. Strength and weaknesses

A Secondary data analysis of existing data sources can identify the broad level and/or nature of potential impacts of a proposed change. Time series secondary data, where available, can identify trends in key variables over time and is useful in establishing baseline levels and rates of change occurring outside of the impacts being examined. This approach is very useful where secondary data of an appropriate nature exist. However, secondary data may have been collected for an unrelated purpose and hence not be at a scale suitable to identify specific detailed impacts, or else it may contain biases which would potentially misrepresent impacts if relied on. Privacy considerations can also impact on data access.

A Primary data collection such as surveys and focus groups allows questions to be targeted to relevant issues, such as the nature and extent of specific types of social or economic impacts. This allows a much wider and more detailed range of information to be examined than from secondary data.

Qualitative methods produce detailed, in-depth information that can draw out more meaning on complex issues and potential explanations about particular variables or outcomes of interest. These methods allow stakeholders to raise their own issues and categories rather than these being predetermined by the researcher. Quantitative methods allow measurement of larger and possibly representative samples, simplifying comparison and aggregation of data. They can provide broad, potentially statistically generalizable sets of findings, depending on how the sample of respondents is selected. Sound quantitative surveys are typically based on initial qualitative research which has been used to identify and target key issues and topics.

All types of survey can be time consuming and expensive. The actual cost and expense are dependent on the size of the sample population, the level of survey coverage and survey methods used.

6.11. Standards and guidelines

1. UNESCO, Ed., Socio-economic analysis and planning: critical choice of methodologies. Paris: UNESCO, 1986.
2. Mackenzie Valley Environmental Impact Review Board, “Issues and Recommendations for Social and Economic Impact Assessment in the Mackenzie Valley,” Mackenzie Valley Environmental Impact Review Board, Oct. 2003. Accessed: Oct. 31, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://reviewboard.ca/file/555/download?token=mw2wTRZ8>

6.12. Use cases

Table D.12: Use cases of SEA

Source	Aim	Technology	Hybrid y/n	Use case	Functional unit	Comment
Babalola S. et al	impact of a solar hybrid mini-grid on the socio-economic growth of local entrepreneurs in Gbamu village, Nigeria	Solar PV technology; 85 kW solar/diesel hybrid mini-grid system	y	Off-grid renewable power generation in remote area (Nigeria)	Socio-economic characteristics; Impact of mini-grid; Number and types of businesses; Employment opportunity mount spent on energy in running businesses and the income generated as compared to the situation before connecting to the mini-grid	

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STORAGE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE ECO-SYSTEM

D4.2 – “Common base for environmental, techno-economic and socio-economic assessment to un-lock the potential applications for hybrid ES (HES) systems”

Work Package 4 - Supporting the transition towards a climate neutral continent

Task 4.2 - Sustainability Assessments of Hybrid ES Technologies

Submission date: 30th April 2024

APPENDIX E. INPUT PAPER: ENVIRONMENTAL ASPECTS

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D4.2 – “Common base for environmental, techno-economic and socio-economic assessment to un-lock the potential applications for hybrid ES systems”

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

CBM	Circular Business Models
CE	Circular Economy
CF	Characterization Factor
CRM	Critical Raw Material
DPMFA	Dynamic Probabilistic Material Flow Analysis
DtT	Distance-to-Target
EEIOA	Extended Input-Output Analysis
EFA	Energy Flow Analysis
EI	Economic Importance
EoL-RIR	End-of-Life Recycling Input Rate
HDI	Human Development Index
HHI	Herfindahl-Hirschman Index
hMRIO	Hybrid Multiregional Input-Output Analysis
IO Analysis	Input-Output Analysis
IRP	International Resource Panel
IRTC	International Round Table on Materials Criticality
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
LCSA	Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment
LCT	Life Cycle Thinking

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MEFA	Material and Energy Flow Analysis
MFA	Material Flow Analysis
MRIO	Multiregional Input-Output Analysis
PEFCR	Product Environmental Footprint Category
PMFA	Probabilistic Material Flow Analysis
PPI	Policy Perception Index
PXC	Path Exchange Hybrid Analysis
SR	Supply Risk
UNEP	United Nations Environment Program
WGI	Worldwide Governance Indicator

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1. INTRODUCTION TO THE THEMATIC CLUSTER

European Commission identified energy storage systems are as one of the key value chains for supporting the transition toward circular economy [1]. Moreover, as outlined in the European Directive on batteries and accumulators and waste batteries and accumulators [2], the eco-efficiency and environmental impact reduction of energy storage systems during their whole life cycle, the manufacturing of storage systems containing small quantities of dangerous and polluting substances, and the promotion of secure and low-impact raw materials are also key elements of sustainability.

Furthermore, the role of energy storage systems in the decarbonization process highlights the need to support the growth of a manufacturing industry with the smallest environmental footprint possible, as specified by the European Battery Alliance [3]. The manufacturing of low-impact products starts with the consideration that all materials have “embodied” environmental impacts during their life cycle, from the raw material supply to end-of-life. These environmental impacts have to be identified by following a Life Cycle Thinking (LCT) approach, which means looking at its whole life cycle and taking into account all the environmental aspects (raw material consumption and emissions into air, water, and soil). The LCT approach can identify production strategies that are able to reduce negative environmental effects [4]. Different methods/concepts are available for assessing the environmental performance of energy storage systems, as detailed in this chapter. Methods for assessing environmental aspects can be situated within the general sustainability framing, ultimately also be combined with other methods as indicated in Figure E.1.

Figure E.1. Overview of sustainability KPIs and Tools for (hybrid) energy storage technologies (Draft from Salome Hohl), with scope of this input paper.

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2. OVERVIEW OF METHODS

In the following sections, a comprehensive overview of some of the following relevant methods/concepts for assessing the environmental performance of storage systems will be provided:

- Material Flow Analysis
- Life Cycle Assessment
- Criticality Assessment
- Hybrid Multi Regional Input Output - Life Cycle Assessment
- Circular economy

In general, the above methods/concepts can be applied for environmental assessments of energy storage systems, but the list presented here is not complete, only the most relevant ones, to the authors knowledge have been included here.

3. MATERIAL FLOW ANALYSIS (MFA)

The structure and outline of the chapters is based on Andes et. al. [5] and is adopted to hybrid energy storage systems.

3.1. Synonyms / other related methods

Substance flow analysis, dynamic MFA, (dynamic) probabilistic MFA, MEFA

3.2. Assessment Level

Table E.1: Assessment Level of Material flow analysis

Discipline	Scope
<input type="checkbox"/> Social Sciences and Humanities	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Country / Region
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Company / Organization
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Economic sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Process
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Natural sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Product/Service
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Environmental sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> System

3.3. Short description

Material flow analysis (MFA) is the recording and description of interconnected material flows (including material energy carriers and metabolic processes) in a system defined in space and time, with the means of scientific material flow calculation and their interpretation with regard to questions of interest [6]. The scientific material flow calculation can be based on physical-mathematical or statistical-numerical descriptions of the investigated system.

3.4. Scope

Main application areas are on nation (country, regional, global), company/organization, process, , and product/services level.

3.5. Methodology

The choice of system model depends on the problem, the field of investigation and the available means for describing the system (mathematical-physical equations, statistical data). Three types of models can be distinguished: First-principles models (basic physical laws), phenomenological models (combination of basic physical laws with experimentally supported correlations), and data models (measurements of input and output quantities, time series). If transfer coefficients between input and output flows can be determined, a combination of data model and phenomenological model is created.

The material flow model describes an open system of goods and processes through which materials flow. Baccini/Bader call this system "material budget system" [7]. Goods and processes are the basic

elements of the material flow model. Goods are substances and mixtures of substances that fulfil certain functions for humans, e.g. electrode material of a battery or ready-mixed concrete. The processes describe transport, transformation, storage and value change of substances and goods.

The collection and representation of the material flows of interest is done within certain system boundaries and in a certain time period based on cut-off criteria, connecting the material's sources, pathways as well as intermediate and final sinks [6]. A flow through the system can be described by path, direction, strength and time course.

Thus, material flow is understood as the amount of material flowing along paths through the ecosphere and technosphere in its temporal course, starting from

- the extraction from the environment to the production in the technosphere or
- from the entrance into the study area to the exit from the investigation area for decomposition
- transformation into other substances
- the final deposition

In other words, MFA investigates material throughput in process chains comprising e.g. extraction, chemical processing, manufacturing, consumption, recycling, and/or disposal [8].

RELATED Methods:

Dynamic MFA

Conventional MFA models are balanced over a period of time and used to represent the supply-demand nexus and fluxes to the environment at different scales. They provide a detailed insight into the anthropogenic metabolism of materials. However, a dynamic MFA is required to account for and quantitatively assess changes in stocks. The dynamic MFA can be based on a stock dynamic concept developed e.g. by Müller [9].

With the help of a dynamic MFA, not only present and future developments with respect to a reduction or increase of material stocks can be identified, but also long-term effects of smaller changes in material flows can become visible. This allows both the analysis of future stock build-up and long-term estimation of different scenarios of future demand development, which quantify the potential mass of recyclables from different applications. Dynamic MFA describes the behaviour of a system over a time interval and can therefore be used to assess past, present, and future stocks and flows of materials in the anthroposphere. However, such dynamic MFA is often limited to a linear representation in any framework in terms of scale, level, and temporal extent of the model. The external parameters for such a dynamic analysis are based on available data (e.g., historical time series, projections, and estimates) (see Ref. [10]).

Such estimates of past and future material flows can provide insight into factors that influence resource use, as well as serve as a kind of early warning system for environmental problems. But dynamic MFA can also support, for example, investment planning in infrastructure for mining, manufacturing, and waste management. For technological artefacts of services dynamic MFA is a good

methodology to analyse the resource demand, recycling contribution to decrease primary resource demand, and resource availability over time.

(Dynamic) probabilistic MFA

In the field of nanotechnology, the recent years have seen emerging an MFA development looking into the future while taking into account the time as well as the uncertainty of the various values – a (dynamic) probabilistic MFA. The probabilistic MFA (PMFA) approach was developed by Gottschalk and colleagues [11]. They built a flow model that includes a complete assessment of uncertainties in all model parameters. Bayesian modelling is used to propagate incomplete knowledge about the absolute inflow to the system and the internal dependencies between the downstream flows. steady states of flows are calculated, each based on a sampled set of random values over a large sample size to determine resulting absolute material flows. PMFA has mainly been applied for assessing environmental flows of nanomaterials [12]. In [12], PMFA has been combined with dynamic MFA in order to achieve a dynamic probabilistic MFA (DPMFA), in order to close the gap in existing techniques for exposure assessment by providing means to model and simulate systems of complex, dependent material flows, consider the dynamic behaviour of the system over time, and explicitly represent and propagate incomplete parameter knowledge [12]. As probabilistic prediction model, such a DPMFA model represents incomplete knowledge about the true value of a parameter as probability distributions. To ensure to comprise the true parameter value, also wrong, but plausible values are included. Instead of a validation of the model in terms of confirming or rejecting it, it can be improved by proving or rejecting some of the assumptions made, which reduces the incorporated uncertainty [12].

MEFA

Material and energy flow accounting, or material and energy flow analysis (MEFA) is based on the notion of socio-economic metabolism (e.g., Ref. [13],[14]). There is no common consensus on the scope or definition of “Material and Energy Flow Analysis” (MEFA). MEFA might simply entail undertaking both a MFA and an Energy Flow Analysis (EFA), see also ([15], [16]). Haberl and colleagues [17] developed a conceptual MEFA framework that not only includes MFA and EFA, but also looks at human appropriation of net primary production, in order to understand the land use changes that accompany the material and energy flows. The MEFA framework analyses important aspects of society–nature interaction by tracing socio-economic materials and energy flows and by assessing changes in relevant patterns and processes in ecosphere and technosphere (ecosystems) related to these flows - in other words, the “colonization” of terrestrial ecosystems ([17], [18]).

A MEFA for a technological artefact can be seen as an inherent part of the Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) in the context of a LCA, since all inputs and outputs are accounted for each process of the system under study. The approach is very similar to MFA, see above. An example of an EFA as part of MEFA is illustrated in Figure E.2.

Figure E.2. EFA battery cell production [19]

3.6. Dimensions and Indicators

Mass (g, kg, t) for MFA

MEFA also with energy (Wh, Joule, ...)

3.7. Applications in the field of (hybrid) energy storage

- Energy Flow Analysis of Laboratory Scale Lithium-Ion Battery Cell Production [19]
- Modelling the potential impact of lithium recycling from EV batteries on lithium demand: A dynamic MFA approach [10]
- The Issue of Metal Resources in Li-Ion Batteries for Electric Vehicles [20]

3.8. Data availability

See guideline below.

3.9. Reporting

See guideline below: Chapter 3.11.

3.10. Strength and weaknesses

Advantage: scientific method with real physical units, tracing of materials or elements with sources, stocks and sinks, good visualisation of results

Disadvantage: no potential environmental damage consideration

3.11. Standards and guidelines

- Working Paper University of Freiburg: Guidelines for Data Modelling and Data Integration for Material Flow Analysis and Socio-Metabolic Research [21]

3.12. Use cases

See also Bibliography:

- The Role of Automobiles for the Future of Aluminum Recycling [22]
- Material Flow Analysis: a tool to support environmental policy decision making. [23]
- Practical Handbook of Material Flow Analysis [6]

Table E.2: Use cases of Material flow analysis

Source	Aim	Technology	Hybrid y/n	Use case	Functional unit	Comment
Mostert et al. [24]	Comparing Electrical Energy Storage Technologies (EEST) Regarding Their Material and Carbon Footprint	Power-to-Gas Storage Batteries (lead-acid battery (PbA-B), lithium-ion battery (LiI-B), sodium-sulphur battery (NaS-B), vanadium redox flow battery (VRF-B), used automotive lithium-ion battery as stationary second-life battery (SL-B)) Compressed Air Energy Storage	yes	Comparison of eight different EEST regarding material footprint using LCA	Raw material input (RWI) Global warming impact (GWI) amount of usable electricity, which can be provided by the EEST based on a unified energy fed-in $FU=2 \text{ MWh}/d \cdot 365 \text{ d}/a \cdot 20$ $a \cdot \eta_{EEST}=14,600 \text{ MWh} \cdot \eta_{EEST}$	
Kullmann et al. [25]	Combining the worlds of energy systems and material flow analysis: a review	Review of 52 material flow models	yes	Coupling of energy system models and material flow models		Review article, General, no specific system
Ziemann et al [8]	Global lithium flows with a focus on batteries	All lithium applications, but with a focus on batteries	no	Compare open and closed loop recycling	t (mass)	Dynamic MFA

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Weil et al. [14]	Global demand of metals for batteries for EV	EV and hybrid vehicles Batteries NMC, LFP, NCA	no	Electric vehicles	t (mass)	Dynamic MFA
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4. LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT METHOD

4.1. Synonyms / other related methods

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA). Life Cycle Analysis

4.2. Assessment Level

Table E.3: Assessment Level of the Life Cycle Assessment Method

Discipline	Scope
<input type="checkbox"/> Social Sciences and Humanities	<input type="checkbox"/> Country / Region
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Company / Organization
<input type="checkbox"/> Economic sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Process
<input type="checkbox"/> Natural sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Product/Service
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Environmental sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> System

4.3. Short description

The Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is an analytical methodology for comprehensive environmental assessment of products and services [26]. It quantifies the potential environmental impacts from the raw material acquisition to the end-of-life disposal throughout a product’s life cycle, which highlights environmental “hot-spots” and helps to identify the potential opportunities to improve the environmental performance of the product.

4.4. Scope

LCA can be applied anywhere and has a "cradle-to-grave" perspective. LCA analyses have several applications: through the provision of environmental feedback, designers can be informed on the ecological situation in the entire life cycle, compare products and services, develop and improve them. Furthermore, LCA studies can be used for strategic planning, marketing and on higher levels, for public policy making.

4.5. Methodology

The following Figure E.3 illustrates a simplified overview of the LCA methodology derived from the ISO standard 14040 (ISO, 2006a [26], [27]). In detail, the systematic procedure of an LCA consists of four phases:

- The goal definition defines the purpose of the analysis. Scope definition determines the functional unit to be analyzed and system boundaries regarding spatial and temporal characteristics and methods used for impact assessment. Particularly, the functional unit is the

reference unit which is used to normalize all the inputs and outputs in order to compare them with each other.

- Life Cycle Inventory Analysis (LCI): this step refers to the analysis of the material and energy flows and the study of the working system. On the other hand, the data collection for the entire life cycle implies the modelling of the analyzed system. Moreover, one of the most critical aspects of this phase is the quality of inputs, which must be verified and validated in order to guarantee the data reliability and correct use. The Life Cycle inventory is the most crucial stage in the LCA study. It corresponds to the finding and selecting of the input data, in order to express the examined scenarios in quantified terms.
- Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA): this step includes the assessment of the potential impacts associated with the identified forms of resource use and environmental emissions.
- Interpretation: in this phase, the analyst aims to scrutinize the results and discuss them, giving as precise information as possible to the decision makers.

Figure E.3. The LCA methodology [28]

4.6. Dimensions and Indicators

The selection of impact categories and characterization models is an integral part of the goal and scope definition phase of an LCA, and further extends to the LCIA phase. In detail, in the choice of impact categories practitioners should take into account the consistency with the goal and scope definition: any choice made by the practitioner has to support the defined goal and scope; that means for the

indicator selection that when, for example, environmental sustainability assessment is the goal of a study, the practitioner cannot choose a limited set of indicators, or a single-indicator footprint approach, as this would be inconsistent with the sustainability objective of avoiding burden shifting among impact categories [28]. Moreover, the practitioners should also take into account the comprehensiveness of environmental issues related to the product system being studied and the appropriateness of the characterization mode in the context of the goal and scope of the study.

Some of the most commonly used impact categories in LCA studies are:

- Depletion of abiotic resources potential (kg Sb_{eq}). This impact category indicator is related to extraction of minerals and fossil fuels due to inputs in the system ([29], [30]).
- Global warming potential (kg CO_{2eq}). Climate change is related to emissions of greenhouse gases to air. The characterization model is developed by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [31].
- Ozone depletion potential (kg CFC-11_{eq}). The characterization model is developed by the World Meteorological Organization and defines ozone depletion potential of different gasses ([29], [30]).
- Human toxicity potential (kg 1.4 DB_{eq}). This category concerns effects of toxic substances on the human environment ([29], [30]).
- Ecotoxicity potential (kg 1.4 DB_{eq}). This category indicator refers to the impact on different ecosystems (fresh water, marine or terrestrial), as a result of emissions of toxic substances to air, water and soil ([29], [30]).
- Photochemical ozone creation potential (kg C₂H₄_{eq}). Photo-oxidant formation is the formation of reactive substances (mainly ozone) which are injurious to human health and ecosystems, and which also may damage crops ([29], [30]).
- Acidification potential (kg SO₂_{eq}). Acidifying substances cause a wide range of impacts on soil, groundwater, surface water, organisms, ecosystems and materials (buildings).
- Eutrophication potential (kg PO₄₃-eq). Eutrophication includes all impacts due to excessive levels of macro-nutrients in the environment caused by emissions of nutrients to air, water and soil ([29], [30]).
- Global energy requirement (MJ). The assessment of the environmental impacts related to a product or process is based on one parameter: the total energy demand for production, use and disposal expressed in primary energy. Every direct and indirect (e.g. construction of

infrastructure) energy input is taken into account, obtained from process or input-output analysis. It is also divided between non-renewable and renewable primary energy use [32].

4.7. Applications in the field of (hybrid) energy storage

LCA is widely applied in the field of energy storage technologies environmental evaluation ([4], [33]). This method can be used to compare the environmental impacts of competing storage technologies, or simply understand the full impact of increased system production and use. Moreover, LCA results can be used to inform battery research and development efforts aimed at reducing adverse environmental impacts, compare competing storage technology options for a particular use case, or estimate the environmental implications of large-scale adoption applications.

LCA studies of different energy storage systems have been conducted in the scientific literature, providing an overview of their energy and environmental impacts, and identifying the key issues to be investigated to reduce these impacts. However, few studies rely on primary data (data measured directly at production sites). Therefore, even if the issue of LCA applied to storage systems has already been discussed in the literature, further research is needed on specific materials / components and processes related to these technologies in order to acquire more knowledge in this field. Moreover, the comparison of studies is often a difficult task, due to different methodological assumptions (e.g. functional units, system boundaries, cut-off rules, uncertainty of secondary data, variation of primary data, etc.). In addition, only a limited number of studies investigate the environmental performance of storage systems taking into account the end of life of these technologies. Although this stems from the fact that the production and use stages are often those with the greatest contribution over the entire life cycle, proper recycling and the corresponding reduction in demand for raw materials have the potential to reduce the impact.

4.8. Data availability

The quality of LCA strongly depends on the quality and the level of detail of the input data. At present, the problem of data quality still represents one of the critical points of the LCA methodology, since there are both too many confidential data and the lack of primary data of innovative technologies and related materials and processes.

The quality of the data collected and used in the inventory phase determines the quality of the whole LCA study. In general, there are two types of data used in a LCA study. The data measured directly are defined as primary data while those obtained from literature and databases are defined as secondary data. Generally, the calculation of environmental performance must be conducted using mainly primary data referring to the reference year of the study and specific to the investigated system. In the absence of primary data, it is possible to refer to secondary data. Regardless of the origin of the data, it is of fundamental importance that the data are as representative as possible of the analyzed model. The validity of the data must be checked already during the collection process, by means of mass and energy balances and comparative analyses on emission factors. In the event of anomalies in the data,

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alternative values must be sought that confirm the quality requirements established in the phase of defining the objectives and the field of application under study.

4.9. Reporting

There are no standards for reporting of LCA of storage systems.

4.10. Strength and weaknesses

The last few decades have seen a marked rise in the application of life cycle assessments in virtually all countries around the world. This growing interest can be attributed to the powerful support the tool provides to decision makers. As with all complex assessment tools, the LCA methodology has its limitations as well as strengths [28].

LCA is a cradle-to-grave analytical method that captures the overall environmental impacts of all the life cycle stages associated with a product, process or human activity from raw material acquisition, through production and use phases, to waste management. This comprehensive view makes LCA a unique approach in the suite of environmental management tools available to decision makers. Without life cycle thinking, we risk focusing on the environmental issues that demand our immediate attention, and ignoring or devaluing issues that may occur either in another place or in another environmental impact. Such focused assessments can lead to decisions that are based on incomplete information.

Moreover, LCA highlights potential environmental trade-offs. The broad scope involved in conducting LCA makes users more aware of the complexities of integrated industrial systems and ecosystems, and the appropriate corresponding remedy for a given situation. LCA encompasses all the interacting activities, media, and impacts and the identification of potential trade-offs from one phase of the life-cycle to another, from one region to another, or from one environmental problem to another that may occur as a result of a decision (that is, resulting from a change to a system or from choosing between systems).

The ISO series of standards provides us with a definition of LCA along with a general framework for conducting an assessment in four inter-related phases (goal and scope, inventory analysis, impact assessment, interpretation) [27]. On the other hand, they leave much to interpretation by the person conducting the assessment.

Taking into account the full and complete analysis of a system’s environmental impacts is likely a more complicated endeavour than many organizations are willing to undertake. It is anticipated that the continued conduct of LCAs will make organizations and consumers more aware of the interconnections of operations, while providing producers, consumers and regulators with the necessary baseline information and data to move forward [34]. The challenge now is to find an affordable, efficient way to share this growing database of knowledge with users across the globe. Although LCA databases and software have become more widely available in recent years, the lack of readily available inventory data continues to be a major hurdle for LCA practice. Inventory data can be created by collecting

primary data directly from the sources, such as material and product manufacturers. More often data are collected from secondary sources such as reports, publications and databases. While the use of readily-available software tool makes it easier to conduct an LCA, it is not always completely clear how the data were modelled in order to create the data found within them. The numerous, underlying assumptions, such as exclusions which were applied during data collection, are not typically revealed in most pre-packaged data programs.

4.11. Standards and guidelines

The ISO 14040 series standards are the core standards of LCA. These are the leading international standards on LCA. ISO 14040 is an overarching standard encompassing all four phases of LCA [26]. ISO 14041 deals with goal and scope definition and life cycle inventory methods. ISO 14042 deals with life cycle impact assessment methods and ISO 14043 life cycle interpretation methods. ISO 14044 specifies requirements and provides guidelines for life cycle assessment [27]. ISO/TS 14048 provides the requirements and a structure for a data documentation format to be used for transparent and unambiguous documentation and exchange of LCA and LCI data, thus permitting consistent documentation of data, reporting of data collection, data calculation and data quality, by specifying and structuring relevant information [35]. ISO/TR 14049 provides examples about practices in carrying out a LCI as a means of satisfying certain provisions of ISO 14044 [36]. ISO 14067 specifies principles, requirements and guidelines for the quantification and reporting of the carbon footprint of a product ([37]). ISO 14020, ISO 14021, ISO 14024, ISO 14025, and ISO 14026 on environmental labels [38–42]: these standards set out principles, requirements and guidelines for the development and use of environmental labels and declarations, as well as for the communication of footprint information.

Moreover, across the globe, countries have formulated a large variety of standards and guidelines. Some of the most renowned are:

- The International Reference Life Cycle Data System (ILCD) handbook [30], which was developed by the European Commission Joint Research Centre, offers technical guidelines on conducting detailed LCA studies. It contains detailed descriptions and requirements in order to reduce flexibility in choices and to support the consistency of LCA results and quality assurance related to these. It is consistent with the ISO 14040 and 14044 LCA standards.
- PAS 2050 (UK) on greenhouse gas emissions [43]. It provides a method and guidelines for calculating greenhouse gas emissions “within the life cycle of goods and services.” It was one of the first standards for calculating carbon footprints, and it has been applied in many countries around the world.
- EcoLeaf Environmental Labelling Program (Japan). It describes the methodology for assessing the environmental impact of products throughout their life cycle. This framework is a result of

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the integration of two different Japanese frameworks, EcoLeaf and Carbon Footprint of Products (CFP). The framework is consistent with the LCA ISO 14040 series.

In addition to the generic product standards and guidelines, there are more-product-specific international standards. However, unlike other sectors, such as the construction sector, in field of storage systems no supplementary standards have been established. On the other hand, a Product Environmental Footprint Category Rules (PEFCR) is available for High Specific Energy Rechargeable Batteries for Mobile Applications [44]. This PEFCR provides a structure to ensure that all Product Environmental Footprints for high specific energy rechargeable batteries used in these applications are derived, verified and presented in a harmonized way.

4.12. Use cases

Some use cases for LCA are available in Table E.4. Table E.4: Use cases for LCA and (hybrid) energy storage

Source	Aim	Technology	Hybrid y/n	Use case	Functional unit	Impact Categories
Christina Wulf, Petra Zapp [45]	analysing the potential of defossilizing industrial specialty glass production with hydrogen by LCA (LCA) is performed to evaluate different hydrogen supply methods for the furnace	PEM Electrolysis Hydro-generation Dehydro-generation Glass melting (trough) Air separation	Yes - Power to gas?	Defossilisation of glass production, reducing energy	Hourly rate of glass production	Climate change kg CO ₂ -eq Particulate matter kg PM _{2.5} -eq. Ozone depletion kg CFC-11.eq Photochemical ozone formation (POF) kg NO _x -eq. Acidification kg SO ₂ -eq Water consumption m ³ Fossil depletion kg oil-eq. Land use annual crop-eq.*a Metal depletion kg Cu-eq.
ITAS Website Peters et al. [46]	LCA of Sodium-ion batteries (SIB) and comparison with lithium-ion batteries (LIB)	Sodium-ion batteries (SIB) lithium-ion batteries (LIB)	no	Cradle-to gate comparison (Production phase, Recycling, Efficiency and battery lifetime (use phase))	one kWh of electricity provided by the battery system for the defined service over its entire lifetime	global warming potential (GWP) i.e., GHG emissions abiotic resource depletion potential (ADP) acidification potential (AP) human toxicity potential (HTP)
Borbala Rebeka David et al. [47]	LCA for comparison of thermal battery and lithium-iron-phosphate battery LIPB	“Thermal battery” = thermal energy storage (sensible) lithium-iron-phosphate battery LIPB	no	Cradle-to-gate approach, comparison of the production of LIPB and “thermal battery”, no recycling/disposal	discharge potential of 1000 kWh	Climate change kg CO ₂ eq Ozone depletion kg CFC-11 eq Terrestrial acidification kg SO ₂ eq human toxicity kg 1,4-DB eq photochemical oxidant formation kg NMVOC particulate matter formation kg PM ₁₀ eq ionizing radiation kBq U235 eq freshwater eutrophication kg P eq marine eutrophication kg N eq terrestrial ecotoxicity kg 1,4-DB eq freshwater ecotoxicity kg 1,4-DB eq marine ecotoxicity kg 1,4-DB eq agricultural land occupation m ² *a urban land occupation m ² *a

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						natural land transformation m ² water depletion m ³ metal depletion kg Fe eq fossil depletion kg oil eq
Pasqua L'Abbate, Michele Dassisti and Abdul G. Olabi [48]	Environmental Sustainability Analysis of Small-Size Vanadium Redox Flow Batteries	Vanadium Redox Flow Battery: reduction – oxidation	Yes? One anolyte, one catholyte tank -> two storages	production of all raw materials of the parts to be assembled (electrodes and cells, membranes, laboratory-prepared vanadium electrolyte, battery cases, hydraulic system), assembly, use, and disposal	Number of stack 1 Nominal power 150 W # Cells/stack 5 Average voltage at end discharge (SoC 0.2) 6 V Energy density of electrolyte 36.18 Wh/l Electrolyte volume 6 l Overall efficiency 0.85 Average current 25 A Charge energy 176.47 Wh Discharge energy 127.5 Wh Cycle time (charge and discharge) ~3 h	agricultural land occupation m ² ×a natural land transformation m ² marine eutrophication kg freshwater eutrophication kg particulate matter formation kg marine ecotoxicity METP100 (kg) terrestrial acidification TAP20 (kg) terrestrial ecotoxicity TETP100 (kg) water depletion m ³ metal depletion MDP (kg) fossil depletion FDP (kg) photochemical oxidant formation POFP (kg) climate change GWP20 (kg) ionizing radiation IRP_I (kg) freshwater ecotoxicity FETP100 (kg) urban land occupation m ² × a human toxicity HTP100 (kg) ozone depletion ODP inf, x (kg of ODS x and kg CFC-11 equivalents/kg)
Sonia Longo et al.[4]	LCA of a sodium–nickel chloride cell in order to identify the shape of the cell (tubular or planar)	Sodium–nickel chloride battery	No	“from cradle to gate” approach and include the raw materials supply and the manufacturing processes of the main input materials used for the cathode, electrolyte, and anode production	A cell with a capacity of 1 Ah	Global Energy Requirement GER (MJ) Global Energy Requirement—non-renewable GER-nr (MJ) Global Energy Requirement—renewable GER-r (MJ) Global Warming Potential GWP (kg CO ₂ eq) Ozone Depletion Potential ODP (kgCFC-11eq) Human Toxicity—Cancer effects (HT-c CTUh) Human Toxicity—Non-cancer effects (HT-nc CTUh) Particulate Matter PM (kg PM _{2.5} eq) Ionizing Radiations HH IR-HH (kBq U ₂₃₅ eq) Ionizing Radiations E IR-E (CTUe) Photochemical Ozone Formation POF (kg NMVOCeq) Acidification Ac (molc H+eq)

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						<p>Terrestrial Eutrophication TE (molc Neq) Freshwater Eutrophication FE (kg Peq) Marine Eutrophication ME (kg Neq) Freshwater Ecotoxicity FET (CTUe) Land Use LU (kg C deficit) Water Depletion WD (m3 watereq) Resource Depletion—mineral, fossil, renewable RD (kg Sbeq)</p>
Sonia Longo et al. [49]	LCA of a sodium/nickel chloride battery considering two different operational scenarios	Sodium–nickel chloride battery	No	The system boundaries include the battery manufacturing phase, the operational phase and the end-of-life phase.	The entire battery, including the battery management interface	<p>Global energy requirement GER (MJ) Non-renewable energy requirement NRE (MJ) Renewable energy requirement RE (MJ) Global warming potential GWP (kg CO2eq) Ozone depletion potential ODP (kg CFC-11eq) Human toxicity HT (CTUh) Photochemical ozone formation POF (kg NMVOCeq) Acidification Ac (mol H+eq) Terrestrial eutrophication TE (mol Neq) Freshwater eutrophication FE (kg Peq) Marine eutrophication ME (kg Neq) Land use LU (kg C deficit) Water resource depletion WRD (m3 watereq)</p>
Cusenza et al. [50]	Assessment of the environmental sustainability of using battery storage systems for stationary applications made of used batteries from Plug-in hybrid electric vehicle in substitution of new batteries in a life cycle perspective	Lithium manganese oxide-nickel manganese cobalt oxide/graphite	No	The system boundaries include the battery manufacturing phase, the operational phase and the end-of-life phase.	Yearly averaged energy use in the building and in the transportation sector	<p>Cumulative energy demand CED (MJ/year) Abiotic depletion potential ADP (kgSbeq/year) Global warming potential GWP (kgCO2eq/year) Ozone depletion potential ODP (kgCFC-11eq/year) Human toxicity, non-cancer effects HT-nce (CTUh/year) Human toxicity, cancer effects HT-ce (CTUh/year) Particulate matter PM (kg PM2.5eq/year) Ionizing radiation, human health IR-hh (kBqU235eq/year) Photochemical ozone formation potential POF (kgNMVOCeq/year)</p>

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						<p>Acidification potential AP (molH+eq/year) Terrestrial eutrophication EUT (molNeq/year) Freshwater eutrophication EUF (kgPeq/year)</p> <p>Marine eutrophication EUM (kgNeq/year) Freshwater ecotoxicity EFw (CTUe/year)</p>
<p>Eleonora Crenna et al. [51]</p>	<p>Towards more flexibility and transparency in life cycle inventories for Lithium-ion batteries</p>	<p>Lithium-Ion Batteries (NMC111, NMC811, NCA)</p>	<p>no</p>	<p>flexible and transparent life cycle inventories (LCI) of LIB for background databases by means of a consequently modular approach</p>	<p>Comparison on a per mass basis as well as on a per kWh stored energy basis</p>	<p>climate change. ozone depletion. ionising radiation. photochemical ozone formation. particulate matter. human toxicity noncancer. human toxicity cancer. acidification. eutrophication freshwater. eutrophication marine. eutrophication terrestrial. ecotoxicity freshwater. land use. water use. resource use- fossils. resource use- minerals and metals</p>

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5. CRITICALITY ASSESSMENT

5.1. Synonyms / other related methods

Critical raw material (CRM), supply risk, vulnerability, scarcity, rarity, criticality, depletion, availability, resource efficiency

5.2. Assessment Level

Table E.5: Assessment Level of Criticality Assessment

Discipline	Scope
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Social Sciences and Humanities	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Country / Region
<input type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Company / Organization
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Economic sciences	<input type="checkbox"/> Process
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Natural sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Product/Service
<input type="checkbox"/> Environmental sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> System

5.3. Short description

Approaches addressing criticality in a wider perspective often consider the risk of an availability/supply disruption of a mineral resource and the vulnerability of a system to this disruption. The combination of both aspects defines the level of criticality.

5.4. Scope

The topic of criticality has been addressed from different perspectives for several decades. While former discussions concentrated on energy-related supply dependencies, today mostly minerals are in focus, not exclusively in combination with a life cycle approach. Originating from a criticality on country/regional level the question of vulnerability on an economy or company level, down to sector, technology, and product level is stretched.

5.5. Methodology

The discussion on critical materials originates from a long-standing debate within the LCA community about resource use. Topics such as scarcity, rarity, criticality, and depletion resulted in a multitude of assessment approaches. In 2020 an expert task force on “Mineral Resources” initiated by the Life Cycle Initiative [52] has reviewed existing methodological approaches and categorized them into four main groups: depletion, future efforts, thermodynamic accounting, and supply risk methods. While the first two are more “traditional” LCIA addressing physical availability, the latter two provide complimentary information such as geopolitical topics. Additionally, two perspectives were identified. The first focuses on how the use of mineral resources in a product system can affect the opportunities of future use (“inside-out” perspective), whereas the second focuses on how environmental and socioeconomic conditions can affect the accessibility of mineral resources for a product system (“outside-in” perspective). Based on the given perspective recommendations for an application-dependent use of

these methods were elaborated. In the following a brief introduction into most frequently discussed approaches incorporating geopolitical aspects is given.

EU-CRM List

The EU’s criticality methodology [53] has been developed already in 2011 and refined in 2017. Every three years a new list of CRMs has been published, the latest in 2020. The approach defines CRMs as materials of high importance to the economy of the EU, whose supply is associated with high risk. It combines the two main components: supply risk (SR) and economic importance (EI). They are defined as follows [53]:

- Supply risk (SR) - calculated based on factors that measure the risk of disruptions in supply of a given material. It is based on the concentration of primary supply from raw materials producing countries, considering their governance performance and trade aspects.
- Economic importance (EI) - calculated based on the importance of a given material in the EU for end-use applications and on the performance of its substitutes in these applications.

The SR is calculated based on factors that measure the risk of disruptions in supply of a given material (e.g., supply concentration measured by the Herfindahl–Hirschman Index (HHI), import reliance, governance performance measured by the Worldwide Governance Indicators, trade restrictions and agreements, existence, and criticality of substitutes [53]).

$$SR = \left[(HHI_{WGI,t})_{GS} \cdot \frac{IR}{2} + (HHI_{WGI,t})_{EU_{sourcing}} \left(1 - \frac{IR}{2} \right) \right] \cdot (1 - EoL_{RIR}) \cdot SI_{SR} \quad (5.1)$$

- GS : Global supply, i.e., global suppliers’ countries mix
- $EU_{sourcing}$: actual sourcing of the supply to the EU domestic production plus other countries importing to the EU
- HHI : Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (used as a proxy for country concentration)
- WGI : Scaled Worldwide Governance Indicator (used as proxy for country governance)
- T : Trade parameter adjusting WGI
- IR : Import reliance
- EoL_{RIR} : End-of-life recycling input rate
- SI_{SR} : Substitution index related to supply risk

The EI is calculated based on the importance of a given material in the EU for end-use applications and on the performance of its substitutes in these applications. Manufacturing sectors are classified according to the Statistical Classification of Economic Activities in the European Community (NACE) Rev.2 (2-digit level) (classification provided by Eurostat [54]).

$$EI = \sum_S (A_S \cdot Q_S) \cdot SI_{EI} \quad (5.2)$$

- A_S : Share of end use of a raw material in a NACE Rev. 22-digit level sector
- Q_S : NACE Rev. 22-digit level sector’s value added

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- SI_E : Substitution index related to economic importance
- S : denotes sector

A systematic two-stage supply chain assessment (mining, processing) is considered for those materials where two clear stages could be identified, as bottlenecks can occur also during processing of the materials. In the 2017 updated methodology [53], end-of-life recycling input rates (EoL-RIR) were improved by using higher quality EU-based data. Output of the assessment are the two indicators calculated by material, which is defined as critical if it exceeds both the threshold for EI and SR at the same time. The thresholds above which a material is called critical are defined by experts as follows: $SR \geq 1$ and $EI \geq 2.8$ [53]. Above these thresholds there is no ranking of criticality.

The latest 2020 version assesses 83 individual materials, with 47 materials (including the individual HREEs, LREEs, and PGMs) being deemed as critical (Table E.6). Independent of the criticality status, the list provides EI and SR values for each material. Also, additional figures needed for the calculation of EI and SR are given. For each of the material considered factsheets are regularly updated by experts providing additional specific information.

Table E.6. Critical raw materials for the EU 2020 [55]

2020 Critical Raw Materials (30)			
Antimony	Fluorspar	Magnesium	Silicon Metal
Baryte	Gallium	Natural Graphite	Tantalum
Bauxite	Germanium	Natural Rubber	Titanium
Beryllium	Hafnium	Niobium	Tungsten
Bismuth	HREEs	PGMs	Vanadium
Borates	Indium	Phosphate rock	Strontium
Cobalt	Lithium	Phosphorus	
Coking Coal	LREEs	Scandium	

A group from the European Commission’s Joint Research Centre (JRC) has addressed open issues regarding implementing aspects of SR into LCIA [56], [57]. Evaluating different concepts of integrating the SR of all materials (critical or non-critical) as characterisation factor (CF) into the assessment they recommended the combined use of SR related to the annual mining production: SR/p . This method gives higher importance to specialty metals and reflects more closely the results of the EU CRM list. The EI was not considered since it relates to the European economy as a whole and could be less meaningful for supply chain analysts at corporate level. Since then, other approaches have been tested to integrate SR and EI [58–60] but without consensus so far.

GoPolRisk

As a start the GeoPolRisk method was developed to calculate the supply risk of a resource from the point of view of a country, region, or group of countries and serves to complement environmental indicators in LC(S)A [61], [62]. The method was extended by Helbig et al. (2016) [63] to add domestic production as a risk mitigation option. By adding vulnerability also, the economic importance dimension was integrated into the assessment [64]. In the following, substitutability and recycling were included as further risk mitigation factors [65], [66] Beside an indicator on midpoint level also an

indicator at endpoint level (GeoPolEndpoint) was developed to measure socio-economic impacts [67]. For a defined resource and year, results can be interpreted as average increased costs caused by geopolitically driven supply disruptions. In all versions the argumentation was, that criticality exists independent to the amount of a material used in the system. Therefore, no relation to the values of the inventory were drawn. The latest development, however, redefines the characterization model to measure the supply risk potential by integrating a mass-based midpoint indicator [62], to be aligned with LCA methodology.

The current version of the indicator formula to obtain the GeoPolRisk of a resource “A” from the perspective of a country “c” in a given year is as follows [62]:

$$GeoPolRisk_{Ac} = HHI_A \sum_i \frac{g_i + f_{Aic}}{p_{Ac} + F_{Ac}} \quad (5.3)$$

- HHI_A : Herfindahl-Hirschman Index for resource A
- g_i : Geopolitical (in) stability of country i
- f_{Aic} : Imports of resource A from country i to country c
- F_{Ac} : Total imports of resource A to country c
- p_{Ac} : Domestic production of resource A in country c (incl. recycled material estimated from the EoL-RIR)

The endpoint indicator is defined as:

$$GeoPolEndpoint_{Ac} = GeoPolRisk_{Ac} \cdot \varepsilon \cdot p \quad (5.4)$$

- ε : inverse price elasticity of the resource A
- p : average price of the resource A in the analyzed year

Right now, the GeoPolRisk web page (<http://geopolrisk.org>) provides an open tool to calculate the indicators for 26 materials and energy carrier for eight countries or regions on a yearly basis up to 2020, which shall be expanded to other materials. Those indicators can be combined with the inventory of an investigated system to express the criticality of the system. Practitioners do not need to gather the necessary information by themselves. So far, many commodity materials (Al, Co, Ni, Cu, Fe) are included in the list. However, it needs future expansion to other specialty materials used in storage technologies.

ESSENZ

The ESSENZ method was developed by Technische University at Berlin (TUB) in cooperation with six European companies during a three-year project [68]. It aims to provide characterization factors with global applicability, especially for multinational companies having operations all over the world. To cover all dimensions of sustainability overall 21 categories are established to measure impacts on the environment, physical and socio-economic availability of the used resources as well as their societal acceptance. Besides traditional environmental impact categories, 11 geopolitical and socio-economic indicators are considered as well as additional social indicators. An aggregation of the different indicators is not recommended. The development of the CFs for each socio-economic indicator and material follows a four step-approach: 1) in a first step the impact values for each indicator are determined; 2) in a distance-to-target (DtT) approach each indicator is divided by a target value above

which accessibility constraints are assumed to occur, the higher the value, the higher the risk; 3) this DtT ratio is normalized by global production data to reflect the assumption that constraints can be more severe for resources produced in relatively small amounts. 4) scale-up (to a range between 0 and 1.73×10^{13} in each category) to show differences in very small normalized DtT figures and to ensure a similar range of CFs among the supply risk categories. A portfolio of 36 metals and four fossil raw materials. So far one update of CF factors in 2019 was performed [69].

SPOTTER

The most recent development is the SPOTTER approach. It aims to assess site-dependent overall supply disruption impacts for complete supply chains and supply disruption hotspots separately [70]. While the overall impacts are assessed based on the total of impacts along the supply chain (i.e. resource, material, and product), the hotspots are identified by key supply bottlenecks, representing the inventory flows with the highest impacts. While flows of the same material/product between different countries will be evaluated differently, some supply disruption events are expected to have equivalent impacts around the world. For the first time not only short-term (< 5 years) risks are considered, but also future developments up to 5 – 15 years are assessed, so that practitioners can identify the appropriate responses at different time. Only future inventory flows are assessed, as they allow a resilient design, precaution, or risk mitigation to be taken. Data from typical LCA databases (e.g. ecoinvent [71]) and/or trade databases (e.g. BACI [72]) can be used for the short term assessments. Data provided in publications such as technology forecasts or roadmaps should be chosen for medium term assessments.

The supply disruption impacts are described by two different impact categories, which are cost variability and limited availability. The former refers to supply disruption events that may increase the prices of the supplied materials/products, which then results in changes of costs for their production. The latter refers to supply disruption events that may reduce or remove the access to input flows, which then results in a limited availability of the output from the product system [70].

The supply disruption impacts are assessed individually for all inventory flows within the chosen scope describing the cause-effect chains between respective supply disruption events and impact by CFs. Each impact score is calculated by the multiplication of the amount of the specific resource, material or product that is used for a unit process (m_{matUP}) with the respective CF that defines one type of supply disruption impact (CF_{matUP}). The CFs are defined as follows [70]:

$$CF = (EI \cdot t) \cdot (DI) \cdot (PVI) \cdot (EVI) \quad (5.5)$$

- *EI*t*: supply disruption event over time period
- *DI*: diversity of supply
- *PVI*: vulnerability to physical shortage
- *EVI*: economic importance or economic damage

Overall, the CFs in the SPOTTER approach reflect the different time horizons (i.e. short- or medium-term), spatial scopes (i.e. country-specific or global), inventory flows (i.e. resource or material/product) and impact categories (i.e. cost variability or limited availability). The variations/combinations

result in eight groups of CFs for each inventory flow. To overcome the challenge of limited data availability for all the indicators necessary a simplification of the procedure has been proposed. The materials are limited to the list of critical raw materials defined by the European Commission [55] and case-specific flows that occur along the supply chain of these raw materials [70] . However, the practicability of the SPOTTER approach has to be proven in case studies.

5.6. Dimensions and Indicators

Criticality assessment combines various dimensions from geological, technological, geopolitical, social, and environmental aspects, depending on the stakeholder perspective and the corresponding methodological approach. Basis for many approaches are two indicators developed by the US National Research Council in 2008 [73]: supply risk or probability of a supply disruption and impact of supply restriction or vulnerability to a supply disruption. However, many methodological specifications of these two indicators have been developed since. International experts of the EIT Raw Materials project IRTC (“International Round Table on Materials Criticality”) categorized indicators applied after reviewing more than 200 papers and reports. Figure E.4 summarizes indicators most frequently used in studies [74].

Figure E.4: Indicators for the probability of a supply disruption and/or the vulnerability to a supply disruption [75]

The European Commission’s criticality assessment methodology considers two indicators as a composition of various sub-indicators (see methodology description): SR and EI. Several of these sub-indicators also form the basis for geopolitical-motivated methodologies, e.g. GeoPolRisk, ESSENZ, SPOTTER. Table E.7 gives an overview of sub-indicators used in the different methods.

Table E.7: Sub-indicators used in various geopolitical-motivated methods

Method	Indicator	Sub-indicators
EU CRM List [Lit]	Supply risk (SR)	Global suppliers’ country mix Actual sourcing of supply to the EU HHI WGI Trade restrictions and agreements Import reliance End-of-life recycling input rate (EoL-RIR) Substitution index related to SR
	Economic importance (EI)	Share of material end use in a NACE sector level sector’s value added Substitution index related to EI
GeoPolRisk	GeoPolRisk	HHI GWI-PV Imports of resources Domestic production of resource incl. EoL-RIR
	GeoPolEndpoint	Average price Price elasticity
ESSENZ	Resource efficiency, socio-economic dimension	HHI Reserve-to-annual production ratio Co-production Policy potential index Enabling trade index GWI Percentage of annual growth Recycled content of material Price volatility
SPOTTER	Short-term	GWI Child labour Trading across border indicator Price volatility EoL-RIR Ratio production to stock Depletion of economic stock
	Medium-term	Demand growth Co-production Primary raw material reliance Depletion of ultimate resources

5.7. Applications in the field of (hybrid) energy storage

The elementary need of storage technologies for transformation processes towards carbon reduced systems but also the increasing use in the defence sector were key drivers of criticality assessments for entire economies or governments, to evaluate their vulnerability to a supply disruption of specific materials. Beside the physical availability and scarcity of several materials being used in storage

technologies the geopolitical dimension due to a concentrated production capacity in Asia became eminent. Several studies on dual use also include batteries and hydrogen systems [75].

Especially the case of Li-batteries was chosen often for clarifying methodological choices and outcomes [59], [62], [76–80]. However, the variety of approaches and indicators considered makes a comparison of results nearly impossible.

Another field of frequently assessed energy storage technologies are electrolyzer and their materials [62], [81–84].

5.8. Data availability

To assess criticality the inventory for the environmental LCA can be deployed. The elementary flows of natural resources can be used when applying the assessment on foreground and background systems. Depending on the scope of the study, the Bill of Materials (BoM) and the source/origin of materials are sufficient when the foreground system is in focus, which is most often the case.

Ideally, publicly available data shall be used, which are updated on a regular basis. Major data providers are geological surveys (USGS, BGS, BGR, etc.), the World Bank providing the Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI), the Fraser Institute Annual Survey of Mining Companies reporting the Policy Perception Index (PPI) [85], scientific literature (scientific paper and technical reports), United Nations Environment Program (UNEP), International Resource Panel (IRP) data on recycling rates [86], UNDP’s Human Development Index (HDI), ecoinvent or other LCA databases for environmental data, as well as a wide range of industry reports (e.g., Roskill) and expert opinions. All data sources provide data with different uncertainties, which ideally are stated.

5.9. Reporting

There is no standard on reporting critical materials existing. Depending on the criticality method chosen the identified critical materials are either simply listed, qualitatively discussed or quantified.

5.10. Strength and weaknesses

Table E.8: Strength and weaknesses of Criticality Assessment

Strength	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LCI provides necessary information • Geopolitical data, such as HHI or GWI are updated on a regular basis • SR and EI of the EU-CRM List are updated every three years, material list is extended • GeoPolRisk data are updated annually and provided in an open tool • risk-mitigating measures can be developed • SPOTTER include future orientation into assessment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Only very limited materials are identified to be critical in all approaches • Many approaches consider only a small number of materials • Data availability for many materials is limited • Not all approaches consider recycling and substitution as risk-mitigation options • Dissipative losses are not considered in any application • Bottlenecks in processing steps are often not considered in the method • Thresholds of EU approach is output of a consultation process and not physically derived • No harmonized relation between supply risk and vulnerability has been defined

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Statistical data do not represent stakeholder specific supply dependencies• Prices fluctuation for some materials is very high• Especially trade data are often not made public• No approach is suitable for consequential LCA
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5.11. Standards and guidelines

There is no generic standard approach on how to conduct criticality assessment available yet. The diversity of stakeholder perspectives has resulted in a variety of approaches with different indicators being applied. However, the international expert group IRTC was brought together to move the harmonization process further.

5.12. Use cases

Mini Review of uses cases is given in form of Table E.9

Table E.9: Use cases of Criticality Assessment

Source	Aim	Technology	Hybrid y/n	Use case	Functional unit
Abdelbaky et Al. [78]	A comparative assessment of resource-use criticality in advanced lithium-ion battery technologies evaluates resource inaccessibility of battery raw materials to include refining and use stages inefficiencies in the assessment	LIB batteries	no	Battery raw materials (Li, Ni, Co, Cu, Mn, Al, C, Si) assessed with ESP (economic resource scarcity potential method) Recycling rates from hydrometallurgical battery recycling process. indicator for trade barriers mine production: share of mine production under export restrictions.	Comparison by bill of material of a 1 kilowatt-hour (kWh) energy storage system
Mori et Al. [81]	Criticality assessment (and LCA) of Fuel-Cell and Hydrogen Technologies: polymer-electrolyte-membrane fuel cells, solid-oxide fuel cells, polymer-electrolyte-membrane water electrolyzers, alkaline water electrolyzers.	polymer-electrolyte-membrane fuel cells, solid-oxide fuel cells, polymer-electrolyte-membrane water electrolyzers, alkaline water electrolyzers.	no	Critical materials within the four FCH (fuel-cell & hydrogen) technologies identified according to three criteria: hazardousness, price and EU criticality methodology	mass of 1 g of material
Gielen [87]	Critical materials for the energy transition	Batteries for EVs Permanent magnets for wind turbines Solar PV technology trends Permanent magnets for EVs Electricity grids	yes	Definition of critical materials, Evaluation of scarcity indicators, strategies to mitigate critical material dependencies, material demand projections and prospects, innovation effect on the demand of critical materials, geopolitical aspects	
Koyamparambath et al. [88]	Supply risk evolution of raw materials for batteries and fossil fuels for selected OECD countries (2000–2018)	Batteries: Zinc-carbon, Alkaline, Silver oxide, Li-ion, Zn-Air, Ni-Cd, Ni-MH, Pb-Acid, Coal, petroleum, natural gas	no	Comparison of raw materials of all major types of batteries, primary fossil fuels: coal, petroleum, natural gas.	Geopolitical supply risk
Baumann et al. [89]	Prospective Sustainability Screening of Sodium-Ion Battery Cathode Materials	Sodium-ion batteries (SIB) (Lithium-ion batteries (LIB))	no	Cathode Active Material (CAM) screening including over 40 material compositions, overview of potential sustainability hotspots for SIB in early-stage research. SIB cathodes are benchmarked against state-of-the-art LIB CAM: costs, material criticality, and carbon footprint (CF)	Criticality $SR^{\wedge}EU$ CF in kg CO ₂ eq Cost in €/kWh

6. HYBRID MRIO - LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT

In section 4, we have introduced LCA as the most used methodology for the estimation of potential environmental impacts products and services. However, one of the recognized limitations of LCA is the need for highly detailed technical data and the high amount of time required to perform a complete LCA. Determining all process inputs and outputs for the components and subcomponents of the product or service under analysis could result in a huge database and complex relationships between each process [90]. As a consequence, LCA practitioners always define a system boundary, and this inevitably leads to truncation errors [91] as the processes lying outside the elected boundaries are considered negligible [92]. These truncation errors have revealed to be significant in some cases [93], [94]. Therefore, LCA would in principle underestimate the potential environmental impact.

Another method increasingly used for the environmental analysis of products along their value chain is the Input-Output (IO) Analysis extended with environmental accounts. A detailed description of the method and its multiregional version (MRIO) can be found in (Integrative methods input paper). The main disadvantage of MRIO and its extensions is the highly aggregated representation of processes and activities which happen in the economy since they are grouped in economic sectors which are assumed as uniform with unique technology and performance. The accuracy of the results will depend on how typical the studied product is in relation to the sector where it is contained [95]. In the case of too heterogeneous sectors, the values reported in the MRIO matrixes, and the associated environmental accounts do not correctly reflect a particular process or product [96]. Other potential weaknesses for environmental assessment depending on the MRIO include the lack of updated data, the use of monetary units (uncertainties subject to price fluctuations and inhomogeneity), insufficient handling of waste treatment, and a limited number of environmental indicators. In order to potentiate the advantages and limit the disadvantages of these two methods, hybrid approaches have been proposed [96], [97]. The use of MRIO avoids the necessity to draw system boundaries maximizing the completeness of the assessment solving the truncation error of LCA, while LCA provides the technological representativeness overcoming the aggregation error that affects MRIO.

6.1. Synonyms / other related methods

Hybrid MRIO, hMRIO, EIO-LCA, hLCA

6.2. Assessment Level

Table E.10: Assessment Level of Hybrid MRIO-LCA

Discipline	Scope
<input type="checkbox"/> Social Sciences and Humanities	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Country / Region
<input type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input type="checkbox"/> Company / Organization
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Economic sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Process
<input type="checkbox"/> Natural sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Product/Service
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Environmental sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> System

6.3. Short description

Hybrid LCA-MRIO is a way of combining conventional process-based LCA and environmentally extended input-output analysis (EEIOA) in a variety of ways in order to improve the accuracy and completeness of the analysis.

6.4. Scope

Hybrid LCA - MRIO is seen as state of the art in life cycle assessments and carbon footprint analyses [94], and the scope of the applications is the same as that of LCA or MRIO.

6.5. Methodology

Hybridization approaches have been grouped in four main categories [98](Crawford et al., 2018):

- i) tiered hybrid analysis,
- ii) path exchange hybrid analysis (PXC),
- iii) matrix augmentation (or IO-based LCA) and
- iv) integrated hybrid analysis.

Tiered hybrid analysis is conducted by adding IO-based life cycle inventories (LCI) to process-based LCA inventories [99]. There are some limitations associated with this hybridization system. First, significant errors can be introduced if important processes are modelled using the aggregated IO information. Second, there could be double-counting problems difficult to avoid. And third, it only remediates the truncation of foreground processes, but background processes are still truncated (Age z et al., 2020).

PXC was conceptualized by Lenzen and Crawford in 2009 [97]. The method consists of disaggregating the input output table into a series of mutually exclusive nodes that represent a good or service provided by a particular sector. Each specific node can be modified using process data (coming from LCA) related to the value or the environmental flow associated with the node [100].

The economic IO-based LCA model or Matrix Augmentation method was initially developed by Joshi in 1999 [101] and later by Suh and Huppes in 2005 [99]. It consists of disaggregating industry sectors to improve process specificity. The environmental extension vectors should be disaggregated as well using detailed emission data of the disaggregated processes using life cycle inventories (ibid).

Finally, integrated hybrid LCA departs from constructing a hybrid matrix in which input-output and physical flows are fully incorporated at the unit process level. Wiedmann et al. [94] assessed wind power case study in UK using this method.

6.6. Dimensions and Indicators

Hybrid LCA-MRIO can potentially be used to assess different dimensions of sustainability as Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA) and extended MRIO can. In literature, hybrid LCA-MRIO has been

used to assess environmental sustainability impacts. As in LCA, there are many different types and forms of indicators, and the number of indicators within each dimension is limited by the available extension vectors in MRIO. The available extension vectors are commonly used to estimate global warming impacts but also other environmental impacts categories such as acidification, eutrophication, photochemical ozone formation, diseases caused by respiratory inorganics, land use, water use and water scarcity, resource use: energy carriers and resource use: mineral and metals and other.

6.7. Applications in the field of (hybrid) energy storage

No application of hybrid LCA-MRIO to (hybrid) energy storage has been found in literature.

6.8. Data availability

Data sources for hybrid LCA-MRIO are those of LCA and extended MRIO (EMRIO) respectively and the reader is referred to [APPENDIX E. - 4. Life Cycle Assessment Method](#) and Integrative methods input [APPENDIX G. - 4. Extended Multi-regional Input Output Analysis \(EMRIO\)](#).

6.9. Reporting

There are no specific reporting requirements for hybrid LCA-MRIO.

6.10. Strength and weaknesses

Hybrid methods have been proposed to circumvent the limitations of LCA and EMRIO when used independently as they are designed to avoid the truncation error that affects LCA while retaining the technological accuracy of LCA thus avoiding the typical aggregation error that affects EMRIO. However, the different hybridization approaches have their own limitations. Tiered hybrid LCA runs the risk of double counting. Additionally, if the added products are represented by IO sectors that aggregate very different products, hybrid LCA runs the risk of overestimation. Path exchange hybrid analysis is a complex method that involves a high amount of data, and this precludes a wider application. Matrix augmentation suffers from the uncertainty inherent to expanding the IO matrix. And, finally, integrated hybrid analysis has the problem of adequately bridging process- and IO-based models in the hybrid matrixes constructed. In fact, price information for certain products may not be available or can be distorted and data years may be very different for the process model and the IO model. These problems often result in increased uncertainty [102].

Table E.11: Strength and weaknesses of Hybrid MRIO-LCA

Strength	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Avoid truncation errors that are typical in process LCA - Avoids the aggregation error that usually happens when using environmentally extended MRIO 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Possibility of double counting and overestimation - Limited number of environmental indicators. - Increased complexity of the analysis - Uncertainty in the expansion of the input-output matrix

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	- Uncertainty in bridging process and IO models
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6.11. Standards and guidelines

There are no specific standards for hybrid LCA-MRIO.

6.12. Use cases

No use cases of hybrid LCA-MRIO to (hybrid) energy storage have been found in literature.

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7. CIRCULAR ECONOMY

7.1. Synonyms / other related methods

Circular economy (CE), Circular business models (CBMs)

7.2. Assessment Level

Table E.12: Assessment level of Circular Economy

Discipline	Scope
<input type="checkbox"/> Social Sciences and Humanities	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Country / Region
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Company / Organization
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Economic sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Process
<input type="checkbox"/> Natural sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Product/Service
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Environmental sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> System

7.3. Short description

Circular economy represents an economy in which the value of products, materials and resources are maintained in the economy for as long as possible, and the generation of waste is minimized. It moves away from the linear “take-make-use-dispose” model and switches to a regenerative growth model.

7.4. Scope

In general, the CE concept can be applied anywhere and has a "cradle-to-cradle" perspective. There is no ISO standard for CE approach until now. However, the ISO/TC 323 committee is working currently on a series of standards, aiming to cover all aspects of a circular economy including public procurement, production and distribution, end-of-life as well as wider areas such as behavioural change in society, and assessment, such as some kind of circularity footprint or index.

7.5. Methodology

CE refers to a new economic model based on the basic principle of “everything is an input to another,” which is entirely different from the view of the traditional linear economy. European Commission (2015), in its Action Plan [103] on CE, stated that “in a CE, the value of products and raw materials is maintained for as long as possible; waste and resource use are minimized, and resources are kept in the economy when a product has reached the end of its life cycle, to be used to continue to create even more value”. According to the Ellen MacArthur Foundation a CE is “a system that is restorative and renewable through proactive planning and design. It replaces the concept of "end-of-life" of materials with the concept of recovery, shifting towards using renewable energy, not using harmful chemicals and reducing waste reduction through the design of materials, products, engineering systems, and business models within that system” [104]. The purpose of the CE is to prolong the useful life of products and increase the productivity of resources. All “waste” of one manufacturing process

is considered raw material for other manufacturing processes. The CE development strategy focuses on efficient use of resources, minimizing waste, reusing materials, and improving the ecosystem through business activities.

The core principles of the CE are widely recognized as reduce, reuse, recycle and recover. Besides that, repair, refuse, rethink, refurbish, remanufacture and repurpose are also considered CE principles [105–107]. In a recent paper, Desing and co-workers [108] established a link between CE and sustainability – as circular is not sufficient and synonym with sustainable. According to them, the environment is seen therein as the unnegotiable and irreplaceable frame for all human activities. Within these boundaries, only a limited number of materials and energy can be appropriated without disturbing the integrity and functioning of the Earth system beyond its safe limits [108].

The key elements of the CE can be grouped in the 10R framework, summarized in Figure E.5.

Figure E.5. The 10R Framework [109]

According to Ellen MacArthur Foundation [110], a circular economy has three principles, including regenerating ecosystems (natural systems), designing out waste and pollution, and keeping products and materials in use longer. A representation of the 10R framework, the 5R framework (a simplified 10R) most commonly applied to supply chains and manufacturing, and Ellen MacArthur Foundation circular economy principles are given in Figure E.6.

CIRCLE ECONOMY'S CORE ELEMENTS	STRATEGIES FOR RESOURCE CYCLING ¹³	10R FRAMEWORK	5R FRAMEWORK	ELLEN MACARTHUR FOUNDATION
 Prioritise Regenerative Resources	Regenerate flows			Regenerate ecosystems
	Narrow flows	Refuse		Design out waste
Reduce		Reduce		
Rethink				
 Stretch the Lifetime	Slow flows	Reuse	Reuse	Keep products in use for longer
		Repair	Repair	
		Refurbish	Refurbish	
		Remanufacture		
 Use Waste as a Resource	Close flows	Repurpose		Design out waste
		Recycle	Recycle	
		Recover		

Figure E.6. 10R framework, 5R framework and Ellen MacArthur Foundation circular economy principles [111]

The transition to more circular production and consumption systems affects businesses and forces them to redesign their business strategies and models. These business models are identified as CBMs. According to OECD [112] “CBMs represent fundamentally different ways of producing and consuming goods and services. They have the potential to drive the transition towards a more resource-efficient and circular economy and, in doing so, significantly reduce the environmental pressure resulting from economic activity”. Rovanto and Bask [106] stated that “a circular business model is the company-level application of a CE. It is the logic of slowing and/or closing material loops by which an organization creates, delivers, and captures value with long-term environmental, economic, and social implications systemically on the micro, meso, and macro levels to accomplish sustainable development”. Unlike the traditional business model, the CBM focuses on extending the product’s life cycles to maintain the economic values of the product for as long as possible and reducing the impact on the environment. CBMs have a core role in building a sustainable economy.

There are various types of CBMs according to different classifications. Some authors categorized circular business models into circularity design, optimal use, and value recovery [113]. Others categorized CBMs according to material flows, including short loop, long loop, rearrangement, and pure loop ([114], [115]). OECD [113] reclassifies circular business models into five categories such as:

(1) circular supply models, (2) resource recovery models, (3) product life extension models, (4) sharing models, and (5) product service systems models. Lüdeke-Freund et al. [115] proposed six main CBMs: (1) repair and maintenance; (2) reuse and redistribution; (3) refurbishment and remanufacturing; (4) recycling; (5) cascading and repurposing; and (6) organic feedstock.

A CBM has the following essential roles. Firstly, CBM plays a core role in building a sustainable economy (green economy, circular economy) by helping quickly reduce the growing amount of waste from human consumption. Besides, a CBM also helps to reduce overexploitation of resources, to prolong the product life, thereby decreasing users' costs through activities such as renewing/refurbishing, remanufacturing, etc. CBM, although still taking profit as the first condition, aims at restructuring economic activities based on natural processes, making them renewable and with low amount of waste.

7.6. Dimensions and Indicators

CE covers the environmental, economic and social dimension of sustainability, even if it is mainly focused on the environmental dimension (resource consumption and waste). For this latter, Desing and co-workers [116] established with the “resource pressure” method an approach to guide designers to make most use out of the limited sustainable resource base [108]. This method aims to offer decision support for this challenge, both in qualitative guidelines and a quantitative indicator. Pressure on primary resources is exerted by the product system twofold: directly thorough the intake of primary materials and indirectly through the generation of final losses, which can no longer be used elsewhere in the socio-economic system. Therefore, the resource pressure method aims at identifying and quantifying the circular strategies reducing the pressure on primary inputs as well as final losses most effectively.

Typical indicators of CE are showed in Figure E.7.

Figure E.7. Typical indicators of CE [117]

7.7. Applications in the field of (hybrid) energy storage

CE can be applied for energy storage considering the principles of the 10R framework and the different CBMs.

7.8. Data availability

Not applicable.

7.9. Reporting

There are no standards for reporting in CE. However, general standards of transparency and traceability of used data and modelling approach should be part of the report.

7.10. Strength and weaknesses

Strength of CE

CE can be applied to many different scales, from micro to macro, as well as to individual households. It helps to take advantage of used materials instead of losing them, to minimize the exploitation of natural resources, to make the most of the value of resources, and to reduce waste and emissions into the environment. CE helps to reduce social costs in management, to increase the environmental protection and response to climate change; it creates new markets and job opportunities and improves people's health. CE contributes to reduce the risk of overproduction and resource scarcity crisis; it creates motivation to invest, innovate technology, reduce production costs, and increase the sustainability of the supply chain.

Weaknesses of CE

CE is in the development stage, so there are many different views and application forms, leading to difficulties communicating about the circular economy to adopters and product users.

The adoption of a circular economy leads to a significant change in the old business model, the results of which may have to be built from scratch, which is a substantial obstacle for businesses. This change is not easy and takes a long time. Furthermore, the application of the circular economy is associated with technological changes, also in waste treatment technology. This change requires human resources and investment capital. In addition, applying a circular economy requires synchronous participation of partners; everyone's understanding of the circular economy is not the same, causing asynchronous partner participation.

7.11. Standards and guidelines

- ISO/TC 323 Circular economy [118], under development
- A new Circular Economy Action Plan For a cleaner and more competitive Europe [1]

7.12. Use cases

Table E.13: Use cases for CE and (hybrid) energy storage

Source	Aim	Technology	Hybrid y/n	Use case	Functional unit	Comment
Longo et al. [4]	Eco-design of cells	Sodium-nickel chloride	N	Battery cells	1 Ah	
Cusenza et al. [50]	Second life of batteries	Lithium manganese oxide-nickel manganese cobalt oxide/graphite	N	Battery as storage in building and vehicle	Yearly averaged energy use in the building and in the transportation sector	

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STORAGE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE ECO-SYSTEM

D4.2 – “Common base for environmental, techno-economic and socio-economic assessment to un-lock the potential applications for hybrid ES (HES) systems”

Work Package 4 - Supporting the transition towards a climate neutral continent

Task 4.2 - Sustainability Assessments of Hybrid ES Technologies

Submission date: 30th April 2024

APPENDIX F. INPUT PAPER: SOCIAL ASPECTS

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

AoP	Areas of Protection
CF	Carbon Footprint
EF	Ecological Footprint
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
EIS	Environmental Impact Statement
E-LCA	Environmental Life Cycle Assessment
GRI	Global Reporting Initiative
IAIA	International Association for Impact Assessment
ISPO	Indonesian Sustainable Palm Oil
LCC	Life Cycle Cost
LCOS	Levelized Cost of Storage
NPV	Net Present Value
OR	Occupational Risk
PSILCA	Product Social Impact Life Cycle Assessment Database
RSPO	Round Table Sustainable Palm Oil
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SFM	Social Footprint Method
SHDB	Social Hotspots Database
SIA	Social Impact Assessment
SIMP	Social Impact Management Plan
S-LCA or sLCA	Social Life Cycle Assessment

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SROI	Social Return on Investment
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
TAF	Technology Acceptance Framework
WF	Water Footprint

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1. INTRODUCTION TO THE THEMATIC CLUSTER

According to [1], the battery industry bears besides the environmental burdens and questionable viability of battery applications also significant social risks. These could be attributed throughout the whole life cycle of batteries (“cradle to grave”). The sociological aspects of the energy technology transitions are therefore an important part of current research agendas. Compared to the environmental or economic assessments, the social counterpart is a relatively new research field and studies on social impacts are much less developed than environmental impacts [2]. Moreover, in connection with emerging battery technologies, represent the social dimension untapped potential for integrating new dimension of research. Also, methods for the assessment of social aspects can be situated within the general sustainability framing, ultimately also be combined with other methods as indicated in Figure F.1.

Figure F.1. Overview of sustainability KPIs and Tools for (hybrid) energy storage technologies (Draft from Salome Hohl), with scope of this input paper

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2. SHORT OVERVIEW OF DIFFERENT METHODS

- **Social LCA** is assessing social impacts based on social hotspots or detailed analysis in the supply chain. It has gained attention recently not only by LCA practitioners due to the need for more sustainable battery life cycle.
- **Social Footprint/Social Handprint** initiated by the idea of Ecological Footprint (EF).
- **Social Impact Assessment** and specifically Product Social Impact Assessment.
- **Social Return on Investment** originally focusing on non-profit sector.

There are also other research directions related to the next generation batteries in different applications, such as technology acceptance studies on users' adoption of specific technologies and products (social acceptance in connection with the application sector of batteries, such as automotive and grid-scale). Additionally, there are existing methods used for specific purposes or environments, such as Human Rights Impact Assessment, or Social & Human Capital Protocol.

3. SOCIAL LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT

The structure and outline of the chapters is based on Andes et. al [3] and is adopted to hybrid energy storage systems. Here partially, text from StoRIES Deliverable 4.1 “Guideline for collection and access to FAIR and open data for environmental, techno-economic and socio-economic Assessments” is used.

3.1. Synonyms / other related methods

social LCA, S-LCA, sLCA, S(O)-LCA

3.2. Assessment Level

Table F.1.: Assessment Level of the social Life Cycle Assessment

Discipline	Scope
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Social Sciences and Humanities	<input type="checkbox"/> Country / Region
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Company / Organisation
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Economic sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Process
<input type="checkbox"/> Natural sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Product/Service
<input type="checkbox"/> Environmental sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> System

3.3. Short description

S-LCA can be considered as an extension of the LCA framework. The goal of social LCA as a life cycle-based assessment is to identify social hotspots and to go into more detail along the life cycle of a product. The method offers a starting point for improving the living conditions of stakeholders and provide information for further research and detailed data collection. The method can be used on its own or may be combined with other methods as LCA and LCC in frame of LCSA.

3.4. Scope

The aim of S-LCA is to analyse potential impacts of a products life cycle on stakeholder's wellbeing [4]. Each phase of a product life cycle can be allocated to a specific location (mine, factory, end user, recycling facility, etc.) with social and socioeconomic impact on different stakeholders. S-LCA can cover different levels including:

- Full Life cycle of products and services (cradle-to-grave; from resource extraction to end-of-life).
- Supply chain of the product (cradle-to-gate; exclude use phase and end-of-life).
- Parts of the Life Cycle (gate-to-gate or gate-to-grave).

Depending on the scope, only individual, particularly critical sections or stakeholder groups can be considered related to questions about corporate responsibility for the actors involved along the process chain and the social conditions and social impacts [3].

3.5. Methodology

Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) is the latest Life Cycle methodology developed, in chronological order. It has been conceived to evaluate social impacts deriving from products or services’ life cycles, affecting different typologies of stakeholders, such as workers, local communities, value chain actors, consumers, societies, and children. Since the beginning, it was deemed to assess social impacts in the same way LCA does it for the environmental ones; but while LCA is regulated by specific ISO norms (14040-44:2021), S-LCA is still not consensually defined, and the most diverse methodologies have been proposed in literature. A specific ISO norm, the 14075 “Principles and framework for social life cycle assessment”, is under development (in preparatory phase). Recently, UNEP (2020) updated the Guidelines for S-LCA, and the Methodological Sheets for subcategories in S-LCA (UNEP, 2021) [5] providing some guidance for S-LCA practitioners. An overview of the overall Assessment system from stakeholder to impact categories to inventory data is provided in Figure F.2.

Figure F.2: Assessment system from categories to inventory data, [6]

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3.6. Dimensions and Indicators

In general S-LCA takes a look at potential or actual Social and Socio-economic impacts (depending on its application) out of several stakeholder perspectives. These impacts are monitored alongside the entire life cycle or value chain of a product and have a strong relation to the seventeen SDGs that have been internationally accepted by governments, industries, and organizations.

3.7. Applications in the field of (hybrid) energy storage

In general, S-LCA can be applied for a wide range of topics related to energy storage.

- Support energy storage manufacturers to build up strategies for social policies
- Support decision making processes with multiple stakeholders (different backgrounds and knowledge), e.g., selection of a new production site, selection of suppliers for raw materials etc.
- Managing of social risks via identification of social hotspots (e.g., alongside the supply chain for manufacturing a storage unit)

3.8. How to

The S-LCA is has a strong basement within the ISO 14040 framework for E-LCA. Similarly, it includes four phases:

1. Goal and scope: This is the key phase for S-LCA and includes the definition of the system boundaries, categories of impact, functional unit, cut-off criteria, foreground, and background processes, considering all possible phases of the system under study. The definition of named aspects should be carried out in concordance wit stakeholders' groups related to considered subcategories.

System boundaries: These boundaries determine the parts of a storage system that will be considered in a S-LCA. It typically entails foreground processes (situated closer to the studied product, thus more likely to be directly studied; for which often specific data are collected) and background processes (further upstream or downstream, for which often generic data from databases are applied) in the product system.

Functional Unit: A proper definition of a functional unit is of high importance, as it characterizes the assessed product. In this case an energy storage technology, with its major characteristics, its location for the use. This can be in analogy to LCOS or LCC impact per converted kWh or power output of a storage unit.

Cutt-off criteria: these are needed out of operationalization reasons, e.g., amount of data needed. However, cutting off, means that critical issues might be missed. In general, three cut-off criteria can be named: i) social significance, ii) identical elements and iii) available resources [6].

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2. An inventory analysis: here all relevant input and output flows as well as relevant social inventory indicators are identified. Included data has to be normalized and can then be interlinked through so called activity variable. This is e.g., hours of exposure for each life cycle phase and task (such as manual and intellectual working tasks, input supplying, transport, consumption, living in the proximity of companies, etc.), classifying the typology of exposure (manual or mechanical work, temperature, exposure to chemicals, noise, etc.). A literature review of studies on particular working and living conditions that entail exposure to psychosocial risk factors is necessary to retrieve appropriate occupational risks (ORs). Each statistical association can be classified according to its intensity: according to [7], associations can be considered weak with $OR= 1-1,3$; moderate with $OR= 1,3-1,7$; strong with $OR= 1,7-8$; and very strong with $OR>8$.

3. Social Life cycle impact assessment: This phase aims to connect and understand the potential social and socio-economic impacts related to the product under assessment. The construction of a Psychosocial Risk Factor matrix, where every condition of exposure that occurred in the scenarios is linked, as retrieved from scientific literature to physical or psychosocial disease. The assessment of social impacts through the quantification of hours when stakeholders are exposed to specific conditions represent factors of psychosocial risks. There are two main families of approaches, corresponding to different impact assessment procedures and each of them responding to different practical research aims: the Reference Scale Approach (Type I), and the Impact Pathway Approach (Type II). S-LCA Type I assesses the social performance of companies or organizations involved in the product system, by comparing their behaviour to a reference scenario (for example, specific legal regulations or norms). The comparison is made according to specific primary or secondary data, information or stakeholders' opinions, and therefore the evaluation consists in the description of a current status and not in the accounting of the links between the activity and long-term impacts. Therefore, the characterization process is mainly based on interpretation.

S-LCA Type II evaluates social impacts through causal or correlation/regression-based relationships (impact pathways) between the product/service life cycle and possible social impacts in the short or long term. The characterization process is based on an analytical and quantifiable identification of the consequences of the life cycle. According to UNEP (2020) [6] the S-LCA Type II is epistemologically and methodologically more in line with environmental LCA, where inventory inputs are quantitatively linked with environmental impacts.

This duality of procedure is due to the multi paradigmatic characteristics of social sciences: therefore, in S-LCA, both interpretivist and post-positivist epistemological positions have been applied in scientific literature [8]. Most of the articles published are framed within the interpretivist paradigms, evaluating in a qualitative or normative way a wide range of impact categories mostly linked to companies' behaviour (e.g. child labour, corruption, fair salary, etc.), rather than to the life cycle functioning. Few studies can be found in literature framed in the post-positivist paradigms, i.e. quantifying cause-effect relationships between life cycle functioning and Areas of Protection (AoP) in an objective and generalizable way.

4. Interpretation of results: This is the last phase of a S-LCA. Here all obtained results are analyzed following the ISO 14044 including completeness check, consistency check, sensitivity and data quality

check, a materiality assessment and final conclusions, limitations, and recommendations. Finally, insights useful for stakeholders (private or public ones), practitioners and academics have to be retrieved.

Recommendations

To harmonize the life cycle approaches of the project, a post-positivism-oriented S-LCA methodology (type II according to UNEP, 2020 [6]) could be more suitable, because it allows:

- an objective assessment of potential impacts aligned with ISO norms 14040-44 (2021) [9], [10]
- connecting quantitatively inventory input to possible impacts
- a rational use of elements such as the Functional Unit, the setting of system boundaries, the rational choice of cut-off criteria, which are often blurred and confused in S-LCA type I approaches
- generalizing the insights to the whole productive sector, when using average data

Among the possible S-LCA type II methods, the Psychosocial Risk Factor (PRF) impact pathway [11] allows to assess the social impacts of a product life cycle by quantifying the risk of psychosocial impacts on different typologies of stakeholders, according to the duration of exposure to certain living and working conditions that can lead to health issues. Cox et al. [12] defined PRFs as the aspects and characteristics of work planning and management that can potentially lead to physical or psychological damage. The psychosocial risks will be measured using odds ratios (ORs), a statistical measure of the intensity of association between two variables, e.g., as the ratio between the odds of exposure for people with a disease and the odds of exposure for healthy people [13]. Measuring the psychosocial risks with the ORs is a retrospective analysis of a phenomenon, expressed with a non-dimensional value, and it can assume values between 0 and $+\infty$. A value of 1 indicates that there is no association between disease and exposure, while values > 1 indicate a positive association (the risk factor can provoke the disease/disorder); higher values show a stronger association between exposure and disease [7].

Data will be retrieved from previous scientific studies that examined the relationships between specific living and working conditions and diseases (or disorders), such as for example [11] low income and myocardial infarction (OR: 3,53) and stroke (OR: 3,73) [14], long working hours and metabolic syndrome (OR: 1,66) [15].

3.9. Data availability

Data collection would consist in using i) primary sources through site specific data collection (surveys to specific stakeholders or experts by means of a structures questionnaire, other quantitative data, e.g. on the number of occupational accidents) and ii) secondary sources via dedicated input-output database (as the SHDB (Social Hotspots Database) [16], PSILCA (Product Social Impact Life Cycle Assessment Database), and life cycle assessment database GaBi Social Life Cycle Assessment (sLCA)) and iii) through input-output of other databases (scientific and grey literature, as e.g. company information systems) [17]. Here it is worth to mention that SHDB and PSILCA databases are based on

global input-output models and that you can only achieve a hotspot analysis with these databases. In general, it is important to check the credibility of the data sources used. With the so-called triangulation, different methods and data sources are combined in order to better identify subjective elements [3].

3.10. Reporting

There is no direct standard for reporting. However general standards of transparency and traceability of used data and modelling approach should be part of the report. Also, sufficient sensitivity analyses shall be provided. Also, specific requirements for reporting can be derived from ISO 14044 for Life Cycle Assessment.

3.11. Strength and weaknesses

In general, S-LCA offers several advantages and challenges as summarized in Table F.2. Here it is worth to point out that there is a need for methodological development.

Table F.2. Overview of strength and weaknesses of the social Life Cycle Assessment

Strength	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of social problem areas, in particular unknown hotspots, for stakeholder groups and participating companies • Highlighting social grievances and development opportunities, opening up options for action, and prevention of mere shifting of problems between life stages and processes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transfer of results to other spatial units or objects of consideration is not readily possible due to context-specific peculiarities • Several methodological improvements needed • High effort for data collection and to identify relevant key processes as well as stakeholders • Collection of generic and site-specific data with high regional resolution • adequate participation of stakeholders

Some recommendations for methodological development are provided by Andes 2020 [3]

- Choosing between and dealing with qualitative and quantitative information or indicators and their linkage to the functional unit of the product system (e.g. the relation of data on the organizational level to the behaviour of a company on process units)
- Harmonization with LCA and LCC (system boundaries, functional unit, etc.) in terms of the feasibility of a Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA)

3.12. Standards and guidelines

- A UNEP/SETAC approach towards a life cycle sustainability assessment—our contribution to Rio+20 [18]
- Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of Products [19]
- Defining the baseline in social life cycle assessment [20]
- Life Cycle Assessment [4]
- Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Organizations 2020 [6]

3.13. Use cases

Table F.3. Use cases for social Life Cycle Assessment (hybrid) energy storage

Source	Aim	Technology	Hybrid y/n	Use case	Functional unit	Comment
Zimmermann et al. 2015 [21]	LiFePO4 produced in the USA	LFP	No	Cradle to Gate		Poster publication, SHBD used
Thies et al 2019 [22]	Assessment of the social sustainability hotspots of lithium-ion batteries	Lithium Ion batteries	No		Equivalent medium risk hours	SHBD used, Risks considered: child labour, corruption, occupational toxics and hazards, and poverty
Mancini et al, 2021 [23]	Assessing impacts of responsible sourcing initiatives for cobalt: Insights from a case study	Relevant for all Co-containing battery systems	No	Relevant for applications with batteries with Co-content		Primary data was collected in a cobalt mine
Bamana et al, 2021 [24]	Addressing the social life cycle inventory analysis data gap: Insights from a case study of cobalt mining in the Democratic Republic of the Congo	Relevant for all technologies with Co content	No	Relevant for applications with batteries with Co-content		S-LCA relevant for enable more holistic evaluations of emerging technologies but results are insufficiently robust for use in policy
Bouillas et al, 2021 [25]	Step-by-step social life cycle assessment framework: a participatory approach for the identification and prioritization of impact subcategories applied to mobility scenarios	Electric vehicle transportation technologies in comparison with the conventional ones	No	“Cradle-to-Grave” and “Well-to-Wheel”	Transportation of passengers in France for a mid-sized vehicle	PSILCA

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4. SOCIAL FOOTPRINT/HANDPRINT

4.1. Synonyms / other related methods

Social Footprint-method (SFM), PROSA-method, SHDB-method, S-LCA, SO-LCA, LCSA

4.2. Assessment Level

Table F.4. Assessment Level of Social Footprint/Handprint

Discipline	Scope
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Social Sciences and Humanities	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Country / Region
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Company / Organization
<input type="checkbox"/> Economic sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Process
<input type="checkbox"/> Natural sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Product/Service
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Environmental sciences	<input type="checkbox"/> System

4.3. Short description

The foundation of the idea of the social footprint lies within the concept of sustainability. It is a part of the three pillars of sustainability: environmental, economic and social footprints [26]. The footprints related to these pillars help to comprehend the complex entanglements that human’s impacts on ecosystems, societies and economies have. Introduced in the wake of the Earth Summit 1992 in Rio by Rees and Wackernagel [27], [28], the ecological footprint was a new accounting method to measure human demands on the biosphere taking into account earth’s ability to regenerate. After its introduction, several other environmental footprints have been introduced. Each footprint indicates particular classes of pressures associated with process, product, or activity from the life cycle perspective [29]. Related methods are accordingly all sorts of lifecycle-assessments, especially when it comes to S-LCA. From this starting point implementing a social dimension followed at a later point in time, leading to the concept of the social footprint among others. The social footprint usually measures a company’s effect on their employees or certain parts of the population and communities using specific indicators.

Even later the concept of the social handprint was developed. Introduced during UNESCO’s 4th International Conference on Environmental Education in 2007 actions towards sustainability where described, which subsequently evolved into the concept of the social handprint as a concept that puts positive impacts in the foreground. The principle behind handprints is being regarded as a consistent estimate of the impacts of positive change [30]. Thus, in contrast to the social footprint the social handprint focuses on the positive effects towards sustainability, including for instance actions towards biodiversity conservation, education for sustainable development or efforts referring to solve environmental problems [31].

4.4. Scope

Where in theory the scope of social footprints covers everything that impacts this planet on a social level in terms of sustainability. In reality it is mainly used as a means to quantify the social sustainability performance of organizations or enterprises. The social footprint furthermore contributes to reveal social vulnerabilities in supply chains, especially for companies based in countries, which pay little attention to social factors such as human rights.

Social handprint and social footprint have a common scope since they both share basic principles, what they also do have in common is the goal to advance the social well-being. What they do not have in common is their point of view, since they look at events from opposite sides. The application of social handprints however differs from its counterpart since as a concept introduced later in comparison, is not yet used as much in LCA/SLCA/LCSA studies.

4.5. Methodology

Hand- and footprints are usually implemented into Lifecycle assessments, such as the social life cycle assessment (S-LCA). There is a variety of different methods to gather and implement information to be able to evaluate the social footprint of a company or product. Many of them use large amount of data feed their analysis, such as the PROSA-method [32] or the Social Hotspot Database (SHDB)-method [33]. Weidema in contrast focuses on impact pathways in order to more easily tell apart important from not-important data on one hand and not having to rely on such a wealth of information to gain findings. The method focusses on macro-scale impacts of income redistribution and productivity impacts of missing governance, leading to an analysis that does not depend as much on enterprise-specific data, instead data can be quantified using national statistics [34]. The Social footprint method (SFM) apart from that is used to measure and report the social sustainability performance of organizations and is based on the idea of anthro-capital, which includes human-, social- and constructed capital. In contrast to the natural or ecological capital, anthro-capitals are produced by and for humans and can subsequently be also increased with falling supply [35]. The subsequent construction of a social sustainability quotient measures the relation of an organization's impacts on capital on one side and its proportionate share of the supply of such capital on the other side enabling the quantitative measurement of its impacts on resources.

Social handprints measure the results of changes of the status quo in reference to an organization or value chain thus reducing the existing social footprint, it also regards the changes in comparison to formerly used processes.

In order to combine social handprints with lifecycle-thinking patterns of sustainable development must be taken into account, which includes combining the understanding of social, environmental and economic impacts with decision-making. Lifecycle- thinking and approaches can be combined with social handprints using lifecycle management. Literature for this very reason shows that there are implications of different life cycle approaches (LCA,S-LCA,SO-LCA) for the assessment of social sustainability handprints [31]. These thinking patterns help to work out challenges and limitations and

furthermore support development of focus areas regarding social handprints. With the focus on the S-CLA interconnection to social handprints, the life-cycle approaches support social handprints when it comes to the assessment of social development and application of the sustainability indicators, the use of site-specific and generic information/data and the integration of social sustainability into decision-making [31]. Furthermore Alvarenga et al. [30] present a framework to distinguish and classify various types of handprint for the use in LC(S)A-Studies for a better understanding of the beneficial, adverse and net-effects to emerge thus enabling the constant use of the handprint concept into LC(S)A in the future. The three types proposed are therefore direct, indirect, and relative, distinguishing between the absolute positive impacts a product can bring to its intended user, to unintendedly affected subjects and the relative positive impacts a product has in comparison to a benchmark for the intended user and/or the unintended affected subjects.

4.6. Dimensions and Indicators

Indicators enable researchers to track specific human pressures on their environment, there is a vast number of different indicators in reference to footprints. Literature shows that the indicators used in sustainability research focus mainly on ecological-, energy-, carbon- and water footprint, representing the very threats humanity faces [26]. As already addressed in the methodology-section all of the methods are based on indicators, some need more and some less. The already mentioned social hotspot database (SHDB) features the most the most complete product systems with data on working hours and several forms of risk data for more than 200 countries [34]. Social indicators include female employment, income, work hours, rates of unemployment, fatal cases in workplace or percentage of population with lower than high school diploma among others [36]. Since most of the time research have to work with generic data, the significance of the results is limited to this kind of data. Original data, as it is with other footprint models like carbon footprint (CF) and water footprint (WF), is hard to come by. Since handprints frequently use the lifecycle-models as well the same limitations apply when it comes to indicators. SHDB (v5) for example offers to calculation models on social footprints and social handprints as well as for identifying hotspots. The indicators correspondingly remain within the range of available data used for social footprints, the perspective on the data is the decisive difference. The interpretation of the indicator's changes depending on whether the handprint-perspective is being regarded or the footprint-perspective.

4.7. Applications in the field of (hybrid) energy storage

When linking energy as a general topic with the concept of footprints there is a higher density of publications, however most of these publications refer to ecological, energy, carbon, and water footprints, representing shared global concerns regarding food security, energy security, climate security, and water security [26]. Battery storage technologies are being reviewed for examples when it comes to social impacts the implementation into S-LCA, analysing the social footprint of hydrogen production of alkaline water Electrolysis [37], [38]. In a broader sense, social aspects are being evaluated in terms of assessing energy equity through energy storage. Thereby giving an insight on the

lack of access to energy technologies as well as the inequitable distribution of the benefits and burdens energy systems create [39], [40].

4.8. Data Availability

Social indicators are evaluated throughout the entire process of goods or services. Different Models exist to incorporate data into a life-cycle. As already mentioned the “Dimensions and Indicators”-section the Data itself on many of the indicators however is hard to come by, many existing LCSA methods require an exorbitant amount of data [34]. Although databases, index/indices and metric(s) gather information within the lifecycle of products, as well as activities and operations of organizations, there is a lack of original data, which make results a matter of interpretation as well.

4.9. Reporting

The Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) is an independent organization that develops and updates guidelines for corporate sustainability reporting in an ongoing multi-stakeholder process. GRI-Standards are the dominant global standard when it comes to reporting on ecologic, economic or social impacts, they set the global standards to be met in order to achieve transparency through standardization and comparability [32]. By 2020, already 80% of companies worldwide reported on sustainability, which turned third-party assurance of sustainability information into a major business. Not only the US, having the highest reporting rate globally, but also Asia-Pacific, as well as the Middle East and Africa are growing in numbers when it comes to reporting on sustainability. The increasing connection between companies and the UN sustainable development goals (SDG’s) drives the implementation of social indicators in reporting, although most of them belong to the moderately or least prioritized groups [41].

4.10. Strengths and weaknesses

Table F.5. Overview of strength and weaknesses of the social Life Cycle Assessment

Strength	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can be easily implemented into a life-cycle-system • Can be combined with other footprints • Does provide an overview when it comes to need for change • Good detection of needed measures • Ability to transform sustainable development from a vague concept into measurable objectives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Large amount of data needed • Lack of original data • Danger to be abused for greenwashing activities • Has to simplify social entanglements

4.11. Standards and guidelines

In contrast to the product carbon footprint (PCF) there is not yet a standard when it comes to the social footprint. There are international and national standards to cover some of the footprints. The ISO 14067 standard builds largely on other existing ISO standards for LCA for example. It was published in 2018 and can be considered the international reference standard for conducting PCF. There are several global guidelines within the SLCA for social impacts with different impact categories or/and indicators such as GRI, UNEP/SETAC, additionally certain branches or regions have their own guidelines and Standards, for example “Roundtable Sustainable Palm Oil” (RSPO) and “Indonesian Sustainable Palm Oil” ISPO for the palm oil production [42].

4.12. Use cases

Table F.6. Use cases for social Life Cycle Assessment (hybrid) energy storage

Source	Aim	Technology	Hybrid y/n	Use case
Schlör et al. [38]	Analysis of the social footprint of hydrogen production	Alkaline Water Electrolysis - Hydrogen	no	Hydrogen production
Werker et al [37]	Analysis of the social footprint of hydrogen production	Alkaline Water Electrolysis - Hydrogen	no	Hydrogen production
Norris et al. [33]	supply chains of products and detect social hotspots using the SHDB	Hydrogen production using Alkaline Water Electrolysis	no	Hydrogen production
Nasution et al [42]	Social sustainability assessment of palm oil production process	Example sectoral application, not relevant for ES	no	Non ES relevance

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5. SOCIAL IMPACT ASSESSMENT

5.1. Synonyms / other related methods

Social impact assessment (SIA), was regarded as a part of an environmental impact assessment (EIA) in the production of an environmental impact statement (EIS).

5.2. Assessment Level

Table F.7. Assessment Level of Social Impact Assessment

Discipline	Scope
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Social Sciences and Humanities	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Country / Region
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Company / Organisation
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Economic sciences	<input type="checkbox"/> Process
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Natural sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Product/Service
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Environmental sciences	<input type="checkbox"/> System

5.3. Short description

Social impact assessment (SIA) is a process to analyse the social impacts associated with plans, policies, projects, and other developments. The SIA Methodology is usually used to study the social effects of planned development interventions. SIA is an interdisciplinary and/or transdisciplinary social science that incorporates many fields including sociology, anthropology, demography, development studies, gender studies, social and cultural geography, economics, political science and human rights, community and environmental psychology, social research methods and environmental law, among others

5.4. Scope

Social impact assessment is a specific social science research method applied to policies or projects, which is aimed at understanding the situation, reasons, and results of social life. The objective of social impact assessment is to achieve sustainable development outcomes. Scientific knowledge and methods will be used to analyse the social changes, impacts, and results caused by policies or projects, and useful knowledge or policies will be offered to reduce negatives and achieve effective management. [43].

5.5. Methodology

Considering International Association for Impact Assessment (IAIA), SIA process is depicted as comprising four phases (see Figure F.3) that are somewhat sequential, but which also overlap. Through data collection and analysis, SIA is a learning process, and consequently initial assumptions and preliminary understandings may need to be modified in the light of new information, so there needs

to be an iterative process of validation and update informed by an on-going process of consultation with project proponents and other stakeholders, especially from impacted communities. [44]

Figure F.3. Four phases of SIA, [44] page 15.

Social impact assessment involves the use of methods of sociological research, both quantitative (statistical) and qualitative (observation, interviews, case studies etc.). Each Environmental Impact Statement (EIS) will involve research into context: community size, the group of direct and indirect beneficiaries, the social, educational, economic, and ethnic backgrounds, values and needs. Expertise is usually required. Interaction with affected communities and groups is critical since the social and cultural context and individual values are intrinsically related. There are many methods by which this interaction is feasible. From participatory observation (in which the analyst lives in the community to learn how it works) to group interviews, individual and opinion polls. Choice of methods will be based on the time and financial resources available, depending on the type of community and experts’ opinion towards the social problems and the community needs. [45]

5.6. Dimensions and Indicators

The indicators and indices can be built through the process of turning the basic concepts into quantifiable variables. This is a specific case of social research methodology. The first step is to turn

concepts into variables. Variables obtained are indicators of the future monitoring and evaluation model. Based on their calculations can be made and can be derived indices to express, condensed, different trends. Also, in this stage we should determine the type of indicators (impact, net impact, efficiency, effectiveness, performance, etc.).

Indicators can be:

- Population demographics: size, age, ethnic groups, gender
- % of the population with access to social services (health, education, recreation, social support)
- % of the population with access adequate water, sanitation, electricity

5.7. Applications in the field of (hybrid) energy storage

There are some cases where the evaluation of different storage technologies has been evaluated from the social perspective. An example is the analysis of an integrated system based on intermittent and non-intermittent renewable sources and energy storage made by A. Sanchez et al [46]. Here, a social index indicates the regions where these facilities could be installed to mitigate social inequalities.

5.8. Data availability

Reliability and validity, robustness and significance levels are important methodological issues in a SIA study. A report needs adequate details about methods, sources and assumptions.

The quality of analysis is another area of variability. While there are legitimate constraints on the level of analysis that is possible, a good use of scoping and issue prioritization can assist in allocating resources efficiently and in ensuring that in-depth analysis is undertaken for all key issues.

The adequacy of public participation continues to be an issue. Public participation ranges from being the provision of periods for public comment and the supply of information, to being the active involvement of stakeholders in shaping the SIA process and the opening-up of governance processes to include local communities in decision-making about projects. Of course, the demands of community consultation can lead to fatigue in communities and local governments. Also, the public availability of SIA reports, baselines and agreements is an ongoing issue as far as the publicly available SIAs can be difficult to locate after submission, especially in the absence of online repositories.

At the end, because of the confidentiality of personal data and the identities of who was included in the research, care must be taken to ensure that all data are stored securely and safe from unauthorized access. It is also expected that there be a stated timeline after which the data would be destroyed. Because of institutional requirements that practitioners should be able to produce raw data in the event of an audit or complaint and to safeguard against fraud, typically this would be several years after completion of the project.

5.9. Reporting

Research methods and analytical procedures must be fully disclosed to enable replication of the research by another practitioner; enable peer review of the adequacy and ethicality of the methodology; and to encourage critical self-reflection on the limitations of the methodology and any implications for the results and conclusions.

Best practice in SIA is to provide a Social Impact Management Plan (SIMP), which more than just lists likely impacts, it emphasizes how the impacts will be managed, what mitigation will be provided, what enhancement measures will be provided, what ongoing monitoring shall be provided, and what governance arrangements will apply.

A SIA is likely to include Applicable Legal Framework and Standards, Community Profile and Social Baseline, Prioritized Listing of Key Social Impacts, Summary of Mitigation and Management Measures, Monitoring Plan and Contingency Plan (Adaptive Management)

5.10. Strength and weaknesses

Table F.8. Strength and weaknesses of Social Impact Assessment

Strength	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SIA methods implement ongoing social monitoring and management programs, and community feedback mechanisms Possible to evaluate to evaluate community development alternatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integration with environmental, health and cultural heritage issues can be superficial. . The demands of community consultation can lead to fatigue in communities and local governments

5.11. Standards and guidelines

The activities typically undertaken in an SIA process are well established and documented (see [44])

1. Guidelines and principles for social impact assessment [47]
2. Social Impact Assessment: Guidance for assessing and managing the social impacts of projects [44]

5.12. Use cases

Table F.9. Use cases of Social Impact Assessment

Source	Aim	Technology	Hybrid y/n	Use case	Functional unit	Comment
A. Sanchez et al., 2022 [46]	Evaluation of integrated power facilities: several Spanish locations are assessed as case studies	Solar, wind, battery, fuel cell	y	Spain		
L. Jicheng et al., 2021 [48]	Social effects assessment of photovoltaic-coupled energy storage system application projects based on local social economy/ environment/ energy/ public aspects	Solar, photovoltaic-coupled energy storage system		China		

6. SOCIAL RETURN ON INVESTMENT

6.1. Synonyms / other related methods

SROI, Social impact investing, Corporate Social Responsibility, Triple Bottom Line, Blended Value

6.2. Assessment Level

Table F.10. Assessment Level of Social return on investment

Discipline	Scope
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Social Sciences and Humanities	<input type="checkbox"/> Country / Region
<input type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Company / Organization
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Economic sciences	<input type="checkbox"/> Process
<input type="checkbox"/> Natural sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Product/Service
<input type="checkbox"/> Environmental sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> System

6.3. Short description

The Social Return on Investment (SROI) measures the value added to the society caused by different interventions. SROI in essence means that more or less extensively monetized impacts are correlated to monetary and (to a limited extent) monetized input [49].

SROI is a framework for measuring and accounting for this much broader concept of value; it seeks to reduce inequality and environmental degradation and improve wellbeing by incorporating social, environmental and economic costs and benefits [50].

6.4. Scope

The SROI approach essentially focuses on impacts, their measurement, analysis, and representation. This is more meaningful than a focus on performance. It particularly applies where performance is targeted at positive societal development and is not an end in itself [49]. Originally developed by Roberts Enterprise Development Foundation in the United States in 1996 for non-profit sector and social enterprises, the method has gained attention also in the for-profit sector as well [51]

6.5. Methodology

The SROI calculation is based on cost-benefit approach, utilizing the Net Present Value (NPV). The SROI model was developed and structured as a specific blended value-accounting method, i.e. taking into account economic, environmental, and social dimensions into value creation [52].

$$SROI = \frac{NPV (stakeholder\ value)}{NPV (investment)} \quad (6.1)$$

SROI comprises six stages: identifying key stakeholders, mapping outcomes, evidencing outcomes, establishing impact, calculating the SROI and reporting, using and embedding the report. Although it is technically similar to the cost– benefit analysis, it attempts to be more holistic [53].

The assessment is performed in six steps:

1. establishing scope and identifying key stakeholders
2. mapping outcomes
3. evidencing outcomes and giving them a value
4. establishing impact
5. calculating the SROI
6. reporting, using and embedding [54].

6.6. Dimensions and Indicators

SRI is relevant to the social dimension of sustainability.

6.7. Applications in the field of (hybrid) energy storage

With the help of blended value and triple bottom line concepts, SROI can be used to identify the social hotspots in the energy storage value chain.

6.8. Data availability

Mix of qualitative and quantitative data is usually needed. SROI is often seen as an approach that monetizes outcomes, which can then be aggregated to create a measure of efficiency with which resources are turned into value [50].

Adding currency symbols to quantitative measures, i.e., monetizing employment increments and service decrements, can exaggerate the reliability, validity, and significance of evaluation findings [55].

6.9. Reporting

The SROI model was developed as a specific blended value-accounting method based on the calculation of the SROI ratio. The SROI analysis can focus either on a specific program or an entire organization in two different directions: evaluative and forecasting [56].

6.10. Strength and weaknesses

Table F.11. Advantages and problems of Social return on investment, adopted from [55]

SROI advantages	SROI problems
includes information on the amounts of resources used by the program, in addition to program activities	imprecise measures of societal costs and benefits, and inadequate designs, could engender poor or iatrogenic selection and funding of programs
includes information on the value to society of outcomes achieved by the program, in addition to outcomes not expressed in terms of societal value	training and experience may produce better, more uniform and more informative SROIs, but should this be limited to economists, or evaluators certified to conduct SROI?
allows different programs to be compared even if their outcomes typically are expressed in different unit	politics of SROI can exacerbate problems common in most evaluations
shows possible net gain in societal resources resulting from program operation	privatizing as potentially rationalizing abandonment of hard-earned entitlements
can represent program value to society as a whole rather than to a specific stakeholder group	SROI could justify continued or exacerbated discrimination in program offerings
could motivate multiple stakeholders to participate from the start of an evaluation, because much is at stake	data walks but money talks
	ratios and net benefits are not evaluative criteria in and of themselves
	SROI analyses often ignore the complexity of causal claims they depend on.
	Is SROI worth it? ... is it itself a significant return on investment for society?

6.11. Standards and guidelines

- Guidelines for Social Return on Investment [57]
- A guide to social return on investment (second ed.) [54]

6.12. Use cases

Table F.12. Use cases of Social return on investment

Source	Aim	Technology	Hybrid y/n	Use case	Functional unit	Comment
Adeyeye et al. 2022 [58]	Quantification of the cost and social returns of three micro hydropower	Micro hydropower (MHP)	n	MHP demonstrators in a public and private water supply, and irrigation network Europe	n/a	

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7. TECHNOLOGY ACCEPTANCE

7.1. Synonyms / other related methods

Technology acceptance, social acceptance, societal acceptance, public acceptance, Socio-political acceptance, market acceptance,

7.2. Assessment Level

Table F.13. Assessment Level of Technology acceptance

Discipline	Scope
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Social Sciences and Humanities	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Country / Region
<input type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Company / Organization
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Economic sciences	<input type="checkbox"/> Process
<input type="checkbox"/> Natural sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Product/Service
<input type="checkbox"/> Environmental sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> System

7.3. Short description

In social science research, there are many definitions of the concept of acceptance. Many of these approaches consider an attitude dimension and an action dimension at the same time. Schematically, these dimensions can be represented, for example, in a four-field scheme consisting of protest, rejection, advocacy and support [59]. In a technological context, thus acceptance can be understood as an attitude towards technology, which can result in a behavioural response against or in favour of technology. There is no common definition available for acceptance, rather studies refer to attitudes as acceptance [60]. A high relevance is attributed to acceptance, since behavioural responses of the population and of pressure groups may profoundly influence the success of an energy-related project. This applies in particular to technologies that directly interfere with the public, e.g., on a decentralized level for residual storage by visual impacts, perceived health and safety concerns, etc.

The technology adoption is associated not only with the performance and cost, but there are social aspects covered by energy-related Social Sciences and Humanities (energy-SSH) research. Energy-SSH considers roles of people and society in energy transition involving disciplines that study social phenomena such as norms, values, institutions, practices, perceptions etc. [61].

7.4. Scope

Acceptance Studies as “Morality and nuclear energy” by de Groot and Steg [62], “Still in love with solar energy?” by [63], “Psychological factors influencing sustainable energy technology acceptance” by Huijts et al [64], just name a few,] highlight that numerous sociopsychological factors can influence the public acceptance energy technologies, such as nuclear power plants, transmission lines, energy storage, biofuels and hydrogen. Most acceptance studies then allow it to determine the influential factors to technology acceptance and adoption which mostly revolve around the topics of trust, affect, risks and benefits, problem perception, knowledge, and experience. Doing so, corresponding

approaches for acceptance assessment provide insights for policy makers, lawmakers and practitioners that are useful for developing strategies, selecting technologies, and facilitating the successful implementation of technologies within the energy transition [60].

The social aspects and their importance were examined in three dimensions of social acceptance, namely socio-political acceptance, community acceptance and market acceptance [65]. This approach has been widely used by researchers with focus on low carbon and renewable energy technologies. Nevertheless, research expansion has been seen towards studying public engagement, participation and energy citizenship issues in energy transitions [66], [61].

7.5. Methodology

There are several approaches available to assess acceptance. These encompass theories from social and environmental psychology, and it is highly important that studies need define which aspect of acceptance is being studied and why it is relevant. A useful work for quantitative empirical research named technology acceptance framework (TAF) is provided in [64], [67]. However, the TAF does not distinguish between local and general acceptance, which is considered in [60]. Here an adapted version of the TAF is applied to investigate the different roles that socio-psychological factors play in selected technologies. Other approaches are based on discrete choice experiments. These experiments can be realized with a variety of economic and psychological models. Some methods named in this context are neoclassical rational choice models or mental models based on inductive search heuristics [68]. Usually, acceptance studies are carried out by reaching out relevant groups via surveys and interviews. Usually, a higher number of participants from a broad societal spectrum is favourable for acceptance studies. A good overview on different acceptance studies, used methods and different use cases is provided in [69].

In general, the approach can, but must not be structured as follows:

- **Development of a conceptual model:** Theoretical foundation to determine relevant variables that allow to determine acceptance as e.g. trust or affect
- **Survey design:** Development of a suitable elicitation method that fulfils neutrality and comprehensibility requirements. Also, all relevant information about the research project and the subjects should be asked. A good guideline to develop survey is provided in [70] and [71].
- **Data collection:** Should be carried out in a transparent way. Usually, surveys can be carried out via telephone or via online surveys. The latter can be distributed via social networks. However, it is recommended to achieve a certain sample size to assure a certain degree of statistical robustness as well as representativeness. This can be realized through panels as ScoSci survey in Germany, lamapoll or q-set. Analytic assessment: After the data collection, usually a statistical analysis is carried out. This can be realized by commercially available statistical software solutions such as 'R' or SPSS when it comes to quantitative analysis. Using a qualitative approach software-solutions like MaxQDA can be used evaluate statements. Several analyses can then be carried out using e.g., descriptive statistics, explorative factor analyses, conceptual model analysis.

- Interpretation: Finally, an interpretation based on considered previous theoretical assumptions and empirical results is carried out.

7.6. Dimensions and Indicators

There are no direct indicators for the assessment, it is rather unclear what the concept acceptance entails [68]. Some factors named are direct, indirect and total effects for trust in one’s municipality, trust in industry, environmental self-identity, perceived problems of the current energy system, the role of institutions or the impact of knowledge in terms of energy technologies [60].

7.7. Applications in the field of (hybrid) energy storage

In general, the analysis of “acceptance” is relevant for hybrid energy storage technologies. As stated before, challenges can arise through local resistance that can even lead to a failure of project planning (e.g. as in the case of the pumped hydro storage power plant Atdorf [72]. There are studies that analyse stationary battery storage and hydrogen fuel stations pointing out that there is a certain difference in local and general acceptance: [60], [73–75].

7.8. Data availability

Usually, acceptance studies are carried out by reaching out relevant groups via surveys and interviews. Usually, a higher number of participants from a broad societal spectrum is favourable for acceptance studies.

7.9. Reporting

There is no standard in reporting.

7.10. Strength and weaknesses

Table F.14. Strength and weaknesses of Technology Acceptance approaches partially based on [76]

Strength	Weaknesses
Gives impression about potential pitfalls	Very time consuming
Can help to facilitate the implementation of new technologies	High number of Feedback required
Allows to avoid problems in future projects	Development of surveys and statistical evaluation complex
Easy to comprehend	Neglects the diverse needs relevant in the voluntary consumer context
Demonstrated a high level of predictiveness in many contexts	Lack of subjective norms or social impact

7.11. Standards and guidelines

There are no standards available. Some Frameworks are:

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- Psychological factors influencing sustainable energy technology acceptance: a review-based comprehensive framework [77].
- Hydrogen fuel station acceptance: a structural equation model based on the technology acceptance framework [67].

7.12. Use cases

Source	Aim	Technology	Hybrid y/n	Used method	Functional unit	Comment
Baur et al. [73]	Assesses the social acceptance of three energy technologies relevant for the German energy transition	Stationary battery storage, biofuel production plants and hydrogen fuel station.	No	Online survey was conducted	Study provides evidence for the existence of a “general–local” gap	Collected data can provide stakeholders with an overview of worries that might need to be addressed when planning to implement a certain energy project
Emmerich et al. [60]	Give insights into socio-psychological factors that influence both the general and the local acceptance of emerging energy technologies.	Stationary battery storage, biofuel production plants and hydrogen fuel station.	No	Extended technology acceptance framework TAF [67] model analyses factors such as trust in industry, trust in municipalities, perceived problems of the current energy system and environmental self-identity with regard to acceptance both in general (general acceptance) and in the context of a scenario featuring a nearby implementation (local acceptance).	Perceived effects, including perceived benefits, costs and risks	Results provide evidence that these factors and mediators are relevant for the acceptance of emerging energy technologies in Germany. However, their impact differs for each of the selected technologies and depending on whether general or local acceptance is examined.
Fett et al [78]	Analysis of user acceptance of PV battery storage systems	Battery storage in combination with PV	No	Technology acceptance model (TAM) and theory of planned behaviour (TPB)	Perceived knowledge about battery storage systems, perceived ease of use, and perceived usefulness	Results indicate a high degree of acceptance for PV battery storage systems

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STORAGE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE ECO-SYSTEM

D4.2 – “Common base for environmental, techno-economic and socio-economic assessment to un-lock the potential applications for hybrid ES (HES) systems”

Work Package 4 - Supporting the transition towards a climate neutral continent

Task 4.2 - Sustainability Assessments of Hybrid ES Technologies

Submission date: 30th April 2024

APPENDIX G. INPUT PAPER: INTEGRATIVE ASPECTS

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D4.2 – “Common base for environmental, techno-economic and socio-economic assessment to un-lock the potential applications for hybrid ES systems”

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

CE	Circular Economy
EIO	Environmental Input-Output Analysis
ESS	Energy Storage System
GTAP	Global Trade Analysis Project
ICIO-OECD	Inter Country Input-Output Tables of the Economic Cooperation and Development
ILO	International Labor Organization
IOT	Input-Output Table
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
LCSA	Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment
LN	Logarithmic Normalization
MADM	Multi-Attribute Decision Making
MCDA	Multi-criteria Decision Analysis
MODM	Multi-Objective Decision Making
MRI	Multiregional Input-Output Analysis
MRIO	Environmental Extended Multiregional Input-Output Analysis
MRIOA	Multi-regional Input-Output Analysis
MRIOT	Multiregional Input-Output Table
PEF	Product Environmental Footprint
RoW	Rest of the World

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SHDB	Social Hotspots Database
SLCA	Social Life Cycle Assessment
VA	Value Added
WB	World Bank
WIOD	World Input-Output Database

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1. INTRODUCTION TO THE THEMATIC CLUSTER

Decision-making with regard to the sustainability assessment of energy technologies is complex due to sometimes conflicting goals (e.g., low costs for end users, minimum environmental impact, maximum social acceptance) and requires an integrated consideration of economic, environmental and social criteria. This thematic cluster includes a description of the methods used to simultaneously assess these three aspects of sustainability.

Figure G.1. Overview of sustainability KPIs and Tools for (hybrid) energy storage technologies (Draft from Salome Hohl), with scope of this input paper.

2. OVERVIEW OF METHODS

Among the methods proposed in literature to simultaneously assess the different sustainability aspects, an important role is associated to methods that apply life cycle thinking such as the Life Cycle Sustainability assessment (LCSA) [1]. This approach ensures that no burden shifting among impact categories and along steps of the supply chain occur [2].

Multi Regional Input Output (MRIO) [3] extended with environmental and social accounts is also a pivotal approach to assess sustainability as it provides a system-wide overview of the functioning of value chains involved in supplying products or services, which otherwise would be difficult to assess.

Results from both LCSA and MRIO, are a compilation of indicators belonging to various sustainability dimensions that need to be combined in a common framework in order to have solution-oriented sustainability assessment tools. In this vein, Multicriteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) is often used to reconcile the often-conflicting results from these analyses [4].

In the following sections, these methods are briefly described.

2.1. Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA)

Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment is a well-known measurement tool for any service, industrial system, or manufacturing process to standardize and quantify its impacts in environmental, economic, and social aspects. The three individual assessments for environmental, economic, and social analysis, respectively, contained in LCSA are life cycle assessment (LCA), life cycle costing (LCC), and social life cycle assessment (SLCA).

2.2. Extended Multiregional Input Output Analysis (EMRIO)

Multi-Regional Input-Output analysis is a macroeconomic tool that tracks financial flows between countries' major economic sectors. When extended with socioeconomic and environmental vectors, MRIO models can be used for the analysis of the sustainability impacts of any given investment. It has been extensively applied to the assessment of sustainability impacts of products, and technologies but also to the assessment of sustainability impacts of investments, the footprint of countries and the impacts of trade.

2.3. Multicriteria Decision Analysis (MCDA)

Multicriteria Decision Analysis is considered a branch of operations research that deals with decision problems that may involve multiple criteria, alternatives, and stakeholders. MCDA is generally divided into MODM (Multi-Objective Decision Making) and MADM (Multi-Attribute Decision Making). While MODM finds an optimal trade-off between criteria free of concrete alternatives (continuous solution space), MADM finds the best alternative between a set of concrete alternatives (discrete solution

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space). In this paper, the focus is on MADM methods as they are suitable for comparing concrete technology alternatives, but also scenarios and policy instruments.

2.4. Major recommendations for the use of identified methods

Although the usefulness of the identified methods is undeniable, performing a sustainability assessment is more than an integration of results from different methodologies. It requires integrating sustainability principles and employing transdisciplinary approaches in order to become a solution and action-oriented assessment able to guide the transformation of our society towards sustainability [5].

In general, low attention is devoted to the higher-level approach to sustainability beyond the discrete dimensions of the three pillars. There is a need to transcend the reductionism of the different methods and pursue a holistic approach that takes into consideration the complex relationships between the nature and society, states explicitly the sustainability principles and employs transdisciplinary to create strong links with the social context and to engage stakeholders in knowledge co-production [6].

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3. LIFE CYCLE SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT (LCSA)

3.1. Synonyms / other related methods

Life Cycle Sustainability Analysis, Triple Bottom Line analysis

3.2. Assessment Level

Table G.1. Assessment Level of LCSA

Discipline	Scope
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Social Sciences and Humanities	<input type="checkbox"/> Country / Region
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Company / Organization
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Economic sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Process
<input type="checkbox"/> Natural sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Product/Service
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Environmental sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> System
	<input type="checkbox"/> Sector

3.3. Short description

Life cycle sustainability assessment (LCSA) is a well-known measurement tool for any service, industrial system, or manufacturing process to standardize and quantify its impacts in environmental, economic, and social aspects. The three individual assessments for environmental, economic, and social analysis, respectively, contained in LCSA are life cycle assessment (LCA), life cycle costing (LCC), and social life cycle assessment (S-LCA) – all of them [1], [7]. In the recent past, methodological discussion started in order to include with circularity and criticality two further aspects into such an overall LCSA framework (see e.g. on-going activities of the ORIENTING project¹).

3.4. Scope

While a first article for LCSA allocated this method mainly to products [1], recent publications show that this method can be used in a much broader sense for any service, industrial system, or manufacturing process, and even any organization [8], to standardize and quantify its impacts in environmental, economic, and social aspects [9].

3.5. Methodology

According to the report [9] from the UNEP Life Cycle Initiative related to LCSA, this latter "refers to the evaluation of all environmental, social and economic negative impacts and benefits in decision-making processes towards more sustainable products throughout their life cycle". LCSA as a methodology

¹ <https://orienting.eu/>

allowing a detailed representation of technologies in their processes from a life cycle perspective and enables sustainability assessments in its different perspectives (environmental, economic, and social). For these three dimensions, well-known approaches are usually applied – i.e. life cycle assessment (LCA), life cycle costing (LCC), and social life cycle assessment (S-LCA). According to the ORIENTING project, the general framework behind LCSA looks as the following:

Figure G.2. Building blocks of the LCSA framework [10]

When taking a more detailed view – as done recently by the ORIENTING project [11] – each of these dimensions shows various options in terms of procedure (such as e.g. for the environmental dimension following the ISO 14040 standard or the European PEF rules, a detailed overview is provided in the [APPENDIX D. Input Paper: Economic Aspects](#) and data sources that are applicable – and each having its advantages/strong points as well as its inconveniences/limits.

3.6. Dimensions and Indicators

In such an LCSA study, according to [9], "inventory and impact indicators must be related to a common product functional unit, which is the basis of all techniques described. As with the S-LCA, it is recommended that the functional unit describes both the technical utility of the product and the product's social utility". Concerning the system boundaries (and thus the included process steps), [9] recommends that "the overall LCSA system boundary contains all unit processes relevant for at least one of the techniques." Then when applied individually, each life cycle technique tends to draw different system boundaries based on their respective relevancy to aspects of sustainability. Hence, as in e.g. classical LCA studies, reasons for the exclusion of specific life cycle stages with the examined system need to be justified.

An important – further – element in the whole LCSA discussion is the procedure, i.e. the way, how the results from these three dimensions are combined in the frame of the creation of an overall conclusion; or, how it is written in the objectives of the ORIENTING project: the practical approach in order to assess in an integrated way environmental, social, economic, circularity and criticality aspects. While Klöpffer in his publication [1] shows two principal ways to go - (i) an additive option (i.e. $LCSA = LCA + LCC + SLCA$), and (ii) an integrative option (i.e. $LCSA = 'LCA\ new'$ including LCC and SLCA as additional impact categories within the applied life cycle impact assessment method), the ORIENTING team investigated a whole bunch of integration approaches, split into three groups (i.e. group 1 = integration methods across sustainability domains / group 2 = visualization approaches / group 3 = commonly used weighting methods in the environmental and/or social fields), and analyzed according to relevant issues that need to be consistently assessed in an LCSA framework. In total 15 different integration approaches have been evaluated and assessed against seven main items (i.e. weak vs strong sustainability / double-counting / benefits and burdens / relative vs absolute sustainability / communication purposes / uncertainty analysis / policy linkages) [10].

Finkbeiner and co-authors [12] wrote more than ten years ago, that "the inherent complexity of an approach that is supposed to allow a valid measurement of the sustainability performance is a challenge for decision-makers. Therefore, effective, and efficient ways to present LCSA results are needed. This is a prerequisite for the communication of LCSA results to the non-expert audience of real-world decision-makers in public and private organizations. LCSA is intended to have a tangible effect on the sustainable development of our society. To achieve that, it has to become both valid and applicable."

So far, all the European experts involved into the ORIENTING project did not come up with a clear recommendation how this integration step shall be done.

3.7. Applications in the field of (hybrid) energy storage

Use case of LCSA analysis of storage technologies are scarce in literature. Examples have been found for batteries and pumped hydro electricity production.

3.8. Data availability

As LCSA is actually a combination of well-known approaches with life cycle assessment (LCA), life cycle costing (LCC), and social life cycle assessment (S-LCA), the data availability is related to the application of those approaches. Overall, the quality of an LCSA study depends on the quality of data that are available in all the included dimensions. In the field of S-LCA, there are two bigger data sources with the PSILCA and the social Hotspot databases available. For LCA, as stipulated in the respective report about the environmental aspects ([APPENDIX E. Input Paper: Environmental Aspects](#)), "the problem of data quality still represents one of the critical points [...], since there are both too many confidential data and a lack of primary data". For LCC, the report about economic aspects ([APPENDIX D. Input Paper: Economic Aspects](#)) stipulates that "the availability of reliable cost and technology performance

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data is vital when performing LCC. [...] Ideally LCC covers all expenses related to every life cycle phase of a product which should be identified accordingly, which is in most cases however not an easy task."

3.9. Reporting

As mentioned above already, there are no standards for reporting in LCSA for the moment. However, the general standards for transparency and traceability of used data and modelling approach should be applied here as well in order to get scientifically sound and robust results.

3.10. Strength and weaknesses

Life cycle assessment (LCA) provides a standardized and transparent method for determining reliable statements on environmental impacts. The adoption of the principles of ISO 14040/14044 for the LCSA prevents mere shifts (between life cycle stages/dimensions/countries/in the dimensions/countries/in the future) of undesirable effects. The benefits of combining LCA, LCC, and S-LCA include cost savings due to simultaneous data collection, mitigating the risk of double counting, establishing comparability by referring to the same functional unit, and increasing motivation for sustainable action on the part of the stakeholders involved. By producing three separate balances, the LCSA follows a reductionist logic. However, a description of the overall system cannot be made on the basis of the individual system elements and their properties, as this would not take into account the mechanisms and relationships within the system and relationships within the system remain unconsidered. Methodological difficulties arise especially with regard to the quantification of the effects and their meaningful linkage to the system and their meaningful linkage to a functional unit or the interpretation of the results especially since some indicators show a high variance at the local level. Further. there is a need for further research on the (1) identification of relevant process chains, (2) assessment of trade-offs within and between dimensions, (3) provision of a coherent set of impact indicators, (4) aggregation of different types of data, (5) interpretation of the types, (5) interpretation of results and development of an appropriate results format and standards for communication and dissemination of results, (6) Operationalization of normative aspects, (7) definition of product benefits, allocation and cut-off criteria, (8) development of criteria, (8) development of application tools (software programs, databases), and (9) implementation of case studies.

3.11. Standards and guidelines

There is no standard or guideline for LCSA for the moment; however, one of the objectives of the ORIENTING consortium is it to create and/or define such a general guidance (similar to what the PEF has done in the ecological field).

3.12. Use cases

Some use cases for LCSA and storage technologies are listed in Table G.2.

Table G.2. Use cases for LCSA and (hybrid) energy storage

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement N. 101036910

D4.2 – “Common base for environmental, techno-economic and socio-economic assessment to un-lock the potential applications for hybrid ES systems”

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Source	Aim	Technology	Hybrid y/n	Use case	Functional unit	Comment
Guo et al. [13]	To conduct a comprehensive analysis of conventional pumped hydro energy storage (CPHES) and underground pumped hydro energy storage UPHES, using life cycle sustainability assessment (LCSA)	Conventional and underground pumped hydro energy storage	n	Electrical energy storage		The results show that CPHES has better performance in economy and environment than UPHES because of the economies of scale, while the UPHES has better performance in social sustainability impact because of the absence of stages of excavation and backfilling
Vogt-Gwerder et al. [14]	To assess the sustainability of meeting electricity and heating needs in off-grid homes	Lead acid batteries and Li Ion batteries	n	Meeting the household's electricity and heating need	1 kWh of electricity and 1 MJ of heat	The paper presents a combined Life-Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA) and Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) approach
Guo et al. [15]	This study aims at developing a life cycle sustainability decision-making framework for the prioritization of electrochemical energy storage under uncertainties by combining multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) method and life cycle sustainability assessment	Electrochemical energy storage	n	Electrical energy storage		
Amini Toosi et al. [16]	This study proposes a streamlined LCSA Machine learning-based optimization model applicable to the design process of new buildings and Energy Retrofit Measures	Energy storage systems (in a housing context)	n	Energy storage systems in housing context		This paper proposes a new comprehensive LCSA model to be integrated into the design process of new buildings and energy refurbishment scenarios of existing ones. The proposed model consists of sets of mathematic equations to describe LCSA pillars of buildings, including Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Life Cycle Costing (LCC), and Social Life Cycle Assessment (SLCA) as the intermediate indices.

4. EXTENDED MULTI-REGIONAL INPUT OUTPUT ANALYSIS (EMRIO)

4.1. Synonyms / other related methods

Environmental Input-Output (EIO), (EEIO), environmentally extended multiregional input-output (EE MRIO), Multi-Regional Input-Output Analysis (MRIOA), environmentally extended (EE) input– output (IO) analysis

4.2. Assessment Level

Table G.3. Assessment Level of EMRIO

Discipline	Scope
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Social Sciences and Humanities	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Country / Region
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input type="checkbox"/> Company / Organization
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Economic sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Process
<input type="checkbox"/> Natural sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Product/Service
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Environmental sciences	<input type="checkbox"/> System
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sector

4.3. Short description

Multi-Regional Input-Output (MRIO) analysis is a macroeconomic tool that tracks financial flows between countries’ major economic sectors. MRIO approaches can be extended from pure economic flows to estimate sustainability impacts (i.e., employment creation, environmental footprints, and social risks) by incorporating data from environmental, socioeconomic, and social accounts at the sector level.

4.4. Scope

Extended MRIO models can be used for the analysis of the sustainability impacts of any given investment. It has been extensively applied to the assessment of sustainability impacts of products [17], and technologies [18] but also, to the assessment of sustainability impacts of investments [19], the footprint of countries [20] and the impacts of trade [21].

4.5. Methodology

The input-output framework consists of a system of tables that serve as an accounting tool for economic analysis, since they make it possible to measure and describe the productive interrelationships in one or several economies, including the links that arise from the transactions between them. The symmetric Input-output table (IOT) is a matrix that captures the output of an economy in a given year. It describes how the total supply (total resources) equals the total demand (output). The IOT describes, in columns, the monetary value of products that a sector needs from the rest of the sectors to obtain its total production (inputs); whereas rows show the distribution in monetary values of the production of a sector over the rest of the sectors (outputs). The IOT comprises

two main components, the inter-industry flows, or transaction matrix, which describes the flows from sector i to sector j , and the final demand. The transaction matrix Z thus collects the intersectoral transactions of intermediate consumption, which are intermediate goods and services that will be further processed by other sectors [22]. Final demand includes purchases of finished goods and services, ready for use or consumption, that the different economic agents (households, companies, non-profit associations, government) acquire from the different productive sectors, as well as exports to the rest of the world. The added value (VA) row shows the remuneration of the productive factors (labour, capital, taxes) that each sector requires to produce. Multi-regional input-output tables (MRIOT) make the international trade of intermediate goods and services endogenous, capturing inter-sectoral and interregional relations (see Figure G.3).

Figure G.3. IOT and MRIOT structure. Source: Banacloche et al [23]

The equation at the core of input-output analysis is the following:

$$X = (I - A)^{-1}Y \tag{4.1}$$

where X is the total output of an economy, $(I-A)^{-1}$ is the Leontief's inverse matrix, I is the identity matrix and A is the technical coefficients matrix (obtained by dividing the intermediate consumption matrix Z by the output X). Y is the final demand of the economy.

An exogenous boost in final demand creates ripple effects in the production process and total effects include direct and indirect effects, being direct effects related to the demand requirements for the project and indirect effects those inputs necessary to satisfy the direct demand. The multiplier effect gives information about the total stimulation produced from direct effects and the Leontief's inverse matrix acts as a multiplier of production.

This methodology has been extended to cover not only economic interlinkages between sectors, but also sustainability impacts (e.g. value added and employment, emissions, social risks), by adding vectors describing specific impacts per monetary unit produced in each economic sector. These impacts can be calculated by the following expression:

$$F = \hat{f} \cdot (I - A)^{-1} \cdot Y \quad (4.2)$$

Where F is the total socioeconomic/environmental effect, f is the socioeconomic/environmental vector (i.e. direct value added/employment/ CO_2 emissions per output unit), and Y vector is final demand.

While extending the model is theoretically easy, it requires lots of data in practice. There are several extended MRIO tables that have been developed and can be used for the analysis.

4.6. Dimensions and Indicators

Extended MRIO can be used to simultaneously assess different dimensions of sustainability. There are many different types and forms of indicators, and the number of indicators within each dimension is limited by the available extension vectors. In the case of the socio-economic dimension, value-added and employment generation are usually the indicators used. As for the environmental dimension, the available extension vectors are commonly used to estimate global warming impacts but also other environmental impacts categories such as acidification, eutrophication, photochemical ozone formation, diseases caused by respiratory inorganics, land use, water use and water scarcity, resource use: energy carriers and resource use: mineral and metals and others [24]. As for the social dimension, there are several indicators that can be used ranging from human rights to gender equality and from qualitative to quantitative indicators [18]. Finally, some authors have also used extended MRIO to analyze dependence and governance covering the potential risks associated with a diversified portfolio of suppliers from countries with various levels of governance [25].

4.7. Applications in the field of (hybrid) energy storage

Use case of MRIO analysis of storage technologies are scarce in literature. Examples have been found for batteries and hydrogen production.

4.8. Data availability

The main MRIO databases are the World Input-Output database (WIOD)², Eora Global MRIO³, EXIOBASE⁴, Global Trade Analysis Project (GTAP)⁵, and the Inter-Country Input-Output Tables of the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (ICIO-OECD)⁶. Many of these databases have time series and integrate their own satellite accounts correctly harmonized with their structures. The selection of the best database to use depends on the concrete aim of the research, being EXIOBASE best suited for sustainability analysis due to its powerful environmental extension while GTAP is more oriented to the application of computable general equilibrium models. The use of different MRIO databases may lead to different for the same indicator, such as GHG emissions [26].

EXIOBASE3 is one of the most used MRIOT for sustainability assessment. It consists of an MRIOT constructed for 44 countries and five Rest of the World regions (RoW), disaggregated into 163 industries and covering a period of 17 years (1995–2011). EXIOBASE has also many extension vectors (vector f) covering socioeconomic and environmental impacts. EXIOBASE provides data on industry-specific air emissions data for 27 pollutants, water use and consumption, material consumption data (179 crops, seven forestry and four fishery items, two crop residues, and grazing), 12 metal ores, eight industrial and construction minerals, and nine fossil fuels), land use data, waste production and use, and several socioeconomic indicators.

In some MRIO extensions, the social pillar is integrated by combining the MRIOT with the Social Hotspot Database (SHDB)⁷. The SHDB quantifies social risks for every country-specific sector. It contains a wide variety of social indicators mainly based on public data from institutions such as the International Labor Organization (ILO), World Bank (WB) and other organizations that periodically gather large volumes of social data.

For the determination of the Y vector, it is essential to gather detailed cost data of all the components of the technology under analysis including the following:

- 1) location of the investment: identify the host country/region
- 2) detailed cost breakdown of the components and services required as final goods to deploy the technology at both, investment and operation and maintenance stages

² <https://www.rug.nl/ggdc/valuechain/wiod/>

³ <https://worldmrio.com/>

⁴ <https://www.exiobase.eu/>

⁵ <https://www.gtap.agecon.purdue.edu/>

⁶ <https://www.oecd.org/sti/ind/inter-country-input-output-tables.htm>

⁷ <http://www.socialhotspot.org/>

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- 3) allocate the cost breakdown to the MRIOT most representative sectors
- 4) components' origin: if there are imported final goods or services, they should be identified to allocate the correspondent countries
- 5) techno-economic aspects (lifespan, discount rate, exchange rate, inflation rate) are also necessary to those costs that persist in time more than a year

Although it can be assumed that the investment can be done within a year, the operation and maintenance costs are expected to be undertaken during several years. Bringing these flows to current monetary units (present value) is needed. Collected data need to be brought to the selected MRIO format.

4.9. Reporting

There are no standards for reporting in MRIO. General standards for transparency and traceability of used data and modelling approach should apply.

4.10. Strength and weaknesses

MRIO analysis provide a very systemic overview of the origin and destination of final and intermediate products and is especially well suited to analyze the characteristics and role of global value chains. Additionally, IO models have the advantage of incorporating processes that would otherwise not be captured by process based LCA. These processes include a wide range of services (renting of machinery or EPC, technical consulting, and project management). Additionally, IO avoids double counting since the input-output tables are based on the principle of symmetry and show a balanced picture of the economic inputs and outputs in which the economy consists of representing the interconnections between economic sectors to satisfy the demand of commodities and the provision of services [27]. This avoids the need for drawing system boundaries.

Thanks to environmental satellite accounts, EMRIO analysis allows the quantification of environmental impacts along the whole value chain. Another advantage of the use of MRIOT is that there are satellite accounts for socioeconomic and social impacts that allow the analysis of the economic and social dimensions of sustainability. This approach allows for simultaneously analysing the three social, economic, and environmental dimensions [18]. It can even be extended with additional analysis such as geopolitics and security of supply issues [25].

MRIO analysis has some limitations that are summarized in the following. Sectorial aggregation is one of the most important limitations. IO tables offer a simplified overview of an economy classified in a limited number of sectors. In the case of too heterogeneous sectors, the values reported in the MRIOT, and the associated environmental accounts do not correctly reflect a particular process or product. Other potential weaknesses for environmental assessment depending on the MRIO model are [28] the lack of updated data, the use of monetary units (uncertainties subject to price fluctuations and inhomogeneity), insufficient handling of waste treatment, the use of fixed technical coefficients that

makes economies of scale impossible, the exclusion of capital investments and a limited number of environmental indicators.

Although these limitations are not negligible, the advantages of the input-output model outweigh its flaws. The level of sectoral disaggregation that it provides, the measurement of intersectoral links, its extensions and applications (structural breakdown, impact analysis, value chains, environmental and socioeconomic impacts), confer usefulness to the model, which is currently widely used. Input-output analysis is unique for analysing global value chains, capturing the role of international trade in a context of increasing globalization and fragmentation of production [29].

One way to avoid the aggregation problem is disaggregating the sectors into different subsectors, corresponding more precisely to the different commodities. However, higher disaggregation is challenging both in terms of data collection and numerical complexity.

Hybrid approaches between Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and MRIO have also been proposed in the literature in order to circumvent the lack of technical detail of MRIO. There are different ways of hybridizing and they have been grouped into four categories [30] i) tiered hybrid analysis [31], ii) path exchange hybrid analysis (PXC) [32], iii) matrix augmentation (or IO-based LCA) [33] and iv) integrated hybrid analysis [34].

Table G.4. Strengths and weaknesses of MRIO

Strength	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allows the analysis of the global value chains capturing the role of international trade • Includes processes usually not included in process based (mainly services and cut-off processes) • The extended versions allow the simultaneous analysis of three social, economic, and environmental dimensions of sustainability • It can even be extended with additional analysis such as geopolitics and security of supply issues 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High sectorial aggregation • Lack of updated data • Use of monetary units (uncertainties subject to price fluctuations and inhomogeneity) • Insufficient handling of waste treatment • Use of fixed technical coefficients that makes economies of scale impossible • Exclusion of capital investments • Limited number of environmental indicators.

4.11. Standards and guidelines

There is no standard or guideline for MRIO analysis. In their well-known book “Input-Output Analysis: Foundations and Extensions”, Miller and Blair [35] provide an essential reference for input-output analysis that reflects the most important developments and applications in the field.

4.12. Use Cases

Some use cases for MRIO and storage technologies are available in Table G.5.

D4.2 – “Common base for environmental, techno-economic and socio-economic assessment to un-lock the potential applications for hybrid ES systems”

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Table G.5. Use cases for MRIO and (hybrid) energy storage

Source	Aim	Technology	Hybrid y/n	Use case	Functional unit	Comment
Sanfelix et al. [36]	Analysis of environmental and economic impacts	Lithium based energy storage system	n	Battery electric vehicle	1 ESS of a 150,000 km lifetime for EV applications	
Cobas-Flores et al. [37]	Analysis of environmental and economic impacts	Lead acid batteries	n	Battery for automobiles	\$10 million spending	
Cantono et al. [38]	Analysis of environmental impacts	Hydrogen	n	Fuel cell vehicles		
Hienuki [39]	Environmental and Socio-Economic Analysis	Hydrogen	n	Fuel cell vehicles		

5. MULTI-CRITERIA DECISION ANALYSIS (MCDA)

The section on MCDA is based on the work of Ref. [40–44] with a focus on energy storage.

5.1. Synonyms / other related methods

Multi-criteria decision making (MCDM), Decision aid methods, Multi-Attribute Decision making (MADM)

5.2. Assessment Level

Table G.6. Assessment Level of MCDA

Discipline	Scope
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Social Sciences and Humanities	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Country / Region
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering	Company / Organisation
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Economic sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Process
<input type="checkbox"/> Natural sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Product/Service
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Environmental sciences	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> System
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sector

5.3. Short description

MCDA is considered as aid for decision making, helping to organize available information, identify the relation of alternatives and to explore stakeholders' own perceptions and needs [45]. MCDA methods allow it to consider different criteria or indicators simultaneously, to quantify and integrate normative preferences of stakeholders and make their influence on the results visible. Methods within MCDA concentrate on problems with discrete decision spaces where a set of decision alternatives has already been predetermined. In general, MCDA problems can include m alternatives which are evaluated on n criteria which can be expressed in a grouped decision matrix as follows [46]:

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \text{Criteria } C_1 \dots C_n \\
 \text{(Weights } w_1 \dots w_n) \\
 \text{Alternatives } A_1 \dots A_m
 \end{array}
 \begin{array}{l}
 x_{ij} \dots \text{Performance of the } j\text{-th of the } i\text{-th alternative} \\
 w_j \dots \text{weight of criteria } j \\
 n \text{ is the number of criteria} \\
 m \text{ is the number of alternatives}
 \end{array}$$

$$X = \begin{matrix} A_1 \\ \vdots \\ A_m \end{matrix} \begin{pmatrix} x_{11} & \dots & x_{1n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ x_{m1} & \dots & x_{mn} \end{pmatrix}_{m \times n}$$

Figure G.4: Example for a decision matrix (based on [46])

5.4. Scope

There are several MCDA methods available that are suitable for different scopes. Depending on the type, they allow to consider both quantitative and qualitative decision variables from different

sustainability dimensions. To carry out an MCDA, the modeler has to identify the stakeholders, the emergency of the decision, different alternatives, consequences, criteria quality and quantity of information [47]. Recommendations stemming from MCDA related to energy storage technologies are dependent on e.g. the grid or heat system service(s) aimed to be provided as well as a selection or combinations of suitable storage alternatives to cover these and the targeted stakeholder group. This makes problem structuring in the area of (hybrid) energy storage challenging. In general, decision making in the field of energy storage is shaped by many open questions regarding business models, ownership, changing energy markets and regulations as well as technology performance [48]. The scope of an MCDA can vary strongly, covering e.g., decision making in a company or governmental decision on a district, regional or national level. Also, it can be part of the development of new storage technologies by providing aid in the selection of suitable materials or in the case of hybrid storage systems for the combination of storage systems.

5.5. Methodology

Generally spoken, MCDA represents approaches that enable integrated assessments by handling individual indicators and criteria in a comprehensive manner, considering interrelations among them as well as different degrees of importance they might have [49]. MCDA can be schematized into two phases which are by nature overlapping and cannot be separated sharply from each other. These two phases can, but must not be subdivided as follows [47]:

Construction phase: i) Definition of goals, scopes & alternatives ii) Identification and selection of criteria and choice of suitable MADM method(s) iii) Creation of stakeholder interface.

Exploitation phase: i) Criteria performance measurement, ii) Criteria weights elicitation iii) Criteria aggregation iv) Comparison of results.

The construction phase starts by structuring the decision problem through the definition of the goal and the decision problem the study tries to solve. This structuring phase includes the selection of suitable methods, relevant alternatives, definition of corresponding evaluation criteria and their relation to each other (e.g., hierarchy). Most importantly, an interface needs to be created that allows to grasp preferences for different criteria from different stakeholders with different methods (e.g., a scale or pairwise comparison).

After this construction phase, the exploitation phase starts. Here, criteria weights are elicited, and the selected storage alternatives performance is calculated and made comparable with other alternatives (often named as aggregation or aggregation problem [50]. There are several methods available for weights elicitation and aggregation, among these the most suitable ones have to be chosen according to the goal and problem definition during construction phase [51]. Most MADM methods show high flexibility regarding the input, allowing to integrate a high variety of data typologies with various degrees of freedom into an assessment [49]. It is worth mentioning, that normalization methods have to be selected accordingly alongside with criteria that have different scales as these can have high impact on results. Some methods to be named are vector normalization, linear normalization, non-

monotonic normalization or logarithmic Normalization (LN) method [52], [53]. An overview of a general MCDA procedure is given in Figure G.5.

Figure G.5. Generalized MCDA approach based on [41]

Most important elements of the overall process of a MCDA referring to integrative assessment of energy technologies will be explained in the following:

5.6. Selection of alternatives, criteria, and methods

A minimum of two alternatives has to be compared with each other. The selection of alternatives should be seen as process with equal participation of the stakeholders. In general, the selection of alternatives should reflect seeking a way to ideally achieve previously defined goals [44]. For energy storage it is important to consider that performance of ESS (Energy Storage System) is highly dependent on the system design that is determined by a particular application and its requirements. It is thus recommended to refer to an application as a base for common system sizes/ designs using comparable storage capacities and e.g. energy to power (E/P) ratios for the technologies compared [41]. Wang and co-workers introduced, beside some basic selection principles, the following selection methods for criteria in sustainable energy decision making: Delphi method, Least mean square method, Minimax deviation method, and correlation coefficient method. In sub-section “Criteria and indicators” common criteria and indicators for ESS are presented. In order to indicate the relative importance of different criteria, weights need to be assigned to the criteria [46]. Depending on whether and to what extent stakeholders are to be included or not, different subjective and objective weighting methods as well as combinations can be applied for weights elicitation. After having determined the criteria weights, the ranking order of the different alternatives can be calculated using

aggregation procedures. Selecting a certain method for weighting and aggregation among others should be highlighted in any case, helpful and detailed sets of guidelines for MADM methods selection are provided in [47] and [54]. Most common methods are presented in sub-section “Methods for aggregation” and sub-section “Weighting methods”.

5.7. Criteria and Indicators

There are several criteria that can be used in frame of an MCDA for technology assessment. These can entail various indicators but mostly refer due to operationalization reasons to environmental, economic, technological and social dimensions. These dimensions are analyzed in depth in the corresponding input papers and the main guideline. However, it is important that selected criteria meet certain requirements: completeness, informativeness, non-redundancy, independence, decomposability. Use of vague or unstructured criteria should be avoided [55]. Additionally, a common language for criteria description should be used, avoiding further potential misinterpretations [56].

Economic indicators: These play an important role as the market success of an energy technology is highly determined by its economic performance [57], [58]. This comes in particular true for energy storage technologies which might be applied in comparable application areas to each other (e.g., CAES, PHS, etc.) or other flexibility options as demand response measures, electricity grid extension or gas turbine power plants. Here, up to now mainly economic drivers determine the implementation of an alternative against another one.

Environmental Criteria: Here often a life cycle perspective is used to determine the impact of different energy storage technologies. The life cycle includes production, use, and disposal or recycling of a product. They allow to quantify potential effects on the environment (e.g., land use, global warming, and eutrophication potential). Some work on these aspects has been carried out for e.g., battery systems [59–62], CAES [63] or PHS [64].

Technical criteria: Technical criteria directly influences environmental, social as well as the economic performance of an ESS. Often, efficiency, maturity and system life (in years or number of cycles) are named by most of the studies, wherein cycle lifetime is often considered as a significant factor for battery ESS [40], [65].

Social criteria: It is nowadays widely accepted that social aspects represent a crucial factor for the success or failure of a distinctive technology [66]. Social aspects as acceptance or trust are often addressed in the literature, but there are rarely any definitions given [67] and no approved theories available [68], making the identification of these types of criteria difficult.

Table G.7. Overview of the frequency of different criteria used for energy storage and corresponding MCDAs, based on [41]

Main Criteria	Sub Criteria	Daniel et al. (2012) [20]	Krause et al. (2012) [27], [80]	Barré et al. (2009) [81]	Ba et al. (2011) [85], [81]	Oguzturk et al. (2010) [87]	Raza et al. (2014) [28]	Wang et al. (2016) [89]	Rajeev et al. (2018) [93]	Pei et al. (2018) [92]	Yu et al. (2018) [95]	Cowan et al. (2019) [93]	Ba et al. (2017) [84]	Wang et al. (2018) [97]	6 sum
Social	Acceptance	1	1			2		1		1	1	1			8
	Other	1	4			1						1			7
Economic	Capital cost	1					1	1	1	1	1	1		1	4
	Cost (general)		1	1	1										7
	O&M cost	1	3			2		1	1	1	1	1		1	5
Technological	Other	1											1		8
	Efficiency	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1		1	11
	Maturity	1		1	1		1	1	1	1					6
	Lifetime	1					1	1	1	1		1			6
	Capacity	1						1	1		1	1			4
	Cycles					1		1							2
	Energy density						1	1	1	1					3
	Response time					1	1							1	3
Other	2	5	2	2	4	4	5	1		2		1	1	29	
Environmental	CO2 related		1		1	1		1	1	1	1		1		7
	Environmental	1	1				1	1	1	1		1		1	5
	Wildlife impacts	1	2			3									3
	Other	1												6	

5.8. Weighting methods

For the determination of criteria weights, the variance degree of criteria, the independency of criteria, and the subjective preference of the stakeholders are usually considered [46]. In order to account for the relative importance of different criteria, rank-order weighting methods are applied (see [46]). Weighting methods can be classified into three categories: subjective weighting methods (e.g., pair-wise comparison, AHP, SMART, SIMOS), objective weighting methods (e.g., entropy method, principal component analysis) and combinations (e.g., additive synthesis). While subjective weighting methods depend on the preferences of stakeholders only, objective weights are obtained based on the analysis of the initial data. In MCDM, there is a requirement to integrate the objective and subjective weights since the objective weighting methods ignore the stakeholders' experiences and the subjective weighting methods ignore the performance ratings of the alternatives with respect to different criteria [69]. An overview on common subjective and objective weighting methods can be found in Table G.8.

Table G.8. Overview of common weighting methods, based on [70].

Method	Ref.	Description
Subjective methods		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> criteria weights elicitation by using stakeholders' preferences reflect the judgments and knowledge of stakeholders
Pair-wise comparison	[70]	In the pair-wise comparison method, participants are asked to compare the importance of two criteria at a time and the relative importance is scored. The scales can be various, for example, a scale of 0 (equal importance) to 3 (absolutely more important) is commonly adopted. It does not allow to check the consistency of participants' preference.
AHP	[70], [71]	The AHP method builds on the pair-wise comparison model for determining the weights for every unique criterion and sub-criterion. The AHP concept basically allows the decision-makers to evaluate the importance of each selected criterion when compared to other criteria on a scale from 1 to 9, ranging from 'same importance' (1) to 'absolutely more important' (9).

Simple multiattribute rating technique - SMART	[72] [73]	With SMART, the weights are elicited in two steps (1. Ranking the importance of the changes in the attributes and 2. Making ratio estimates of the relative importance of each attribute). Alternatively, direct assignment of importance weights on a 0-100 scale can be carried out.
Objective methods		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • criteria weights elicitation by using measured data and information • reflect the difference degree of data and information
Entropy method	[70]	The relative importance of each criterion is assessed according to the difference between the observed values of each criterion. If the variance between these schemes to one criterion is smaller, this criterion will be less important in the evaluation.

5.9. Methods for aggregation

MADM methods, i.e. methods to determine preference orders of alternatives, can be separated into elementary methods, single or unique synthesizing methods and outranking methods [46], [47], [74]. Each of these methods has different theoretical and technical properties that can be (but must not be) divided into three aspects; i) input capabilities, ii) preference elicitation and modeling, and iii) the aggregation procedure [47]. A detailed overview on the respective methods and their calculations can be found in the corresponding sources. It should be kept in mind that some of these methods are fully compensating (e.g., single synthesizing methods), some are partially compensating (e.g., PROMETHEE) while some are non-compensating (e.g. ELECTRE). Compensation in this sense means that bad performance for some criteria can be offset by good performance for other criteria [49].

Table G.9. Overview of common MADM methods, their description, utility (pros + and cons -), and exemplary applications in the field of energy (inspired by [46–49], [75], [76] and based on [41], [44])

Method	Ref.	Description	Utility	Applications*
Elementary methods		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • straightforwardness and minimum calculation efforts • non-preference information methods without decision maker (e.g., dominance, maximin, maximax, lexicographic) • multi-attribute information methods with decision maker input as weighted sum method (WSM) or weighted product method [46]. • do not consider trade-offs or potential inconsistencies of attributed weights to different criteria [77] 		
Weighted sum method - WSM	[78], [79]	Simple linear additive models, where weights are multiplied with the performance measure of an alternative to calculate final scores. The WSM based approaches use simple, ordinal scales (1-10 and typically Likert scale 1-5) for weight attribution.	+simple computation, transparent / -only basic estimations, - only single preference	Selection of renewable energy sources [80]
Compensating methods	[46], [47], [81]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • assign a utility value to each alternative • offer a total preorder of given alternatives • partial utility values (attributes) are first determined, which together form the total utility value of an alternative. • total utility value of an alternative 		
Multi-Attribute Utility Theory - MAUT	[76], [82]	In MAUT utility functions are defined to convert performance values of different alternatives considered. on, e.g., a 0-10 scale. An advantage of the method is its simplicity as well as robustness.	+ simple computation / - Difficult to get precise information from stakeholders	energy planning [83]

Multi-attribute Value Theory - MAVT	[82]	MAVT is comparable to MAUT but also takes into account the importance of criteria weights. This is often carried out by direct ratings	+simple computation / - Difficult to assign utility functions	Electricity generation (power expansion alternatives) [84]
Simple Multi-Attribute Rating - SMART	[75]	Different way to apply MAUT through the use of weighted linear averages, which give close approximations to utility functions	+ Simple computation / - weights not clearly related	Renewable energy deployment decisions [85]
Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution - TOPSIS	[86]	TOPSIS is a method built on a simple principle: the selected best alternative should have the shortest (Euclidian) distance from the positive ideal solution in a geometrical sense while it has the longest distance from the negative ideal solution.	+ simple computation / - does not consider difference between neg. & pos. values	Selection of sustainable electricity generation [87]
Analytical Hierarchy Process - AHP	[88], [89]	The decision problem is structured within a hierarchy. At the top is the general objective (e.g., choice of technology or policy). Criteria are set below this goal and can be further decomposed into sub-criteria; alternatives are at the bottom of this hierarchy. Within AHP, stakeholders attribute an individual preference to each criterion by pairwise comparisons (in total $(n(n-1)/2)$).	+Simple computation, consistency threshold / - interdependence of objectives	Electricity generation (H2-natural gas) [90]
Best-Worst Method - BWM	[91], [92]	Based on pairwise comparisons (2n-3). a) a set of criteria is determined, b) best and worst criteria are identified; c) determination of preferences of the best criterion in relation to the other criteria (1-9 scale), d) the same is conducted for the worst criterion in relation to all other criteria; e) optimal weights have to be determined by minimizing the maximum absolute differences (e.g., through linear programming).	+ less comparisons as in AHP / - no consistency measurements	Supplier selection [93] Energy efficiency in buildings [94]
Multicriteria Optimization and Compromise Solution - VIKOR	[95–97]	VIKOR determines the compromise ranking-list, the compromise solution, and the weight stability intervals for preference stability of the compromise solution obtained with the initial (given) weights. It focuses on ranking and selecting of alternatives in the presence of conflicting criteria based on the “closeness” to the “ideal” solution.	+ adapted to solve quite different energy problems and tolerant to deviations of values in the assessment period / - narrow experience in the field of energy	Selection of a renewable energy investment project [81] Optimal combination of renewable energy resources in Columbia [98]**
Outranking methods		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • seek to eliminate alternatives that are particularly dominating. • Alternatives are compared in pairs across all evaluation criteria using simplified preference functions. • the weighted aggregation of the preference matrices for each evaluation criterion results in an overall preference matrix, which allows the alternatives to be ranked according to their suitability. • weak preferences and incomparability can be represented do not allow full compensation of criteria values possible mainly to create transparency in the decision process, understanding of the problem, 		

ELimination and Choice Expressing REality ELECTRE	[54], [99], [100]	This method is based on two main procedures: i) a multiple criteria aggregation procedure including the construction of outranking relation to compare each pair of actions; ii) result are then chosen, ranked or sorted. Outranking relations are based on concordance, dis-concordance indexes, and threshold values	+ Rankings are validated / - complex to apply, less versatile	Selection of wind energy location [101]
Preference Ranking Organization METHod for Enrichment of Evaluations - PROMETHEE	[56], [65]	The method is comparable to ELECTRE but uses preference functions that allow it to measure difference between two alternatives related to any criteria. Six criteria functions are used to do so. Two pre-orders of alternatives are provided; based on ingoing and outgoing flows. Rankings are based on net flow yields	+ considers interdependency of criteria / - complex method, computation efforts high	Characterization generation technology, Ranking of Biomass - feedstocks [102]

*Retrieved from [76] if not indicated differently

**Retrieved from [96]

5.10. Sensitivity and robustness analysis

Sensitivity analyses in MADM are typically carried out by i) changing criteria weights or ii) varying performance measurement (e.g., cost values, scores) [49]. Both procedures enable the determination of (weight) stability intervals, preserving the ranking [103]. In the first category, authors observe the impact on varying weights on final ranks. Sensitivity analyses in the second category analyze impacts of varying performance measurement data on final ranking using constant or equal weights. In order to assure robustness of rankings, iii) addition or deletion of alternatives or criteria and iv) comparing resulting rankings using a different MADM method can be carried out. Both robustness checks might lead to so-called rank reversals due to the structure of the decision model [49]. Including the latter can be considered the optimum, it might often be unfeasible for most MCDA studies due to the high time effort though [41]. In any case, sensitivity and robustness analyses allow it to better understand the results and potential implications related to decision problems.

5.11. Applications in the field of (hybrid) energy storage

As explained before, MCDA can be applied to various decision problems considering multiple dimensions related to sustainability. Some examples for application of MCDA in the field of energy storage are:

- related to the development, for e.g., materials selection [104]
- manufacturing of energy storage technologies, e.g., selection of suitable production sites or raw material provision [104]
- Combination of different energy storage technologies for hybridization
- Dimensioning of energy storage technologies considering multiple criteria (power and capacity)

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- Energy storage project evaluation [82]
- Selection of suitable energy storage alternatives for specific application fields [42].

5.12. Data availability

Several qualitative and quantitative methods are used and (in most cases) combined to carry out an MCDA, in particular to quantify the used criteria (e.g. global warming potential or cost). There are several ways to gather data for this purpose:

- Literature review (strong to low dependency)
- Use of expert ratings for evaluation. (e.g., to rate the degree of social acceptance, environmental impacts)
- Use of own estimations (e.g., deductive reasoning for indexing of environmental impacts)
- Use of own calculations for criteria quantification (e.g., LCA or cost calculation)

Considering the application field for evaluating different ESS can be a decisive factor. Most ESS have very different cost structures and environmental impacts depending e.g. on their energy to power ratio (E/P ratio) [105] for electricity as storage service, or temperature level for thermal energy storage which is determined by the application [106], [107]. This has to be considered when data is used as an input for a MCDA. In particular, methods as e.g., LCA and LCC and social assessments are time and data demanding which is addressed in detail in the corresponding input documents.

5.13. Reporting

There is not standard for reporting of MCDA results. However, there are recommendations provided by Baumann et al [41] of how to present results. In case of the provision of rankings, these should be set into context where they are applicable (application case, consulted stakeholders, potential shortcomings). Most importantly, a fully transparent MCDA process increases the degree of acceptance of stakeholders related to given recommendations. It is important to not give the impression that analyzed energy storage options are mutually exclusive as these are often implemented conjointly in the real world [50]. One example could be thermal storage in combination with battery storage for multiple service provision [108]. Rankings should always be seen as only indicative and can be interpreted in different ways [50].

5.14. Strengths and weaknesses

Talukder und Hipel 2021 [109] summarize in their review on MCDA for Sustainability Assessment that MCDA leads to sensible, justifiable and explainable decisions, helps to rank different options and to find the most desirable outcome, and is capable of considering a broad variety of conflicting but

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associated criteria. Nevertheless, MCDA also has some weaknesses that should not be ignored. In Table G.10, strengths and weaknesses of MCDA are listed.

Table G.10. Overview of S&W based on [43]

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can capture the multi-dimensionality of the effects of numerous decision problems • weights can be adjusted in the analysis process and thus the influence of changes in the weight on a decision process can be determined. • early involvement of stakeholders in the development of criteria or the determination of weights of criteria increases the gain in knowledge on the one hand, and on the other hand increases the acceptance of the stakeholders towards the final result 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • criteria should be independent of each other which is difficult to implement. • Determining individual utility functions can be related to high efforts for data collection. • Uncertainties can arise in respect to preferences, weighting and aggregation of criteria based on subjective values, data availability and quality. • requires high knowledge and experience with evaluations. • Stakeholders need skills to deal with the results • Data collection can be challenging • evaluation of the data represents a considerable additional expenditure •

5.15. Standards and guidelines

There are no standards available for MCDA, rather a set of literature that provides aid for the development and realization of the same. Some helpful sources are named in the following (sorted by year):

- Guitouni und J.-M. Martel, „Tentative guidelines to help choosing an appropriate MCDA method“, *Eur. J. Oper. Res.*, Bd. 109, Nr. 2, S. 501–521, Sep. 1998, doi: 10.1016/S0377-2217(98)00073-3. [47]
- P. Goodwin, *Decision analysis for management judgment*, 3rd ed. Hoboken, NJ: Wiley, 2004.[89]
- J. Figueira, S. Greco, M. Ehrgott, und C. Henggeler-Antunes, Hrsg., *Multiple criteria decision analysis: state of the art surveys*. New York, NY: Springer, 2005. [110]
- J. Wang, Y.-Y. Jing, C.-F. Zhang, und J.-H. Zhao, „Review on multi-criteria decision analysis aid in sustainable energy decision-making“, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, Bd. 13, Nr. 9, S. 2263–2278, Dez. 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2009.06.021.[46]

- M. Cinelli, S. R. Coles, K. Kirwan, “Analysis of the potentials of multi criteria decision analysis methods to conduct sustainability assessment”, *Ecological Indicators* 46, 138-148, 2014 [49]
- A. Kumar, B. Sah, A. R. Singh, Y. Deng, X. He, P. Kumar, R.C. Bansal, “A review of multi criteria decision making (MCDM) towards sustainable renewable energy development”, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, Volume 69, March 2017, Pages 596-609 [75]
- M. Baumann, M. Weil, J. F. Peters, N. Chibeles-Martins, und A. B. Moniz, „A review of multi-criteria decision making approaches for evaluating energy storage systems for grid applications“, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, Bd. 107, S. 516–534, Juni 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2019.02.016. [41]
- Cinelli M, Kadziński M, Miebs G, Gonzalez M, Słowiński R. Recommending multiple criteria decision analysis methods with a new taxonomy-based decision support system. *European Journal of Operational Research*. 2022;302:633-51. [111]

5.16. Use cases

There are several use cases for MCDA on energy storage available that have been analyzed in detail in Baumann et al. 2019 [41]. In the following, some examples are provided in Table G.11

Table G.11. Use cases of MCDA

Source	Aim	Technology	Hybrid y/n	Use case	Functional unit	Comment
Daim et al. [112]	Choice of reliable and cost-effective storage option for investor-owned or public utilities	PHS CAES NaS	No	Balancing reserves for wind	Several dimensions, with 13 criteria	AHP, Fuzzy Delphi
Ren et al [113]	Prioritization of sustainable energy storage technologies	PHS CAES Lead Acid Li-Ion Flywheel	No	No use case, general approach	7 different sustainability criteria	AHP, Non-Linear Fuzzy Prioritization IMADA is used to rank technologies
Murrant et al. [82]	Inform the Cornwall Council / Focus on existing storage projects in Cornwall UK	liquid air energy storage Battery storage + PV Thermal energy storage Battery storage with wave energy (wave hub) Power to gas Virtual battery sys	No	Existing projects / see source for details	7 different project related criteria	MAVT

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Baumann et al. [42]	Identify most suitable battery system for different applications	Lithium ion batteries Sodium Sulfur batteries Redox-Flow batteries Lead Acid battery	No	Evaluation of different applications Energy time shift Primary regulation Wind energy storage Distributed storage	4 Sustainability dimensions and 11 corresponding criteria	AHP+TOPSIS
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6. LINK TO CROSS TOPICS

6.1. Circularity

The circular economy (CE) is considered a sustainable economic system because of the reduction of use and recirculation of natural resources. However, it is important to a knowledge that a higher circularity does not ensure higher social, economic, and environmental sustainability. There are several ways in which circularity concepts can be integrated in sustainability assessment. Up to now, most of the work has been devoted to circularity indexes or indicators and several metrics have been proposed. However, according to a Corona and co-workers [114], none of them are addressing the CE concept comprehensibly. This could lead to undesirable burden shifting from reduced material consumption to increased environmental, economic, or social impacts. Additional research is needed then to develop a holistic approach able to assess the sustainability impacts of CE strategies [115].

6.2. Acceptance

Nothing is more pivotal to the transformation of the energy system than public acceptance and this applies both to the development of new and unfamiliar energy technologies, and to new applications of existing ones [116]. Technological solutions to energy problems are often promoted without considering the social processes that affect their acceptance and use. These elements include both risks and opportunities [117], [118]. A correct approach to social acceptance of energy storage technologies would need to consider aspects such as public attitudes towards energy storage developments, levels of social trust on energy developers and regulators, presence of new ownership models of energy storage systems, opportunities for citizens and/or stakeholders to participate in public energy planning, and the realization of stakeholders and citizen engagement campaigns.

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STORAGE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE ECO-SYSTEM

D4.2 – “Common base for environmental, techno-economic and socio-economic assessment to un-lock the potential applications for hybrid ES (HES) systems”

Work Package 4 - Supporting the transition towards a climate neutral continent

Task 4.2 - Sustainability Assessments of Hybrid ES Technologies

Submission date: 30th April 2024

APPENDIX H. USE CASES SELECTION FOR SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT OF HYBRID ES SYSTEMS

Project Acronym	StoRIES
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PU

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

AC	Acidification
AEL	Alkaline water electrolysis
Al	Aluminium
BoP	Balance of Plant
CAPEX	Capital Expenditures
CCS	Carbon Capture and Storage
CED	Cumulative Energy Demand
CR	Central Receiver (Solar power plant)
CSP	Concentrated Solar Power
DC	Direct Current
ELECTREE	Elimination Et Choix Traduisant la REalité
EPC	Engineering, procurement, commissioning
ES	Energy Storage
ETS	Electricity Time Shift
Fe	Iron
FE	Freshwater Eutrophication
FLHs	Full Load Hours
GER	Global Energy Requirement
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GT	Gas Turbine
GVC	Global Value Chain

GWP	Global Warming Potential
HT	Human Toxicity
ILCD	International Reference Life Cycle Data System
IOA	Input-Output Analysis
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
LCoE	Levelized Cost of Electricity
LCOH	Levelized Cost of Hydrogen
LCSA	Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment
LFP	Lithium Iron Phosphate
LIB	Lithium-ion Battery
LMO	Lithium Manganese Oxide
LTO	Lithium Titanate Oxide
LU	Land Use
MACRS	Modified Accelerated Cost Recovery System
MCDA	Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis
ME	Marine Eutrophication
MRIO	Multiregional Input-Output Analysis
Na	Sodium
NCA	Nickel Cobalt Aluminium Oxide
NCM	Nickel Cobalt Manganese Oxide
NPV	Net Present Value
NRE	Non-renewable Energy Requirement

ODP	Ozone Depletion Potential
OPEX	Operational Expenditures
PEM	Polymer Exchange Membrane (fuel cell)
POF	Photochemical Ozone Formation
PR	Primary Regulation
PROMETHEE	Preference Ranking Organization METHod for Enrichment Evaluation
PT	Parabolic Through (Solar power plant)
PV	Photovoltaics
PVSC	Photovoltaics Self Consumption
RE	Renewable Energy Requirement
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
RS	Renewables Support
RTE	Round-trip Efficiency
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SHDB	Social Hotspots Database
S-LCA	Social Life Cycle Assessment
SOFC	Solid Oxide Fuel Cell
ST	Steam Turbine
TE	Terrestrial Eutrophication
TOPSIS	Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution
VRFB	Vanadium Redox Flow Batteries
VRLA	Valve-Regulated Lead-Acid
WACC	Weighted-Average Cost of Capital

D4.2 – “Common base for environmental, techno-economic and socio-economic assessment to un-lock the potential applications for hybrid ES systems”

PU

WRD	Water Resource Depletion
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1. USE CASES ON ECONOMIC SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT OF HYBRID ES TECHNOLOGIES

In line with anticipated micro and macro-economic benefits to support the sustainable development, economic sustainability has a major influence on the feasibility of energy storage (ES) projects. Hence, a use case selection of ES technology economic assessments is presented here. Particularly, the aim is to provide practical guidance for the economic assessments of hybrid energy storage technologies using various methods.

1.1. Use Case: Hybrid Energy Storage and Hydrogen Supply Based on Aluminium—a Multiservice Case for Electric Mobility and Energy Storage Services

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Year: 2022

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Storage Media	Aluminium
Delivered Energy	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Electricity <input type="checkbox"/> Heat <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fuels (Please specify: Hydrogen)
Technological Readiness Level (TRL)	<input type="checkbox"/> TRL 1-3 (Research) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TRL 4-6 (Development) <input type="checkbox"/> TRL 7-8 (Deployment)
Hybridization Level	<input type="checkbox"/> None <input type="checkbox"/> Material <input type="checkbox"/> Device <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> System
Storage technology classification	<input type="checkbox"/> Mechanical <input type="checkbox"/> Electrochemical <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Chemical <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (power plants, CSP) <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (buildings, district) <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (non-residential) <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (industrial) <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (solar, PV, wind)
Application field	<input type="checkbox"/> TSO <input type="checkbox"/> DSO <input type="checkbox"/> Private actors <input type="checkbox"/> Energy Supplier <input type="checkbox"/> Aggregator <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Industrial Actors <input type="checkbox"/> Power plant operator <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Industrial Clients <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Power plant operator incl. PtX
Storage duration	<input type="checkbox"/> Short-term <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mid-term <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Long-term
Services	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Generation support and bulk storage (minutes to hours) <input type="checkbox"/> Transmission infrastructure support (ramp-up, milliseconds or minutes) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Distribution infrastructure support (one or more hours) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Ancillary services <input type="checkbox"/> Behind-the-meter (>=100 kW) <input type="checkbox"/> Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G)
Key performance indicators (KPIs)	Levelized cost of electricity (LCoE) Levelized cost of hydrogen (LCoH)
Hybridization purpose	Increased storage volumetric energy density, supply duration, and on-site hydrogen supply.
Remarks	

1.1.1 Introduction

Climate change impacts and the need to reduce Earth's CO₂ budget have accelerated efforts for rapid decarbonization across all sectors. The energy supply sector, responsible for 73% of global greenhouse gas emissions, requires a shift towards sustainable energy technologies, particularly renewable

energies [1]. This transition has also increased the demand for sustainable energy storage technologies and carriers, in line with the integration of renewables into the grid [2]. Among all energy carriers, hydrogen (H₂) is considered as the most critical energy carrier as it has the highest gravimetric energy density. Nevertheless, high cost of electrolyzers and techno-economic -mainly due to very low volumetric energy density and high storage costs obstacles encountered for its use in Power-to-X context hasten its overall use [3]. Hence, diversifying the energy carriers and increasing distributed energy storage is vital for the power supply security. All these obstacles brought the use of metals as energy carriers again on the table since metals are energy carriers with high energy densities (both volumetric and gravimetric) [4]. Moreover, abundant metals such as aluminium (Al), and iron (Fe) are produced in large quantities with a long-term secured availability [5]. Herein, considering all the sustainable renewable energy carrier requirements of the future energy grid, an aluminium-based hybrid energy storage technology is proposed as a solution for supplying electric and H₂ demand of the mobility sector and providing additional flexibility to grid [6], [7]. The proposed system is evaluated from a techno-economic perspective for a refueling station and storage business case as presented.

1.1.2 Background – metals as combustibles

Besides metals being favorable electrochemical energy carriers, they can be considered as combustible fuels due to their high reactivity. In addition to that, once the metal is activated, they can be easily oxidized using both water and oxygen in the air as an oxidizer. As summarized in the given overview in Table H.1, some metals e.g., Al, Fe, and Na are compatible energy carriers considering also the earth abundance and European supply security concerns in addition to energy densities [8].

Table H.1 Energy density and supply aspects of reactive metals and semi-metals in the periodic table.

Energy Carrier	Gravimetric Energy Density [kWh kg ⁻¹]	Gravimetric Energy Density [kWh kg ⁻¹]	Earth abundance	Secured Supply
B	16.4	38.3	-	+
Li	12.7	6.8	-	-
Al	8.6	23.5	+	+
Fe	2.1	16.7	+	+
Na	5.9	5.7	+	+
Mg	7.3	12.6	+	-
Si	9.1	22.5	+	-

As can be concluded from the given table above, Al demonstrates very motivating properties both in energy density and supply constraints as it can be easily recycled. Additionally, it is highly reactive and can be oxidized through the following oxidation reactions:

The first reaction refers to direct oxidation of Al metal, and the second reaction expresses the wet-combustion path where it delivers 4.2 kWh kg_{Al}⁻¹ heat and 0.111 kg H₂ (4.4 kWh kg_{Al}⁻¹ heat equivalent). Though, the latter is more interesting for the hybrid energy storage use case where the designed business case will benefit from the H₂ carrier feature of Al. In this study, an Al combustion plant presented using solid Al particles and steam for oxidation. The released heat and H₂ are then used for electricity and H₂ supply for mobility and the grid via the Al combustion plant situated in a refueling

station. The business case is based on a sector coupling between Al producers and refueling station operators where Al is purchased from the producers (with a reduced prices) and combustion product Al_2O_3 is returned to producers for Al again through Hall-Héroult process. In order to evaluate the business case a techno-economic evaluation model is developed based on the explained methodology in the following.

1.1.3 Methodology

1.1.3.1. Technical Design and Evaluation Methodology

A OD process simulation model is developed for simulating an Al combustion system using a steam turbine for reactor cooling and a solid-oxide fuel cell (SOFC) which is connected to the system for the utilization of H_2 and generating electricity with a design power of $\sim 4 MW_e$. In addition to that, a heat recovery section is thermally integrated to heat the compressed air required for the fuel cell to turbine to utilize the excessive unreacted H_2 in the SOFC. Remaining waste heat is then used for preheating the feedwater as described in detail in [8]. Considering the designed business case, previous system design is modified to enable partial load operation of the SOFC and enable use of H_2 on demand. A H_2 compression section is also integrated to the system to allow flexible hybrid operation. (See Figure H.1)

Figure H.1 Simplified Al wet combustion plant layout showing main energy and material streams [7].

The developed system is then further optimized to determine efficient partial SOFC operation loads to maintain the operation temperature. Finally, the technical performance of the system is evaluated as presented.

1.1.3.2. Economic Evaluation

The provided system design is divided into its counterparts in order to estimate the required capital investment for building such a system. Design specification of each system component is obtained

from the process simulation model as far as possible. The potential variations on the equipment specifications based on commercially available process equipment are also considered as uncertainties. Using learning curves, the equipment cost of the system is estimated as explained in detail in [9]. Furthermore, installation cost, engineering, procurement and construction (EPC) costs and working capital are estimated using Guthrie’s method [9]. The estimated direct and indirect investments costs hence constitute the depreciable capital expenditures (CAPEX) of the system. Considering an investment lifespan of 20 years, the estimated CAPEX is then depreciated using Modified Accelerated Cost Recovery System (MACRS) to determine the annual depreciation cost. For estimating the operational expenditures (OPEX), fixed and variable OPEX are classified based on the defined operation aspects in the technical design. These are fixed and variable O&M costs, fuel cost (net Al price) and transportation. Noting that, the net Al price refers to deducting Al_2O_3 economic value from the Al price as it is returned to the Al producers. Since it is a hybrid energy storage case, varying operation conditions (only electricity supply, or simultaneous electricity and H_2 supply) allocation of the CAPEX and OPEX needs a particular allocation to quantify the cost of the delivered energy. To do so, capital weighted cost allocation method is implemented in the economic evaluation to consider expenditures based on the operation modes. Consequently, with the aid of estimated CAPEX and implemented OPEX estimation methodology in the model levelized cost of electricity and H_2 (LCOE and LCoH, respectively) are estimated across varying full load hours (FLHs) and scenarios. For a more detailed understanding on the economic model, the readers are referred to the published research article. (see [7])

1.1.4 Results

1.1.5 Technical Evaluation Results

The defined system is simulated under variable operating modes and two partial operation modes are determined as optimized partial SOFC loads 65% and 80%. In other words, the SOFC below 65% partial load proves unstable efficiency dynamics due to non-uniform temperature distribution in the stacks. As limiting element is the SOFC, considering efficiency and hybridization constraints other energy conversion equipment (steam turbine (ST) and gas turbine (GT) are also optimized accordingly. Technical performance evaluation at different partial operation modes is summarized in Table H.2.

Table H.2 Energy density and supply aspects of reactive metals and semi-metals in the periodic table.

SOFC Part Load	SOFC [kW]	GT [kW]	ST [kW]	H_2 Compressor [kW]	Total Power [MW]	H_2 Flow Rate [$kg\ h^{-1}$]
100%	2,000	1,064	0.0	0.0	3.9	-
80%	1,600	916	53.2	53.2	3.1	28
65%	1,300	884	89	89	2.6	46.8

Therefore, based on these limits the system can be operated efficiently providing a certain flexibility depending on the H_2 production rate and electricity demand. For the defined operating points, the Al-to-Power efficiency (η_{Al-P}) values are determined in the range of 54-81% decreasing in parallel with the SOFC partial load. However, the overall Al-to-X efficiency (η_{Al-X}) of the system increases up to 93%. Meaning, increased H_2 production increases the Power-to-X conversion efficiency. As in this case Al serves as a renewable energy storage medium, another important technical performance parameter

is the round-trip efficiency (η_{RTE}) which expresses the overall efficiency considering the necessary amount of energy to produce Al. Assuming an Al production energy intensity of 11 kWh kg⁻¹ Al, the η_{RTE} of the entire concept ranges between 35.6% and 40.7%, inversely related with the SOFC partial loads.

1.1.6 Economic Evaluation Results

Using the previously explained methodology, the baseline specific system cost is estimated as 5,250 € kW⁻¹ (lower: 4,200 – higher: 6,200 € kW⁻¹). As for OPEX, putting all the operational aspects together, the described economic evaluation model is used for estimating the cost of the provided energy for the varying operational points. As a base case an electricity price 50 € MWh_e⁻¹ is considered for Al production, the LCoE and LCoH are estimated. The estimated LCoE and LCoH indicate that it is possible to provide electricity at a cost of 238-353 € MWh_e⁻¹ and H₂ ranging from 9 to 12 € kg⁻¹ H₂. To further evaluate the cost reduction potential three scenarios concerning variable electricity prices, Al prices, and energy intensities are considered as follows:

- **Scenario-I:** Average Al price 1.65 € kg_{Al}⁻¹, Al smelting energy intensity 14.25 kWh kg_{Al}⁻¹, electricity price 50 € MWh_e⁻¹. This scenario aims to simulate the system using actual parameters.
- **Scenario-II:** Assuming an average Al price 1.26 € kg_{Al}⁻¹, Al smelting energy intensity 11 kWh kg_{Al}⁻¹, electricity price 30 € MWh_e⁻¹ to simulate the system for near future parameters.
- **Scenario-III:** This scenario considers an average Al price 0.93 € kg_{Al}⁻¹, Al smelting energy intensity 11 kWh kg_{Al}⁻¹, electricity price 0 € MWh_e⁻¹ to determine the lowest extreme economics limits.

Considering the above introduced scenarios, the economic evaluation model is run for 1,000 – 8,760 annual FLHs (11- 100% capacity factor equivalent). As somewhat expected, both LCoH and LCoE are showing decreased energy costs with reduced flexibility. To sum up, Scenario-I proves relatively high electricity and H₂ costs, but Scenario-II implies that it is possible to produce 30% cheaper electricity and H₂ if required conditions are maintained. As an extreme case, if the electricity is supplied free of charge (Scenario-III), a cost reduction on both LCoE and LCoH are estimated approximately 55%. All these scenarios are highlighting the fact that the potential of the concept is highly dependent on electricity prices.

1.1.7 Conclusion

All in all, the techno-economic evaluation results indicate a business case development potential considering the estimated electricity and H₂ costs. In particular, the on-site production and consumption of H₂ bring numerous advantages to avoid large H₂ storage and transportation demand. To make a decent comparison, some renewable fuels are selected for comparison where Al based H₂ even with today's energy intensity and energy prices demonstrates high competitiveness as illustrated in Figure H.2. As for electricity prices, in comparison with several battery technologies, the proposed system with the reduced electricity prices (starting from Scenario-II) displays high potential for further consideration. Especially, with respect to the PEM FC /electrolyzer combination with salt cavern storage, cost competitiveness of Al and on-site operation could make the concept more attractive. It is important to mention that increased share of renewables will yield more frequent price reductions

(even negative electricity prices) that will create an arbitrage market with higher profit expectations. But only an electricity price of 30 € MWh_e⁻¹ already makes Al a high potential renewable energy carrier.

Figure H.2 a) Comparison of net fuel production costs based on 4000 FLHs, and b) LCoE of various storage technologies based on power-to-power conversion path. (The power capacity of the selected technologies for comparison is 100 MW_e and estimated LCoE values are based on the assumed 10h of daily storage duration.) FT Kerosene: Fischer–Tropsch synthesis kerosene, NMC: nickel–manganese–cobalt, LFP: lithium–iron– phosphate, PSH: pumped storage hydropower, CAES; compressed air energy storage.) [7].

Moreover, implementation of the inert anodes and drained cathodes will be sufficient for eliminating the direct emissions once 100% renewable electricity is used for the Al production. Also, produced Al can be considered as secondary as the Al₂O₃ returned to the smelter Al which will not increase demand on bauxite and Al will be used repeatedly. Another potential improvement could be using low grade Al where the electricity consumption is reduced. However, a life-cycle assessment of the entire concept is a necessity for certain statements about its sustainability. Also, in framework of ALU-STORE project to utilize the high energy density of the Al metal additionally another energy conversion path (i.e., electrochemical) is being investigated for a seasonal energy storage case employing a mechanically rechargeable Al-air battery. The project aims to reach higher round-trip efficiencies. Eventually, the project outcomes will enable to make a comparison between electrochemical and thermochemical conversion pathways.

1.2. Use Case: True Cost of Solar Hydrogen

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Storage Media	Hydrogen
Delivered Energy	<input type="checkbox"/> Electricity <input type="checkbox"/> Heat <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fuels (Please specify: Hydrogen)
Technological Readiness Level (TRL)	<input type="checkbox"/> TRL 1-3 (Research) <input type="checkbox"/> TRL 4-6 (Development) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TRL 7-8 (Deployment)
Hybridization Level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> None <input type="checkbox"/> Material <input type="checkbox"/> Device <input type="checkbox"/> System
Storage technology classification	<input type="checkbox"/> Mechanical <input type="checkbox"/> Electrochemical <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Chemical <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (power plants, CSP) <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (buildings, district) <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (non-residential) <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (industrial) <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (solar, PV, wind)
Application field	<input type="checkbox"/> TSO <input type="checkbox"/> DSO <input type="checkbox"/> Energy Supplier <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Industrial Actors <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Industrial Clients <input type="checkbox"/> Private actors <input type="checkbox"/> Aggregator <input type="checkbox"/> Power plant operator <input type="checkbox"/> Power plant operator incl. PtX
Storage duration	<input type="checkbox"/> Short-term <input type="checkbox"/> Mid-term <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Long-term
Services	<input type="checkbox"/> Generation support and bulk storage (minutes to hours) <input type="checkbox"/> Transmission infrastructure support (ramp-up, milliseconds or minutes) <input type="checkbox"/> Distribution infrastructure support (one or more hours) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Ancillary services <input type="checkbox"/> Behind-the-meter (>=100 kW) <input type="checkbox"/> Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G)
Key performance indicators (KPIs)	Levelized cost of hydrogen (LCoH)
Hybridization purpose	nd.
Remarks	

1.2.1 Introduction

The hydrogen sector and the hydrogen economy have experienced another wave of strong political support as enablers for a future carbon-neutral energy system. A lot of emphasis is put on the different “colours” of hydrogen, which muddles the big picture: eventually, all energy sources need to be renewable, and hydrogen will be “green”. Solar photovoltaics (PV) and wind power will be the heart of the 100% renewable system because both are substantially scalable and enabled by battery storage and hydrogen [10], [11]. At the moment, the main benefits in terms of economy of scale are to be found in large-size electrolyzers, where anything below 1MW still shows very high CAPEX. Direct solar hydrogen generation via photoelectrolysis is less mature than electricity-based electrolysis, whereas fast progress in solar-to-hydrogen conversion efficiencies of up to 20% have been demonstrated for a growing number of materials [12]. The projected cost is indicated for about 100 €/MWh_{H₂,LHV} (3.4 €/kg_{H₂}) for a midterm commercialization, based on present lab-scale technology status.

This research investigates solar PV electricity utilized for solar hydrogen generation via electrolysis, as all technologies are commercially available for large-scale applications.

1.2.2 Methodology

This article investigates the current and future cost of utility-scale solar PV hydrogen, starting from the capital (CAPEX) and operational expenditure (OPEX) projections for solar PV and electrolysis technology. Historical learning rates (LRs) are used for the future cost projections together with several volume growth scenarios. The levelized cost of hydrogen (LCOH) is calculated for five European and five non-European locations with different solar irradiation levels and with several WACC.

1.2.2.1. Sensitivity Analysis

Because there are substantial uncertainties on the future development of the various parameters affecting the LCOH, a thorough sensitivity analysis was made by varying 11 key input parameters. In addition to location, nominal WACC, annual inflation, PV volume growth, electrolyzer LR, FLH, CAPEX, volume growth, OPEX, efficiency, lifetime, and stack replacement were chosen.

1.2.3 Results

With the current cost of solar hydrogen, 31–81€/MWh_{H₂,LHV} (1.0–2.7€/kg_{H₂}), green hydrogen is not yet competing with natural gas as a fuel. However, this will change rapidly as both solar electricity and water electrolysis costs are decreasing fast, and as soon as the CO₂ emissions cost of a realistic level is fully factored in. By 2030, the LCOH of solar hydrogen will decrease to 20–54€/MWh_{H₂,LHV} (0.7–1.8€/kg_{H₂}), making it a competitive clean fuel globally compared with hydrogen produced from natural gas with CCS.

Another factor currently increasing the LCOH in many estimations is the extremely high OPEX used in the calculations. Proper sizing of the system is key: the peak power of the PV system should always be oversized compared with the electrolyzer input power because the PV system seldom generates electricity with its full peak power. Because of the complementary generation curves of solar and wind power, a hybrid PV–wind system would significantly increase the electrolyzer full load hours (FLHs). Hourly optimization using cost assumptions from 2018 and hybrid PV–wind systems led to a green hydrogen production cost of about 40–80€/MWh_{H₂,LHV} (1.3–2.7€/kg_{H₂}) in 2030 in a range of comparable regions in the world, compared to a decrease to 20–54€/MWh_{H₂,LHV} (0.7–1.8€/kg_{H₂}) found in this research for PV-based green hydrogen, which documents the strong dynamics in cost reduction of solar PV and electrolyzers. Further LCOH reduction would be possible directly using DC power generated by the PV system. Direct DC systems are not yet standard solutions in the hydrogen sector but should be developed for local solar hydrogen production. Another potential further cost reduction potential may come from polymer electrolyte membrane (PEM) electrolyzers, which are not yet at the same maturity level as alkaline electrolyzers. Finally, as the electrolyzer technology further matures, the related risk perceived by investors should decrease, lowering the WACC rate of the investment.

1.2.4 Conclusion

Green hydrogen will be the main fuel as well as a fundamental energy vector for the future 100% sustainable energy and industry system. Up to one-third of the required solar and wind electricity would eventually be used for water electrolysis to produce hydrogen, increasing the cumulative electrolyzer capacity to about 17 TW_{el} by 2050. There is a huge growth potential from the current 20

D4.2 – “Common base for environmental, techno-economic and socio-economic assessment to un-lock the potential applications for hybrid ES systems”

PU

GW_{el} and the cost of electrolysis will decrease accordingly with mass production and volume growth, as well as with scaling up the electrolyzer unit size. Electrolyzer CAPEX for a large utility-scale system is expected to decrease from the current 400€/kW_{el} to 240€/kW_{el} by 2030 and to 80€/kW_{el} by 2050. Together with the continuing solar PV cost decrease, this will lead to an LCOH decrease from the current 31–81€/MWh_{H₂,LHV} (1.0–2.7€/kg_{H₂}) to 20–54€/ MWh_{H₂,LHV} (0.7–1.8 €/kg_{H₂}) by 2030 and 10–27€/MWh_{H₂,LHV} (0.3–0.9 €/kg_{H₂}) by 2050, depending on the location. The share of PV electricity in the LCOH will increase from the current 63% to 74% by 2050. Already during this decade, solar hydrogen will be globally a less expensive fuel compared with hydrogen produced from natural gas with CCS.

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1.3. Use Case: Life-Cycle Costs of Electrochemical Energy Storage for Stationary Grid Applications

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Year: 2017

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/ente.201600622>

Storage Media	
Delivered Energy	<input type="checkbox"/> Electricity <input type="checkbox"/> Heat <input type="checkbox"/> Fuels (Please specify: _____)
Technological Readiness Level (TRL)	<input type="checkbox"/> TRL 1-3 (Research) <input type="checkbox"/> TRL 4-6 (Development) <input type="checkbox"/> TRL 7-8 (Deployment)
Hybridization Level	<input type="checkbox"/> None <input type="checkbox"/> Device <input type="checkbox"/> Material <input type="checkbox"/> System
Storage technology classification	<input type="checkbox"/> Mechanical <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (buildings, district) <input type="checkbox"/> Electrochemical <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (non-residential) <input type="checkbox"/> Chemical <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (industrial) <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (power plants, CSP) <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (solar, PV, wind)
Application field	<input type="checkbox"/> TSO <input type="checkbox"/> DSO <input type="checkbox"/> Private actors <input type="checkbox"/> Energy Supplier <input type="checkbox"/> Aggregator <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial Actors <input type="checkbox"/> Power plant operator <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial Clients <input type="checkbox"/> Power plant operator incl. PtX
Storage duration	<input type="checkbox"/> Short-term <input type="checkbox"/> Mid-term <input type="checkbox"/> Long-term
Services	<input type="checkbox"/> Generation support and bulk storage (minutes to hours) <input type="checkbox"/> Transmission infrastructure support (ramp-up, milliseconds or minutes) <input type="checkbox"/> Distribution infrastructure support (one or more hours) <input type="checkbox"/> Ancillary services <input type="checkbox"/> Behind-the-meter (>=100 kW) <input type="checkbox"/> Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G)
Key performance indicators (KPIs)	€/kWh, kGCO ₂ eq/kWh
Hybridization purpose	No
Remarks	

1.3.1 Introduction

As the shift towards a decentralized electricity generation system primarily reliant on renewable energy sources (RES) gains momentum, the importance of stationary energy storage has significantly increased. Within this context, battery systems have emerged as crucial players due to their efficiency and rapid response capabilities. However, the production of batteries is relatively expensive and environmentally impactful in terms of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Consequently, substantial efforts are being made to reduce their costs and environmental footprint. This study undertakes a comprehensive analysis, considering both economic and environmental factors, to assess various battery technologies for hypothetical stationary energy storage systems throughout their lifespan. The investigation focuses particularly on different lithium-ion battery (LIB) chemistries and encompasses diverse application scenarios. Furthermore, the study includes case-specific optimization of battery systems, thus providing a thorough understanding of the potential performance of different technologies in this domain, along with the corresponding uncertainties.

The study evaluates four main battery chemistries, namely LIBs, Valve-Regulated Lead-Acid (VRLA) batteries, Sodium Nickel Chloride (NaNiCl) batteries, and Vanadium Redox Flow Batteries (VRFBs).

However, particular emphasis is placed on LIBs due to their current significance in the field. Within the scope of this study, five different types of LIBs are considered: Lithium Iron Phosphate (LFP), Lithium Titanate oxide (LTO), Lithium Manganese Oxide (LMO), Nickel Cobalt Aluminium Oxide (NCA), and Nickel Cobalt Manganese Oxide (NCM).

1.3.2 Methodology

LCC serves as a methodical means to compare different project designs by taking into account the overall costs incurred throughout the entire economic lifespan of a product, which includes initial investment, capital, replacement, operation, energy, disposal costs, and more. Additional details about LCC can be found in the guidelines IEC 60300-3-3 or VDI 2884, which provide an explanation of LCC's purpose and significance, as well as an outline of the general approach to implementing it.

Operating conditions exert a significant influence on various aspects such as required maintenance efforts and battery lifespan. These factors, in turn, impact potential replacements, thereby affecting both the total life cycle cost (LCC) and carbon footprint (CF) of the battery system. This influence becomes particularly noteworthy for battery technologies with relatively short cycle or calendar life expectancies. Hence, it is crucial to carefully select and define the future application field in order to conduct a meaningful and case-specific assessment. To achieve this, four representative application fields have been identified, utilizing normalized load profiles primarily based on the research conducted, who provide a comprehensive overview of typical applications for stationary battery systems. The four application cases are considered:

- Electric time shift (ETS), also known as "arbitrage,"
- Increasing photovoltaics self-consumption (PVSC) refers to the use of energy storage by end-use customers to reduce their electricity bills.
- Primary regulation (PR) is a set of measures implemented to quickly balance supply and demand in the electricity grid.
- Renewables support (RS) involves storing excess electricity generated by renewable sources, such as wind turbines.

The life-cycle costs of the considered batteries are determined using the annuity method, which evenly distributes the net present value (NPV) over the entire product lifespan, resulting in annual cash flow series. The depreciation rate assumed for private households (PVSC application case) is 4%, while for utilities (ETS, PR, and RS), it is 8%.

The estimation of initial investment costs is based on the specific battery costs in euros per kilowatt-hour (€/kWh) and the rated power and capacity. To facilitate comparisons, all batteries are scaled to the same available capacity. This means that any losses due to varying efficiency grades are compensated by appropriately sizing each battery. The ratio between the annuity and the total amount of energy stored and released by a battery represents the life-cycle cost (LCC) of electricity storage in euro cents per kilowatt-hour (€cent/kWh). It should be noted that the end-of-life handling of the battery is not considered in the LCC analysis. However, some battery cells may have residual life expectancy and economic value for further use beyond the considered 20-year period. In such cases,

a linear accounting depreciation over 10 years is considered, and the corresponding value is credited to the present value of each battery type.

The operation of the battery is optimized from an economic perspective by adjusting the minimum state of charge (SoC), which directly impacts the battery's cycle lifetime. A higher depth of discharge (DoD), meaning deeper cycling, generally leads to a reduction in the battery's cycle life. Consequently, batteries are frequently oversized to prolong their operational duration. The objective of the optimization process is to minimize the overall LCC by finding an optimal balance between the initial investment cost (battery oversizing) and the replacement costs (reduced battery life) under specific conditions for each application case.

1.3.3 Results

The optimization algorithm is employed to find the optimal nominal battery size by striking a balance between battery oversizing (which enhances cycle life by reducing deep cycling) and the need for battery replacements throughout the 20-year total lifetime. The outcome of the optimization process yields diverse battery configurations, varying significantly depending on the specific application case.

Significant variations in the LCC per kilowatt-hour (kWh) of supplied electricity are observed across the four analyzed application cases. While the costs ETS, PVSC, and RS are relatively similar, the costs for PR are notably higher, along with increased uncertainties associated with it. Furthermore, the ranking of different battery chemistries changes depending on the specific application case, underscoring the criticality of designing a storage system that is optimized for the intended application.

When comparing the overall performance of different battery types, it is observed that LFP, NCA, and NCM exhibit similar and comparatively LCC across all application cases. However, the results for LMO are highly dependent on the application case, with higher LCC values obtained for ETS and PR due to its lower cycle life and greater sensitivity to the cycling profile dictated by the application. On the other hand, LTO demonstrates a very high cycle life, making the results relatively independent of the application's demand profile, although it incurs higher costs due to increased investment in cell components. VRLA batteries, despite their low cell costs, exhibit high LCC levels in all cases due to the need for significant oversizing to achieve acceptable cycle lifetimes, resulting in frequent replacements.

The life cycle cost of VRFB displays a strong dependence on the application case. For ETS and RS, VRFB shows competitive LCC values comparable to LIBs. However, for the other two application cases, particularly PR, the LCC for VRFB is significantly higher, reaching up to an order of magnitude difference. This can be attributed to the substantial impact of the energy-to-power (E/P) ratio on VRFBs. High-power applications necessitate larger cell stacks and membrane areas, leading to steep increases in investment costs. As a result, from an economic standpoint, VRFBs are primarily advantageous for low-power applications.

Across all application cases, the initial investment costs represent a significant portion of the total LCC, even when considering a minimum DoD of 10% (with little to no oversizing). Comparing these findings with existing literature, there is generally good agreement. Additionally, the contributions of different

components within the battery system to the overall investment costs exhibit a strong correlation, except for VRFB, where literature shows higher variation. This indicates a need for further research in this area to better understand and refine the cost factors associated with VRFBs.

1.3.4 Conclusion

The main drivers of LCC are identified to be the initial investment costs and battery replacements. Consequently, the LCC results are highly influenced by the costs associated with battery cells. Moreover, it is crucial to achieve long cycle lives to avoid frequent cell replacements, which would drive up costs and emissions. In future work, a detailed analysis will be conducted to examine whether increased energy densities require greater safety efforts and how this affects the impact on LCC and CF for the various systems under consideration.

A comprehensive evaluation is conducted by calculating a single score that combines carbon footprint (CF) and cost considerations, leading to a final recommendation that combines environmental impacts and costs. Most of the assessed LIBs demonstrate favorable performance across all application cases, positioning them as promising technologies for stationary electrochemical energy storage. LIBs are characterized by their efficiency, stability, and the expectation of further cost reductions in the future. Notably, LIB types such as LFP, NCA, and NCM consistently achieve excellent final results regardless of the application case and the relative weight assigned to LCC compared to CF. Similar positive outcomes are observed for NaNiCl batteries, which display comparable performance. On the other hand, VRLA batteries, despite their initial affordability, are less recommended for all application cases due to their low cycle life and efficiency.

Regarding VRFBs, the results are accompanied by significantly higher uncertainties and should be viewed as indicative. VRFBs exhibit favorable economic performance in applications with a high energy-to-power (E/P) ratio but do not demonstrate advantages in the inverse scenario. This can be attributed to the high costs associated with the separator membrane, which become less significant for larger storage capacities and lower nominal power (characterized by higher electrolyte quantities and reduced membrane area). However, CF results present a contrasting picture, indicating good performance in applications with a high E/P ratio. Therefore, the performance of VRFBs is highly sensitive to the load profile of the specific application considered, as well as the relative importance assigned to costs versus CO₂ emissions.

2. USE CASES ON ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT OF HYBRID ES TECHNOLOGIES

2.1. Use Case: Life cycle energy and environmental impacts of a solid oxide fuel cell micro-CHP system for residential application

Authors: Sonia Longo, Maurizio Cellura, Francesco Guarino, Giovanni Brunaccini, Marco Ferraro

Year: 2019

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.05.368>

Storage Media	
Delivered Energy	<input type="checkbox"/> Electricity <input type="checkbox"/> Heat <input type="checkbox"/> Fuels (Please specify: _____)
Technological Readiness Level (TRL)	<input type="checkbox"/> TRL 1-3 (Research) <input type="checkbox"/> TRL 4-6 (Development) <input type="checkbox"/> TRL 7-8 (Deployment)
Hybridization Level	<input type="checkbox"/> None <input type="checkbox"/> Device <input type="checkbox"/> Material <input type="checkbox"/> System
Storage technology classification	<input type="checkbox"/> Mechanical <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (buildings, district) <input type="checkbox"/> Electrochemical <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (non-residential) <input type="checkbox"/> Chemical <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (industrial) <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (power plants, CSP) <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (solar, PV, wind)
Application field	<input type="checkbox"/> TSO <input type="checkbox"/> DSO <input type="checkbox"/> Private actors <input type="checkbox"/> Energy Supplier <input type="checkbox"/> Aggregator <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial Actors <input type="checkbox"/> Power plant operator <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial Clients <input type="checkbox"/> Power plant operator incl. PtX
Storage duration	<input type="checkbox"/> Short-term <input type="checkbox"/> Mid-term <input type="checkbox"/> Long-term
Services	<input type="checkbox"/> Generation support and bulk storage (minutes to hours) <input type="checkbox"/> Transmission infrastructure support (ramp-up, milliseconds or minutes) <input type="checkbox"/> Distribution infrastructure support (one or more hours) <input type="checkbox"/> Ancillary services <input type="checkbox"/> Behind-the-meter (>=100 kW) <input type="checkbox"/> Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G)
Key performance indicators (KPIs)	
Hybridization purpose	
Remarks	

2.1.1 Introduction

Europe is moving towards a clean energy transition by increasing renewable energy. The increased renewable energy will rely on fuel cell technologies, in order to ensure a consistent electricity supply, for both stationary and mobile applications. Therefore, a scientifically reliable analysis on the energy and environmental impacts over the entire life cycle of fuel cell is needed. This study aims at assessing the life cycle energy performance and environmental impacts of a solid oxide fuel cell (SOFC), identifying new design solutions and defining eco-design criteria.

The literature analysis indicated a lack of primary data on stack and balance of plant manufacturing processes. At the same times, literatures used simulated data or data from industry catalogues for the operation and start-up steps. Besides, some LCA studies stopped at life cycle inventory of SOFC. As a

result, this study contributed by using primary data for manufacturing step, laboratory data for operation step, and performing a life cycle impact assessment of the product system.

2.1.2 Methodology

The study used life cycle assessment (LCA) for the assessment of the life cycle energy and environmental impacts and the life cycle hot-spots of a SOFC micro- CHP (combined heat and power) system that produces electricity and heat for a household application.

The functional unit is 1 MJ of exergy (MJ_{ex}); the reference flow is one SOFC system with a useful life of 10 years (8,758h per year) or about 243 GJ_{ex} . The system boundary covers manufacturing process, start-up of the system, operation, and maintenance; and excludes the production of machinery and plants used in the manufacturing process, transport, the use stage of the electricity and heat produced by the system and the end-of-life stage.

The calculation is conducted on SimaPro 8.5 with application of Cumulative Energy Demand (CED) method for energy analysis and ILCD 2001 midpoint method for environmental impact assessment.

2.1.3 Results

The life cycle inventory data are collected from various sources. The manufacturing process of the system was modelled by using primary data supplied by the manufacturer. Data on the start-up and operation phases are from laboratory measurement. Data for maintenance step are taken from industry datasheets. Background data from fuel production and electricity generation of Italian energy mix and raw material supply are from Ecoinvent 2.2.

The examined system is 2.5 kW SOFC micro-CHP generating power and heat for residential electrical and thermal loads. The system is based on different components of stacks, balance of plant (BoP) cold box, BoP hot box and casting.

The CED of the product system is 10.8MJ per functional unit, in which 97.8% originates from the operation step. At the same time, operation step is the main contributor of half of examined environmental impacts. In detail, its contribution varies from about 63.3% of particulate matter, to about 98.8% of ozone depletion. This is mainly due to the fuel supply (natural gas), and to the CO_2 emissions during the conversion of chemical energy into electricity.

Manufacturing step is the main responsible of the remaining half of the impacts. It contributes from about 38% of the impact on Ionizing radiation on ecology, to about 66.1% of the impact on Human toxicity non-cancer effect. A detailed analysis of these impacts shows that the disposal processes during the supply chains of the fuel cell components cause about 60.1% of the human toxicity cancer effect, 72.5% of the human toxicity non-cancer effect, 99.2% of freshwater eutrophication and 91% of freshwater ecotoxicity.

For almost half of the examined impact, a contribution of 20–30% is caused by the maintenance step, with a relevant contribution of the stacks and DC/DC booster substitutions. Negligible impacts (less than 1.4%) are caused during the start-up and shut-down processes.

The analysis highlights that eco-design solutions of the assessed system can be traced in the improvement of the energy system efficiency and reduction of emissions during the operation, and in the increase of the durability of the system components, thus reducing the number of their substitutions. The results of a sensitivity analysis on the selection of the functional unit also clarified the importance of the recovery of the thermal energy generated by the fuel cells, in order to avoid concurrent energy generation from conventional sources.

2.1.4 Conclusion

The study aimed at assessing the life cycle energy and environmental impacts of a SOFC system, considering the production of 1 MJ of exergy. The results indicated that the operation step causes more than 97% of the energy impact and gives a contribution from about 63.3% to about 98.8% to almost half of the examined impacts (human toxicity, ionizing radiation - ecology, freshwater eutrophication, freshwater ecotoxicity, water resource depletion). The remaining impacts are mainly generated (from about 38% to about 66.1%) during the manufacturing of the system (that includes the raw materials supply). The maintenance step is responsible of about 20–30% of the impacts related to human toxicity, ionizing radiation, freshwater eutrophication, freshwater ecotoxicity, water resource depletion.

The results highlighted the importance of taking into account the operation as well as other steps during the life cycle of the product system in order to develop a reliable evaluation of energy technologies. Considering the operation, the improvement of the efficiency and the reduction of the emissions during the conversion of chemical energy into electricity can help more environmentally sustainable systems reach the marketable stage. Focusing on the manufacturing and maintenance, extending the useful life of the components of the system can be a valid eco-design solution for improving its energy and environmental performance as well as reducing the exploitation of critical raw materials without affecting its functionality.

The sensitivity analysis on the selection of the functional unit showed that if the thermal energy is wasted, the energy and environmental impacts of the electricity produced increase.

Finally, the study highlighted a lack of data for modelling the eco- profile of some materials used for the SOFC system. Thus, realizing data- bases containing site-specific data for the materials used in the energy fuel cell systems should be a priority for improving the reliability of the results in this field. This requires an effort by firms that should be willing to share primary data on their productive processes; by policy makers that should stimulate the producers to carry out LCA studies of their products; and by LCA experts that should assess the energy and environmental performances of these materials to be implemented in specific databases.

2.2. Use Case: Life cycle assessment of storage systems: the case study of a sodium/nickel chloride battery

Authors: Sonia Longo, Vincenzo Antonucci, Maurizio Cellura, Marco Ferraro

Year: 2014

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2013.10.004>

Storage Media	
Delivered Energy	<input type="checkbox"/> Electricity <input type="checkbox"/> Heat <input type="checkbox"/> Fuels (Please specify: _____)
Technological Readiness Level (TRL)	<input type="checkbox"/> TRL 1-3 (Research) <input type="checkbox"/> TRL 4-6 (Development) <input type="checkbox"/> TRL 7-8 (Deployment)
Hybridization Level	<input type="checkbox"/> None <input type="checkbox"/> Device <input type="checkbox"/> Material <input type="checkbox"/> System
Storage technology classification	<input type="checkbox"/> Mechanical <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (buildings, district) <input type="checkbox"/> Electrochemical <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (non-residential) <input type="checkbox"/> Chemical <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (industrial) <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (power plants, CSP) <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (solar, PV, wind)
Application field	<input type="checkbox"/> TSO <input type="checkbox"/> DSO <input type="checkbox"/> Private actors <input type="checkbox"/> Energy Supplier <input type="checkbox"/> Aggregator <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial Actors <input type="checkbox"/> Power plant operator <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial Clients <input type="checkbox"/> Power plant operator incl. PtX
Storage duration	<input type="checkbox"/> Short-term <input type="checkbox"/> Mid-term <input type="checkbox"/> Long-term
Services	<input type="checkbox"/> Generation support and bulk storage (minutes to hours) <input type="checkbox"/> Transmission infrastructure support (ramp-up, milliseconds or minutes) <input type="checkbox"/> Distribution infrastructure support (one or more hours) <input type="checkbox"/> Ancillary services <input type="checkbox"/> Behind-the-meter (>=100 kW) <input type="checkbox"/> Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G)
Key performance indicators (KPIs)	
Hybridization purpose	
Remarks	

2.2.1 Introduction

Electricity storage technologies play an important role in facilitating renewable energy and distributed energy generation. In transportation sector, the sodium / nickel chloride battery or zero emissions battery research activities (ZEBRA) battery has been applied in electric cars, vans, buses, hybrid vehicles and marine technologies. Even though the batteries have no direct emission during the operations step and are charged with renewable electricity, they cannot be considered totally clean. In fact, batteries consume energy and cause environmental impacts during their life cycle that cannot be neglected. In such context, the assessment of the real advantage of using ZEBRA batteries for energy storage must include an analysis of the energy and environmental impacts during the life cycle of these systems. This study contributes by identifying the life cycle energy and environmental impacts of the ZEBRA battery and the hot spots of this technologies that need to be carefully considered to improve their efficiency and sustainability.

2.2.2 Methodology

The analysis was conducted using the Life Cycle Assessment methodology according to the standards of the ISO 14040 series. The study system was one ZEBRA battery providing electric storage for a photovoltaic system. The assessment covered the manufacturing, operation, and end-of-life steps of the ZEBRA battery, with a functional unit of a 48-TL-200 ZEBRA battery, including the Battery Management Interface. The transportation of the battery to final users and maintenance steps were excluded from the analysis, as their impacts are either negligible or do not exist.

Some impact indicators are selected to assess the performance of the ZEBRA battery, including: Global energy requirement (GER), Non-renewable energy requirement (NRE), Renewable energy requirement (RE), Global warming potential (GWP) and Ozone depletion potential (ODP), Human toxicity (HT), Photochemical ozone formation (POF), Acidification (AC), Terrestrial eutrophication (TE), Freshwater eutrophication (FE), Marine eutrophication (ME), Land use (LU), Water resource depletion (WRD). The selected impact assessment methods are Cumulative Energy Demand (CED) and ILCD 2011 midpoint.

Two scenarios were developed, in which the battery operates continuously (scenario A) and with stand-by periods (scenario B).

2.2.3 Results

The inventory analysis indicated the consumption of 7.13MJ of electricity and 116 MJ of natural gas for cell manufacture. It also indicated the materials used for main components of the battery and the cells, the materials and energy used for packing, waste disposal and transportation of raw materials and components. During the operation step, the data on electricity consumption was assessed in laboratory test.

The impact assessment showed that Scenario B has the higher impacts than Scenario A. Specifically, The GER is 57.4 GJ in Scenario A and 68.7 GJ in Scenario B. The amount of energy obtained from renewable energy sources varies from 26.5 GJ (46.2% of the total in Scenario A) to 35.5 GJ (51.7% of the total in Scenario B) and is mainly due to the electricity produced by the photovoltaic system and used during the operation step. The contribution of the manufacturing step to the GER ranges from 35.8% (Scenario B) to 42.8% (Scenario A); the operation step contributes from 55.1% (Scenario A) to 70.5% (Scenario B); and the end-of-life of the battery contributes less than 2%. The manufacturing step contributes from 60.7% to 92.1% of the environmental impact for Scenario A and from 54.5% to 90.1% for Scenario B.

Comparing the impacts of ZEBRA manufacturing with other existing batteries, the GER (234.3 MJ/kg) and NRE (222.6 MJ/kg) of ZEBRA are higher than the values reported in the literature. Meanwhile, the GWP (14.32 kgCO₂e/kg) of ZEBRA is lower than the GWP obtained in the literature.

Cell manufacturing is responsible for the main energy and environmental impact of battery manufacturing. The GER for a single cell manufacturing is approximately 217 MJ, of which 95.5% is derived from on-renewable energy sources. In fact, energy consumed during the cell manufacturing process is the main contributor to GER. It is also the main factor in the following impacts: ODP (77.4%), GWP (69.6%) and LU (39.1%). Nickel power manufacturing is the second contributor to GER and the

main contributor to several impacts such as HT (32.7%), TE (42.5%), WRD (48.2%), POF (49.3%), FE (60.5%) and Ac (70.2%).

Monte Carlo analysis indicated that the highest uncertainties exist for the impact categories of FE and HT, cancer effects”, as noted by the coefficient of variation values greater than 50%. For both scenarios, the coefficient of variation values lower than 8% are observed for the impact categories of RE, wind, solar, geothermal, GWP and WRD. This means that the final results are distributed around the mean value and are characterized by very low uncertainty.

A sensitivity analysis was conducted on the different sources of electricity used to charge the battery, such as electricity from solar PV system, from wind turbine, from hydropower, Italian electricity mix and European electricity mix. The results indicated that using electricity from wind turbine or hydropower reduce GER by 20-24T compared to that from solar PV system. GER of battery using electricity from solar PV system is much lower than that of battery using Italian and European electricity mixes. At the same times, environmental impacts reduce when substituting electricity from solar PV system by electricity from wind turbine or hydropower and increase when substituting electricity from solar PV system by Italian and European mixes.

2.2.4 Conclusion

The study evaluated the energy and environmental performance of one ZEBRA battery, examining the manufacturing, operation, and end-of-life steps. The results indicated that the operation step has the greatest energy impact (55 to 70% of the total), due to electricity consumption of the battery during its operation. The manufacturing step, particularly cell manufacturing, contributes the greatest environmental impact (>60% of the total), due to the use of energy (electricity and natural gas) in the cell manufacturing process. The energy and environmental performances of the battery, consequently, can be improved using low carbon electricity during the manufacturing and operation steps and by improving the energy efficiency of the manufacturing processes.

3. USE CASES SOCIAL SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT OF HYBRID ENERGY STORAGE TECHNOLOGIES

3.1. Use Case: Societal Acceptability of Large Stationary Battery Storage Systems

Authors: Dorothee Baur, Manuel Johann Baumann, Patrick Stuhm, Marcel Weil

Year: 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/ente.202201454>

Storage Media	
Delivered Energy	<input type="checkbox"/> Electricity <input type="checkbox"/> Heat <input type="checkbox"/> Fuels (Please specify: _____)
Technological Readiness Level (TRL)	<input type="checkbox"/> TRL 1-3 (Research) <input type="checkbox"/> TRL 4-6 (Development) <input type="checkbox"/> TRL 7-8 (Deployment)
Hybridization Level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> None <input type="checkbox"/> Device <input type="checkbox"/> Material <input type="checkbox"/> System
Storage technology classification	<input type="checkbox"/> Mechanical <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (buildings, district) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Electrochemical <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (non-residential) <input type="checkbox"/> Chemical <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (industrial) <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (power plants, CSP) <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (solar, PV, wind)
Application field	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TSO <input type="checkbox"/> DSO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Private actors <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Energy Supplier <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Aggregator <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Industrial Actors <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Power plant operator <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Industrial Clients <input type="checkbox"/> Power plant operator incl. PtX
Storage duration	<input type="checkbox"/> Short-term <input type="checkbox"/> Mid-term <input type="checkbox"/> Long-term
Services	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Generation support and bulk storage (minutes to hours) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transmission infrastructure support (ramp-up, milliseconds or minutes) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Distribution infrastructure support (one or more hours) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Ancillary services <input type="checkbox"/> Behind-the-meter (>=100 kW) <input type="checkbox"/> Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G)
Key performance indicators (KPIs)	
Hybridization purpose	
Remarks	

3.1.1 Introduction

Battery energy storage plays a crucial role for a successful energy transition. Beside the residential sector, large scale battery storage is foreseen to play a major role in future grid operation. For example, battery Holding and TransnetBW, one of the German transmission system operators announced projects in a scale of 60–250 MW and capacities up to 250 MWh. With the storage technology rising in popularity, many studies are examining the technical, economic, and ecological implications of the technology, but there is a lack of studies which access the social dimension related to the implementation of this technology. This development calls for additional research regarding the social implications of introducing such new storage technologies to enable a smooth and social benign roll out of large-scale battery systems. More specifically, storage units that are not based inside of buildings, e.g., in basements, but rather larger storage units with a size in the multi-kWh >30 kWh to a multi-MWh scale that are extra stand-alone facilities (containers, buildings, etc.) are considered.

3.1.2 Methodology

An online questionnaire was carried out to gather the public opinions on battery storage in Germany in June 2020. The study was conducted via the online panel SoSci Panel (www.soscipanel.de). In total, the questionnaire was completed by 259 participants. A mixed factorial design was used, to gain insights into how the design and siting of battery storage influences acceptability.

First, participants filled in a value questionnaire. Afterward, the broad context of the study was briefly introduced, and participants were asked to indicate their support for the energy transition and renewables as well as their knowledge of energy storage in general and battery storage specifically.

To do so, participants were divided into three groups and were either shown an image of battery storage in an industrial design, an urban design, or no image at all. We then examined how participants evaluated battery storage according to several criteria, such as usefulness, innovativeness, and environmental friendliness. Afterward, we assessed acceptability in four different locations: industrial areas, rural areas, residential areas, and the participant's own neighbourhoods. Additionally, we examined whether predictors of acceptability differed between locations.

To ensure that sufficient attention was paid to the image, participants were asked to indicate the first word, image, or thought they had when looked at the image. Next, participants evaluated battery storage on bipolar attitude scales, judged acceptability of battery storage in four different locations, and indicated how they perceived different mitigation measures.

3.1.3 Results

The first goal of the study was to investigate if the presentation of different images of battery storage in different designs influences the evaluations of battery storage. The findings indicate that participants who were presented with an image of battery storage in an urban design overall evaluated the technology as significantly more positive, environmentally friendly, innovative, and aesthetic compared to people in the industrial design and control group.

The second goal of the study was to highlight the importance of distinguishing between different locations for siting battery storage as well as battery storage design when assessing the acceptability of battery storage. In line with our expectations, acceptability of battery storage was dependent on the location (industrial areas, rural areas, residential areas, own neighbourhood) and design of the battery storage. Our data show a clear preference for industrial areas over the other locations, with acceptability being the lowest in residential areas and the participant's own neighbourhood as indicated in Figure H.3.

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Figure H.3 Battery storage acceptability and the impact of location (industrial area vs rural area vs residential area vs participant's own neighbourhood) and design (industrial vs urban vs control).

The third goal of the study was to explore whether predictors of acceptability would differ between the locations studied. Such predictors are affected, mean attitudes, knowledge battery storage, support energy transition and renewables etc. However, Affect emerged as a consistent and strong predictor across all the locations studied, which is in line with previous studies on technology acceptance (Imagine a battery storage plant was built in the vicinity of your home, which emotions does that elicit in you?) 7-point Likert scale [1 = very negative emotions, 7 = very positive emotions].

The last goal of the study was to examine whether certain mitigation measures could help to increase acceptability of battery storage in residential areas, as we expected acceptability to be low for this location. Both environmental measures and measures relating to participation, compensation, and design were included. All except for one of the mitigation measures (providing a financial compensation) were rated above the midpoint of the scale, pointing to important implications for the implementation of battery storage projects as depicted in Figure H.4. Three of the environmental mitigation measures (ensuring proper recycling of batteries, observing strict environmental and social standards in the extraction of raw material, and storing electricity generated from renewable sources) were rated as significantly more important compared to all other measures included.

Figure H.4 Mean importance of different mitigation measures to positively influence acceptability.

Analyses indicate that BS is more readily accepted in industrial and rural areas compared to residential areas or the participants’ immediate neighbourhoods. Adapting the design of BS to its surroundings can help to increase acceptability in residential areas, whereas battery storage design does not significantly influence acceptability in locations further away from homes.

In line with the survey, the factors of recyclability and environmental impacts (proper recycling, strict environmental and social standards in the extraction of raw material, storing renewable generated electricity) have been named as the most crucial aspects for mitigation of acceptance problems by the participants.

3.1.4 Conclusion

In situations where it is inevitable for battery storage to be built close to or in residential areas (e.g., as a community electricity storage), attention should be paid to minimizing visual intrusion by adapting the exterior of the infrastructure toward its surroundings. While this strategy might come with higher costs, it might mitigate additional costs that may arise in case of project delays due to resistance and protest from the local population. Also, findings concerning public support for diverse mitigation measures regarding the siting of BS in residential areas show that environmental mitigation measures are most supported.

On the other hand, the more innovative the technology is seen, the lower acceptability is. Additionally, our analysis of potential mitigation measures indicates that linking the use of the technology to the energy transition and the use of renewables as well as eliminating environmental concerns may help

D4.2 – “Common base for environmental, techno-economic and socio-economic assessment to un-lock the potential applications for hybrid ES systems”

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to increase acceptability. In line with this, we suggest providing people with more information about the technology while keeping the aforementioned aspects in mind.

In addition, a clear product declaration in frame of the European Battery Directive toward, e.g., a carbon footprint and recyclability and a corresponding labeling of batteries could influence the acceptance of named systems in a positive manner. In any case, more research is required focusing specifically on energy storage in residential areas. Given the small sample size and the fact that the sample of the current study was not representative of the German population, generalizability of the results concerning the mitigation measures cannot be ensured. In line with this, future research could examine potential mitigation measures in more detail.

3.2. Use Case: Working conditions in hydrogen production

Authors: Sally K. Springer, Jasmin Werker, Christina Wulf, Petra Zapp

Year: 2019

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.12840>

Storage Media	
Delivered Energy	<input type="checkbox"/> Electricity <input type="checkbox"/> Heat <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fuels (Please specify: Hydrogen)
Technological Readiness Level (TRL)	<input type="checkbox"/> TRL 1-3 (Research) <input type="checkbox"/> TRL 4-6 (Development) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TRL 7-8 (Deployment)
Hybridization Level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> None <input type="checkbox"/> Device <input type="checkbox"/> Material <input type="checkbox"/> System
Storage technology classification	<input type="checkbox"/> Mechanical <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (buildings, district) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Electrochemical <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (non-residential) <input type="checkbox"/> Chemical <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (industrial) <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (power plants, CSP) <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (solar, PV, wind)
Application field	<input type="checkbox"/> TSO <input type="checkbox"/> DSO <input type="checkbox"/> Private actors <input type="checkbox"/> Energy Supplier <input type="checkbox"/> Aggregator <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Industrial Actors <input type="checkbox"/> Power plant operator <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial Clients <input type="checkbox"/> Power plant operator incl. PtX
Storage duration	<input type="checkbox"/> Short-term <input type="checkbox"/> Mid-term <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Long-term
Services	<input type="checkbox"/> Generation support and bulk storage (minutes to hours) <input type="checkbox"/> Transmission infrastructure support (ramp-up, milliseconds or minutes) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Distribution infrastructure support (one or more hours) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Ancillary services <input type="checkbox"/> Behind-the-meter (>=100 kW) <input type="checkbox"/> Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G)
Key performance indicators (KPIs)	Association and bargaining rights, trade unionism, fair salary, gender wage gap and weekly hours of work per employee
Hybridization purpose	-
Remarks	-

3.2.1 Introduction

Next to environmental, also social impacts are of paramount importance for decision making. Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA), one method to assess social impacts, can influence business and political decision-making by preventing socially unsound investments and informing supply chain decisions. Methodological advancements are developed next to various case studies. Even though progressive development takes place within this assessment method, e.g., the generation of an ISO guidelines, a standardized and accepted framework is still missing.

Within a hybrid approach, quantitative social databases are used and complemented by a case-specific analysis, with which generic data can be verified with company data [13], [14]. To assess social impacts of industrial hydrogen production by using alkaline water electrolysis (AEL), a case study was conducted. Next to previous investigations about environmental and economic impacts which serve as a basis, e.g., in terms of the product system and technical specifications [15], [16], the case study covers the social dimension of sustainability. The manufacturing of the electrolyzer takes place in Switzerland, whereas the hydrogen production is located in Germany, Austria and Spain, respectively.

The Product Social Impact Life Cycle Assessment (PSILCA) database [17], 2nd version, is used and complemented with further raw data and literature research. It is thus a quantitative study following a Type 1 assessment.

As the product system comprises novel technologies, the participation of stakeholders is not possible and thus, a hybrid approach not feasible. Instead, the results obtained with the help of PSILCA are set in relation to its underlying data and additional empirical findings.

3.2.2 Methodology

One central topic of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG's) [18] are working conditions, why the focus of the evaluation of industrial hydrogen production is on this topic and thus, on the stakeholder group of workers. There is no consensus on the selection of impact categories and indicators within the conduction of an S-LCA yet [19]. By considering the key areas of working conditions from the International Labour Organization (ILO) [20], which are influenced by the SDG's, social impact categories within PSILCA were identified. They comprise association and bargaining rights, trade unionism, fair salary, gender wage gap and weekly hours of work per employee.

Data for the production and upstream processes as well as the impact assessment methodology are contained in the PSILCA database V2 [21]. Production processes and their upstream supply chains are represented by Eora, a multiregional input/output database, with economic data of sectors on a global scale [22], [23]. Social and socioeconomic raw data is gathered from different statistical agencies and organizations, e.g., the World Bank or ILO. Within PSILCA, a predefined risk assessment assigns risk levels to each raw data value on an ordinal scale. This can be changed individually. This qualitative information is linked to characterization factors to make it calculable, e.g., 100 for a very high-risk level. Worker hours as an activity variable are used to highlight the importance of each process within hydrogen production. For that reason, the results are expressed in the unit medium risk hours for each indicator individually [21].

The functional unit is defined as 1 kg of hydrogen produced. The manufacturing and assembly of the alkaline water electrolyzer in Switzerland is the first step of the investigated product system. The production of hydrogen takes place in Germany (Berlin), Austria (Vienna), or Spain (Madrid) over a time span of 20 years, where the cell stacks are replaced after ten years. Technical parameters and specifications can be found in [16].

3.2.3 Results

The fewest amount of risk can be found in the impact category weekly hours of work per employee, the most in trade unionism.

Austria: More than 60% of the risk stem from Austria itself, whereas the other risk is induced by the supply chain. The highest impact occurs within the impact categories gender wage gap and association and bargaining rights. The former is especially high compared to Germany and Spain. For the latter, the sector public administration bears a high amount of risk. When it comes to supplying countries, especially China and India influence the result negatively.

Germany: Only 36% of the total risk occurs in Germany, the bulk comes from upstream processes, mainly located in India and China. The impact categories trade unionism and weekly hours of work per employee account for the largest share of risk. No specific sector can be made responsible for the risk, instead, the results are highly differentiated.

Spain: Similar to Austria, also Spain is responsible for most of the risk with 77% being domestic. Within that, trade unionism bears most to the overall risk. Association and bargaining rights have the least risk, where most are occurred by the supply chain in China. Also, for Spain the distribution of risk across sectors is highly differentiated, where no specific sector stands out in particular. Also here, China and India are responsible for high amounts of risks.

Four conclusions can be drawn from the results:

1. Trade union membership in Western Europe is limited.
2. Chinese association and bargaining rights are insufficient.
3. Western European women, particularly in Austria, experience wage discrimination and
4. India's salaries are inadequate to lead a decent life.

The results of the study show that a major amount of risk occurs during hydrogen production within the impact category trade unionism, especially in Western Europe. Trade unionism in PSILCA follows the definition of ILO “Unions are independent workers’ organizations constituted for the purpose of furthering and defending the interests of workers [...]. The trade union density rate is the share of employees who are union members.” [24]. Looking at the trade union membership in Western Europe, statistics show a decrease in the trade union density in the past 30 years [25], which is in line with the results. However, trade union density alone cannot indicate the protection of freedom of association and bargaining within a country; instead, the consideration of the social and political context is important, e.g., the historical development.

The impact category association and bargaining rights accounts for a high share of risk in China. This impact category is a combination of three indicators in PSILCA, the right to collective bargaining, the right of association and the right to strike [21]. For the former, only minor restrictions exist. The right of association is limited to a large extend and a right to strike does not exist in China [25]. Even though the overall situation improved over the last years, mainly because of pressure from international investors, the situation remains problematic.

The results of the gender wage gap as an impact category reveal high risk especially occurring in Austria. The underlying data is presented on a monthly basis and therefore cannot take into account effects like part-time work. Nevertheless, this is not the only reason for the results. What is more important are the sectors in which women are more likely to be employed in. In addition, once employed in a minimum wage job or an employment with low wages, it is hard for women to climb the social ladder [26]. The difference of results in the study between Austria, Germany and Spain can be, in addition to the examples of reasons above, explained by the different data sources used by PSILCA for all three countries [21].

When it comes to the impact category of fair salary, which is defined as wages on an adequate level, all three investigated countries show a high-risk level, with a large part of the risk occurring in India. In PSILCA, the impact category is measured with three indicators: minimum wage per month, living wage per month and sector average wage per month. The minimum wage as well as the sector average wage are assessed in relation to the living wage [21]. Especially in developing countries, the determination of a minimum wage is challenging. Often, they are kept at a low level to keep investors in the country and in addition, informal workers are not enclosed into minimum wage concepts [27]. India is a country with a high rate of informal work and, what is more, the economic situation differs throughout the country, due to its large size and population, which has to be taken into account by interpreting results.

3.2.4 Conclusion

The analysis of the social impacts of AEL hydrogen production in Germany, Austria and Spain reveals that the least social issues occur in Germany, in comparison to the other countries. Austria accounts for the highest shares of risks. The process chains in all three countries lack a degree of association of workers in terms of trade unions.

Version 2.0 of the PSILCA database provides meaningful insights into social issues within the life cycles, having said that it cannot reflect upon the reality, as it relies on statistical sources, e.g., where informal work is not included. Therefore, a deep literature research is inevitable for the interpretation of results, also because the unit in PSILCA, medium risk hours, is cumbersome to a certain degree.

The study revealed the somewhat surprising fact that there is a big difference between the results of Germany and Austria, two countries often considered very similar in structural and cultural terms, even though it could not finally investigate the reason for it. Additional research could add to this understanding. For the future, the integration of more stakeholder groups as well as using the same level of abstraction of data sources are advantageous, as PSILCA 2.0 offers a sectoral resolution whereas the complementary literature review is country specific.

The influence on working conditions varies, which has to be taken into account if S-LCA as a decision support tool for the determination of a production country, is used. Association and bargaining rights cannot directly be influenced by a company. On the other hand, for fair salary, gender wage gap and weekly hours of work per employee, companies have to power to change something and also hold the responsibility. Others, like trade unionism are hard to influence, even though it is not impossible.

Companies are in charge of generating a demand for fair working conditions and by doing so, counteract exploitation etc., rather than avoiding certain countries due to problematic social issues and, as a result, generating less investment and thus further worsening of the social situation.

4. USE CASES ON INTEGRATIVE SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT OF ES TECHNOLOGIES

4.1. Use Case: Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis to find the more sustainable location for hydrogen production in Europe

Authors: Christina Wulf, Petra Zapp, Andrea Schreiber and Wilhelm Kuckshinrichs

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Storage Media	
Delivered Energy	<input type="checkbox"/> Electricity <input type="checkbox"/> Heat <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fuels (Please specify: hydrogen)
Technological Readiness Level (TRL)	<input type="checkbox"/> TRL 1-3 (Research) <input type="checkbox"/> TRL 4-6 (Development) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TRL 7-8 (Deployment)
Hybridization Level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> None <input type="checkbox"/> Device <input type="checkbox"/> Material <input type="checkbox"/> System
Storage technology classification	<input type="checkbox"/> Mechanical <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (buildings, district) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Electrochemical <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (non-residential) <input type="checkbox"/> Chemical <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (industrial) <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (power plants, CSP) <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (solar, PV, wind)
Application field	<input type="checkbox"/> TSO <input type="checkbox"/> DSO <input type="checkbox"/> Private actors <input type="checkbox"/> Energy Supplier <input type="checkbox"/> Aggregator <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Industrial Actors <input type="checkbox"/> Power plant operator <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial Clients <input type="checkbox"/> Power plant operator incl. PtX
Storage duration	<input type="checkbox"/> Short-term <input type="checkbox"/> Mid-term <input type="checkbox"/> Long-term
Services	<input type="checkbox"/> Generation support and bulk storage (minutes to hours) <input type="checkbox"/> Transmission infrastructure support (ramp-up, milliseconds or minutes) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Distribution infrastructure support (one or more hours) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Ancillary services <input type="checkbox"/> Behind-the-meter (>=100 kW) <input type="checkbox"/> Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G)
Key performance indicators (KPIs)	Outranking flow
Hybridization purpose	-
Remarks	

4.1.1 Introduction

The transformation of the energy system is a critical endeavour in order to fulfil the objectives outlined in the Paris Agreement [28]. To facilitate this process, innovative energy technologies are essential in making significant contributions. In line with this, the European Commission has proposed the European Green Deal [29] as a comprehensive strategy to enable Europe to achieve climate neutrality by 2050 and drive sustainable economic transformation within the EU. A key component of this transformation is the utilization of hydrogen, a secondary energy carrier, which has gained prominence in various energy scenarios [30], [31]. Hydrogen offers advantages such as ease of storage, potential use as feedstock, and the ability to facilitate the electrification of multiple sectors beyond energy, including mobility and industry. However, it is crucial to consider a comprehensive sustainability

assessment that encompasses not only environmental impacts but also economic and social implications, in order to evaluate the potential for greenhouse gas reduction without neglecting other associated effects. Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA) has emerged as a valuable approach for conducting holistic assessments of emerging technologies [32]. Nevertheless, the interpretation phase of LCSA poses challenges due to the multitude of individual results obtained, necessitating the exploration of unambiguous solutions. To address these challenges and provide structured guidance for decision-making processes, the Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) has been developed. MCDA encompasses mathematical approaches that enable the clustering of numerous individual results into more manageable outcomes [33], [34]. While simpler methods like the weighted sum approach exist, they may not adequately address complex decision-making contexts. Therefore, more elaborate MCDA approaches such as Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS), Preference Ranking Organization METHod for Enrichment Evaluation (PROMETHEE), and Elimination Et Choix Traduisant la REALité (ELECTRE) have been developed to tackle complex problems. Regardless of the specific MCDA method employed, fundamental value-based choices must be made during the guidance process. A critical decision involves determining the extent to which compensation between indicators is permissible. Non-compensatory methods, such as PROMETHEE, employ outranking techniques to compare different options, without compensating for differences.

To illustrate the practical application of the proposed approach, this study applies LCSA to evaluate the industrial production of hydrogen using alkaline water electrolysis (AEL) within the European context. The assessment compares three potential production locations: Austria, Germany, and Spain based on already existing publications on Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) [15]. Life Cycle Costing (LCC) [35] and S-LCA [36] (see [Use Case: Working conditions in hydrogen production](#)) of the same case study. By integrating MCDA into the interpretation phase of LCSA without permitting compensation, the study seeks to provide unambiguous conclusions regarding the preferred production location among these similar systems.

4.1.2 Design of the study

4.1.2.1. Methodology

Indicator selection

The LCSA indicator set comprises indicators from LCA, LCC, and S-LCA. The recommendations of the International Reference Life Cycle Data System (ILCD) [37] were used for the LCA indicators together with the more recent guidance from the UNEP/SETAC [38], [39] on a midpoint level. For the assessment of water, however, the scarcity method AWARE, was applied [40]. The analysis is performed with the GaBi software [41] using the ecoinvent [42] as well as the GaBi professional database [43]. The LCC indicators refer to a guide prepared by the European Investment Bank [44] and literature on economic assessment of energy technologies, e.g. [45]. For the S-LCA, the Product Social Impact Life Cycle Assessment (PSILCA) database 2.0 [21] as implemented in openLCA [46] were applied. Next to the recommendations of the specific LCA, LCC and S-LCA methodologies, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) were used for the selection of useful indicators [47].

Weighting of indicators

Various MCDA approaches can be used to derive weighting factors for the indicators in LCSA. However, existing weighting factors developed for LCA do not consider all dimensions of LCSA. In this study, a two-stage (hierarchical) equal-weighting approach is adopted to simplify the weighting process. In the first step, each sustainability dimension (LCA, S-LCA, and LCC) is equally important (weighting factor $w_{SUS,i} = 1/3$). Within each sustainability dimension (second step), indicators receive equal weights, with $w_{LCC,i} = 1/4$, $w_{LCA,i} = 1/15$, and $w_{S-LCA,i} = 1/26$. The absolute weighting factor for each indicator is determined by multiplying the respective weighting factors ($w_{SUS} \times w_i$), resulting in lower weights for indicators when there are more indicators within a dimension. This approach acknowledges that indicators from different dimensions can have different weights if the number of indicators varies. Conversely, if equal weights are desired for indicators, the dimensions may have different weights depending on the number of indicators they contain.

MCDA aggregation method

The two most popular outranking methods are ELECTRE [48] and PROMETHEE [49]. This publication focuses on PROMETHEE as it provides guidance throughout the entire decision-making process. PROMETHEE is a family of outranking methods developed by Brans and colleagues in the early 1980s [49], [50]. Variations of PROMETHEE include PROMETHEE I-VI and the visual interactive module GAIA. For this study, PROMETHEE I and II will be used. PROMETHEE involves a pairwise comparison of alternatives based on recognized criteria or indicators. The method consists of five steps:

1. Determining deviations through pairwise comparisons.
2. Applying the preference function.
3. Calculating the global preference index.
4. Calculating positive and negative outranking flows for each alternative.
5. Calculating the net outranking flow and deriving a complete ranking (PROMETHEE II only).

PROMETHEE I provides a partial ranking based on outranking flows Φ_+ and Φ_- . Higher Φ_+ and lower Φ_- indicate a better overall rank. However, incomparability may arise when Φ_+ and Φ_- indicate different preferences. PROMETHEE II adds step 5 to derive a complete ranking by calculating the difference between the two flows (Φ_{net}), although some detail may be lost. Preference functions are introduced in step 2 to further refine the outranking process. These functions account for small differences between indicators and methodological uncertainties. PROMETHEE proposes six different preference functions, tailored to the nature of the values and level of uncertainty. In this study, a linear preference function with indifference and weak preference zones is used.

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Figure H.5 Preference function: Criterion with linear preference (weak preference zone: q-p) and indifference zone (0-q) (q: indifference threshold; p: strict preference threshold).

The preference function (Figure H.5) is defined by two parameters, q and p, representing absolute values. The indifference threshold (q) denotes the point at which two results are considered equal, while the strict preference threshold (p) indicates the value above which strict preference is given. Weak preferences exist between q and p. These thresholds help address uncertainties in obtained indicator values but determining appropriate values can be challenging.

For these relative thresholds q and p were used. They are defined as 5% and 10% of the minimal indicator result, respectively. By using relative thresholds, options with relatively small differences are not ranked harshly, thus avoiding overly strict differentiations.

4.1.2.2. Case study

Hydrogen production by an advanced AEL in three European countries is the objective of this LCSA. It is assumed that the AEL electrolyzer is manufactured in Switzerland using technical input data from a local AEL supplier. The constructed AEL unit, which has a pressurized 6 MW capacity, consists of four cell stacks, each containing 139 cells within a stack framework. The balance of plant (BOP) includes tanks, heat exchangers, pumps, power electronics/inverter, and a potassium hydroxide filter. More details can be found in Koj et al. [15]. After the construction of the electrolyzer it is transported to three different locations in Europe (i.e., Spain, Germany and Austria, see Figure H.6).

Figure H.6 Outline of the 6 MW alkaline water electrolyzer system [51].

The expected technical lifetime of the AEL unit is 20 years, with cell stack replacements required after ten years. Assuming an annual operation time of 8300 h, the 6 MW AEL unit produces hydrogen at a

rate of 118.25 kg hydrogen per hour, resulting in an annual production rate of 980 t based on scaled-up data [52]. The inputs for the operation of the AEL include electricity, de-ionized water, potassium hydroxide solution (KOH), process steam, and nitrogen. Electricity, de-ionized water, and KOH are continuously required for the electrolysis process, while process steam and nitrogen are only necessary during the run-up phases. The functional unit of the assessment is the production of 1 kg of hydrogen at 33 bar and 40 °C. The study does not consider hydrogen compression, storage, transport, or further use. End-of-life treatment and the utilization or sale of the by-product oxygen are also not included due to data availability limitations. No allocation is necessary for the by-product oxygen.

Table H.3 summarizes the specific material and energy inputs for the 6 MW AEL unit corresponding to the production of 1 kg of hydrogen. The table also indicates the industrial sectors used in the S-LCA modelling with PSILCA.

Table H.3. Summary of specific material and energy inputs for AEL unit for 1 kg of hydrogen.

	Unit per kg H ₂		DE	AT	ES
Electricity	kWh _{el}	53.9	Electricity and district heat	Electrical energy, gas, steam and hot water	Production and distribution of electricity
Water, de-ionized	kg	10.11	Water supply	Collection, purification and distribution of water	Collection, purification and distribution of water
KOH solution	mg	275	Manufacture of chemical products	Chemicals, chemical products and man-made fibres	Basic chemical products
Process steam	g	38	Gas supply/ Coal, coke and petroleum products, nuclear fuels/ Water supply	Electrical energy, gas, steam and hot water/ Coke, refined petroleum products and nuclear fuel/ Collection, purification and distribution of water	Manufacture and distribution of gas/ Coke, refined petroleum products and nuclear fuel/ Collection, purification and distribution of water
Nitrogen	mg	71.15	Manufacture of chemical products	Chemicals, chemical products and man-made fibres	Basic chemical products

Although the technology parameters are identical for all countries considered in the study, the supply of inputs is country-specific. The electricity supply reflects the national gross production mixes, and the costs for investment, operation, and maintenance correspond to the specific markets and regulatory conditions of each country.

4.1.3 Results

4.1.3.1. Indicator results

LCSA of hydrogen production is based on three existing assessments: LCA [15], LCC [16], and S-LCA [36]. The previous LCA compared environmental effects across nine impact categories, later adding six additional categories [47]. The results, highlight the significant influence of the electricity mix during the operational phase, with Austria showing the lowest environmental impacts in most categories. However, Austria performs poorly in the 'Eutrophication, freshwater' category due to phosphorous compounds from bioenergy in the electricity mix, while Spain fares better in 'Human toxicity' related to cancer effects.

Table H.4. LCSA indicator results, based on [47].

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Indicator	Unit	DE	AT	ES
LCA				
Acidification	mMole H ⁺ eq.	44.5	21.6	50.3
Climate change	kg CO ₂ eq	29.8	10.2	16.2
Cumulative energy demand	MJ	534	341	513
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	CTUe	5.59	3.31	3.71
Eutrophication, marine	g N eq	11.2	7.31	11.6
Eutrophication, freshwater	mg P eq	128	133	93
Eutrophication, terrestrial	mMole N eq.	116	65	121
Human toxicity cancer	nCTU _h	37.5	14.8	27.1
Human toxicity non-cancer	nCTU _h	977	507	434
Ionizing radiation	Bq U235 eq	2760	32	3200
Ozone depletion	ng CFC-11 eq	63.2	43.8	50.3
Particulate matter	mg PM _{2.5} eq	2000	870	246
Photochemical ozone creation	g NMVOC	30.0	16.4	33.0
Resource depletion – Abiotic resources	mg Sb eq	129	388	938
Resource depletion – Water	m ³ world eq.	23.6	23.9	43.9
LCC				
Levelized cost of hydrogen	€ ₂₀₁₅ /kg H ₂	3.64	4.22	4.31
Profitability index*	-	-6.38	-7.45	-7.74
Net present value*	m€ ₂₀₁₅ /kg H ₂	-50.1	-58.1	-59.4
Marginal cost	€ ₂₀₁₅ /kg H ₂	3.72	4.52	4.73
S-LCA				
Active involvement of enterprises in corruption and bribery	Med. rh	2.15	2.94	4.55
Association and bargaining rights	Med. rh	6.54	16.48	1.81
Certified environmental management system	Med. rh	19.41	37.19	20.47
Child labour, total	Med. rh	0.98	1.08	0.60
Drinking water coverage	Med. rh	2.60	2.90	1.65
Education	Med. rh	3.01	2.32	4.56
Fair salary	Med. rh	5.46	7.73	2.30
Fatal accidents	Med. rh	0.40	0.55	0.26
Frequency of forced labour	Med. rh	0.46	0.57	0.16
Gender wage gap	Med. rh	5.47	31.94	7.96
Goods produced by forced labour	Med. rh	0.30	0.29	0.22
Health expenditure	Med. rh	6.07	6.24	3.59
Illiteracy, total	Med. rh	4.45	4.43	2.21
Indigenous rights	Med. rh	1.44	1.79	0.78
Non-fatal accidents	Med. rh	4.03	13.82	27.12
Public sector corruption	Med. rh	15.99	16.85	12.68
Safety measures	Med. rh	4.89	5.71	5.15

Indicator	Unit	DE	AT	ES
Sanitation coverage	Med. rh	13.89	14.17	8.15
Social security expenditures	Med. rh	5.79	5.72	2.62
Trade union density	Med. rh	25.75	18.46	43.89
Trafficking in persons	Med. rh	2.30	2.81	1.34
Unemployment	Med. rh	0.81	0.77	37.43
Violations of employment laws and regulations	Med. rh	1.93	3.22	3.04
Weekly hours of work per employee	Med. rh	0.26	0.48	0.45
Women in the sectoral labour force	Med. rh	1.85	1.93	3.93
Youth illiteracy, total	Med. rh	0.75	0.81	0.45

CTU: Comparative toxic unit; Med. rh: medium risk hours

*Only costs and no revenues are considered, leading to negative values

Regarding 'Resource depletion - water,' hydrogen production in Spain has the highest impact due to water scarcity accruing during the electricity generation for the electrolyzer. However, the electrolyzer production contributes the most to this impact across all three process chains due to upstream nickel extraction. 'Ozone depletion' is primarily influenced by nickel and polytetrafluoroethylene used in cell manufacturing. Construction of system components and cell stack replacements have minimal contributions to other impact categories. From an environmental perspective, hydrogen production in Austria is the most favorable option, while Spain and Germany rank closely, with Germany performing the worst in eight categories but excelling in one.

When considering economic impacts, German hydrogen production performs best due to favorable regulatory conditions for energy-intensive industries, outweighing the lower investment and labour costs in Spain. Austria consistently falls between Germany and Spain in financial metrics.

The S-LCA complements the environmental and economic assessments by addressing working conditions in industrial hydrogen production. Austria presents the highest risks in four out of five categories, followed by Spain and Germany. Other upstream locations like India and China negatively affect the Austrian and German chains in terms of 'Trade union density' and 'Fair salary.' 'Gender wage gap' and 'Weekly hours of work per employee' mainly stem from Austria and Spain. Austria performs the worst in 15 out of 21 social indicators, while Spain exhibits the lowest risks in 13 categories. Water and electricity sectors, along with their upstream chains, contribute significantly to the identified risks.

In summary, there is no clear winner when considering the three dimensions of sustainability. Austria generally has the lowest environmental impacts, Germany has the lowest costs, and Spain frequently has the lowest social risks. This underscores the importance of using MCDA to combine these diverse outcomes, while also addressing uncertainties and thresholds in the assessment process.

4.1.3.2. MCDA results

Given that each analysis (LCA, LCC, S-LCA) suggests a different optimal location for hydrogen production, it is essential to conduct an outranking process to determine the best option. To make this decision, PROMETHEE is utilized. Considering that previous studies have shown similar impact ranges for various factors, it is reasonable to employ thresholds. In this context, the outcomes of PROMETHEE

are presented using relative common default thresholds: q (5% of the minimal indicator result) and p (10% of the minimal indicator result).

The application of thresholds affects the different dimensions of LCSA unevenly. Among the 15 LCA indicators, only 'Resource depletion—Water' shows similar results for Germany and Austria, while all other indicators clearly differentiate between the two options. Weak preference is observed three times between Germany and Spain ('Cumulative energy demand,' 'Eutrophication, marine,' and 'Eutrophication, terrestrial'), and once for 'Eutrophication, freshwater' between Germany and Austria. In terms of LCC, three out of four indicators exhibit indifference between Austria and Spain, with only a weak preference observed for the remaining indicator. This suggests the need for a more detailed analysis, considering factors such as grid connections and electricity prices in Austria. For S-LCA, six out of 26 indicators show indifference between two options, always between Germany and Austria. Additionally, weak preference is observed five times, but it is evenly distributed across country pairings and never affects all three options of one indicator.

These absolute thresholds are utilized to calculate the PROMETHEE I and II results for selecting the location of industrial hydrogen production in Europe. Figure H.7 displays the corresponding outranking flows in a bar chart. The outcomes of PROMETHEE I (Φ_+ and Φ_-) and PROMETHEE II (Φ_{net}) exhibit consistent tendencies. Hydrogen production in Germany is deemed more sustainable than in Austria or Spain, with production in Spain consistently being the least sustainable option. As a result, no incomparability arise, and both PROMETHEE I and II lead to the same conclusions (Figure H.7).

Figure H.7. Outranking results using default thresholds {Wulf, 2021 #1982}

4.1.4 Conclusion

Previous evaluations of electricity-intensive industrial hydrogen production conducted in Spain, Germany, and Austria presented divergent preferences across LCA, LCC, and S-LCA analyses. This disparity prompted the adoption of a Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) approach. Moreover, considering the similarities among these three Western European countries, employing an outranking method appeared logical.

D4.2 – “Common base for environmental, techno-economic and socio-economic assessment to un-lock the potential applications for hybrid ES systems”

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After applying PROMETHEE to the case study results a clear decision can be made for hydrogen production in Germany. The results from PROMETHEE I and II both indicate that in Germany the hydrogen would be produced more sustainable than in Spain or Austria.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement N. 101036910

4.2. Use Case: Sustainability Assessment of Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) plants with thermal storage in Spain compared to photovoltaic systems with batteries

Authors: Santacruz Banacloche, Ana Rosa Gamarra, Félix Téllez and Yolanda Lechón

Year: 2020

DOI: <https://mustec.eu/sites/default/files/reports/MUSTEC%20Deliverable%209.1.pdf>

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2022.113004> (only CSP results)

<https://zenodo.org/record/3964021>

Storage Media	
Delivered Energy	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Electricity <input type="checkbox"/> Heat <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fuels (Please specify: hydrogen)
Technological Readiness Level (TRL)	<input type="checkbox"/> TRL 1-3 (Research) <input type="checkbox"/> TRL 4-6 (Development) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TRL 7-8 (Deployment)
Hybridization Level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> None <input type="checkbox"/> Material <input type="checkbox"/> Device <input type="checkbox"/> System
Storage technology classification	<input type="checkbox"/> Mechanical <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Electrochemical <input type="checkbox"/> Chemical <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Thermal (power plants, CSP) <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (buildings, district) <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (non-residential) <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (industrial) <input type="checkbox"/> Thermal (solar, PV, wind)
Application field	<input type="checkbox"/> TSO <input type="checkbox"/> DSO <input type="checkbox"/> Energy Supplier <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Industrial Actors <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial Clients <input type="checkbox"/> Private actors <input type="checkbox"/> Aggregator <input type="checkbox"/> Power plant operator <input type="checkbox"/> Power plant operator incl. PtX
Storage duration	<input type="checkbox"/> Short-term <input type="checkbox"/> Mid-term <input type="checkbox"/> Long-term
Services	<input type="checkbox"/> Generation support and bulk storage (minutes to hours) <input type="checkbox"/> Transmission infrastructure support (ramp-up, milliseconds or minutes) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Distribution infrastructure support (one or more hours) <input type="checkbox"/> Ancillary services <input type="checkbox"/> Behind-the-meter (>=100 kW) <input type="checkbox"/> Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G)
Key performance indicators (KPIs)	Outranking flow
Hybridization purpose	-
Remarks	

4.2.1 Introduction

The European Union targets towards the energy transition require an increasing deployment of renewable energy sources (RES). This deployment can be understood as green investments that reduce greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions. These energy investments in RES do have intrinsic and inevitable impacts in the economy, the society, and the environment. Deploying power plants is expected to generate employment and economic growth across many sectors and countries. It would also imply a GHG emission expected mitigation once the new facilities are deployed fully. However, the manufacturing, construction, and installation stages are likely to impact the environment and the society in many senses. All along the production process up to the final installation, greenhouse gases will be emitted; water will be consumed, and the risk of social impact will be increased. Due to the so-called global supply chains, it is likely that unfair wages would be paid somewhere, and children would be exploited in some economic activities. These negative environmental and social risks should be

considered when investing in energy projects. Concentrating Solar Power (CSP) has been confirmed to have a niche in the future of European Union [53]. Hence, it is expected that additional installed capacity will have a multiplier effect on the economy, society, and environment. Components will be produced, intermediate inputs (both domestic and imported) will be required, commodities will be extracted, fuel will be consumed, and personnel will be necessary to undertake these activities. In a world where the production process is determined by the so-called global value chains (GVC), identifying where (which countries and sectors) impacts (value added, employment, GHG emissions, etc.) are being generated becomes crucial.

This case study provides a quantitative assessment of the potential impacts (direct and indirect effects) across sectors worldwide on 6 indicators that cover the three sustainability pillars. This report presents the results of the sustainability assessment of two CSP technologies: a parabolic trough power plant (PT) and a central receiver power plant (CR). For each of these technologies three scenarios are evaluated: A Pure Spanish Investment scenario (S1) where most of the investments are made by Spanish firms, a second scenario that exemplifies a possible cooperation project with Germany as off-taker (S2) and a third scenario that considers China as a supplier of some components (S3). Finally, we also present sustainability assessment results for an alternative technology equivalent in terms of flexibility and dispatchability that uses PV panels and batteries (PV+BATT)

4.2.2 Methodology

The methodology followed in this work is based on input-output analysis (IOA) [54]. Input-output analysis (IOA) and the global version, Multiregional Input-Output analysis (MRIO) has become a well-known and widely-used methodology to measure the total, direct and indirect, impacts of energy-related investments [55], [56].

Three main pillars define the datasets used in the present case study: the multi-regional input-output table MRIOT EXIOBASE, the Social Hotspot Database (SHDB), and the cost-specific data of analyzed power plants. Based on a Multiregional Input- Output (MRIO) framework, we link the cost data of the investment project and the extended MRIO results with social risk data from the Social Hotspots Database (SHDB) to integrate the social with the environmental and economic pillars.

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Figure H.8. Outline of the methodological approach followed.

Six socioeconomic, social, and environmental indicators have been chosen (see Table H.5). Two socioeconomic indicators that measure value added (GDP contribution) and employment creation, two environmental indicators focused on climate change and water consumption impacts and two social risk indicators measuring the risk of low wages and child labour occurrence.

Table H.5. Socioeconomic and environmental indicators covered.

Impact	Database	Indicator	Measure
Socioeconomic	EXIOBASE3	Value added	M.EUR
		Employment	Thousands of people engaged
Environmental	EXIOBASE3	Climate change	kt CO2 eq
		Water consumption	Blue and green water m3
Social	SHDB	Sweat free wage	Medium risk hours
		Child labour	Medium risk hours

A 200MW of CSP power plant has been considered. Spain has been chosen as the host country regarding the location of the hypothetical CSP plant. The southern part of Spain still offers a multitude of feasible potential sites with high levels of Direct Solar Radiation (above 2,000 to 2,200 kWh/m² - year). Two technologies have been considered: parabolic trough (PT) with synthetic oil as heat transfer fluid (HTF) and thermal storage using molten nitrate salts and central receiver (CR) on tower using molten salts both as HTF and as thermal storage.

Regarding the country-origin of CSP plant components, three scenarios have been proposed:

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- Pure Spanish Investment (S1): all final components, except for the molten salts that come from Chile and the thermal oil that comes from Germany, are produced in Spain. The construction, installation and Operation and Maintenance goods and services involved are also Spanish.
- Alliance with Germany (S2): as part of the possible clauses of a hypothetical cooperation agreement between Spain and Germany, we consider that Germany supplies some of the components of the plant. Specifically, in the case of parabolic troughs Germany provides the mirrors and steam turbine. In the case of central receiver, Germany provides the mirrors, the frames and support structures, the drive mechanisms and track systems, the steam turbine and the heat exchangers.
- China as a supplier (S3): assuming that China is going to have a relevant role in the future of CSP, under this scenario, the country supplies components related to the solar field, with a cost reduction of 20%. In the case of parabolic trough technology, China would supply the receiver tubes, the drive mechanisms and track systems and the steam turbine. In the case of the central receiver, China will supply the drive mechanisms and the steam turbine. The installation process (civil works related to the tower, solar field, thermal heat storage system and the power plant) is assumed to be undertaken by both Spanish and Chinese workers (the later with labour costs reduction of approximately 80%).

In order to make CSP and PV+BATT comparable (same electricity production during the lifespan of the plants), the storage system remains 200MW with 11 hours (as the TES in the CSP) and the PV infrastructure must be escalated to 739MW (see Figure H.9). The purpose of this exercise is to compare the sustainability implications of a PV+BATT system as a substitute of CSP in terms of dispatchability and flexibility.

Figure H.9 Comparison of equivalent CSP and PV+BATT configurations.

4.2.3 Results

Three main questions are addressed here to identify the potential impacts associated to the future deployment of CSP cooperation projects, according to six indicators.

1. Does CSP generate value added and employment in Europe?

The initial investments (INV) made to install a CSP plant or a PV+BATT in Spain require components. However, to become final goods destined for investment, these components have required intermediate inputs that have been produced with primary factors (labour, capital, land), both domestic and foreign, all along their supply chain. When estimating value added, these primary factors can be identified by country and sector, enabling a better interpretation of where economic growth is being created.

Total value-added created ranges from 899 up to 984 M.EUR for the CSP power plants and is calculated in 1,888 M.EUR for the PV+BATT system (see Table H.6). While this later scenario creates much more value added, the amount of this value added that is created in Europe is very similar to the CSP power plants since most of the value added created remains in China. Indirect value added is very important especially in the case of PV+BATT scenario where the ratio indirect/direct value added is around 4.

Table H.6. Total, both direct and indirect, value added creation (Investment and O&M Stages) (M.EUR)

Region	PT_S1	PT_S2	PT_S3	CR_S1	CR_S2	CR_S3	PV+BATT
ES	604	525	484	731	476	604	674
DE	40	119	38	22	288	18	28
REU	51	51	42	62	61	49	59
European	695	695	564	815	825	671	761
CN	10	10	108	12	12	120	852
WL	149	149	150	66	63	66	28
OECD	30	32	33	35	38	38	125
ROW	46	43	45	57	46	54	123
Total	930	930	899	984	984	949	1,888
Direct	462	467	442	451	477	420	372
Indirect	468	463	458	534	508	529	1,515

When talking about value added, other regions (and sectors) where no initial investment was made now appear as important because their role in the global value chains. As an example, in CR_S1, 95% of the investment consists of Spanish final components and services, except for the molten salts coming from Chile. However, roughly 75% corresponds to Spanish primary factors payment (value added and thus, economic growth). The rest remains intermediates produced in REU, OECD, DE, CN, and ROW. Hence, this indicator redistributes the effect of the investment in terms of economic growth.

Figure H.10 captures the difference in investment and value-added regional share.

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Figure H.10 Regional share of investment and value added created for PT and CR technologies under scenarios S1 to S3 and PV+BATT.

In terms of employment, Table H.7 shows employment per megawatt in the investment and operation and maintenance stages expressed in full time equivalent jobs (FTE). Under CR_S1, 46.4 FTE/MW remain domestic (that is, 9,280 jobs-year originated in the European Union), followed by CR_S2 (43.8 FTE/MW, 8,760 jobs-year). Indirect impacts in employment are in the range of 48 to 53% of total employment when direct jobs from the installation and the operation stage are accounted for.

Table H.7. Total, both direct and indirect employment (FTE/MW).

Region	PT_S1	PT_S2	PT_S3	CR_S1	CR_S2	CR_S3
ES	32.3	28.2	26.7	42.7	30.6	35.8
DE	1.6	4.5	1.6	0.8	10.3	0.7
REU	2.1	2.1	1.7	2.8	3	2.3
European	36	34.8	30	46.4	43.8	38.8
CN	1.8	2	19.2	2.5	2.7	27.1
WL	1.9	1.9	1.9	1.9	1.5	1.9
OECD	1.2	1.3	1.3	1.5	1.7	1.7
ROW	16.7	16.1	16.5	23	20	22.4
Total	57.8	56	67	75.4	69.8	88.1
Direct	20.4	19.5	21.1	26.8	25	28.6
Indirect	37.3	36.6	45.9	48.5	44.7	59.6
Direct installation and O&M	18.9	18.9	19.6	23.2	23.2	24.1
TOTAL EUROPEAN	54.9	53.7	38.7	69.5	67	48.5
TOTAL SPAIN	51.2	47.1	35.4	65.9	53.8	45.5
TOTAL	76.7	74.9	86.6	98.5	92.9	112.1

2 . How can CSP minimize the environmental impacts?

Figure H.11 presents the Carbon and Water footprints of the investments proposed, that is the CO₂eq and water embodied in goods and services that are consumed in the power plants, identifying where they are produced.

Figure H.11 Carbon and water footprints of the CSP investments in the different scenarios.

Total GHG emissions range from 15 to 28 gCO₂ eq/kWh, values that are perfectly in line with values reported in life cycle assessment literature with median life cycle GHG emission estimates of 22 - 23 g CO₂ eq./kWh [57]. The highest emissions are produced in S3 for both technologies due to the high carbon intensity of Chinese productive structure (yellow segments in the Figure H.11). Even in this case, emissions are well below those of the alternative fossil electricity generation systems and in the range of the other renewable technologies (IPCC, 2011). The PV+BATT installation generates around 93 g CO₂ eq./kWh and these high emissions are mainly generated in the Chinese productive sectors.

As for water consumption embodied water results range from 0.7 to 1.7 l/kWh well in agreement with values in literature that range from 0.7 to 0.9 l/kWh [58]. Highest values also occur in S3 in both cases due to water consumption from Chinese components. As operational water consumption is quite reduced as we have considered a dry cooling technology, most of the water consumed by the plant is due to the water embodied in components. Chinese productive structure in 2011 is described as water-intensive when compared to the other regions. This is why environmental impacts of S3 in both technologies are the highest. This trend may be tackled and smoothed in the future, though.

3. Does CSP minimize the social risks embodied in global value chains?

It seems rational to think that a high level of development and low social risks in a country are correlated. Usually, developing regions have more undemanding social policies regarding labour rights. Although direct investments are mostly made with European components and services, intermediates all along the GVC coming from developing regions are likely to embody social risks. Most of the social

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risks regarding Sweat free wage and Child labour are expected to occur outside the European Union, especially in China and RoW. CR_S2 performs better than any other alternative, showing the lowest risks in these two indicators. PV+BATT depends on Chinese components in a much higher proportion than CSP, affecting the risks of incurring unfair wages and child labour.

Figure H.12 Social risks of the CSP investments in the different scenarios.

4.2.4 Conclusions

Below we show the key findings of the sustainability assessment performed for a CSP power plant based on the assumptions made for the technologies and scenarios presented and regarding the six indicators assessed.

CSP deployment will create value added and employment that will be mostly retained in Europe

We have shown that the deployment of a 200 MW CSP power plant would generate value added in a range between 900-950 M.EUR of which 70-84% would remain in Europe. Employment creation has been estimated in 75-112 FTE/MW of which 39-70 FTE/MW would be retained in Europe (43-72%). Lowest figures correspond to a scenario of a high penetration of the Chinese CSP industry in the European market.

CSP electricity has a low carbon and water footprint

The electricity generated in this CSP plant would generate between 14-28 g CO₂ eq./kWh of electricity generated. The highest figure corresponds to a scenario of high penetration of the Chinese CSP industry. From the total emissions, only 28-55% of these emissions would be produced in Europe. Water consumption of the CSP power plant ranges from 0.7 to 1.1 l/kWh and is mainly due to the

water embodied in components and not so much to the operational water consumption that is quite reduced.

CSP power plants originate some social risks in their value chain

Most of the social risks regarding fair wages and occurrence of child labour are expected to occur outside the European Union, especially in China and Africa, Rest of Asia and Pacific, and Middle East, and in sectors not directly stimulated by the investments. Hence it is of outmost importance to guarantee the social responsibility along the value chain of all the components of these plants in order to minimize the occurrence of such risks.

The penetration of the Chinese CSP industry in the European market will worsen the sustainability of the CSP plants

The scenarios that consider a higher penetration of the Chinese CSP industry in the European market would reduce the generation of value added at the European but also at the global level. Although these scenarios increase total job creation, this increment only occurs in China and comes at the expense of a decrease in the European employment. The participation of the Chinese industry in the power plants also increase the carbon and water footprints as well as the risk of occurrence of unfair wages and child labour. This situation could be minimized if China moves towards a fair, inclusive and low carbon energy transition.

An equivalent system in terms of flexibility and dispatchability that uses photovoltaic panels and batteries performs worse in all the sustainability indicators analyzed.

Although the value added and employment generated by a PV+BATT system is quite higher than in the case of CSP, the amount of these socioeconomic benefits that remain in Europe is similar since most of these benefits remain in China and do not contribute to the European wealth. For the rest of the sustainability indicators analyzed, the PV+BATT system performs worse than the CSP plant.

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